

FACULTÉ
DES SCIENCES

UNIVERSITÉ LIBRE DE BRUXELLES

Knowing and Governing Super-Wicked Problems

A Social Analysis of Low-Carbon Scenarios

Thesis submitted by Aurore FRANSOLET

in fulfilment of the requirements of the PhD Degree in sciences (“Docteur en sciences”)

Academic year 2018-2019

Supervisor: Professor Tom BAULER

Centre for Studies on Sustainable Development (CEDD-DGES)

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"Some problems are so complex that you have to be highly intelligent and well informed just to be undecided about them." – Laurence J. Peter

"Climate change is not 'a problem' waiting for 'a solution'. It is an environmental, cultural and political phenomenon that is reshaping the way we think about ourselves, about our societies and about humanity's place on Earth." – Mike Hulme

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Abstract

Since various public and private actors at the international, supranational, national and subnational levels started to adopt long-term targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, low-carbon scenario analyses have flourished. Literature reveals an increasing number of analyses envisioning and exploring alternative images of low-carbon futures, as well as their adjacent transition pathways. Scenario approaches or “foresight” is intended to help policy-makers to navigate the maelstrom of confusion and conflicts associated with highly complex societal challenges such as climate change – i.e. the “super-wicked” problems. Typical scenario exercises aim at coping with uncertainty and conflicting values, and hence are often claimed as a suitable approach for knowing and governing super-wicked problems. When reviewing the scenario literature published over the recent years, we observe significant methodological developments, in particular at the level of the calculus or data-sets. These contributions have generated an increasing technical sophistication of scenario building methods, and contrast with the relative absence of social sciences research on scenarios. Scenario analyses have received little academic attention from social sciences, whether they are political science, sociology, philosophy of science or science and technology studies. By providing a SHS-analysis of low-carbon scenarios, the present thesis contributes to bridge this research gap. Scenarios are here understood as “boundary objects” linking different social worlds: science and policy, but also natural and social sciences. This thesis aspires to create an enhanced understanding on how scenario analyses perform such “boundary work”. More specifically, the following analysis of low-carbon scenarios is based on a twofold perspective focusing, on the one hand, on the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance (i.e.: link between science and policy), and, on the other hand, on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (i.e.: link between natural and social sciences). In other words, it explores “scenarios in governance” and “governance in scenarios”. The thesis project includes three research axes, each based on its particular empirics. A first study explores the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance on the basis of a multiple case study analysing the role of four energy foresight studies in policy-making. The other two studies focus on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios. One of them provides an assessment of the knowledge needed to steer the low-carbon transition. The other one aims at contributing to the debate on the relations between quantitative modelling and social sciences by exposing a critical review of socio-technical energy transition models. The objective of the present thesis thus consists in providing an empirical contribution to social sciences research on low-carbon scenarios.

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List of Acronyms

AB-Reoc	Association belge de recherche et d'expertise des organisations de consommateurs
AFOLU	Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use
Agoria	Fédération de l'industrie technologique
APERe	Association pour la Promotion des Energies Renouvelables
AR	Assessment Report
AWAW	Agence Wallone de l'air et du climat (Walloon agency for air and climate)
BBL	Bond Beter Leefmilieu
BEBELGRA	Fédération belge des industries graphiques
BRAFCO	Fédération belge des négociants en combustibles et carburants
CBDR	Common but Differentiated Responsibilities
CCE	Conseil Central de l'Economie
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
CCPIE	Comité de coordination de la politique internationale de l'environnement (Coordinating Committee for International Environmental Policy)
CdH	Centre démocrate humaniste
CELINE	Cellule interrégionale de l'environnement (Interregional Environment Committee)
CESW	Conseil économique et social de Wallonie
CFDD	Conseil Fédéral du Développement Durable
CGSLB	Centrale générale des syndicats libéraux de Belgique
CH₄	Methane
CHP	Combined heat and power
CIE	Conférence interministérielle pour l'environnement (Interministerial Conference for the Environment)
CJG	Centre Jean Gol
CNC	Commission nationale climat (National Climate Commission)
CNDD-11.11.11	Centre national de coopération au développement
CONCERE	State-Regions Concertation Committee on Energy
COP	Conference of the Parties
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
CO₂eq	Carbon dioxide equivalent
CSC	Confédération des syndicats chrétiens
CREG	Commission de régulation de l'électricité et du gaz (Commission for Electricity and Gas Regulation)
CWAPE	Commission wallonne pour l'Énergie (Walloon regulator is the Walloon Commission for Energy)
CWEDD	Conseil wallon de l'Environnement pour le Développement durable
COBELPA	Association des fabricants de pâtes, papiers et cartons de Belgique
COMEOS	Fédération du commerce et des services
CPDT	Conférence Permanente du Développement Territorial
CRP	Collège régional de prospective (Regional Foresight College)
DECC	Department of Energy and Climate Change
DGO2	Direction générale opérationnelle Mobilité et Voies hydrauliques (Operational Directorate-General for Mobility and Waterways)
DGO3	Direction Générale Opérationnelle Agriculture, Ressources naturelles et Environnement (Operational Directorate-General for Agriculture, Natural Resources and the Environment)
DGO4	Direction générale opérationnelle de l'Aménagement du territoire, du Logement, du Patrimoine et de l'Énergie (Operational Directorate-General for Spatial Planning, Housing and Energy)
DGO6	Direction générale opérationnelle de l'Economie, de l'Emploi, de la Formation et de la Recherche (Operational Directorate-General for Economy, Employment and Research)
DGO7	Direction générale opérationnelle de la Fiscalité (Operational Directorate-General for taxation)
DSO	Distribution system operators
ECCP	European Climate Change Program
ECF	European Climate Foundation
ESCO	energy service companies
EDORA	Fédération des énergies renouvelables
EMAS	Eco-Management and Audit Scheme
EPM	Energy Policy Model
Essenscia	Fédération belge des industries chimiques et des sciences de la vie
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
FBB	Fédération belge de la brique
FBP	Federal Planning Bureau
FEB	Fédération des entreprises de Belgique
FEBEG	Fédération belge des entreprises électriques et gazières
FEBELCEM	Fédération de l'industrie cimentière
Febeliec	Fédération des consommateurs industriels d'électricité et de gaz naturel en Belgique
FEBELGRA	Fédération belge des industries graphiques
FEBETRA	Fédération royale belge des transporteurs et des prestataires de services logistiques
FEBIAC	Fédération belge de l'automobile et du cycle
FEDIEX	Fédération des industries extractives de Belgique
Fedustria	Fédération de l'industrie du textile, du bois et de l'ameublement

FETRA	Fédération des industries transformatrices de papier et de carton
FEVIA	Fédération de l'industrie alimentaire belge
FIV	Fédération de l'industrie du verre
FBB	Fédération belge de la brique
FPB	Fédération pétrolière belge
FPS	Federal Public Service
FWA	Fédération Wallonne de l'agriculture
F-Gases	Fluorinated gases
GDP	Gross domestic product
GHG	Green house gaz
GSV	Groupement de la sidérurgie
ICEDD	Institut de Conseil et d'Etudes en Développement Durable (Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development)
IDD	Institut pour un Développement Durable (Institute for a Sustainable Development)
IEV	Institut Emile Vandervelde
IEW	Inter-Environnement Wallonie
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IWEPS	Institut wallon de l'évaluation, de la prospective et de la statistique (Walloon Institute for Evaluation, Foresight and Statistics)
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
MAGICC	Model for the Assessment of Greenhouse Gas Induced Climate Change
MLP	Multi-level perspective
MR	Mouvement réformateur
NCEP	National Energy and Climate Plans
NGO	Non-governmental organizations
NDC	Nationally Determined Contributions
N₂O	Nitrogen dioxide
OPE²RA	Open-source Prospective Energy and Emissions Roadmap Analysis
ORES	Opérateur des réseaux gaz et électricité
PCA	Principal component analysis
PMC	Producteurs Belges de matériaux de constructions
ppm	Parts per million
PS	Parti socialiste
PTB	Parti du travail de Belgique
REDD+	Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation
SAS	Storyline and simulation
SNA	Social network analysis
SRPW	Système régional de recherche et de veille prospective wallon (Walloon Regional Prospective Research and Watch System)
SWOT	Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (
TSO	Transmission system operators
SNCB	Société nationale des chemins de fer belges
STET	Socio-technical energy transition
STS	Science and technology studies
SWEP	Société Wallonne de l'Évaluation et de la Prospective (Walloon Society for Evaluation and Foresight)
Synergrid	Fédération des gestionnaires de réseaux électricité et gaz en Belgique
TIMES	the Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System
UPB	Union Pétrolière Belge
UPTR	Union Professionnelle du Transport et de la Logistique
UCL	Université catholique de Louvain
UCM	Union des classes moyennes
ULB	Université libre de Bruxelles
ULg	Université de Liège
UK	United Kingdom
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNIPSO	Union des entreprises à profit social
UPB	Union pétrolière belge
UPTR	Union professionnelle du transport et de la logistique
UN	United Nations
UNEP	United Nations Environment Program
UNIPSO	Union des entreprises à profit social
UVCW	Union des Villes et Communes de Wallonie
UWE	Union wallonne des entreprises
VITO	Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (Flemish Institute for Technological Research)
WAM	With additional measures
WEM	With existing measures
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WG	Working Group
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature
°C	Degree Celsius

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

1. Towards a Social Analysis of Low-Carbon Scenarios

Box 1 | “Thousand Flowers”: The UK Civil Society-Led Low-Carbon Scenario

“An initial take-up of local generation options is aided by the growth of social movements to address climate change, including the ‘10:10’ and successor campaigns and the Transition Towns movement (Hopkins, 2008), which begins to demonstrate the feasibility of small-scale solutions in many UK cities and towns. A more local bottom-up diversity of solutions begins to flourish, with local community leadership in providing decentralized generation and energy conservation options. Increasingly strong obligations on energy companies to increase the energy efficiency of their consumers are imposed by the Government. These lead to new partnerships between energy companies, local authorities and housing associations to improve the energy efficiency of existing building stock. These are marketed as saving both money and emissions, to appeal to both financially and ‘green-minded’ users. Local district heating systems in urban areas are also increasingly installed more widely, led by local government offering incentives for private investment, after initial successful demonstration in new build developments. The acceptance of local energy efficiency, generation and heating schemes are reinforced by increasing levels of environmental awareness amongst the public and focus on wider ‘quality of life’ benefits, rather than narrow economic assessments of costs and benefits, through a greater focus by Government and the media on ‘happiness’ indicators rather than purely economic indicators. Thanks to the earlier high rates of deployment, a rapid growth in take-up of both domestic and non-domestic distributed generation options occurs in the 2020s. This is led by successful new entrant energy service companies (ESCOs) and some of the large energy companies that have also adopted an ESCO business model, working together with local authorities, housing associations and community groups. This takes place alongside a continuing focus by Government on incentives for improving the energy efficiency of existing and new building stock. Whilst some large energy companies continue to focus only on the centralized generation business model, with continuing large investments in coal carbon capture and storage (CCS) and nuclear power, others diversify by setting up ESCO-type business units to provide an alternative focus for the company’s growth. Electricity demand rises less than expected, despite significant penetration of electric heating and electric vehicles, as consumers demand higher technical energy efficiency of appliances and built infrastructure. Both domestic and non-domestic distributed generation achieve high levels of adoption, meeting nearly half of total demand by 2050. Greater energy efficiency improvements from technical and behavioural changes and use of microgeneration results in a 7.5% decrease in electricity demand by 2050 relative to 2009 levels. This demand is primarily met through a range of renewable energy supply technologies, including micro- and community scale biogas CHP, onshore and offshore wind, solar PV (as well as solar water heating), wave and tidal power, with some coal and gas with carbon capture and storage and remaining nuclear power stations, leading to electricity supply (including imports) in 2050 of 328 TWh. The distributed renewable generation is owned and operated by individuals, community groups and small and large ESCOs, whilst the remaining coal and gas with CCS and nuclear power stations are operated by large integrated energy companies.”

The narrative in the box above is an excerpt from the scenario “Thousand flowers” that has been developed as part of the project “Realising Transition Pathways¹” (see Foxon, 2013). This interdisciplinary project explores transition pathways for a UK low-carbon electricity future by 2050. It has developed and analysed three alternative possible **low-carbon scenarios** distinguished by their dominant governance logic: “Thousand flowers”, “Market Rules” and “Central Co-ordination”. As illustrated in the above-cited excerpt, in the “Thousand flowers” scenario, the low-carbon transition involves local bottom-up initiatives led by citizens, grassroots movements and subnational governments. As its name suggests, the “Market Rules” is based on a governance logic upon which firms drive the low-carbon transition with minimal interference of the state in the market. In contrast,

¹ <http://www.bath.ac.uk/realisingtransitionpathways/>

in the “Central Co-ordination” scenario, the UK government plays central role in the low-carbon transition. Those three governance logics result in radically different low-carbon futures – in term of technology, infrastructures, every day practices and societal organization (Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Foxon & *al.* 2013). This is related to the **co-evolving relation between society and technology** (Foxon & *al.*, 2010; Geels, 2004; Weber, 2003). Technological systems are indeed “*both socially constructed and society shaping*” (Hughes 1987, p. 45).

The “Transition Pathways to a Low-Carbon Economy” project is based on a complementarity-based approach combining qualitative scenarios methods and quantitative modelling. As shown in the following figure, the quantification of the narratives highlights a major shift from fossil fuel to renewable energy for producing electricity in the “Thousand Flowers” scenario [figure 1]. The model run further shows that such shift towards renewable energy should lead to a reduction of the domestic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associate to the power sector of 98% by 2050 compared to 2008 level. It exceeds the long-term GHG reduction target adopted in 2008 by UK in the Climate Change Act. Compared to “Market Rules” and “Central Co-ordination”, “Thousand Flowers” is the scenario that leads to the most important reduction in GHG emissions (Robertson & *al.*, 2017).

Figure 1. Quantification of electricity demand (a) and supply (b) in the “Thousand Flowers” scenario (Robertson & *al.* 2017, p. 301)

Since various public and private actors at the subnational, national, supranational and international levels started to adopt **long-term GHG reduction targets**, scenario building projects like the one illustrated above have flourished. Literature reveals an increasing number of analyses envisioning and exploring alternative images of low-carbon futures as well as transition pathways to reach those futures – i.e.: low-carbon scenario analyses (Miller & *al.*, 2015; Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Torrie & *al.*, 2013; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Scenario approach or “foresight” is intended to help policy-makers to navigate the maelstrom of confusion and conflicts generated by complex societal challenges such as climate change – here referred to as “**super-wicked**” problems. Typical scenario exercises aim at coping with uncertainty and conflicting values, and hence are often claimed as a suitable approach for knowing and governing super-wicked problems (Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Head, 2014; Ho, 2012; Kok & *al.*, 2011; Fobé & Brans, 2013; Sardar, 2010; Marien, 2010; Levin & *al.* 2009; Kosow & Gaßner 2008; Mulder, 2007).

When reviewing the scenario literature published over the recent years, we observe significant methodological developments, in particular at the level of the calculus or data-sets. These contributions have generated an increasing technical sophistication of scenario building methods. That contrasts with the relative **absence of social sciences research on scenarios** (Kaljonen & *al.*, 2012; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; Garb & *al.*, 2008; De Smedt, 2006). Scenario analyses have received little academic attention from social sciences, whether they are political science, sociology, philosophy of science or science and technology studies (STS). Yet, scenario analysis being, in essence, a social activity, social sciences scholars should consider it as an object of study (Garb & *al.*, 2008). Various issues could be addressed under a social scientific perspective on scenarios: “*there is the disciplinary linking of those that study social, technological, and biophysical systems; there are the epistemic questions regarding the coupling of more subjectively and intuitively produced storylines with the*

apparently objective enterprise of quantitative modelling; there are questions related to how the scientific and policy communities respond differently to the indeterminacy of the future versus the determinism of the models used; and there are questions of the intended and actual users and uses of scenario products and their linkage to policy” (Garb & al. 2008, p. 2).

The present thesis intends to bridge this research gap. Scenarios are here understood as **“boundary objects²” linking different social worlds** (van der Steen & al., 2013; Garb & al., 2008; Hulme & Dessai, 2008). In this thesis, two linkages are considered, starting with the link between **science and policy**. As previously mentioned, foresight is by its very nature an orientation and decision support tool. Both scenarios products and processes are intended to contribute – directly or indirectly – to policy-making in environment with high uncertainties and conflicting stakes (Ramos, 2006; De Smedt, 2006; Aligica, 2005; Mermet, 2005; Lévêque & Urien 2005). The second linkage is the disciplinary linking. Since scenario analysis is an interdisciplinary approach addressing technical and social aspects of a problem in a systemic and holistic way, it aims at linking **natural and social sciences** (Petit Jean, 2016; Godet & Durance, 2011; Garb & al. 2008; de Jouvenel, 1999). The interdisciplinary character of foresight is particularly distinguishable in the above-mentioned “Transition Pathways to a Low-Carbon Economy” project which explores the co-evolution between social and technical components of energy system by combining various qualitative and quantitative methods. This thesis aspires to create an enhanced understanding on **how scenario analyses perform such “boundary work”**.

More specifically, the following social analysis of low-carbon scenarios is based on a twofold perspective focusing, on the one hand, on the **interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance (i.e.: link between science and policy)**, and, on the other hand, on the **making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (i.e.: link between natural and social sciences)**. In other words, this analysis explores “scenarios in governance” and “governance in scenarios”. This twofold perspective on scenarios for knowing and governing low-carbon transition is illustrated in the figure below [Figure 2].

Figure 2. Overview of the research

² Boundary objects are “scientific objects which both inhabit several intersecting social worlds and satisfy the information requirements of each of them” (Star & Griesemer 1989, p. 393).

As further explained later in the manuscript, the thesis project includes three research axes, each based on its particular empirics. The objective of the present thesis thus consists in **providing an empirical contribution to social sciences research on low-carbon scenarios**.

2. Ontological and Epistemological Posture

As mentioned above, the objective of the thesis is to provide an empirical contribution to social sciences research on low-carbon scenarios. In social sciences, different research paradigms co-exist. A research paradigm is here understood as “*the basic belief system or worldview that guides the investigator, not only in choices of method but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways*” (Guba & Lincoln 1994, p. 105). In other words, each research is guided by basic assumptions stemming from foundational philosophical presuppositions concerning aspects such as the nature of “reality”, what we can know about the “reality” and how this knowledge can be produced. Those basic assumptions affect the undertaking of knowledge inquiry, the analysis of the data generated by the inquiry and the choice of the criteria for evaluating the quality of the research. It is therefore essential to recognize and acknowledge the posture of the research (Voros, 2007; Marsh & Furlong, 2002).

Five research paradigms are often distinguished³: positivism, post-positivism, critical theory, constructivism and participatory paradigm (Lincoln & Guba, 2000). Those can be differentiated regarding the answers given to ontological, epistemological, methodological and axiological questions – i.e.: “*what is the nature of ‘reality’ and therefore what is there that can be known?*”; “*what is the nature of knowledge, the relationship between the would-be knower and what can be know?*”; “*how can the would-be know or inquirer go about finding out whatever can be know?*”; “*what is intrinsically worthwhile?*” (Lincoln & Guba, 2000 in Voros 2007, p. 6). The following figure outlines the answers given to these questions for the five types of research paradigms considered [Figure 3].

	<i>Positivism</i>	<i>Post-positivism</i>	<i>Criticalism</i>	<i>Constructivism</i>	<i>Participatory</i>
<i>Ontology</i>	naïve realism – ‘real’ reality but apprehendable	critical realism – ‘real’ reality but only imperfectly and probabilistically apprehensible	historical realism – virtual reality shaped by social, political, cultural, economic, ethnic and gender values; crystallised over time	relativism – local and specific co-constructed realities	participatory reality – subjective-objective reality, co-created by mind and given cosmos
<i>Epistemology</i>	dualist / objectivist; findings ‘true’	modified dualist / objectivist; critical tradition / community; findings ‘probably true’	transactional / subjectivist; value-mediated findings	transactional / subjectivist; co-created findings	critical subjectivity in participatory transaction with cosmos; extended epistemology of experiential, presentational, propositional, and practical knowing; co-created findings
<i>Methodology</i>	experimental / manipulative; verification of hypotheses; chiefly quantitative methods	modified experimental / manipulative; critical multiplism; falsification of hypotheses; may include qualitative methods	dialogic / dialectical	hermeneutical / dialectical	political participation in collaborative action inquiry; primacy of the practical; use of language grounded in shared experiential context
<i>Axiology</i>	propositional knowing about the world is an end in itself, is intrinsically valuable		propositional, transactional knowing is instrumentally valuable as a means to social emancipation, which is an end in itself, is intrinsically valuable		practical knowing how to flourish with a balance of autonomy, cooperation, and hierarchy in a culture is an end in itself, is intrinsically valuable

Figure 3. Foundational stances of the five research paradigms (Voros 2007, p. 13)

Defining the ontological and epistemological posture of the research is by no means an easy task. The five research paradigms defined by Lincoln & Guba (2000) are ideal-typical models and do not exist as such. In practice, the boundaries between those different paradigms are permeable. It is therefore complex to put the research into a well-defined category. The positioning task is all the more complex as the following research is multidimensional, involving several interwoven literatures – and thus disciplines –, research axes and methodologies. The ontological and epistemological posture is therefore defined on the basis of how I, as a researcher, perceive the social “reality” and the making

³ Other research paradigm typologies have been proposed, but the typology developed by Lincoln & Guba (2000) is one of the most widely applied typologies (Voros, 2007).

of knowledge about it – assuming that this perception have guided the research. By this way, the research can be seen as constructivist.

Starting with the nature of “reality”, the present research assumes that the world is socially or discursively constructed. As a result, it considers that there is not one objective reality, but a multitude of subjective realities constructed by various actors. For instance, the conception of scenarios as boundary objects linking different social worlds, like science and policy, or natural and social science is socially constructed. It exists only in actor’s subjectivity and such subjectivity vary from one actor to another. This also applies to the social worlds “science”, “policy”, “natural sciences” and “social sciences”, as well as the boundaries that separate them. All these objects are socially constructed and does not exist *per se* – i.e.: independently of the interpretation we make of them.

The aim of the research is to understand the social constructions or interpretations of reality. The task of the researcher thus consists in making those “realities” observable and intelligible. The social constructions of reality can be made observable within the discourses or traditions (Marsh & Furlong, 2002). Intelligibility is created through iterative theoretical interpretation, that consists in reformulating the observed social constructions of reality into more general concepts (Lannoy, 2013). One must acknowledge that such theoretical interpretation is contingent upon researcher subjectivity. Inasmuch as the researcher lives in the social world, he is permeated by social constructions of reality, and therefore not completely “objective”. This is sometimes referred to as double hermeneutic: “*The word is interpreted by the actors (one hermeneutic level) and their interpretation is interpreted by the observer (a second hermeneutic level)*” (Marsh & Furlong 2002, p. 19). As a result, the knowledge produced is discursively or theoretically laden. Against that background, it can be considered that the inquirer is not “*separate and distinct from the object of knowledge*”. Instead, “*findings are co-created by the inquirer and the object of inquiry through the very act of inquiry itself*” (Voros 2007, p. 8).

This ontological and epistemological posture has implications regarding the choice of the method. As will be further discussed later, the following research is based on three empirical studies (see section “2. Empirical studies” in the presentation of the design of the research). Two of them rest on pure discourse analysis methods – the discourse of the actors being, as said before, a medium through which social constructions of reality can be observed. In the first study, I explore the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance on the basis of semi-structured interviews. In the second one, I assess the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition by applying a Q methodology, that is a qualitative but statistically supported survey method aiming at exploring subjectivity (see Barry & Proops, 1990). The last study aims at understanding the making of knowledge about governance in integrated energy models. With this aim in mind, I carried out a critical review of socio-technical energy transition models. This is not a discourse analysis *per se*, but it can be considered as such. Integrated models are human constructions. Their algorithms and hypothesis are contingent upon and reflect how modellers perceive the social reality. Those science-based artefacts tell much about social interpretations of reality. An analysis of the making of knowledge about governance in integrated models thus intends to understand the modellers’ subjective representations of reality. The methodological aspects of the research will be further discussed in the chapters devoted to the empirical studies (see Chapters III, IV and V).

The paradigmatic posture also influences the choice of the quality criteria of the research – an inquiry based on a constructivist perspective cannot be assessed like an inquiry based on a positivist perspective. Lincoln & Guba (2000) propose a set of criteria for judging the “goodness” of a research carried out under a constructivist perspective. Those can be split into two categories: the “trustworthiness” and the “authenticity” criteria. The “trustworthiness” criterion encompasses four criteria: credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability. Regarding the “authenticity” criteria, a research is considered as authentic if it results in an improved understanding of constructions previously provided by other researchers (Lincoln & Guba, 2000). I tried to integrate those criteria in the conception and realization of the research. In the present thesis, the

methodological approach has been described as exhaustively and transparently as possible. The reader should therefore be able to assess the quality of the present research.

3. Outline of the Thesis

The thesis manuscript is organized as follows. Chapter I presents the conceptual and theoretical framework of the research as well as the literature review. It leads to the identification of the three main research questions that structure the thesis. I then present the design of the research, providing an overview of the three empirical studies carried out as part of this research. Chapter II depicts the contextual background for the two first empirical studies. Chapters III, IV and V present the three empirical studies. Chapter III explores the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance on the basis of a multiple case study analysing the role of four energy foresight studies in policy-making. The two last chapters focuses on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios. Chapter IV provides an assessment of the knowledge needed to steer the low-carbon transition. Chapter V aims at contributing to the debate on the relations between quantitative modelling and social sciences by exposing a critical review of socio-technical energy transition (STET) models. *In fine*, the conclusion highlights the key contributions of the research as well as avenues for future research.

CHAPTER I.
**Scenarios for Knowing and Governing Super-
Wicked Problems**

CHAPTER I. Scenarios for Knowing and Governing Super-Wicked Problems

Introduction

The first chapter aims at providing the conceptual and theoretical framework of the research as well as the literature review. After presenting the contextual background, the first section of the chapter conceptualizes the low-carbon transition under the socio-technical approaches and the multi-level perspective on transition. The second section highlights the characteristics that make climate change a super-wicked problem, which allows to better comprehend the difficulties of policy-makers in knowing and governing the low-carbon transition. In that context, I demonstrate that such highly complex problems involving various actors whose values and interests differ cannot be addressed with traditional forms of knowledge productions and modes of governance. The third section introduces foresight, a policy-oriented approach aiming at envisioning and exploring alternative futures with scenarios. I present this non-predictive future-oriented approach as a suitable tool for tackling super-wicked problems like climate change. I then focus more specifically on low-carbon scenarios. The fourth section concerns the governance of the low-carbon transition. I first define and conceptualize this polysemic concept as well as the dimensions it encompasses – i.e.: *policy*, *politics* and *polity*. Based on this conceptual framework, I analyse the governance of the low-carbon transition, pointing the co-existence of traditional and “new” modes of governance. I finally discuss the knowledge gap surrounding the governance of the low-carbon transition. The last section of the chapter aims at connecting low-carbon scenarios and governance. This link is explored under a twofold perspective focusing on the one hand on the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance (i.e.: low-carbon scenarios in governance) and, on the other hand, on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (i.e.: governance in low-carbon scenarios).

1. Transition to a Low-Carbon Society in 2050

1.1. Context

On 11 December 2010, the world leaders gathered at the 16th session of the Conference of the Parties (COP 16) in Cancún agreed to limit the increase in global temperature to 2 Degree Celsius (°C) compared to the pre-industrial era (United Nations, 2011). This objective was confirmed and strengthened in the Paris Agreement adopted in 2015 at the COP 21 (United Nations, 2015). The Paris Agreement, that has been adopted by 195 states, is the first international treaty that provides legal effect to the 2°C objective (Gao & *al.*, 2017). The 2°C global temperature target corresponds to a translation in quantitative terms of the qualitative objective adopted in 1992 as part of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). The main objective of this convention is “*to achieve (...) stabilization of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system*” (United Nation 1992, p. 4). An increase in global temperature above 2°C could actually lead to serious, widespread and irreversible impacts on the climate system. They correspond, among others, to considerable species extinctions, global and regional food insecurity or impacts with a limited potential for adaptation. Note that some risks, such as those associated with extreme weather events, cannot be avoided even by limiting the increase in global temperature to 1°C or 2°C (IPCC, 2014a).

The adoption of the 2°C objective is the result of a long process involving back and forth between policy and science – here embodied by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) that has produced synthesis of current scientific knowledge based on extensive reviews of the literature since 1988. Today, the debate concerning the quantitative objective of limiting global warming is ongoing (Dahan & Guillemot, 2015). Considering that a 2°C temperature rise still exposes the most vulnerable regions to significant risks, small island states, least-developed countries and various non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are pushing for strengthening the objective to 1.5°C⁴ (Gao & *al.*, 2017). This more ambitious target has been in a way integrated in the Paris Agreement. The climate mitigation objective is actually formulated as follows in Article 2 of the Paris Agreement: “*Holding the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels*” (United Nations 2015, p. 3).

According to the IPCC, limiting the global temperature rise below 2°C involves stabilizing the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHG) in the atmosphere below 450 parts per million (ppm). In its Fifth Assessment Report, the IPCC asserts that “*emissions scenarios leading to CO₂-equivalent concentrations in 2100 of about 450ppm or lower are likely to maintain warming below 2°C over the 21st century relative to pre-industrial level*” (IPCC 2014a, p. 20). Stabilizing the concentration of GHG emissions below 450ppm requires a decrease in global GHG emissions of around 40-70% by 2050 compared to the 2010 level. This drastic reduction in GHG emissions should lead to emissions levels near zero or below by the end of the century (IPCC, 2014a). The pathway towards less carbon intensive society is generally referred to as “low-carbon transition”. The following graph summarizes the previously explained relationship between risks from climate change, temperature change, cumulative carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and changes in annual GHG emissions by 2050 [Figure 4].

⁴ Further information on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C and associated greenhouse gas emissions pathways can be found in the last publication of the IPCC (IPCC, 2018).

Figure 4. Relationship between risks from climate change (a), temperature change, cumulative CO₂ emissions (b) and changes in annual GHG emissions by 2050 (c) (IPCC 2014a, p. 18)

More concretely, with a view to achieving the 2°C objective anchored in the Paris Agreement, the Parties are intended to reach global peaking of GHG emission as soon as possible and to rapidly reduce GHG emission afterwards with a view to attain carbon neutrality in the second half of this century. Each Party has to define and review every five years its Nationally Determined Contributions⁵ (NDCs) to the global response to climate change that it intends to achieve (United Nations, 2015). According to the Article 4 of the Agreement, Party NDC “reflects its highest possible ambition, reflecting its common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities, in the light of the different national circumstances” (United Nations 2015, p. 4). In addition to the NDCs, the Parties have to submit long-term low-carbon strategies by 2020 (Service fédéral Climat, 2018).

The European Union (EU) and its Member States haven’t wait to sign the Paris Agreement to engage in a low-carbon transition. In February 2011, the European Council ratified the objective of reducing domestic GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050 compared to the 1990 level (European Council, 2011). This is in line with the decision to limit the increase in global temperature to 2°C adopted at the COP

⁵ <http://www4.unfccc.int/ndcregistry/Pages/All.aspx>

16 in Cancún. Shortly after, in March 2011, the European Commission published the “Roadmap for moving to a competitive low-carbon economy in 2050” (European Commission, 2011). This document includes various possible actions that could enable the EU to reduce its GHG emissions by 80-95% in 2050. It also “*outlines milestones which would show whether the EU is on course for reaching its target, policy challenges, investment needs and opportunities in different sectors*” (European Commission 2011, p. 3). It is in this context that some EU Member States and subnational governments have started to set GHG emission reduction targets, to draw up their own 2050 low-carbon roadmaps and to implement mitigation policies.

Ensuring the transition towards a low-carbon society by 2050 is however a major challenge for policy-makers. The characteristics of climate change problem that make the low-carbon transition so challenging will be discussed in the next section (see section “2. Low-carbon transition: A super-wicked problem” of the same chapter). Despite the increasing number of climate mitigation policies since the institutionalization of climate issues in the early 90’s, the global GHG emissions have continued to increase (Aykut & Dahan, 2016). In average, GHG emissions have grown by 1.3% per year between 1970 and 2000, and by 2.2% per year between 2000 and 2010 – as shown in the following figure [Figure 5]. According to IPCC, this continuous rise in emissions is principally driven by economic and population growth. It has led to unprecedented concentrations of GHG in the atmosphere, generating detectable effects throughout the climate system.

Figure 5. Total annual anthropogenic GHG emissions by gases between 1970 and 2010 (IPCC 2014b, p. 7)

The main anthropogenic GHG is CO₂, which accounted for nearly three quarters of global anthropogenic GHG. This gas is the result of fossil fuel combustion. The other GHG are the methane (CH₄), the nitrogen dioxide (N₂O) and the fluorinated gases (F-Gases). Many sectors contribute to global GHG emissions. Those are energy production, buildings, transports, industry, agriculture, forestry and other land use (IPCC, 2014a). As stated by Bulkeley & al., “*the causes of climate change are implicated in everyday acts of production and consumption and relate to the ways in which societies organize their transportation, housing, energy, water and food systems*” (Bulkeley & al. 2014, p. 1). The following figure summarizes the contribution of each sector in global GHG emissions [Figure 6].

Figure 6. Total anthropogenic GHG emissions by sector in 2010 (IPCC 2014b, p. 9)

Reducing GHG by 80-95% is therefore particularly difficult as it requires a paradigm shift in the way we produce and consume energy. Such a shift affects all aspects of economy and everyday life. Deep GHG emissions cuts can be achieved by combining various technological and structural changes such as replacing fossil fuels by lower-carbon energies like renewable energy or nuclear power, improving energy efficiency and performance of vehicles, deploying infrastructure and services required to enable a modal shift towards less emitting transport modes, increasing energy efficiency of buildings, applying technologies and measures to reduce GHG emissions of industrial sector, and developing energy recovery technologies in industries. More fundamentally, various behavioural (e.g.: modal shift, reduction in meat consumption, voluntary simplicity) and societal changes (e.g.: car sharing, fab lab) can also significantly contribute to reduce energy consumption in several sectors. In addition to substantial changes in energy system, modifications in land use can help to decrease GHG emissions. They concern the reduction of deforestation, reforestation, forest management, management of cropland and pastureland, and restoration of organic soils (BELSPO & Service fédéral Climat, 2014).

1.2. Conceptualization of the Low-Carbon Transition

1.2.1. Socio-Technical Approach

In the present research, the low-carbon transition is understood as a socio-technical transition (Geels, 2002; Geels & Schot, 2007; Smith & *al.*, 2010). In the field of (sustainability) transitions studies, the socio-technical approach “*adopt systemic view of far-reaching transformation processes of socio-technical systems*” (Markard & *al.*, 2012). Assuming the co-evolution of technology and society, this framework emphasizes the importance of social dimensions in transformation processes (Geels, 2004; Weber, 2003). The systemic view implies that a wide variety of elements are closely interrelated and depend heavily on each other (Markard & *al.*, 2012). Under the socio-technical approach, the energy system is conceptualized as socio-technical system. Such system includes the production, distribution and use of energy as well as the artefacts, knowledge, capital, cultural meaning and other types of resources that fulfil those functions. The evolution of the socio-technical system is the result of the activities of individuals or groups that form a network of actors. The activities of the actors are themselves guided by the rules and institutions they carry and (re)produce. In turn, both the activities

of the actors and the system of rules and institutions are shaped by the socio-technical system (Geels, 2004). The following figure summarizes the interactions between the socio-technical system, the network of actors and the system of rules and institutions [Figure 7].

Figure 7. Interactions between the socio-technical system, the network of actors and the system of rules and institutions (adapted from Geels 2004, p. 903)

A socio-technical transition corresponds to “a set of processes that lead to a fundamental shift in socio-technical systems” (Markard & al., 2012). Such a fundamental shift is multi-dimensional as it results of the coevolution between the different sub-systems of the socio-technical system, the activities of the actors and the system of rules and institutions.

1.2.2. Multi-Level Perspective on Transition

In transition studies literature, the socio-technical transition is often conceptualized through the multi-level perspective (MPL). This conceptual framework enables to understand the way fundamental changes occur (or not) in socio-technical systems (Foxon, 2011). Under the MLP, the socio-technical transition is the outcome of the interactions between three nested levels of reality characterized by an increasing level of stability: the niches (micro), the regime (meso) and the landscape (macro) (Grünwald & al., 2013; Foxon, 2011; Geels, 2012 and 2004; Boulanger, 2008). The niches are protected spaces within which radical innovations can develop (e.g.: R&D laboratories, pilot projects, subsidies). The niche innovations can provide seeds for fundamental changes. The regime is the locus of established practices and associated rules. The socio-technical landscape corresponds to the slow-changing mega trends (e.g.: spatial structures, political ideologies, societal values, beliefs, concerns, geopolitics, demographics) and exogenous shocks (e.g.: wars, disasters, crises) that form the broader context in which regimes and niches develop. Generally, the actors have little or no influence over it (Geels & al., 1017; Geels, 2012). The following figure illustrates the way the three levels are interlocked [Figure 8].

Figure 8. Interweaving of niches, regimes and landscape under the MLP on transition (Geels 2012, p. 473).

Socio-technical transition develops over several decades. Due to resistance to changes, lock-in and path-dependence mechanisms, the innovations that occur within the regime are more about replicating this regime than changing it fundamentally. Current regime is actually maintained, defended and incrementally improved by incumbents, who are the dominant actors of this regime. Significant changes rather come from slow changes in the landscape. Such changes can create pressure on the regime and weaken it. This creates windows of opportunities for niche innovations, as the destabilization of the regime entails a phase of reconfiguration during which innovations can penetrate into the existing regime and modify it (Geels & *al.* 2017; Grünewald & *al.*, 2013; Geels, 2012; Foxon, 2011; Boulanger, 2008). The figure hereunder shows the way the niches, the regime and the landscape interact through time as part of a socio-technical transition [Figure 9].

Figure 9. Interactions through time between niches, regimes and landscape under the MLP on transition (Geels & Schot 2007, p. 401)

The socio-technical approach and the MLP on transition are particularly suitable to understand the long-term, multidimensional and radical change process through which dominant unsustainable socio-technical systems become more sustainable (Markard & *al.*, 2012). This conceptual framework is therefore frequently used to analyse sustainability transitions (see Mok & Gaziulusoy, 2018; Næss & Vogel, 2012; Smith & *al.*, 2010), including the low-carbon transition (see Moradi & Vagnoni, 2018; Berkeley, 2017; Geels & *al.*, 2017 and 2016; Kern, 2012; Geels, 2012; Foxon, 2011; van Bree, 2010). When conceptualizing the low-carbon transition as a socio-technical transition, one acknowledges that it does “*not just involve firms and consumers but also a wider range of actors such as civil society groups, the media, local residents, city authorities, political parties, advisory bodies, and government ministries*” and that it is “*not only about the market diffusion of new technologies but also about changes in user practices, cultural discourses, and broader political struggles*” (Geels & *al.* 2017, p. 463-463). The shift from the current dominant high-carbon regime to a low-carbon regime is therefore the result of intricate interplays between the various socio-technical components of the energy system, its network of actors and the system of rules and institutions that guide those actors. When we further analyse the low-carbon transition with the MLP on transition, we note that the high carbon regime is characterized by different elements such as a dependency on fossil fuels, large-scale centralized power generation, extensive road network or efficiency levels correlated to national levels of welfare. On their side, niche innovations are typically renewable energy (e.g.: wind, photovoltaic, biomass...), energy saving measures (e.g.: energy efficiency and performance of vehicles, buildings or industries), electrical vehicles, smart grids or smart appliances. *In fine*, the landscape includes, among other, the paramountcy of the paradigm of economic growth, the increasing global population, the higher standards of living in developing and transitional countries, the depletion of fossil resources and the rising awareness of climate issues (VITO, 2012b). The landscape is therefore crossed by currents in opposite directions that either strengthen or weaken the high carbon regime.

2. Low-Carbon Transition: A Super-Wicked Problem

2.1. Wicked Nature of the Low-Carbon Transition

As shown previously, despite the increasing number of climate mitigation policies since the institutionalization of climate problem in the early 90's, the global GHG emissions have continued to rise (Aykut & Dahan, 2016) (see section "1.1. Context" of the same chapter). This is a symptom of the challenging nature of the low-carbon transition. The transition towards a low-carbon society is a major challenge, both in terms of knowledge and governance. It is indeed extremely difficult for policy makers to understand and respond effectively to problems as complex as climate change (Head, 2014). Conceptualizing climate change as a "super-wicked" problem allows to better comprehend the difficulties of policy-makers to design and implement mitigation policies (Peters, 2018; Sun & Yang, 2016; Fobé & Brans, 2013; Lazaruss, 2009; Levin & *al.*, 2010; Levin & *al.*, 2007).

The concept of "wicked" problems was initially developed by Rittel & Webber (1973) in contrast to "tame" rationality-responsive problems, which are definable, dissociable and representable with linear cause-effect patterns (Sun & Yang, 2016). Rittel & Webber (1973) used the term "wicked" in a sense similar to "*that of "malignant" (in contrast to "benign") or "vicious" (like a circle) or "tricky" (like a leprechaun) or "aggressive" (like a lion, in contrast to the docility of a lamb)*" (Rittel & Webber 1973, p. 160). Such problems involve complex interconnections of multiple causes, effects and actors whose values and interests differs. Those components of wicked problems are embedded in an open non-linear dynamic system (Levin & *al.*, 2017; Wahl, 2017; FitzGibbon & Mensah, 2012). Wicked problems were defined by Rittel as "*a class of social system problems which are ill-formulated, where the information is confusing, where there are many clients and decision makers with conflicting values, and where the ramifications of the whole system are thoroughly confusing*" (Rittel s.d. in Churchman 1967, p. 141). Rittel & Webber (1973) originally referred to the concept of wicked problems to describe city planning problems, but this concept has been increasingly used to characterize the complex contemporary environmental problems (Kuhmonen, 2018; Endl, 2017), including climate change (Lethonen & *al.*, 2018; Peters, 2018; Sun & Yang, 2016; Termeer & *al.*, 2016; Stang & Ujvari, 2015; Head, 2014; FitzGibbon & Mensah, 2012; Lazarus, 2009; Levin & *al.*, 2009; Noble & Bennett, 2007).

Rittel & Webber (1973) identified ten characteristics that make wicked problems so challenging for policy-makers, and climate change meet all of these characteristics. The following section explores the challenging nature of climate change by describing it as a wicked problem as defined by Rittel & Webber (1973).

(1) "There is no definitive formulation of a wicked problem."

Defining a problem requires to gather all the information needed to comprehend and solve it. Since the information needed to comprehend a problem depends on the considered solution, all the possible solutions must be identified beforehand in order to provide an exhaustive definition of the problem. Rittel & Webber explain that "*One cannot understand the problem without knowing about its context; one cannot meaningfully search for information without the orientation of a solution concept; one cannot first understand, then solve*" (Rittel & Webber 1973, p. 162). Describing all the potential solutions is impossible in the case of wicked problems. Given their multi-causal nature, the wicked problems have actually a substantial number of potential solutions. The range of potential solutions is never stabilized since the wicked problems evolve continuously through time. Moreover, every solution to wicked problem reveals new dimensions of the problem (Conklin, 2005).

There is no clear and definitive problem definition of climate change (Levin & *al.*, 2007). If we attempt to understand the problem of climate change, a never-ending stream of questions emerges: Is the combustion of fossil fuel at the root of the unprecedented concentrations of GHG in the atmosphere we are facing today? Is it related to inefficient combustion process or to a greater quantity of fossil fuel consumed? Assuming the later hypothesis, why? Because of economic or population growth? And so forth.

(2) “Wicked problems have no stopping rule.”

There is no final optimal solution to wicked problems. Wicked problems are never completely solved – the problem resolution process stopping when the situation is perceived acceptable or when no more time, money or energy is available. The chain of effects generated by the problem actually never ends (Whal, 2017; Conklin, 2005; Rittel & Webber 1973).

The problem of climate change cannot be completely resolved. Even if we stopped emitting GHG today, the global temperature would still increase, creating a chain of consequences on sea levels, precipitation trends, hydrological cycles (...) that would, in turn, have impacts on ecosystems, and by extension, on various dimensions of human life (Levin & al., 2007).

(3) “Solutions to wicked problems are not true-or-false, but good-or-bad.”

According to Levin & al., “the solution to a wicked problem is not a quest to find truth; rather it is a journey toward an optimal end that is judged in light of norms and interests” (Levin & al. 2007, p. 5). Each actor judges the potential solutions through its own worldviews, values, ideologies and interests. There are therefore no right or wrong solutions to wicked problems. Instead, a solution can be “better”, “worse”, “satisfying”, “good enough” for this or that actor (Whal, 2017; Conklin, 2005; Rittel & Webber, 1973).

Should we limit the global temperature rise to 1.5°C or 2°C? Should we capture and store the carbon? Should we replace fossil fuel by renewable energy or nuclear power? Should we reduce our energy consumption by improving energy efficiency or by changing our behaviour? There is no right or wrong answer for all these questions. Instead, some solutions might appear better or worse depending on to whom the questions are addressed. For instance, while environmental NGO’s might prefer developing renewable energy, incumbent actors might favour nuclear power.

(4) “There is no immediate and no ultimate test of a solution to a wicked problem.”

We cannot assess the effects of an attempt to solve wicked problem right after its implementation. All potential solutions create waves of unintended consequences for a practically unlimited period of time (Conklin, 2005; Rittel & Webber, 1973). Those effects are likely either to exacerbate the original wicked problem and transform it into a “super-wicked” problem (Sun & Yang, 2016; Lazaruss, 2009; Levin & al., 2009) or to generate new wicked problems (Whal, 2017; Conklin, 2005). All the effects of a solution to a wicked problem cannot be assessed because the waves of consequences are diffuse and virtually never-ending (Rittel & Webber, 1973).

Reducing drastically GHG emissions to reach a low-carbon society requires a paradigm shift in the way we produce and consume energy. Transformative solutions to reduce GHG in the sectors of energy production, industry, transport or building will generate waves of long-lasting effects on various components of the system (e.g.: economy, society, environment). It is impossible to trace all the waves of effects generated by the implementation of such solutions.

(5) “Every solution to a wicked problem is a ‘one-shot operation’; because there is no opportunity to learn by trial and error, every attempt counts significantly.”

As mentioned in the previous point, all the potential solutions to wicked problem create waves of unintended consequences. Those consequences not only have a long half live, but they are also irreversible (Rittel & Webber, 1973). Moreover, the solutions are often expensive (Conklin, 2005). As a result, we cannot implement a solution to see how it works, and then undo it if it doesn’t deliver expected results (Rittel & Webber, 1973).

The potential solutions to climate change are often expensive and have irreversible consequences. For example, a possible solution to mitigate climate change consists in developing a smart interconnected electricity network to enable intermittent renewable energy deployment. We can hardly go back after initiating such large public work because of the important investment injected in the project and the impacts on the community (Levin & al., 2007; Rittel & Webber, 1973).

(6) “Wicked problems do not have an enumerable (or an exhaustively describable) set of potential solutions, nor is there a well-described set of permissible operations that may be incorporated into the plan.”

Since there is no definitive formulation of a wicked problem, there is also no definitive formulation of the set of solutions to such a problem. It is indeed impossible to identify and consider all the potential solutions to a wicked problem (Rittel & Webber, 1973).

An uncountable number of potential solutions to address climate change exist. Among the solutions to mitigate climate change, we find various technological (e.g.: renewable energy, efficiency, electrification, carbon capture and storage...), behavioural (e.g.: modal shift, reduction in meat consumption, voluntary simplicity) and societal changes (e.g.: car sharing, fab lab). The range of potential solutions evolves constantly: Some solutions are progressively abandoned, while others emerge. Moreover, among the range of potential solutions, no solution will solve the problem on its own. Mitigating climate change requires the implementation of a mix of solutions (Levin & *al.*, 2007).

(7) “Every wicked problem is essentially unique.”

Every wicked problem is unique because it involves a previously unseen constellation of interconnected causes, effects and actors articulated in a specific system (Andersson & Törnberg, 2018; Whal, 2017; Conklin, 2005). A mix of solutions must therefore be custom designed for each new wicked problem (Conklin, 2005).

Climate change is profoundly different from other environmental problems. The type of solutions that have been implemented to solve other environmental problems does not work when applied to climate change. For instance, in the 90’s, when developing the Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (United Nation, 1998), the international community drew its inspiration from the Montreal Protocol on substances that deplete the ozone layer that was adopted ten years earlier (United Nations, 1987). Since it led to a phasing out of substances responsible for ozone depletion that resulted in a progressive recovery of the ozone layer, the Montreal Protocol is actually seen as one of the major successes of the international cooperation (Gemenne, 2009). One cannot say the same for the Kyoto Protocol, the results of which being very mixed. Replicating the solutions developed for other environmental problems will not solve the problem of climate change. This problem is unique and the mix of solutions to address still remains to be invented.

Moreover, the problem of climate change differs regarding to the context. Even if it is a global problem, its impacts vary *“from nation-to-nation, community-to-community, and ecosystem-to-ecosystem”* (Levin & *al.* 2007, p. 7). For instance, the impacts of climate change are different in intensity and type between small island states, least-developed countries and developed countries, between poor and rich persons within each country, but also between more or less adaptable species. The various regions make also different and unequal contributions to GHG emissions and do not have similar capabilities to address the problem of climate change. Those local specific features are taken into account in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) with the *“Common but Differentiated Responsibilities”* (CBDR) principle. A mix of solutions to climate change must therefore be tailor-made for each particular context (Levin & *al.*, 2009).

(8) “Every wicked problem can be considered to be a symptom of another problem.”

We observe that every wicked problem is the symptom of another wicked problem, that is, in turn, the symptom of another *“higher level”* wicked problem (Rittel & Webber, 1973). Every wicked problem is actually connected to others (Andersson & Törnberg, 2018; Whal, 2017).

Climate change is connected to other wicked problems. For instance, the problem of biodiversity loss can be seen as a symptom of climate change. In turn, the rise in GHG emissions responsible for climate change can be considered as a symptom of *“higher level”* wicked problem such as the global population growth, the paradigm of economic growth, globalization, consumerism or failing institutions. This raises the following question: At which level should the problem be addressed? Should we treat the

symptoms or get to the root of problems – knowing that the higher the level of the problem, the more it is difficult to solve it (Levin & *al.*, 2007).

(9) “The existence of a discrepancy representing a wicked problem can be explained in numerous ways. The choice of explanation determines the nature of the problem’s resolution.”

Wicked problems involve multiple stakeholders with different worldviews, values, ideologies and interests. Each actor understands those multi-dimensional problems through its proper frame of reference (Andersson & Törnberg, 2018). The different actors concur with a causal model that seems to be the more plausible to them, but also the one that best meet their interests and values. The choice of the causal model actually influences the nature of the solutions selected to solve the problem (Whal, 2017; Conklin, 2005). The diversity of perspectives regarding the problem and its solutions gives rise to conflicts among the different actors concerned by the problem.

Climate changes involves many actors whose values and interests differ (e.g.: political and administrative authorities, energy market operators, employers’ federations, workers unions, environmental NGOs, scientists, citizens). Even if there is now more or less a consensus about the existence of a problem and about the anthropogenic origin of this problem, the causal model behind the rise in GHG emissions generated by human activities is uncertain and controversial (Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). Each actor has its own vision of the causes behind climate change, which partly influences his view of the way to address this problem. For instance, some consider climate change as a market failure generated by the externalization of the costs associated with the negative environmental and social impacts of GHG emissions. For them, internalizing those negative externalities by assigning a price to GHG emissions is part of the solution (Andrew, 2008). Others, in line with the report “The limits to growth” of the Club of Rome (Meadows & *al.*, 1972), see climate change as a consequence of the paradigm of constant economic growth. They believe that a deprioritization of economic growth as policy goal with a shift to low-growth, no growth or degrowth society is needed to reduce GHG emissions (Koch, 2015; Victor, 2012). The divergences of opinions regarding the causes and solutions to climate change give rise to conflicts between the different actors involved in the low-carbon transition.

(10) “The planner has no right to be wrong.”

The last characteristic of wicked problem stated by Rittel & Webber (1973) is that political-administrative authorities are not allowed to make mistake: “Here the aim is not to find the truth, but to improve some characteristics of the world where people live. Planners are liable for the consequences of the actions they generate; the effects can matter a great deal to those people that are touched by those actions” (Rittel & Webber 1973, p. 167).

Every political action (or inaction) on climate change can have considerable impacts on individuals. Consequently, political-administrative authorities have no right to be wrong⁶.

A number of authors consider that all the challenges associated with climate change are not completely captured in the definition of wicked problem stated by Rittel & Webber (1973), and that a few extra characteristics render climate change a “**super-wicked**” problem (Peters, 2018; Sun & Yang, 2016; Lazaruss, 2009; Levin & *al.*, 2010; Levin & *al.*, 2007). Levin & *al.* (2010) have added four characteristics to the definition proposed by Rittel & Webber (1973).

⁶ I would like to point out that I do not share the point of view of Rittel & Webber (1973) that (5) “Every solution to a wicked problem is a ‘one-shot operation’; because there is no opportunity to learn by trial and error, every attempt counts significantly” and that (10) “The planner has no right to be wrong”. For me, the fear of error can generate blockages preventing the implementation of innovative but risky actions, leading to conservative decisions, or even inaction. I think that mistakes should be tolerated because they allow to learn from them. Trial and error learning is indeed a potentially powerful method for addressing complex problems.

(11) “Time is running out.”

This time dimension often distinguishes environmental problems from social problems. Super-wicked problems are characterized by a certain degree of urgency. Levin & *al.* explain that, at one point, this type of problem may “*be too acute, have too much impact, or, in the case of climate change, owing to the time lag effects of various GHG, be too late to stop or reverse*” (Levin & *al.* 2007, p. 8). As mentioned earlier, limiting global warming to below 2°C requires a decrease in global GHG emissions of around 40-70% by 2050 compared to the 2010 level (IPCC, 2014a) (see section “1.1. Context” of the same chapter). More the peak of GHG emissions occurs late, more the room for manoeuvre to ensuring the low-carbon transition by 2050 decreases. Consequently, as time passes, limiting global warming to below 2°C is becoming increasingly challenging.

(12) “There is no central authority.”

There is no central authority holding all the political levers to solve the problem of climate change. Since climate change is not limited to national borders, all the states will have to contribute to solve this problem in accordance with the principle of Common but Differentiated Responsibilities. Within each nation-state, the competences to mitigate climate change are fragmented between different political-administrative authorities. The various sectors contributing to GHG emissions (i.e.: energy production, buildings, transports, industry, agriculture, forestry and other land use) are actually controlled by different authorities. Mitigating climate change therefore requires coordination among states, but also among multiple political domains and levels of power within each state. The lack of central authority makes this coordination particularly challenging (Head, 2014; Levin & *al.* 2007).

(13) “Those seeking to end the problem are also causing it.”

Unlike most other environmental problems with well-defined protagonists and antagonists, the individuals and groups who try to mitigate climate change have contributed to climate change and continue to do so. GHG emissions result from our daily practices, and even if we can reduce our emissions by relying on less carbon intensive goods and services, or simply by consuming less, we still generate GHG emissions (Levin & *al.* 2007).

(14) “Hyperbolic discounting”

There is no direct link between the quantity of GHG emitted by a state or a generation and the impacts that affect that state or generation. While they were and still are the largest emitters of GHG emissions, most industrialized countries are not yet significantly affected by climate change impacts. Conversely, even if their contribution to global GHG emissions is very limited, small island states and developing countries are already experiencing the impacts of climate change. The impacts take the form of floods, growing scarcity of water resources, or drop in agricultural yields attributable to droughts. Those regions are all the more affected as they generally have low financial capacity to implement measures to adapt to climate change. To this geographical injustice, one must add an intergenerational injustice. The past and present generations have emitted GHG emissions and continue to do so, but it is probably our grandchildren's generation which will be the most affected by climate change. Several factors explain the transfer of the impacts of GHG to future generations: The significant atmospheric build-up of GHG, the long lifespan of GHG in the atmosphere, the irreversibility of damages caused by climate change and the natural inertia of climate system (Gemenne, 2015). The geographic and temporal distance between the major contributors to GHG and the victims of climate change does not encourage current authorities of industrialized countries to implement ambitious mitigation policies. Such policies would probably have negative impacts and no noticeable results on climate change in the short term, which make their implementation difficult (Lazarus, 2009). Levin & *al.* refer to the concept of “hyperbolic discounting” used by behaviour economists to qualify this tendency of human beings to “*discount the future even beyond what the economic tool of the discount rate suggests is rational*” (Levin & *al.* 2010, p. 8). The hyperbolic discounting is often employed to describe the tendency of

smokers to decide to smoke based on immediate gratification, while they know that tobacco addiction has negative impacts on human health. In the case of climate change, individuals are aware that climate change will have significant impacts on the future welfare, but they tend to make decisions that ignore those impacts and favour the present welfare. To justify such decision, individuals often irrationally refer to the fact that the exact impacts are not certain for any individual. Note that behaviour economists have shown that individuals and groups who recognize that they are subject to hyperbolic discounting can counteract it (Levin & *al.*, 2010).

I would like to highlight the fact that other frameworks, such as Beck's risk society thesis or the "socio-technical controversies" defined by Callon et *al.* (2001) for example, could be mobilized to conceptualize the problem of climate change. Alternative conceptual frameworks could shed light on other aspects of the problem that are not highlighted when conceptualizing it as a super-wicked problem. I chose to define climate change as a super-wicked problem, because this concept provides an easy way to introduce the scenario approach. As explained later in the text (see section "3.2. Scenarios Tackling Super-Wicked Problems" of the same chapter), foresight is considered by many authors as a suitable approach for analysing the future developments of wicked problems (Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Head, 2014; Ho, 2012; Kok & al., 2011; Fobé & Brans, 2013; Sardar, 2010; Marien, 2010 ; Levin & al., 2009; Kosow & Gaßner 2008; Mulder, 2007). Incidentally, the 2015 edition of the World Conference of Futures Research⁷, which brings together each year the main actors in the field of foresight, focused on futures studies for tackling wicked problems.

2.2. Forms of Knowledge Production and Modes of Governance to Address Super-Wicked Problems

The conceptualization of climate change as a super-wicked problem allows to better comprehend the difficulties of policy-makers in understanding and responding to climate change. Indeed, super-wicked problems entail broad knowledge production and governance challenges. Against that background, several authors maintain that those highly complex problems involving various actors whose interests and values differ cannot be addressed with traditional forms of knowledge production and modes of governance (Wright & *al.*, 2018; Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Batie, 2008; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994). The following section discuss the knowledge production and governance challenges associated with super-wicked problems.

2.2.1. From Normal Science to Post-Normal Science and Foresight

According to many authors, traditional ways of producing knowledge, here referred to as "normal" science (see Kuhn⁸, 1970), do not successfully address wicked problems (Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Batie, 2008; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994). Batie claims that "*normal science assumption and approaches are inadequate for addressing the complexities of wicked problems in a policy context*" (Batie 2008, p. 1176). It actually appears that such mode of knowledge production fails to recognize the non-linear, unpredictable, uncertain, value-laden and transversal nature of wicked problems (Wright & *al.*, 2018; Head, 2014; Batie, 2008; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994).

Sun & Yang explain that those highly complex problems cannot be understood under the traditional linear-rational model of sciences "*which takes the straightforward analytical approach of solving problems through cause-effect mathematical equations, or with references to specific assumed logical-positivist laws*" (Sun & Yang 2016, p. 4). The linear-rational model of sciences, which is dominant in

⁷ <https://futuresconference2015.wordpress.com>

⁸ Kuhn (1970) considered scientific activity as a "puzzle-solving", which assumes that a given problem has a solution.

natural sciences and engineering, assumes the existence of simple linear causes and effects of problems, the capacity to predict the future by observing past trends, and the ability of science to control nature. Such model is considered by many authors as not suitable to understand the intricate interconnection of the multiple causes, effects and actors of wicked problems, and even less to envision future development of such complex problems (Sun & Yang 2016; FitzGibbon & Mensah, 2012; Batie, 2008; Funtowicz & Ravetz 1994). We indeed observe that *“the well-known difficulties, if not impossibility, of even probabilistic prediction in the social sciences are magnified for super-wicked problems”* (Levin & al. 2007, p. 10). Just like most of the policy problems, wicked problems are imbedded in open non-linear dynamic systems, where individuals interact in a reflective and unpredictable manner. This, coupled with their high level of complexity, generates a lot of uncertainty regarding the evolution of wicked problems. As a result, the future development of wicked problems cannot be predicted by extrapolating past trends (Sun & Yang 2016; Levin & al., 2007; Batie 2008; Funtowicz & Ravetz 1994). According to Batie (2008), the linear model of sciences might even have contributed to the emergence of wicked problems. Against that background, systemic approaches acknowledging and dealing with their inherent complexity seem necessary to address wicked problems (Wright & al., 2018).

Another feature of the traditional mode of knowledge production is the “silo” nature of mono-disciplinary approaches. A problem is typically split into several parts that correspond to different academic disciplines. One takes a part of the problem and try to find a solution to this specific part, letting the other parts to someone else (de Jouvenel, 2004; Churchman, 1967). Churchman claims that *“attempts to tame a part of a wicked problem, but not the whole, is morally wrong”* (Churchman 1967, p. 142). This approach actually entails a risk of forgetting some parts of the problem (Wright & al., 2018; Churchman 1967). In addition to the risk of exclusion, the monodisciplinary approach does not provide an understanding of the problem in its wholeness, ignoring the complex articulations between its different dimensions (Wright & al., 2018). The limits of the traditional discipline-based approach are widely discussed in the literature (see Holm & al., 2013; Brewer, 1999). Those have been ironically summarized by Brewer as follow: *“The world has problems, but universities have departments”* (Brewer 1999, p. 328). In that context, many authors consider that wicked problems should be addressed in their entirety, ideally through transdisciplinary approaches (Lethonen, 2018; Andersen, 2016; Wright & al., 2018; Whal, 2017; Sun & Yang, 2016; Batie, 2008; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994). Given the highly complex nature of wicked foresight and the limited cognitive processing capacity of the human mind, Wright & al. (2018) proposes an approach involving structured decomposition and subsequent recomposition of the problem.

Finally, as explained in the previous section, wicked problems are characterized by irreducible uncertainties and high values conflicts (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994; Rittel & Webber, 1973) (see section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter). However, it appears that these two components of wicked problems are not addressed in traditional modes of knowledge production, but rather the opposite. As explained by Funtowicz & Ravetz, *“systems uncertainties and decision stakes are the opposites attributes that had traditionally been thought to characterize science, namely its certainty and its value neutrality”* (Funtowicz & Ravetz 1994, p. 1882). For several authors, one should cope with uncertainties and consider values conflicts when addressing wicked problems (Wright & al., 2018; Andersson & Törnberg, 2018; Batie, 2008; Ravetz, 2004; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993).

Compared to classic wicked problems, climate change has four extra characteristics that make it a super-wicked problem. As a reminder, they are the urgency that reduces the room for manoeuvre to ensuring the low-carbon transition by 2050 as time passes; the lack of central authority that raises the question about the coordination among states, but also among multiple political domains and levels of power within each state; the absence of well-defined protagonists and antagonists as those seeking to solve the problem are also causing it; and the hyperbolic discounting that incites human beings to make irrational decisions that discount the future welfare in favour of present satisfaction. The

knowledge production challenges associated with those specific characteristics have, as far as I know, not been discussed in the literature. In my opinion, the four extra characteristics generate additional challenges more in terms of governance, than in terms of knowledge production. The governance challenges associated with super-wicked problems will be discussed later (see section “4.2. Governance of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter).

In light of the abovementioned limits of the traditional ways of producing knowledge, several authors claim that wicked problems should be addressed with multidisciplinary approaches embracing their inherent complexity, non-linearity, unpredictability, uncertainty, and conflicting values (Head, 2014; Batie, 2008). Post-normal science emerged in the early 90’s as a response to wicked problems (Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Batie, 2008; Ravetz, 2004; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993). Funtowicz & Ravetz developed this concept to refer to a knowledge production mode aiming at addressing problems “*where facts are uncertain, values in dispute, stakes high and decisions urgent*” (Funtowicz & Ravetz 1993, p. 744). In such an approach, “*uncertainty is not banished but is managed, and values are not presupposed but are made explicit*” (Funtowicz & Ravetz 1993, p. 740). Post-normal science makes values conflicts explicit by involving stakeholders in the quality assurance of the scientific inputs (Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993). This “extended peer community” process is commonly referred to as “participation” (Ravetz, 2011). The following figure illustrates the differences between normal science and post-normal science in addressing uncertainties and values [Figure 10]. Post-normal science has been used as a scientific approach to address global environmental issues, including climate change (Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Saloranta, 2001).

Figure 10. Post-normal science diagram (adapted from Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994 in Miedzinski 2015, p. 59)

When it comes to analysing the future developments of wicked problems, foresight is often considered as a suitable approach (Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Head, 2014; Ho, 2012; Kok & *al.*, 2011; Fobé & Brans, 2013; Sardar, 2010; Marien, 2010; Levin & *al.* 2009; Kosow & Gaßner, 2008; Mulder, 2007). This approach that aims at envisioning and exploring alternative images of the future with scenarios distinguishes from normal sciences and has many similarities with post-normal sciences as defined by Funtowicz & Ravetz (1993) (Miedzinski, 2015; Guimarães & *al.*, 2007; von Schomberg & *al.*, 2005). Scenario approach and its applications in the field of climate change will be further presented in the next section (see section “3. Knowing super-wicked problems” of the same chapter).

2.2.2. From Traditional Top-Down Modes of Governance to Bottom-Up Approaches Involving Stakeholders

A number of authors explain that just like the classic ways of producing knowledge, the traditional modes of governance do not succeed in addressing wicked problems. They maintain that traditional top-down technocratic approaches are obsolete for governing wicked problems (Termeer & *al.*, 2016; Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). In that context, Koppenjan & Klijn state that *“the wicked problems that confront governments, private companies, and societal interest groups in a complex society require a different, new approach”* (Koppenjan & Klijn 2004, p. 7).

Several characteristics of wicked problems make them difficult to handle for policy-makers. First of all, as said before, every wicked problem is essentially unique and replicating solutions that have been formulated for addressing other wicked problems does not work (see section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter). A specific mix of solutions must therefore be custom designed for each new wicked problem (Conklin, 2005; Rittel & Webber, 1973). Policy-makers have to apply their creativity to develop such solutions. Solutions development is particularly difficult since there is no opportunity to learn by trial and error when it comes to wicked problems – policy-makers having no right to be wrong (Rittel & Webber, 1973). In the specific case of climate change, the problem-solving process is even more challenging as time is running out (Levin & *al.*, 2010). In addition to the difficulty in designing innovative solutions, the implementation of such solutions faces the inability of traditional institutions to allow or enable innovations (Termeer & *al.*, 2016). Tensions between new approaches and those of the established governance systems emerge, reflecting intricate power games (Termeer & *al.*, 2016; Hendriks & Grin, 2007). Such tensions are particularly important in the case of climate governance because the majority of the institutions were designed at a time where climate change was not a public issue (Termeer & *al.*, 2016).

Another difficulty for devising policy responses to wicked problems lies in comprehending such complex problems. As explained in the previous section, wicked problems are ill-defined (see section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter). The nature of those problems as well as the set of solutions to such problems cannot be fully known (van der Steen & van Twist, 2012; Levin & *al.*, 2007; Conklin, 2005; Rittel & Webber, 1973). Against that background, the standard response that would consist in making use of experts to bridge the knowledge gap does not work in the case of wicked problems. Koppenjan & Klijn claims that *“traditional methods of dealing with these problems, which often regard complex problems as an intellectual design activity and approach them by giving research and science a central role, no longer suffice”* (Koppenjan & Klijn 2004, p. 7). The normal science’s underlying idea that new knowledge leads to less uncertainty, which in turn leads to improved decision does not apply to wicked problems – rather the opposite (Curry & Webster, 2013; Batie, 2008). Actually, new scientific findings often highlight new problems, new risks and new uncertainties (see Beck, 2008). An additional reason explaining the failure of new knowledge to create certainty about the nature of the problem and its solutions is connected to the fact that wicked problems involve many actors whose values and interest are different. Each actor interprets available knowledge through its own frame of reference. In that context, many authors consider that the idea whereby objective knowledge on the problem that is the object of a scientific consensus will remove those different interpretations is misleading (van der Steen & van Twist, 2012; Batie, 2008; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). As said before, solutions to wicked problems are not true-or-false, but good-or-bad (Rittel & Webber, 1973). A rational approach consisting in defining the right solution to wicked problem on the basis of objective knowledge can be considered as impossible, as there is no such right solution. Instead, the choice of solutions to wicked problem is a value-laden and subjective process towards an acceptable situation that is assessed in light of the values and interests of the different stakeholders (Levin & *al.*, 2007). Consequently, new knowledge cannot make the different views on the problem and its solutions disappear. On the contrary, the validity of knowledge is often questioned by actors considering that this knowledge goes against their values or interests. It is not unusual to observe debates about the validity of the methods and results of studies addressing controversial issues

(Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). As Oreskes & Conway (2010) has shown in their book “Merchants of Doubts”, scientific knowledge on climate change is the subject of counter-expertise from high-level scientists supported by political actors.

For several authors, the presence of many actors whose values and interest differ also makes the classic top-down mode of governance inadequate to address wicked problems (Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). The top-down approach assumes that a public authority directly influences the range of options available to target groups by limiting or excluding certain behaviours with “command and control” policy instruments like regulations or standards (Kaufmann-Hayoz & Gutscher, 2001). Such unilateral approach excludes stakeholders from the formulation and implementation of policies. In turn, the exclusion of the stakeholders from the problem-solving process often results in strong resistances from those actors whose interests are ignored. The stakeholder’s resistances can constitute an impediment to successful implementation of top-down policies (Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). Moreover, solutions developed under a top-down approach tend to focus solely on the problem as perceived by public authority and therefore does not address other dimensions of the problem. A number of issues are not taken into consideration and the solutions adopted are often far from “ideal” (Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). In that context, several authors consider that modes of governance leaving more room for consultation and cooperation are more suitable for tackling wicked problems (Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). Participatory approaches aiming at articulating the views of different stakeholders could indeed enable a better understanding of all the issues at stake and attenuate the political resistances (Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). Opening up governance systems to wider participation is however a difficult task in practice, partly due to power games that do not ensure balanced participation and the reluctance of mainstream political authorities to open up the systems to other actors (Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009).

To the governance challenges associated to any wicked problems, one must add the four extra challenges specific to climate change that make this problem super-wicked: “Time is running out”, “There is no central authority”, “Those seeking to end the problem are also causing it.” And “Hyperbolic discounting” (Levin & *al.*, 2011) (see section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter). In view of all these challenges, several scholars and various political actors believe that the low-carbon transition requires to deeply rethink, reshape and reform governance (Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Termeer & *al.*, 2016; Jordan & *al.* 2015; Urpelainen, 2013; Kunchornrat’ & Phdungsilp 2012; Montini, 2011; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Foxon & *al.*, 2009; Boulanger, 2008). The specific case of climate energy governance will be further discussed later in this chapter (See section “4. Governing super-wicked problems” of the same chapter).

3. Knowing Super-Wicked Problems

3.1. Foresight and Scenario Approach

As mentioned in the previous section, unlike probabilistic predictions, here referred to as “forecast”, foresight is often considered as a suitable approach for analysing the future developments of wicked problems like climate change (Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Head, 2014; Ho, 2012; Kok & *al.*, 2011; Fobé & Brans, 2013; Sardar, 2010; Marien, 2010 ; Levin & *al.*, 2009; Kosow & Gaßner 2008; Mulder, 2007) (see section “2.2.1. From normal science to post-normal science and foresight” of the same chapter). The following section aims at introducing foresight and scenario approach.

3.1.1. Foresight: Conceptual Clarification

Many different concepts with close meanings are employed to describe the non-predictive future-oriented approaches. The most common concepts are “foresight”, “strategic foresight”, “future(s) studies”, “future(s) research”, “futurology”, “*prospective*”, “futurism” and “scenario approach”. There is no clear and consensual conceptual framework that allows to distinguish those different terms (Sardar, 2010; Petit Jean, 2016; Voros, 2001). Some of them are even sometimes used interchangeably (Sardar, 2010; Riedy, 2009). This is at the root of a lot of semantic confusions (Sardar, 2010; Burt & van der Heijden, 2008). Such confusion stems from the fact that different non-predictive future-oriented approaches emerged in parallel within various contexts (Godet, 2010). Two major traditions of foresight developed after the Second World War in the USA with William Ogburn, and in France with Gaston Berger & Bertrand de Jouvenel, as a tool for military and territorial planning (Kuosa, 2011; Godet & Durance, 2011; de Jouvenel, 2004). Over the years, foresight has been increasingly applied in various other fields, like peace and conflict studies (e.g.: Boulding, 1988), gender studies (e.g.: Gunnarsson-Östling & *al.*, 2012), and of course, in the areas of environment and sustainable development (e.g.: Mont & *al.*, 2014; Vergragt & Quist, 2011; Robinson & *al.*, 2011; Höjer, 2011; Svenfelt & *al.*, 2010; Mermet, 2005). The concepts and methods have evolved through the appropriation of scenario methods by practitioners from various fields (Kuosa, 2011; Godet, 2010; Marien, 2010). The lack of theorization on the fuzzy entity of foresight and the fact that it is not (yet) established as a discipline or a field are not conducive to conceptual clarification (Marien, 2010; Burt & van der Heijden, 2008).

In the following research, I’m using the term “foresight” to describe the non-predictive future-oriented approaches. I have selected this designation because it is the one that is the most commonly used in the literature (Massini, 2010). The concept of “future(s) studies” is also very popular. However, even if its definitions vary from one author to another, this concept usually involves a more encompassing understanding of future explorations, ranging from rigorous scenario analyses to fictional literary writing (Petit Jean, 2016). The later type of future exploration falls out of the scope of this research which focuses on foresight exercises in the context of policy-making. The concept “*prospective*” is also widely used, but it has a limited semantic field in English – its use being often restricted to French literature (Godet, 2010).

Foresight is here understood as a policy-oriented approach assuming that the future is multiple, uncertain and potentially radically different from the present. It aims at envisioning and exploring in a systemic and holistic way alternative images of the future. This definition of foresight has been elaborated on the basis of the “laws” of the future defined by the futurist Jim Dator (2002). Those are summarized in the following table [Table 1]. In the rest of the section, I further develop what is (and is not) foresight by referring to Dator’s laws of the future.

-
- I. **"The future cannot be predicted because the future does not exist"**
 - a) "The future cannot be predicted, but alternative futures can, and should be forecast".
 - b) "The future cannot be predicted, but preferred futures can and should be envisioned, invented, implemented, continuously evaluated, revised, and re-envisioned."
 - c) "To be useful, futures studies need to precede, and then be linked to strategic planning, and thence to administration."

 - II. **"Any useful idea about the futures should appear to be ridiculous."**
 - a) "Because new technologies permit new behaviours and values, challenging old beliefs and values which are based on prior technologies, much that will be characteristic of the futures is initially novel and challenging."
 - b) "The most likely future is often one of the least likely futures"
 - c) "If futurists expect to be useful, they should expect to be ridiculed and for their ideas initially to be rejected."
 - d) "Decision-makers, and the general public, if they wish useful information about the future, should expect it to be unconventional and often shocking, offensive, and seemingly ridiculous."

 - III. **"We shape our tools and thereafter our tools shape us"**
-

Table 1. Dator's Laws of the Future (adapted from Dator, s.d.)

Assuming that the future is not written, foresight is founded on the principle that the future does not exist. Consequently, the future cannot in any way be predicted (Svenfelt, 2010; Mermet 2005; Lvque & Urien, 2005; de Jouvenel, 2005; Voros, 2001; Robinson, 1988) (i.e.: Law of the Future nI). According to Robinson, "To the degree that the future is not already determined but remains to be created, then the search for the most likely future (i.e.: the best prediction) is not only often misguided (since we are usually wrong) but actually counterproductive" (Robinson 1988, p. 326). Trying to determine the more likely future is all the more misguided and counterproductive because the most likely future is most of the time one of the least likely futures (Dator, 2002). The future will be probably different from the present in numerous aspects. This is related to the fact that the various components of the system are closely interrelated and co-evolve. As explained in the chapter devoted to the socio-technical approach to transition, future developments are the result of the co-evolution of technology and society (see section "1.2.1. Socio-technical approach" of the same chapter). New technologies lead to the emergence of new values, behaviours, lifestyles, forms of social, economic and political organizations, and institutions, which, in turn, enable the development of certain new technologies, and so forth (i.e.: Law of the Future nIII). Such multidimensional changes render the future potentially radically different from the present, and extremely difficult to envision. A future where almost everything is new might appear "obscene, impossible, stupid, "science fiction" or ridiculous" through the prism of our current frame of reference (Dator s.d., p. 2). It would presumably not be considered as a likely future. In that context, Dator states that, to be useful, foresight should explore disruptive ideas of the futures – even if they might be perceived as ridiculous today (i.e.: Law of the Future nII). Considering that the future is not predetermined and potentially radically different from the present, foresight assumes that the future is open and that an infinity of potential alternative futures exist (Guyot, 2014; Svenfelt, 2010; Godet, 2004; Voros, 2001). As shown above, the plurality of alternative potential futures is often represented with the future cone developed by Charles Taylor (1990) (Voros, 2017; Candy, 2010; Kosow & Gasner, 2008; Hancock & Bezold, 1994) [Figure 11].

Figure 11. Future cone (Candy 2010, p. 34)

Another founding principle of foresight is that the future is influenced by the decisions we make in the present. The decisions we take in the present regarding our actions (and inactions) have consequences and should therefore be taken as wisely as possible (Voros, 2001). In other words, the decisions we take today contribute to build our future (Bell & Olick, 1989). In that context, the French prospectivist Hugues de Jouvenel asserts that *“the future is a realm of freedom, of power and of will. It is at once a land to be explored, and a land to be built”* (de Jouvenel 2004, p. 10). By envisioning and exploring alternative “images” of the future (see Polak, 1973), foresight aims to help us to build our future (de Jouvenel 2004). Fred Polak, one of the founding fathers of foresight, states that *“once he [i.e. man] became conscious of creating images of the future, he became a participant in the process of creating this future”* (Polak, 1973). Foresight invites human beings to take their future in hand, by helping them to react to anticipated changes (i.e.: “preactivity”) and to act with a view to achieving desired changes (i.e.: “proactivity”) (Godet, 2004). Since it is intended to throw light on action, foresight is often considered as a decision support tool for public and private actors. In order to fulfil this decision support role, several authors explain that scenarios should not only envision images of the future, but also link those futures to the present (Hughes & Strachan, 2010; Godet, 1986; Kahn & Weiner, 1967). Foresight actually consists in making a detour by the future to take more enlightened decisions in the present (Stassart & al., 2007). In that context, Jim Dator explains that to be useful, foresight has to *“be linked to strategic planning activities, which in turn determine day-to-day decision-making”* (Dator s.d., p. 1). The role of foresight in policy-making will be discussed later in the chapter (see section “5.2.2. Role of scenario analyses in policy-making” of the same chapter).

3.1.2. Scenarios for Envisioning and Exploring Alternative Images of the Future

Foresight distinguishes itself from science fiction movies and fictional literary writing by its theories and methods that make it a scientific⁹ approach (Masini, 1993). The alternative images of the future result from the articulation of various trends and events, whose development is founded on theories and methods (Candy, 2010; Dator, 2002). This is what Jim Dator (2002) call “basic paradigm” of foresight. The Dator’s basic paradigm of foresight is illustrated in the following figure [Figure 12].

Figure 12. Basic paradigm of foresight (adapted from Dator 2002 by Candy 2010, p. 30)

Across the literature, we observe that practitioners use a great variety of methods when undertaking foresight exercises (Jackson, 2013; Sardar, 2010; Kosow & Gaßner, 2008; Popper, 2008; Burt & van der Heijden, 2008; Börjeson & al., 2006). On the basis of an extended review of foresight exercises, Popper (2008) has compiled and classified the more common foresight methods. They are displayed in the

⁹ In the present research, foresight is considered as a scientific approach. However, the scientific nature of foresight is highly controversial, even among foresight practitioners (Mermet, 2005; Bell, 1997a; Masini, 1993). Eleonora Barbieri Masini claims that *“Scientificity is the most debated of the characteristics of futures studies and indeed, according to many scholars, is not to be considered a quality of futures studies at all”* (Masini 1993, p. 23). If referring to criteria of scientificity established in line with the traditional (post-)positivist philosophy of sciences, which is still dominant in many disciplines, foresight is not a science since there is no verifiable objective reality about the future (Alicia 2003, de Jouvenel, 1967). Scenario approach envisions and explores images of the futures that cannot be observed (Svenfelt, 2010; de Jouvenel, 1967). There is no knowledge of the future (Svenfelt, 2010; Bell & Olick, 1989). The images of the future outlined in the scenarios do not exist and will probably never exist (Alicia, 2005). In that context, some consider that foresight is not a science, but an art (Bell, 2009; Burns, 2003). Since foresight aims at supporting policy-making, others associate it with action science (Bell, 2009; Ramos, 2006). In the same vein, Niiniluoto (2001) sees foresight as a design science.

foresight “diamond”. As shown below, this representation classifies foresight methods along two dimensions [Figure 13]. The horizontal axis (i.e.: expertise *versus* interaction) corresponds to a continuum between methods based on expert knowledge and those involving layman knowledge. The vertical axis (i.e.: creativity *versus* evidence) is a continuum between the methods based on original and imaginative thinking and those founded on reliable documentation and means of analysis. In the foresight diamond, qualitative, semi-quantitative and quantitative methods are also distinguished (Popper, 2008). Foresight exercise often involves a combination of different methods. The articulation of several methods is often seen as a major strength of the scenario approach (Hughes & Strachan, 2010; Wack, 1985).

Figure 13. Foresight diamond (Popper 2008, p. 66)

One of the most widely used method for envisioning and exploring alternative images of the future is the scenario approach (Popper, 2008; Börjeson & al., 2006). A scenario corresponds to a narrative about the future. This includes a representation of the current state of the system (base), a description of the future situation (i.e.: “*futurable*” or image of the future), and the trajectory that connects the present to the image of the future (i.e.: pathway) (Godet, 2007; de Jouvenel, 2004). Various scenario types and techniques exist. The scenario approaches are often differentiated on the basis of the mode of thinking about the future they rest upon. Three broad modes of thinking about the future are often distinguished depending on whether they explore “probable”, “possible” or “preferable” futures. This classification developed by the futurist Roy Amara (1974) appears to be one of the most widely used (Voros, 2017; Candy, 2010; Börjeson & al., 2006; Bell, 1997b; Hancock & Bezold, 1994). The probable, possible and preferable futures can be displayed in the future cone, as shown in the figure below [Figure 14].

Figure 14. Probable, possible and preferable futures (Candy 2010, p. 35)

On the basis of the distinction between probable, possible or preferable futures, Börjeson & *al.* (2006) have developed a scenario typology. In this typology, the “predictive”, “explorative” and “visionary¹⁰” scenarios respectively aim at exploring probable, possible or preferable futures. Each type of scenario can be associated to a specific question about the future. The predictive scenarios aim to answer the question “What *will* happen?”, the explorative scenarios address the question “what *could* happen?”, and the visionary scenarios ask the question “what *should* happen?” (Vergragt & Quist 2011; Börjeson & *al.*, 2006). The following figure illustrates the three types of scenarios [Figure 15]. In a particular foresight exercise, one of the modes of thinking about the future and the related scenario approach is usually dominant and provides the study its character (Dreborg, 2004).

Figure 15. Predictive, explorative and visionary scenarios (adapted from van Bers & *al.* 2016, p. 35)

As said before, foresight doesn’t intend to answer the question “What the future will be?” (Voros, 2001). This approach should therefore exclusively be based on explorative or visionary scenarios and exclude predictive scenarios. However, in practice, a foresight exercise often involves the development of one predictive scenario in addition to explorative or visionary scenarios (Candy, 2010). Generally known as “business as usual” scenario, the predictive scenario is used as a reference to compare alternative scenarios.

Inasmuch as all the foresight exercises analysed in the following research are based on scenarios, the terms “foresight”, “scenario approach” and “scenario analysis” are used interchangeably.

¹⁰ I prefer using the designation “visionary” rather than “normative” as proposed by Börjeson & *al.* (2006), because the latter suggests that other types of scenarios are value-neutral. Yet, this is rarely the case, even for the seemingly neutral quantitative scenarios. For instance, the definition of models’ assumptions is not neutral and objective (Voinov & *al.*, 2014).

3.2. Scenarios Tackling Super-Wicked Problems

I mentioned earlier that, conversely to traditional modes of knowledge production, foresight is often considered as a suitable approach for tackling wicked problems (Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Head, 2014; Ho, 2012; Kok & *al.*, 2011; Fobé & Brans, 2013; Sardar, 2010; Marien, 2010; Levin & *al.*, 2009; Kosow & Gaßner, 2008; Mulder, 2007). As a reminder, wicked problems are ill-defined problems involving complex interconnections of multiple causes, effects and actors whose values and interests differs. The figure hereunder recaps the main features of these highly complex problems [Figure 16].

Figure 16. Recap of the main features of wicked problems (Hadden, 2018)

The present section aims at presenting the meeting points between scenario approach and wicked problems. The discussion is articulated around the desirable attributes of approaches designed to tackle wicked problems identified earlier (see “section 2.2.1. From normal science to post-normal science and foresight” of the same chapter). Those criteria are summarized in the following table [Table 2].

I.	<i>A multidisciplinary approach linking social and natural sciences</i>
II.	<i>A holistic approach addressing the problem in its entirety</i>
III.	<i>A systemic approach addressing the non-linear interconnections of the multiple dimensions of the problem</i>
IV.	<i>An approach acknowledging the unpredictability of the future developments of the problem</i>
V.	<i>An approach acknowledging and coping with the uncertainties</i>
VI.	<i>An approach considering the values and interests of the different stakeholders, and making the conflicts explicit</i>

Table 2. Desirable attributes of approaches designed to tackle wicked problems

As will be discussed below, foresight meets all the desirable attributes of approaches designed to tackle wicked problems. Foresight is not, however, the only approach that has all those desirable attributes. For instance, I explained previously that post-normal sciences emerged as a response to wicked problems (see Batie, 2008; Ravetz, 2004; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993) (see section “2.2.1. From normal science to post-normal science and foresight” of the same chapter). There is not any approach better than any other. Each approach addresses wicked problems from a specific point of view, providing different types of solutions. Foresight tackle problems by making a detour by the future. Before presenting the convergences between foresight and wicked problems, I would like to point out the added value of future-oriented approaches for addressing such complex problems. In my view, three characteristics of wicked problems make future-oriented approaches relevant to address them: (1) wicked problems are constantly evolving, (2) all their potential solutions create waves of long-lasting irreversible consequences, and (3) the situation is problematic and has to change. Michel Godet identifies four possible attitudes towards the future: “passivity” (“like the ostrich that puts up with change”), “reactivity” (e.g.: “like the firefighter who wait for the fire to be declared

to fight it”), “preactivity” (“like the insurer who prepares for foreseeable changes because he knows that compensation is more expensive than prevention”), and “proactivity” (e.g.: “like the conspirator who acts to bring about the desired changes”) (Godet 2007, p. 9). It is obvious that we cannot remain passive in the face of wicked problems. Given the magnitude of the effects of wicked problems and their solutions, adopting a “reactive” attitude might not be the best option either. The impacts already observed have to be addressed, but it is probably wiser to adopt a “preactive” attitude regarding the potential future impacts. It is actually judicious to anticipate the possible evolutions of wicked problems (1) in order to help policy-makers to implement preventive actions. It is equally important to anticipate the potential consequences of the solutions that could be implemented to address wicked problems (2). *In fine*, we have to adopt a “proactive” attitude to cope with wicked problems. Facing such problematic situation (3), it is necessary to act with a view to reach a “better” situation. Both the “preactive” and the “proactive” attitudes involve having a look at the future in order to take decisions today. Foresight can help policymakers to adopt “preactive” and “proactive” attitudes (Godet, 2004). The exploratory scenarios that respond to “what *could* happen?” foster “preactivity”, and the visionary scenarios that respond to “what *should* happen?” foster “proactivity”.

A meeting point between foresight and wicked problems lies in the first founding principle of foresight – i.e.: the future cannot be predicted. Foresight therefore acknowledges by default the inherent unpredictability of wicked problems. In addition, contrary to traditional linear-rational approaches that aim at predicting the future by extrapolating past trends, foresight does not presuppose the existence of simple linear causes and effects. Instead, foresight considers that the various components of the system are closely interrelated and co-evolve. The future developments are therefore non-linear. The future developments are even less linear since several scenario methods integrate turning points (Petit Jean, 2016). When developing scenarios, foresight practitioners often use “surprises”, “wild card” (or “black swans”) and “weak signals”. Those unlikely or even strongly improbable events aim at including discontinuity in scenarios (Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Saritas & Nugroho, 2012; Taleb, 2010; van Notten & al., 2005). Here understood as “*temporary or permanent, sometimes unexpected, break in a dominant condition in society*”, discontinuity enables to consider the non-linearity of future developments (van Notten & al. 2005, p. 179).

In the present thesis, it is considered that tackling wicked problems requires multidisciplinary approaches linking social and natural sciences, which is provided by foresight (Petit Jean, 2016; Godet & Durance, 2011; de Jouvenel, 1999). As said before, foresight, as defined in this research, aims at envisioning and exploring alternative images of the future in a systemic and holistic way. According to Hugues de Jouvenel, this approach is “*based on the principle that the problems we face cannot be correctly understood if reduced to one dimension and divided up into several parts, as we usually see things according to distinct academic disciplines*” (de Jouvenel 2004, p. 44). Considering that the various dimensions of the problem are interconnected, foresight aims at embracing it in its entirety. Strongly inspired by system analysis, foresight offers a broad range of tools to capture the intricate interconnections between multiple causes and effects of wicked problems (de Jouvenel 2004). A scenario approach usually involves two main tasks: the generating task that consists in collecting ideas, knowledges and views, and the integrating task that aims at articulating all these data into wholes (Börjeson & al., 2006). The generating task intends to identify all the independent and dependent variables of the problem, as well as the shapes that the variables can take. This task can be carried out on the basis of different data collection techniques such as citizen or expert panels, workshops, surveys, Delphi, interviews or literature review. The set of variables is intended to describe the various components of the system (Popper, 2008; Börjeson & al., 2006). The variables are therefore of different natures (i.e.: social, technological, economic, environmental) and their analysis involves multiple disciplinary anchors (de Jouvenel 2004). The second task of the scenario approach aims at articulating all the collected data into wholes. Such integrating task consists in analysing the interactions between various variables. Different configurations that can arise from the articulation of various system components are outlined in the form of alternative scenarios. Several techniques can

be used to undertake the integrating task, including modelling, cross-impact analysis, morphological analysis or narrative methods (Miller & *al.*, 2015; Börjeson & *al.*, 2006). Through the generating and collecting tasks, foresight address problems in a systemic and holistic way, thus embracing their complexity. This approach is therefore seen as particularly suitable for tackling problems involving complex interconnections between multiple dimensions, like wicked problems.

By assuming that it is impossible to know what the future will be, foresight also acknowledges the existence of uncertainty. In addition to acknowledging the existence of uncertainty, foresight aims at coping with it (Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Svenfelt, 2010; Aligicia, 2005; Mermet, 2005). In her doctoral thesis on the use of foresight as a tool for dealing with uncertainty in environmental policy-making, Åsa Svenfelt (2010) distinguishes three types of uncertainty: epistemic uncertainty, ontological uncertainty and ambiguity (see Walker & *al.*, 2003; Brugnach & *al.*, 2008). Wicked problems are subjected to those three types of uncertainty. Depending on the type of uncertainty considered, foresight either reduce it, or manage it. Epistemic uncertainty is the result of a knowledge gap that can be reduced with additional research (Svenfelt, 2010). Scenarios can potentially reduce epistemic uncertainty. As a reminder, the integrating task of the scenario building process aims at articulating various knowledge in the form of scenarios (Börjeson & *al.*, 2006). By combining all this various knowledge in scenarios, foresight generates new configurations of knowledge, which can shed new light of the object of study (Aligica, 2005). As a result, one can consider that through its holistic approach, foresight is likely to reduce epistemic uncertainty. Ontological uncertainty stems from inherent variability. This type of uncertainty is at the root of the impossibility to predict the future. Assuming that we cannot predict the future, scenario approach does not aim at reducing ontological uncertainty. Instead, the exploration of possible futures intends to deal with this type of uncertainty by *“increased knowledge of alternative actions in relation to several possible developments (...) and enhance preparedness for the unforeseeable and unexpected”* (Svenfelt 2010, p. 46). This refers to the foresight’s objective of fostering *“preactivity”* (Godet, 2004), which can be achieved with exploratory scenarios. Some futurists also consider ontological uncertainty as a window of opportunity for building the future we want (Svenfelt, 2010; Godet & Roubelat, 1996). In this regard, Godet & Roubelat explains that *“without this uncertainty, human activity would lose its degree of freedom and its meaning – the hope of a desired future”* (Godet & Roubelat 1996, p. 1). Foresight based on visionary scenarios can help to build such desired future. This refers to the second objective of foresight, namely fostering *“proactivity”* (Godet, 2004). Åsa Svenfelt (2010) distinguishes the ontological uncertainty connected to variables we can control (e.g.: behavioural and societal variables) and the ontological uncertainty connected to variables over which we don’t have much control (e.g.: natural variables). She explains that when the later are more important, it is explorative scenarios outlining possible futures to take anticipative action against those potential future developments which are needed, and conversely, when uncertainties related to behavioural and societal variables are more important, it is visionary scenarios envisioning the individual and societal actions to take towards a desired future that are needed. When those two types of ontological uncertainty are mixed up, explorative and visionary scenarios can be combined (Svenfelt, 2010). The last type of uncertainty took into consideration is the ambiguity. It corresponds to the uncertainty that occurs when different actors have divergent interpretations of a same object. Participatory foresight exercises enable discussions between various stakeholders, which can promote mutual understanding (van der Heijden, 1996). Such participatory process can therefore reduce ambiguity.

The issue of participation in scenario building process leads me to mention the last meeting point between foresight and wicked problems. Foresight increasingly rests on participatory approaches (Quist, 2013; Robinson & *al.*, 2011; Da Costal & *al.*, 2008). Participatory foresight exercises involve various stakeholders in the scenario building process through scenarios workshops for instance. Such exercises consider the views of the different stakeholders, thus rendering values conflicts explicit (Carlsson-Kanyama & *al.*, 2008). Participatory foresight exercises could therefore be particularly suitable for tackling wicked problems. Indeed, as stated before, wicked problems typically involve

many actors with different perceptions of the problem and its solutions, and, according to several authors, those conflicting views should be taken into consideration when addressing wicked problems (Wright & *al.*, 2018; Andersson & Törnberg, 2018; Batie, 2008; Ravetz, 2004; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993). Depending on the type of scenario approach and on the level and mode of participation, the value conflicts are naturally more or less explicit. The foresight approach based on visionary scenarios is, for instance, explicitly normative since it invites participants to debate their visions of preferable futures. As explained by Carlsson-Kanyama & *al.* (2008), *“In the participative visioning work, the possibility of several different Images of the Future was seen as means to cope with the rather likely possibility of differing opinions and values among the group of stakeholders as regards how sustainability should be implemented”* (Carlsson-Kanyama & *al.* 2008, p. 37). On the contrary, the value-laden nature of foresight approach based on exploratory scenarios is not necessarily acknowledged. Regarding the mode of participation, van de Kerkhof (2006) distinguishes stakeholders dialogues as deliberation and as consensus building. She explains that the later approach can potentially discard important issues and diverging values (van de Kerkhof, 2006). According to Hage & *al.* (2010) the participatory approach in knowledge production can in turn facilitate the policy-making process, in particular when it comes to problems involving uncertainties and stakes – just like wicked problems do. The later issue will be further discussed in the section exploring the role of foresight in policy-making (see section “5.2.2. Role of scenario analyses in policy-making” of the same chapter).

This section pointed out how foresight meets the desirable attributes of approaches designed to tackle wicked problems. The desirable attributes suit to my perception of what an ideal approach for addressing wicked problem should look like. This perception is shared by many authors referred to above. However, it has to be acknowledged that it is not supported unanimously. Everyone does not value the above-mentioned criteria, it is rather the opposite. For instance, some authors like McGrane (2009) and Friedrichs (2011), who are attached to traditional “normal” scientific values and who consider science as a value-free pursuit of truth, strongly oppose to participatory modes of knowledge production embracing uncertainties and values as proposed by post-normal science. Those authors believe that post-normal science does not improve knowledge production process or product. Instead, they claim that such an approach dilutes scientific rigor and paves the way for corruption of science. McGrane claims that *“Once there was modern science, which was hard work; now we have postmodern science, where the quest for real, absolute truth is outdated, and ‘science’ is a wax nose that can be twisted in any direction to underpin the latest lying narrative in the pursuit of power. Except they didn’t call it ‘postmodern’ science because then we might smell a rat. They called it PNS (post-normal science) and hoped we wouldn’t notice.”* (McGrane, 2009). For his part, Friedrichs states that climate science has moved towards post-normal science, highlighting the risks associated with those modes of knowledge production embracing uncertainties and values, and how they have undermined scientific authority: *“Post-normal science can hardly tackle a problem of epic proportions such as climate change. On the contrary, post-normal science about such planetary risks carries the seeds of its own destruction. (...) The inherent ambiguities of post-normal science have plunged climate science into a deep legitimacy crisis”* (Friedrichs 2011, p. 473). Jerome Ravetz, who developed with Silvio Funtowicz the idea of post-normal science, says the opposite. To him, the legitimacy crisis that has hit climate science – here embodied by the Climatic Research Unit email controversy also known as “Climategate” – has its origin in the application of normal science approach for addressing the wicked problem of climate change: *“We can understand the root cause of Climategate as a case of scientists constrained to attempt to do normal science in a post-normal situation”* (Ravetz 2011, p. 151).

Besides the open debate on the desirable attributes of approaches designed to tackle wicked problems like climate change, it has to be noted that a number of authors consider the criteria presented in this thesis as desirable but fail to apply them when designing and implementing scenario building approach. Such gap between rhetoric and practice can be observed through the IPCC foresight activities. Readers interested in learning more about the scenario approach developed by the epistemic authority on climate change are invited to have a look at the box hereinbelow [Box 2].

Box 2 | Reading of the IPCC Scenario Assessments through the Lens of the Desirable Attributes of Approaches Designed to Tackle Wicked Problems

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) was established in 1988 by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) in order “to assess on a comprehensive, objective, open and transparent basis the scientific, technical and socio-economic information relevant to understanding the scientific basis of risk of human-induced climate change, its potential impacts and options for adaptation and mitigation” (IPCC 2013, p. 1). This panel has succeeded in bringing together the world's leading experts on climate issues in policy advice activities. In so doing, “it has spoken on behalf of global science with one voice, thereby acquiring a reputation as the epistemic authority in matters of climate policy” (Beck & al. 2014, p. 80). Considered as the principal source of knowledge to support international climate negotiations, the IPCC positions itself at the interface between science and policy (Van der Sluijs, 2012).

The IPCC gathers, analyses and articulates into reports the available scientific knowledge on climate change. Such Assessment Reports are intended to inform the policy-making process. The IPCC has hitherto published an updated Assessment Report every five or six years to reflect changes in the state of knowledge. Since 1990, five Assessment Reports have been published – the sixth Assessment Report being expected in April 2021 (IPCC, 2018). Every Assessment Report is divided into three partial reports, each completed by a specific Working Group (WG): The physical science basis (WG1), Impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability (WG2), and Mitigation of climate change (WG3). For each partial report, a full report, a summary for policy-makers and a technical summary are published. A synthesis report compiling the main contribution of the three partial reports is also available. Besides the Assessment Report, the IPCC also publishes special reports, the latter of which was on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C (see IPCC, 2018).

Foresight has a central position in the IPCC reports, especially in the partial report devoted to mitigation of climate change (WG3). Such report assesses several scenarios envisioning and exploring alternative evolutions of GHG emissions and associated global temperature rises. As part of the last Assessment Report (AR5) (see IPCC, 2014b), approximately 300 reference or “business as usual” scenarios and 900 mitigation scenarios were gathered through an open call from integrated modelling teams around the world. In total, the AR5 scenario database includes 1,184 scenarios and 31 models. Most of these scenarios were developed as part of nine model inter-comparison exercises¹¹. The models that generated the scenarios assessed in the AR5 are primarily large-scale integrated models designed to project low-carbon transition pathways to 2050 and beyond. Integrated models consist in “simplified, stylized, numerical approaches to represent enormously complex physical and social systems. They take in a set of input assumptions and produce outputs” (IPCC 2014b, p. 422). The input assumptions generally concern the future developments of population, GDP, natural resources, technology and mitigation policy. The outputs of the models consist in an assessment of the effect of the input assumptions on various components such as energy system, land-use, economy, and GHG emissions. Besides those shared features, the models generating the scenarios included in the AR5 scenario database can differ significantly, particularly regarding degree of detail with which they represent the earth system process (e.g.: carbon cycle), the GHG emission, the various sectors and regions, the technology or the economic system. In order to remove the variations stemming from the use of different models and to ensure the comparability of the scenarios included in the AR5 scenario database, the GHG emissions and climate implications of all the scenarios were run through a same climate model, i.e. the Model for the Assessment of Greenhouse Gas Induced Climate Change (MAGICC).

As shown in the following figure, the scenarios analysed as part of the AR5 involve different levels of GHG emissions and associated concentrations of CO₂eq in the atmosphere, ranging from 430ppm CO₂eq to above 1000ppm CO₂eq [Figure 17].

¹¹ A list with the models and the model inter-comparison exercises generating the scenarios included in the AR5 scenario database may be found in the Annex II “Metrics & Methodology” of the AR5 (IPCC, 2014b).

Figure 17. GHG emission pathways for the scenarios assessed by the IPCC as part of the AR5 (IPCC 2014b, p. 11)

The scenario analysis reveals that, without additional mitigation policy, the 450ppm CO₂eq threshold – that is consistent with a *likely* chance to keep temperature change below 2°C – should be exceeded by 2030. This business as usual scenario should reach CO₂eq concentration levels between 750ppm and more than 1300ppm CO₂eq by 2100. Such growth in GHG concentration in the atmosphere should result in global temperature rise ranging from 3.5 to 4.8°C, as showed in the figure below [Figure 18].

CO ₂ eq Concentrations in 2100 [ppm CO ₂ eq]	Subcategories	Relative position of the RCPs ⁵	Cumulative CO ₂ emissions ³ [GtCO ₂]		Change in CO ₂ eq emissions compared to 2010 in [%] ⁴		Temperature change (relative to 1850–1900) ^{5, 6}				
			2011–2050	2011–2100	2050	2100	2100 Temperature change [°C] ⁷	Likelihood of staying below temperature level over the 21st century ⁸			
Category label (concentration range) ⁹							1.5°C	2.0°C	3.0°C	4.0°C	
< 430	Only a limited number of individual model studies have explored levels below 430 ppm CO ₂ eq										
450 (430–480)	Total range ^{1, 10}	RCP2.6	550–1300	630–1180	–72 to –41	–118 to –78	1.5–1.7 (1.0–2.8)	More unlikely than likely	Likely	Likely	Likely
500 (480–530)	No overshoot of 530 ppm CO ₂ eq		860–1180	960–1430	–57 to –42	–107 to –73	1.7–1.9 (1.2–2.9)	Unlikely	More likely than not		
	Overshoot of 530 ppm CO ₂ eq		1130–1530	990–1550	–55 to –25	–114 to –90	1.8–2.0 (1.2–3.3)		About as likely as not		
550 (530–580)	No overshoot of 580 ppm CO ₂ eq		1070–1460	1240–2240	–47 to –19	–81 to –59	2.0–2.2 (1.4–3.6)	Unlikely	More unlikely than likely ¹²	Likely	
	Overshoot of 580 ppm CO ₂ eq		1420–1750	1170–2100	–16 to 7	–183 to –86	2.1–2.3 (1.4–3.6)				
(580–650)	Total range	RCP4.5	1260–1640	1870–2440	–38 to 24	–134 to –50	2.3–2.6 (1.5–4.2)	Unlikely	More likely than not	Likely	
(650–720)	Total range		1310–1750	2570–3340	–11 to 17	–54 to –21	2.6–2.9 (1.8–4.5)				
(720–1000)	Total range	RCP6.0	1570–1940	3620–4990	18 to 54	–7 to 72	3.1–3.7 (2.1–5.8)	Unlikely ¹¹	More unlikely than likely	More unlikely than likely	
>1000	Total range	RCP8.5	1840–2310	5350–7010	52 to 95	74 to 178	4.1–4.8 (2.8–7.8)	Unlikely ¹¹	Unlikely		

Figure 18. Main characteristics of the scenarios assessed by the IPCC as part of the AR5 (IPCC 2014b, p. 13)

The analysis further shows that the scenarios limiting the GHG concentration in the atmosphere below 450ppm CO₂eq by 2100 requires to reduce GHG emissions by 40 to 70% by 2050, and to reach near zero emissions or below in 2100. Such substantial reductions in GHG emissions necessitate fundamental changes in energy systems and potentially in land use. The analysis also points out that “*delaying mitigation efforts beyond those in place today through 2030 is estimated to substantially increase the difficulty of the transition to low longer-term emissions levels and narrow the range of options consistent with maintaining temperature change below 2°C relative to pre-industrial levels*” (IPCC 2014b, p. 12). This refers to one of the characteristics that makes climate change a super-wicked problem, namely “Time is Running out” (see section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter). In addition, the scenario analysis highlights significant co-benefits associated with mitigation pathways reaching about 450 to 450ppm CO₂eq by 2100. The co-benefits concern human health, ecosystems and energy security. Moreover, based on the scenarios, the AR5 emphasizes that the efforts required for mitigating climate change and associated costs vary from one country to another.

As illustrated in the following figure, the AR5 also explores sectoral and cross-sectoral mitigation pathways [Figure 19]. It thus analyses the large-scale global changes in the energy supply sector as well as the technological, structural, behavioural and cultural changes in the transport, building and industry sectors, that are required to reach atmospheric CO₂eq concentrations of 450ppm by 2100.

Figure 19. Direct sectoral GHG emissions in the baseline and 450ppm scenarios assessed by the IPCC as part of the AR5 (IPCC 2014b, p. 18)

A reading of the IPCC AR5 through the lens of the desirable attributes of approaches designed to tackle wicked problems is particularly interesting. It reveals that the IPCC concurs with all the criteria above-mentioned (see table 2). The adherence to the criteria is indeed visible through the IPCC discourse. Firstly, in the AR5, the IPCC recognizes the unpredictability of the future developments of the climate change problem:

*“Climate change mitigation and adaptation is a risk management challenge that involves many different decision-making levels and policy choices that interact in complex and often **unpredictable** ways.”* (IPCC 2014b, p. 41)

Then, acknowledging the high uncertainties and conflicting values associated with climate change, the IPCC *“has seen a heroic effort of scientists to engage in post-normal science”* (Friedrichs 2011, p. 474). As previously explained, this approach aims at managing uncertainty and making values explicit, notably by involving the actors affected by the policy in the quality assurance of the scientific inputs (i.e.: “extended peer community”) (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993) (see section “2.2. Forms of knowledge production and modes of governance to address super-wicked problems” of the same chapter). The IPCC willingness to engage in post-normal science is reflected through the following quotations:

*“Effective risk management strategies not only consider **people’s values**, and their intuitive decision processes but utilize formal models and decision aids for systematically addressing issues of risk and **uncertainty**.”* (IPCC 2014b, p. 41)

*“To achieve legitimacy, institutions charged with linking science to policy must also open themselves up to public input at one or more stages in their deliberations. This process of **“extended peer review”** (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1992) is regarded as necessary, though insufficient, for the production of **“socially robust knowledge”**, that is, knowledge that can withstand public scrutiny and scepticism (Gibbons, 1994).”* (IPCC 2014b, p. 178)

Still at the discourse level, the IPCC highlights the advantages of – and the need for – multidisciplinary approach linking social and natural sciences, as illustrated in the quotations hereunder:

*“The Working Group III contribution to the AR5 explores the solution space of climate change mitigation drawing on experience and expectations for the future. This exploration is based on a **comprehensive** and transparent assessment of **the scientific, technical, and socio-economic literature** on the mitigation of climate change.”* (IPCC 2014b, p.ix)

*“Judging whether human interference in the climate system is dangerous therefore divides into two tasks. One is to estimate the risk in material terms (...) The other is to set a value on the risk (...). The first is a task for **natural science**, but the second is not. (...) **Social sciences and humanities** can contribute to this process by improving our understanding of values (...) The sciences of human and social behaviour – among them psychology, political science, sociology, and non-normative branches of economics – investigate the values people have, how they change through time, how they can be influenced by political processes, and how the process of making decisions affects their acceptability. Other disciplines, including ethics (moral philosophy), decision theory, risk analysis, and the normative branch of economics, investigate, analyse, and clarify values themselves. These disciplines offer practical ways of measuring some values and trading off conflicting interests.”* (IPCC 2014b, p. 37)

The epistemic authority on climate change further emphasises the need to address climate mitigation on the basis of a holistic approach considering the problem in its entirety:

*“Analysing how to transition to a sustainable, low-emission pathway (...) would be aided by models with a **holistic framework** encompassing the economy, society, and the environment, that take account of relevant technical constraints and trends.”* (IPCC 2014b, p. 288)

The IPCC also recognises the necessity when addressing problems like climate change to go beyond the traditional model of sciences which assumes the existence of simple linear causes and effects of problems:

*“A majority of people perceive climate in a **linear fashion** that reflects two common **biases**.”* (IPCC 2014b, p. 164)

Furthermore, the AR5 intends to take into consideration unlikely or strongly improbable elements generating discontinuity in transition pathways – referred above as “wild card” or “black swans”:

*“Accurately estimating the benefits of mitigation takes into account the full range of possible **impacts** of climate change, including those with **high consequences but a low probability of occurrence**.”* (IPCC 2014b, p. 6)

This review of the AR5 thus demonstrates that the six desirable attributes of approaches designed to tackle wicked problems are recognised as valuable in the IPCC discourse. However, it appears that this rhetoric is hardly translated into practice. It is indeed observed that the IPCC scenario analysis doesn't meet most of the criteria previously mentioned. Exploring how the IPCC scenario analysis meet the criteria is, of course, highly subjective and debatable – as will be shown later. The following discussion is based on a “quick and dirty” analysis of the AR5 aiming at providing an overview on the foresight activities of the principal science-policy interface organisation for climate science. In no way it intends to give a complete picture of this very broad and complex issue.

A first gap between discourse and practice concerns the way IPCC copes with uncertainty and diverging views. This is related to one of the main principles governing the IPCC work, namely the **consensus-building** (Curry & Webster, 2013; Van der Sluijs, 2012). The procedure recognises that *“in taking decisions, and approving, adopting and accepting reports, the Panel, its Working Groups and any Task Forces shall use all best endeavours to reach consensus”* (IPCC 2013, p. 2). The consensus-building model can be seen as a strategy to deal with uncertainty and diverging views. Such model actually *“acknowledges that available knowledge is inconclusive and that the truth cannot yet be established – and it solves this limitation by assuming a role of “speaking consensus to power”, where consensus is a proxy for truth and is established through a negotiated (among a broad group of peers) widely shared interpretation of the yet inconclusive body of scientific evidence”* (Van der Sluijs 2012, p. 187). The “speaking consensus to power” approach rests on a conception of the relation between science and policy as a linear model of expertise or “speaking truth to power” assuming that scientists produce knowledge and that, in turn, policy-makers use this knowledge to devise policy (Dahan & Guillemot, 2015; Curry & Webster, 2013). The role of consensus in such model makes sense, as explained by Oreskes: *“If there is no consensus of experts – as was the case among earth scientists about moving continents before the late 1960s – then we have a case for more research. If there is a consensus of experts – as there is today over the reality of anthropogenic climate change – then we have a case for moving forward with relevant action”* (Oreskes 2004, p. 372). Yet, as previously shown, the linear model doesn't work for wicked problems involving irreducible uncertainties and profound dissents (see section “2.2.2. From traditional top-down modes of governance to bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders” of the same chapter). Even if the scientific consensus on the anthropogenic origin of climate change demonstrated in the first IPCC report has undoubtedly had a crucial role in putting the climate issue into the political agenda, the observed continuous growth of GHG emissions illustrates that a scientific consensus in itself does not lead to ambitious mitigation policies (Dahan & Guillemot, 2015; Curry & Webster, 2013). Aside from the fact that it doesn't suffice to bring policies required to face climate change, the “speaking consensus to power” approach tends to conceal questions over which there is no consensus¹², while they should, on the contrary, be highlighted (Van der Sluijs, 2012). Underexposing uncertainties and dissent can be seen as problematic inasmuch as it renders *“the chosen policy vulnerable to scientific errors; and it limits the political paying field in which players can present different policy perspectives”* (Curry & Webster, 2013, p. 8). For instance,

¹² Note that within mainstream climate science, the current debates are not so much about the question of whether human activity is the main source of climate change, but about the relative importance of different factors within the climate system as well as the way to improve climate models (Van der Sluijs, 2012).

in light of the current state of knowledge, a lot of uncertainties surround some weak signals such as the tipping points. They can potentially generate significant non-linear impacts, but as they do not enjoy consensus support, they might be underexposed in IPCC report (Van der Sluijs, 2012). In that context, several authors question the “speaking consensus to power” approach and call for the IPCC to better embrace and highlight the (un-)known unknowns as well as the areas of disagreement with a view to offer policy-makers a more complete picture of the state of knowledge on climate science (Beck & *al.*, 2014; Curry & Webster, 2013; Van der Sluijs, 2012; Socolow, 2011; Oppenheimer & *al.*, 2007). It should be mentioned that such an approach can carry the risk of overexposing uncertainty and dissent (Van der Sluijs, 2012). It could, for instance, give too much visibility to climate sceptics’ views.

Since the publication of its first report, the IPCC made substantial efforts for better embracing and highlighting the uncertainties (Curry & Webster, 2013). In the AR5, the authors had to **evaluate and communicate the degree of certainty** in findings of the assessment process by resorting to calibrated language. Two metrics could be used to represent the degree of certainty in findings, namely the confidence and the likelihood. The confidence reflects the authors’ judgements concerning the validity of findings. It is expressed qualitatively based on a five-level scale (“very low”, “low”, “medium”, “high” and “very high”). The level of confidence of a finding is defined by assessing and crossing two dimensions: the type, amount, quality and consistency of evidence, and the degree of agreement [Figure 20] (IPCC, 2010).

Figure 20. Confidence scale used by the IPCC as part of the AR5 (IPCC 2010, p. 3)

The likelihood is a metric used to quantify the uncertainty in a finding [Figure 21]. It is defined on the basis of statistical analysis of observations, model results or expert judgements. Whether they use the confidence or the likelihood, the authors have to provide traceable account describing how they defined these metrics (IPCC, 2010).

Term*	Likelihood of the Outcome
<i>Virtually certain</i>	99-100% probability
<i>Very likely</i>	90-100% probability
<i>Likely</i>	66-100% probability
<i>About as likely as not</i>	33 to 66% probability
<i>Unlikely</i>	0-33% probability
<i>Very unlikely</i>	0-10% probability
<i>Exceptionally unlikely</i>	0-1% probability

Figure 21. Likelihood scale used by the IPCC as part of the AR5 (IPCC 2010, p. 3)

The process developed to evaluate and communicate uncertainty in the AR5 reflects the considerable efforts made by the IPCC to manage uncertainty. Such uncertainty management process is indeed not usually seen in traditional research papers (Saloranta, 2001). Many modelling exercises do not communicate confidence or likelihood of findings – “the exactness of their numbers [giving] the illusion of certainty, which contradicts the fact that models only capture a part of “reality”, providing a narrow view of the future” (Fortes & *al.* 2015, p. 162). A limit of the IPCC uncertainty management approach is nevertheless pointed out by Van der Sluijs (2012) who explains that some uncertainties cannot be expressed quantitatively in a reliable way.

More recently and to a lesser extent, efforts have also been undertaken for opening up the issue of climate change to different views. While the first four AR of the IPCC were based exclusively on **peer reviewed literature**, the AR5 has adopted a procedure for including grey literature. However, other forms of expertise such as local, traditional or layman knowledge are still not included in AR (Dahan & Guillemot, 2015; Beck & *al.*, 2014; Ravetz,

2011). In that context, we can consider that the process of “extended peer review” (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1992) supported by the IPCC has not been implemented in practice. As a result, alternative ways of framing the problem of climate change are automatically ignored, providing a narrow view of the problem that might not take into consideration some important issues or potential solutions. Against that background, several authors – whose view I share – call for “recognising ‘extended facts’, that might be local knowledge and values, as well as unofficially obtained information” (Ravetz 2011, p. 151) in IPCC assessment (Beck & al., 2014; Van der Sluijs, 2012; Ravetz, 2011). Note that some authors consider the process by which political actors from different countries approve “line-by-line” the summary for policy-makers and accept the full AR as an “extended peer review” process (Friedrichs, 2011; Saloranta, 2001). Saloranta indeed claim that “One can easily recognize the essence of the ‘Post-Normal’ Extended Peer Community, where, under coordination of the WG I, diversing and different perspectives are welcomed into the dialogue and, at least seemingly, synthesized into a more or less balanced and quality assessed outcome, the WG I SAR¹³” (Saloranta 2001, p. 400). According to me, this dialogue comes too late in the knowledge production process and does not really allow to consider alternative ways of framing the problem of climate change.

Another mismatch between IPCC claims and “reality” lies in the way the epistemic authority of climate change links natural and social sciences. Holm & Winiwarter explain that “despite the multitude of calls for interdisciplinarity, the need to encourage the integration of human sciences in climate change research remains” (Holm and Winiwarter 2017, p. 115). Social sciences are actually underrepresented in IPCC assessments (Pearce & al., 2018; Holm & Winiwarter, 2017; Dahan & Guillemot, 2015). Except for economy, the rest of the social sciences spectrum is hardly integrated in IPCC reports. This has been demonstrated by Holm & Winiwarter (2017) who have looked at the disciplinary composition of IPCC WGIII. They highlight that 46% of the 468 authors of the WGIII come from social sciences, but among those 46%, the great majority come from the field of economy. More generally, this reflects the **marginal position of social sciences** in climate change studies (Holm & Winiwarter, 2017). There is indeed a “poorly developed and a-theoretical understandings of climate-society relationships in the social sciences” (Hulme 2011, p. 26).

A direct consequence of the underrepresentation of social science in IPCC work is the asymmetrical incorporation of climate and social changes into mitigation scenarios. While the scenario analyses explore in detail the dynamics inherent to the climate system, they hardly address the relation between climate change and social change. The society, the policy and the culture are not considered as object of change in IPCC scenarios (Hulme 2011). When it comes to economy, the economic implications of climate change are represented in an oversimplified way: “The complex relationships that exist between climate and economic performance are first reduced to a dependent relationship between temperature and GDP per capita and then, using projections of future climate warming, future economic performance is predicted for the twenty-first century” (Hulme 2011, p. 17). The lack of theory-making about the interactions between climate and society combined with the rise of a powerful epistemic community of earth system modellers in climate change studies actually led to what Mike Hulme (2011) refers as to “**climate reductionism**” in future-oriented analyses of climate change. By reducing complex problem to simpler problem by excluding some dimensions, the reductionist approach is far from the holistic approach addressing the problem in its entirety – that is considered desirable by the IPCC. Mike Hulme further explains that “by emasculating the future of much of its social, cultural or political dynamism, climate reductionism renders the future free of visions, ideologies and values” (Hulme 2011, p. 33).

In fine, the acknowledgement of the limits of linear thinking by the IPCC materialises in practice through the consideration of **non-linear responses of the climate system** to gradual forcing or volcanic eruptions (Saloranta 2001). The IPCC scenario database actually includes a number of integrated models representing such non-linear processes. However, van Notten & al., who explored the approach to discontinuity in IPCC scenario practice, observe that “the IPCC’s Special Report on Emissions Scenarios states that the scenarios, which address the impact of greenhouse gas emissions on climate change, purposefully exclude catastrophic futures, as they are considered to be unlikely” (van Notten & al. 2005, p. 184-185). By assuming that radical change is unlikely, the IPCC scenarios omit discontinuities (van Notten & al., 2005). In addition, because of their limited representation of social changes, the IPCC scenarios hardly consider improbable geo-political events (e.g.: crisis, war...) that can also potentially generate discontinuity in transition pathways. The latter point closes this discussion on the relation

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between IPCC foresight activities and the desirable attributes of approaches designed to tackle wicked problems. Much more could be said about the making of knowledge on climate change by the IPCC, but this is not the purpose of the present thesis. The interested reader is invited to consult other contributions on the topic (e.g.: Holm & Winiwarter, 2017; Dahan & Guillemot, 2015; Beck & *al.*, 2014; Curry & Webster, 2013; Van der Sluijs, 2012; Hulme, 2011; Ravetz 2011; Friedrichs, 2011; Socolow, 2011; Dahan, 2010; Oppenheimer & *al.*, 2007; Saloranta, 2001).

3.3. Low-Carbon Scenarios

The previous section has demonstrated the suitability of foresight for tackling wicked problems like climate change. It is therefore not surprising that more and more actors develop scenarios to support the transition towards a low-carbon society. Such scenarios envision and explore alternative images of the low-carbon future, as well as the pathways to reduce GHG emissions by 80-95% in 2050. The present section aims at providing an insight into low-carbon scenarios.

3.3.1. Overview

Over the past few years, low-carbon scenario analyses have flourished (Miller & *al.*, 2015; Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Torrie & *al.*, 2013; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Those scenario analyses were carried out or commissioned by a wide variety of actors, starting with public authorities such as the European Commission, which conducted a scenario analysis to develop the above-mentioned “Roadmap for moving to a competitive low-carbon economy in 2050” (European Commission, 2011) (see section “1.1. Context” of the same chapter). The United Kingdom (UK) have initiated this dynamic at the level of EU Member States in 2011 with the 2050 Energy Calculator released by the UK Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC) (Ekins & *al.*, 2013; HM Government, 2011). Since then, many other Member States including Belgium (CLIMACT & VITO, 2013), France (ADEME, 2017), The Netherlands (Centraal Planbureau, 2015), Denmark (Danish Energy Agency, 2014), and Czech Republic (Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic, 2017) have built their own low-carbon scenarios. Governments outside Europe also start to develop scenario analyses to support their low-carbon transition. These include, among others, China (NDRC, 2017), Brazil (Empresa de Pesquisa Energética, 2016) India (NITI Aayog, 2015) and Colombia (Minambiente, 2015). Considering the multilevel nature of climate governance, low-carbon scenarios are developed at multiple scales other than national states, ranging from the local to the global level. At the local level, various cities signatory of the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy envision and explore low-carbon pathways. Those are for instance Paris (Mairie de Paris, 2017), London (Mayor of London, 2016) or Leuven in Belgium (KU Leuven, 2013). At the global level, several intergovernmental organizations such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2014), the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2017) and the International Renewable Energy Agency (IEA & IRENA, 2017) explore low-carbon pathways on the basis of scenario approach. Apart from public authorities, different types of private actors develop low-carbon scenarios. Among them we find various lobbies, including non-governmental organizations (Greenpeace international, 2015), trade associations (European Chemical Industry Council, 2013) and big companies like Shell International (Shell, 2018; Paltsev & *al.*, 2018) or BP Global (BP, 2018). *In fine*, many low-carbon scenario analyses are developed as part of research projects (Schanes & *al.*, 2019; Sharmina, 2017; Neuvonen & *al.*, 2013; Foxon, 2013; Gomi & *al.*, 2011)

Besides the geographical scope, the low-carbon scenarios can differ in terms of material scopes. While certain analyses cover the entire climate-energy systems (Nguyen & *al.*, 2018; Sharmina, 2017; Neuvonen & *al.*, 2013; Ornetzeder & *al.*, 2012; Gomi & *al.*, 2011; Kowalski & *al.*, 2009), others focus on one or more sectors, including energy production (Barton & *al.*, 2018; Wu & *al.*, 2018), buildings (Wang & *al.*, 2018; Svenfelt & *al.*, 2011), transports (Wangel & *al.*, 2013; Zimmermann & *al.*, 2012), industry (Birlain-Escalante & *al.*, 2018; Selvakkumarana & *al.*, 2014), agriculture (Wallgren & Höjer, 2009), or forestry and other land uses (Kallio & *al.*, 2016; Kalt & *al.*, 2016). The level of analysis is also

different from one low-carbon scenario to another. While the policy-orienting scenarios look at the whole society or economy (Sharmina, 2017; Gomi & *al.*, 2011), design-orienting scenarios are developed at the micro-level of the household (Neuvonen & *al.*, 2014; Höjer & *al.*, 2011; Carlsson-Kanyama & *al.*, 2008; Green & Vergragt, 2002). A great diversity across low-carbon scenario is also observed in terms of approach and methods. As explained previously, such methodological diversity is a characteristic of foresight (see section “3.1.2. Scenarios for envisioning and exploring alternative images of the future” of the same chapter). With a view to shedding a little light on the approaches and methods used to explore low-carbon futures, a typology of low-carbon scenarios is presented in the next section.

3.3.2. Typology of Low-Carbon Scenarios

A typology of low-carbon scenarios has been developed by Hugues & Strachan (2010). However, by distinguishing trend-based scenarios, technical feasibility studies and modelling studies, I believe that this typology does not do justice to the diversity of low-carbon scenarios. This is why I have decided to build another typology [Table 3]. To do so, I used the “generic” typology of scenario approaches developed by Börjeson & *al.* (2006) as the backbone. As a reminder, this typology distinguishes predictive, explorative and visionary scenario depending whether the focus is on probable, possible or preferable future (see section “3.1.2. Scenarios for envisioning and exploring alternative images of the future” of the same chapter). For each of the three types of scenario, two subtypes are defined. I have retained the subtypes defined by Börjeson & *al.* (2006) for the exploratory scenarios (i.e.: external and strategic scenarios). I however have not retained the predictive and visionary scenarios subtypes, since they were, in my opinion, not that relevant for the specific case of low-carbon scenarios. The rest of the section describes the types and sub-types of low-carbon scenarios considered in the following research.

Type of future considered	Scenarios		Question on low-carbon transition	Methods		Examples
	Type	Subtype		Generating task	Integrating task	
PROBABLE	Predictive scenarios ("What will happen?")	Predictive scenarios (i.e.: forecast)	"What will happen in the climate-energy system without additional policies?"	Citizen or expert panels, workshop, survey, Delphi, interviews, literature review	Time series analysis, modelling, development of storylines	Business as usual scenarios
POSSIBLE	Explorative scenarios ("What could happen?")	External scenarios	"What could happen in the climate-energy system under alternative developments of external factors?"	"	Cross-impact/structural analysis, morphological analysis, wild cards, weak signals, modelling, development of storylines	World Energy Council 2016; Kalt & al., 2016; Kallio & al., 2016; CLIMACT & al., 2015
		Strategic scenarios	"What could happen in the climate-energy system if we act in a certain way?"	"	Morphological analysis, modelling, development of storylines	Birlain-Escalante, 2018; Nguyen & al., 2018; BP, 2018; ADEME, 2017; Mayor of London, 2016; Selvakkumarana & al., 2014; CEFIC, 2013; Bibas & al., 2012
PREFERABLE	Visionary scenarios ("What should happen?")	Target-orientated backcasting scenarios	"What the low-carbon society should look like?"	"	Backcasting, morphological analysis, modelling, development of storylines	Höjer & al., 2011, Greenpeace & al., 2015; Wanf & al., 2018
		Path-orientated backcasting scenarios	"How to reach a low-carbon society?"	"	Backcasting, morphological analysis, modelling, development of storylines	Mairie de Paris, 2017; Gomi & al., 2011; Wangel & al., 2013; Svenfelt & al., 2011
		Feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios	"Is the low-carbon transition feasible?"	"	Backcasting, morphological analysis, modelling	Sharmina, 2017 CLIMACT & VITO & al., 2012; European Commission, 2011

Table 3. Typology of low-carbon scenarios

Predictive Scenarios

The predictive scenarios aim at defining the probable future. Those scenarios address the question "What will happen in the climate-energy system without additional policies?". They are therefore not low-carbon scenarios as such since the low-carbon transition is not likely to happen without additional climate mitigation policy. A predictive scenario is however included in almost all low-carbon scenario analyses to serve as reference to compare the different low-carbon scenarios. Various methods can be employed to build such "business as usual" scenario. This type of scenario can be developed by extrapolating trends with time series analysis, modelling or qualitative approaches (Börjeson & al., 2006).

Explorative Scenarios

By addressing the question “what *could* happen”, the explorative scenarios are intended to explore alternative possible futures. Two subtypes of explorative scenarios are identified: external scenarios and strategic scenarios. External scenarios aim at responding to the question “What could happen in the climate-energy system under alternative developments of external factors?”. Those scenarios explore alternative development of factors over which the relevant actors have little control (e.g.: effects of climate change, resources of fossil fuel, international market and policy). The objective of this approach is to devise low-carbon strategies that are flexible and adaptive to different potential external developments. Strategic scenarios consider the question “What could happen in the climate-energy system if we act in a certain way?”. In such scenarios, the possible consequences of various climate mitigation policies (e.g.: carbon tax, carbon market, regulations) are analysed. Strategic scenarios focus on factors over which the relevant actors have control, without neglecting external factors. A great variety of more or less participative methods and tools can be employed to build explorative scenarios (Börjeson & *al.*, 2006). Those include, among others wild cards, weak signals, different types of modelling tools (e.g.: accounting models, macro-economic models and partial equilibrium models), soft modelling methods¹⁴ like cross-impact / structural analysis and morphological analysis, and narrative methods (Poppers, 2008; Börjeson & *al.*, 2006).

Visionary Scenarios

The visionary scenarios represent the majority of low-carbon scenarios (Hughes & Stratchan, 2010). By exploring “what *should* happen”, they focus on preferable futures. Those explicitly normative scenarios are usually developed with a backcasting approach. This approach consists in envisioning desirable (or undesirable) image(s) of the future (i.e.: future vision(s)), and then looking backward from the image(s) of the future to the present in order to defining the actions that should be implemented to bring such desirable future(s) about (Quist, 2013). The following figure illustrates the principle of backcasting [Figure 22].

Figure 22. Principle of backcasting approach (Nicolussi 2017, p. 17)

The box below provides some more information on this approach that is widely used for addressing climate-energy issues, and more globally environmental problems [Box 3].

¹⁴ Kosow & Gaßner 2008, p. 66

Box 3 | The Backcasting Approach

Initially developed by Amory Lovins in the 70's (see Lovins, 1976), the backcasting approach was popularized by John Robinson (1982) who called it "energy backcasting". Driven by the environmental awareness that emerged at that time, they designed this method in response to the dominant practices of energy foresight that often assumed the continuous development of large-scale power generation and nuclear power plants, as well as growth in energy demand (Quist, 2013). The specificity of backcasting is its ability to consider major societal changes. The backwards-looking analysis is actually suitable "when the problem being examined is complex, multilateral (affecting many sectors and levels of society), major changes are needed, dominant trends are part of the problem, externalities are involved, and finally when the time horizon is long enough to allow considerable scope for deliberate choice" (Dreborg 1996, in Svenfelt 2010, p. 21). Those characteristics are typical of the contemporary complex environmental problems. It is therefore not surprising that most of the environmental problems have been addressed with the backcasting approach (Wangel, 2012).

There is a great diversity among backcasting approaches. They differ from one another regarding the number of visions developed, the nature of the steps, the methods used, and the level and mode of participation of stakeholders (Quist, 2013; Bows & al., 2009; Anderson, 2001; Robinson, 1990). The figure below shows an example of backcasting approach, highlighting the main steps [Figure 23].

Figure 23. Stages of the backcasting approach. The solid lines correspond to the sequence of steps at first iteration, and the dotted lines the subsequent iterations (Sharmina 2017, p. 305)

In the case of low-carbon scenarios, the starting point of the backcasting analysis is usually an image of the future fulfilling the GHG reduction target that the region under study has adopted or intends to adopt (e.g.: reduction of GHG emissions by 80-95% in 2050). Inasmuch as such foresight exercises consider quantitative GHG reduction targets, they are often based on modelling approaches driven by an overall quantitative emission constraint (Hughes & Stratchan, 2010). Despite the preponderance of number-based approaches, a few purely qualitative exercises exist (e.g.: Hisschemöller & Bode, 2011).

Several typologies of backcasting scenario approaches exist (Wangel, 2012). In the following research, I consider three types of visionary scenarios: target-orientated backcasting scenarios, pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios, and feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios. Those three types of visionary scenarios differ according to the step of the analysis that is considered as of more importance. In target-orientated backcasting scenarios, the more important step is the design of images of the future that fulfil the target. The question that guides the scenario exercise is "What the low-carbon society should look like?". As its name suggests, the pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios focus on pathway development. By addressing the question "How to reach a low-carbon society?", this analysis explores the actions to be implemented with a view to bridge the gap between the images of the future and the present (Wangel, 2012). The last type of visionary scenario is part of technical feasibility studies. The feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios address the following question: "Is the low-carbon transition feasible?" (Hughes & Stratchan, 2010).

Note that many low-carbon scenario analyses cover several types of scenarios and are hardly classifiable in the present typology. According to Robinson (2003), scenario analyses are facing an increasing complexity, resting more and more on complex methodologies mixing different methods. The scenario analyses carried out by the IPCC are particularly revealing of this trend. They are indeed based on an extremely complex methodology combining predictive, exploratory and visionary scenarios (Börjeson & al., 2006).

4. Governing Super-Wicked Problems

4.1. Governance

While the previous section explored the “knowing” dimension, this one focuses on the “governing” dimension. Since governance is a polysemic concept that can be employed in many different ways, a conceptual clarification is first required (Baron, 2003; Crowley, 2003). In the following section, I define and conceptualize governance as understood in this research. After presenting the related definition and concept, I introduce the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance that are used later to analyse the governance of low-carbon transition.

4.1.1. Governance: Conceptual Clarification

Besides its initial use as a synonym of government which became obsolete and its resumption by the World Bank in the early 1990s as a normative framework (see “good governance”), the notion of governance has also been adopted in academic circles (Hufty, 2011a; Baron, 2003). From a research perspective, governance can be understood both as a theoretical paradigm and as a disciplinary paradigm, an ambivalence that lies at the root of quite some epistemological confusions (Paye, 2005).

According to the first understanding, the governance refers to the “*types of political steering in which non-hierarchical modes of guidance, such as persuasion and negotiation, are employed, and/or public and private actors are engaged in policy formulation*” (Héritier 2002, p. 185). This definition of governance is often associated with a theoretical current postulating that this mode of public action becomes dominant (Paye, 2005; Treib & al., 2007). Many researchers actually mention a shift from government to “new governance” implying an increasing participation of private actors in the management of public affairs as well as an evolution of the relations between these actors from hierarchy to network (i.e.: horizontal shift) (Hill, 2013; Hufty, 2007; Eckerberg & Joas, 2004; Lascoumes & Le Galès, 2004; Hassenteufel & Smith, 2002). This shift can also imply a strengthening of power and competencies of the local, regional or international entities to the detriment of the central state (i.e.: vertical shift) (Hufty, 2007; Eckerberg & Joas, 2004). Furthermore, the shift from government to “new governance” is accompanied by a change in the role of the government which moves from manager to enabler, a rejection of command and control instruments in favour of policy instruments based on persuasion and negotiation, and an increasing interest in policy instruments instead of program and agency (Lascoumes & Le Galès, 2004). Whether, to what extent and how the shift from government to “new governance” takes place have been thoroughly discussed in the literature (Arnouts & al., 2012). While the above-mentioned authors recognize a major change in the way society is governed, some consider that hierarchical modes of guidance are still well entrenched (Goetz, 2008), and others acknowledge a co-existence of different modes of steering (Hill & Lynn, 2005). Besides those divergences, there is globally a consensus on the existence of at least a partial shift from government to “new governance” (Treib & al., 2005; Van Kersbergen & Van Waarden, 2004; Pierre, 2000).

As a disciplinary paradigm, the term “governance” refers to a research perspective that entails analysing public action by integrating some aspects that are not addressed in more “traditional” approaches, namely the modes of management of public affairs based on the participation of private actors at different political-administrative levels (Paye, 2005). This understanding does not involve any theoretical position and is based on an encompassing definition of governance as “*every mode of political steering involving public and private actors, including traditional modes of government and different types of steering from hierarchical imposition to sheer information measures*” (Héritier 2002, p. 185). The latter definition is the one adopted in this study. The conception of the governance as a theoretical paradigm which imply a shift from government to “new governance” involving non-hierarchical steering modes and the participation of private actors in the policy process excludes the other modes of public action (e.g.: hierarchical steering modes; auto-regulation by the market). Yet, this mode of public action is a specific historic form, which is far to be universal. For instance, many

non-European countries are not concerned by the shift from government to governance. Such narrow definition of governance cannot be applied generally to any contexts, which is a problem from an analytical point of view. It actually does not necessarily allow to observe and compare different situations, as according to this definition: some countries would not have any governance (Hufty, 2011a; Treib & al., 2007). This is why I have decided to choose a broader definition of governance.

4.1.2. Policy, Politics and Polity Dimensions of Governance

The concept of governance encompasses many different aspects (Hufty, 2011b; Treib & al., 2007). Literature provides various frameworks for conceptualizing governance (Arnouts & al., 2012; Driessen & al., 2012; Hall, 2011; Hufty, 2011b; Treib & al., 2007; Pierre & Peters, 2005). This research distinguishes three dimensions of governance, namely the policy measures, the actors and the institutions. Inspired by Treib & al. (2007), those three dimensions are respectively referred to as *policy*, *politics* and *polity*. The three dimensions of governance are displayed in the figure below [Figure 24].

Figure 24. Policy, politics and polity dimensions of governance

Treib & al. (2007) use the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions “to present a structured overview of different dimensions of modes of governance as they may be found in the literature” (Treib & al. 2007, p. 2). The policy measures, the actors and the institutional structures are actually the issues that are the most frequently addressed in the governance literature – including literature on environmental and climate governance. These three issues used to be addressed separately, though they are strongly interconnected (Tollefson & al., 2012; Howlett & al., 2009; Treib & al., 2007). According to Tollefson & al. (2012), “this has important implications for understanding the real-life hybridity and “messiness” of governance as a social phenomenon” (Tollefson & al. 2012, p. 9). A framework integrating the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance is thus particularly suitable to explore in a systematic and holistic way the complexity of governance. Since the publication in 2007 of the paper written by Treib & al., this conceptual framework of governance has been applied and improved by several authors (Tollefson & al., 2012; Gale, 2009; Howlett & al., 2009; Tollefson & al., 2008).

As part of this thesis, the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions are subdivided into the subdimensions displayed in the following table [Table 4]. The definition of these subdimensions is largely based on Treib & al. (2007). The following dimensions can be used as metrics to analyse governance. Treib & al. (2007) suggest analysing governance in a two-step process. This process consists in addressing the three dimensions separately before exploring the relations between them (Treib & al., 2007).

DIMENSIONS	SUBDIMENSIONS
POLICY	Representation of the societal problem Goals set to deal with the problem Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals
POLITICS	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process Role of the different stakeholders in the policy process
POLITY	Locus of authority Steering mode Institutionalization of the policy process

Table 4. Policy, politics and polity dimensions of governance

The rest of the section further discusses the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance and their associated subdimensions.

Policy

The *policy* dimension corresponds to the study of the policy process. In the following research, I take into consideration three phases of the policy process: the political definition of the public problem, the setting of the goals to deal with the problem and the implementation of policy instruments to reach the goals (Howlett, 2009; Knoepfel & *al.*, 2009). The political definition of the public problem covers the way policy-makers define the extent of the problem, the assumptions on its causes, and the possible options for action to be implemented for solving it (Knoepfel & *al.*, 2009).

The goals set to deal with the problem can be expressed in various ways. Howlett (2009) distinguishes policy goals according to different levels of abstraction. Those are general abstract policy aims, operationalizable policy objectives and specific policy targets. One goal leads to another. A general aim is first defined by the government. This broad aim is then translated into a set of objectives that are, in turn, concretized in a set of on-the-ground targets (Howlett, 2009).

The policy instruments refer to *“the means of intervention by which government attempts to induce individuals and groups to make decisions and take actions compatible with public policies”* (Landry & Varone 2005, p. 107-108). Just like policy goals, Howlett (2009) consider the instruments for achieving these goals according to three levels of abstraction. It involves general policy implementation preferences of government (i.e.: policy style) that lead to the more concrete use of operationalizable instruments which, in turn, imply specific policy instrument calibration. There are different types of policy instruments that correspond to various typologies. Policy instruments typologies have been developed *inter alia* by Vedung (1998), Hood & Margetts (2007) or Kaufmann-Hayoz & Gutscher (2001). It is this last typology that I use in the present research. The typology developed by Kaufmann-Hayoz & Gutscher (2001) distinguishes five main types of instruments that are regulatory or “command and control” instruments, economic instruments, service and infrastructure instruments, collaborative agreements and communication and diffusion instruments. The following table lists these five types of instruments as well as their main characteristics [Table 5].

TYPES OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS	CHARACTERISTICS
Regulatory instruments	Regulatory instruments are legal requirements that, by limiting or excluding certain behaviours, directly influence the range of options available to target groups. These instruments are based on the assumption that the actors act in accordance with the legal requirements in order to avoid the penalties provided for non-respect of the rules. In this context, the implementation of control mechanisms and sanctions is necessary for the proper functioning of regulatory instruments. Since they rest exclusively on command, control and sanctions, these instruments are also called “command and control” instruments.
Economic instruments	Based on the idea that the costs of the impacts of economic activities that are not paid by the actors responsible for them lead to environmental degradation, the economic instruments aim to increase the costs of polluting behaviour, reduce the costs of ecological behaviours or create markets for the rights to pollute. Unlike regulatory instruments, they do not prohibit certain behaviours by the regulatory route and thus influence only indirectly the range of options available to target groups. In this context, they are based on the assumption that the actors tend to adopt environmentally friendly behaviours because these behaviours are economically more profitable.
Service and infrastructure instruments	Service and infrastructure instruments aim to promote certain behaviours by modifying the services or infrastructures that allow these behaviours. The existence but also the quality of services and infrastructures determine the range of action that are achievable as well as the attractiveness of such actions. The implementation of this type of instrument is based on the assumption that the modification of services or infrastructures can promote ecological behaviours or, on the contrary, inhibit behaviour that is harmful to the environment.
Collaborative agreements	Collaborative agreements are binding, or non-binding commitments made by a private sector to the government. The environmental objectives to be achieved by the companies are usually the result of long negotiations between the two parties. Voluntary agreements are distinguished from other instruments by their voluntary and self-regulatory nature. Note, that even if these agreements are said to be voluntary, it is often under the pressure and the threat of more restrictive government interventions that private actors define environmental objectives.
Communication and diffusion instruments	Communication and diffusion instruments aim to influence the internal conditions of the actors. Communication tools are based on the assumption that attitude changes are a prerequisite for behavioural changes and that these changes are likely to occur through communication. These instruments are inseparable from dissemination instruments that aim to disseminate information to a large number of individuals. Communication and dissemination instruments are often used before or in addition to other instruments. They actually enhance the effect of other instruments by making them more understandable and legitimate for target groups

Table 5. Typology of policy instruments (adapted from Kaufmann-Hayoz & Gutscher, 2001)

Politics

The analysis of the *politics* dimension concerns the constellation of actors and their roles in the policy process (Hufty, 2011b; Treib & al., 2007). The actors correspond to “*the individuals and social groups concerned by the collective problem that the environmental policy try to solve, and more specifically, by the issues addressed during one or several phases of the cycle of this policy*” (Knoepfel & al. 2009, p. 37). The actors can therefore be public or private. While the public actors correspond to political and administrative authorities, the private actors cover various civil society organization, like environmental and development NGOs, employers’ federations, workers’ unions and consumers’ organizations, but also scientists, media and citizen movements (Gale, 2009). From one mode of governance to another, the power relation between the actors and their role in the policy-making process vary (Treib & al., 2007; Hall, 2011). Considering the *politics* dimension, modes of governance can be placed on a continuum between state intervention and societal autonomy. The first one corresponds to a mode of governance according to which only public actors are involved in the policy process, and the second one is a mode of governance in which only private actors are involved in self-regulation by businesses or self-organization by communities. Those two modes of governance are not empirically observed. Instead, we can generally see a predominance of a certain type of actor (Treib & al., 2007). On the continuum between pure state intervention and societal autonomy, we find various modes of governance involving both public and private actors (Treib & al., 2007). They correspond, for instance, to different configurations of “policy networks” (see Sørensen & Torfing, 2012; Marin & Mayntz, 1991), “policy communities” (see Richardson, 2000; Richardson & Jordan, 1979), or collaborations between public and private actors as defined in the “new governance” literature (see Salamon, 2002).

Polity

The *polity* dimension corresponds to the institutions, namely to the set of rules that determines the actions of the actors. In this research, three characteristics are used to grasp this dimension. The first one is the steering mode. Independently of the type of actors involved in the policy process, it is possible to distinguish different steering modes (Treib & *al.*, 2008), ranging from top-down hierarchy to bottom-up non-hierarchical approaches (Hall, 2011; Börzel & Panke, 2008). While a “traditional” hierarchical steering mode “involves authoritative decisions, which can be imposed on actors against their will”, a non-hierarchical coordination corresponds to “negotiated compromises on the basis of fixed preferences (*bargaining*)” or to “processes of learning and persuasion (*arguing*)” (Börzel & Panke 2008, p. 155). We can go further in the distinction of steering modes by taking into account the relative power of public and private actors (i.e.: *politics*). By this way, we can distinguish four modes of governance: hierarchies (i.e.: top-down steering mode, dominance of public actors), markets (i.e.: top-down steering mode, dominance of private actors), networks (i.e.: bottom-up steering mode, dominance of public actors), and communities (i.e.: bottom-up steering mode, dominance of private actors). Those are represented in the following figure [Figure 25]. Specific types of policy instruments (i.e.: i.e.: *policy*) can be associated to each of the four modes of governance. For instance, a hierarchy will probably rely more on *command and control* instruments, a market on economic instruments, a network on collaborative agreements, and a community on self-regulation (Hall, 2011).

Figure 25. Hierarchies, markets, networks and communities modes of governance (adapted from Hall 2011, p. 443)

The second characteristic associated with the *polity* dimension is to the locus of authority. The authority can be dispersed across different levels and actors, or, on the contrary, centralized. It is therefore about determining whether the authority is dispersed or centralized, and if necessary, identifying the locus of authority (Treib & *al.*, 2007). When the authority is distributed, we refer to “multi-level governance” (Galarraga & *al.*, 2011; Eckerberg & Joas, 2004; Hooghe & Marks, 2003). Two types of multi-level governance are often distinguished, namely vertical and horizontal multi-level governance. The vertical multi-level governance implies that the authority is divided among different political-administrative levels, ranging from the local to the global level. In the case of horizontal multi-level governance, the authority is dispersed across various public and private actors. Such shift of responsibilities from public to private actors can occurs at all levels (Eckerberg & Joas, 2004). The figure below illustrates the vertical and horizontal interactions in multi-level governance [Figure 26].

Figure 26. Vertical and horizontal interactions in multi-level governance

Finally, the last characteristic of the *polity* dimension is the degree of formal institutionalization of the policy processes. An institutionalized policy process implies “*relatively clear rules as to who is involved in decision-making, how decisions may be reached, how they have to be implemented and who is in charge of monitoring compliance*” (Treib & al. 2007, p. 10).

4.2. Governance of the Low-Carbon Transition

The previous section has presented the concept of governance as a research perspective for analysing public action which considers various steering modes, ranging from top-down hierarchies to bottom-up approaches involving private actors. By distinguishing the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance, I attempted to render this concept operational. The following section articulates these three dimensions with a view to provides a broad picture of the governance of the low-carbon transition. After presenting the causal model of long-term climate mitigation policy, the policy goals and the constellation of actors involved in the low-carbon transition, I move on to a discussion on the steering modes on which climate mitigation governance is based. In that context I show the coexistence of traditional top-down modes of governance and bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders. *In fine*, I introduce the multilevel framework of climate governance and highlight the recent development of subnational actions and transnational cooperation in a polycentric system. While the first two points consist primarily of a personal analysis developed on the basis of the analytical framework of governance presented in the previous section, the last point rests more on the literature.

4.2.1. Causal Model, Policy Goals and Constellation of Actors

As will be discussed in further detail in the section devoted to the main climate mitigation policies, climate change is a very recent political matter (see section “3.5. Main climate mitigation policies” of Chapter II). The problem of climate change became a public issue between the late 1980s and the early 1990s. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) established in 1988 highlighted the anthropogenic origin of climate change in its first report published in 1990, and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) was adopted two years later. The general policy aim of climate mitigation policy as written in the UNFCCC is “*to achieve (...) stabilization of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system*” (United Nations 1992, p. 4). This global policy aim has been translated in a more operationalizable policy objective, namely limiting the global temperature rise below 2°C (see section “1.1. Context” of the same chapter). This objective, which has been adopted in the Cancún Agreement and confirmed by the Paris Agreement, requires a decrease in global GHG emissions of around 40-70% by 2050 compared to the 2010 level. In that context, various entities have adopted specific policy targets for reducing GHG emissions by 2050 as well as intermediate GHG emissions reduction targets by 2020 and 2030.

The policy process for reducing GHG emissions involves a great variety of actors whose values and interests differ. As explained before, this is a typical characteristic of wicked problems (see section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter). However, what makes climate change mitigation particularly challenging compared to other wicked problems is the density of the constellation of actors concerned by the problem. The following figure displays the constellation of actors involved in the long-term climate mitigation policy^{15 16} [Figure 27]. It is drawn up on the basis of the triangular model developed by Knoepfel & *al.* (2009). This conceptual framework represents a space of interactions formed by different types of actors connected to each other by the causal model at the base of every environmental policy. This model includes the assumptions about the actors responsible for the problem and the means by which these target groups can change their behaviour in order to solve the problem in question (Knoepfel & *al.*, 2009). The figure includes four types of actors, namely the target groups of the long-term climate mitigation policy, the final beneficiaries of this policy, the potential winners and losers of the low-carbon transition, and the actors who participate in the policy-making process. The target groups include the actors whose behaviour is, according to the causal model, at the origin of the collective problem that the policy is seeking to solve. They are therefore the target of policy that aims to change their behaviour. The final beneficiaries are the actors affected by the problem that the policy is trying to solve, and for whom the implementation of public policy is supposed to improve their situation (Knoepfel & *al.*, 2009).

Figure 27. Constellation of actors involved in the long-term climate mitigation policy

¹⁵ The size and the position of the circles do not represent the influence of the actors in the policy process.

¹⁶ The role of science in policy-making will be discussed in the section where are linked knowledge and governance (see section “5.2.1. Knowledge and governance: Beyond the rational knowledge-based policy-making model” of the same chapter).

The development of GHG emissions reduction policy is based on a causal model acknowledging that various sectors contribute to anthropogenic GHG emissions, namely energy production, buildings, transports, industry, agriculture, forestry and other land use (IPCC, 2014a). Those sectors cover all aspects of economy and everyday life. As stated by Bulkeley & al. (2014), *“the causes of climate change are implicated in everyday acts of production and consumption and relate to the ways in which societies organize their transportation, housing, energy, water and food systems”* (Bulkeley & al. 2014, p. 1). This implies that everyone is part of the target groups for long-term climate mitigation policy. The fact that everyone is the target of climate mitigation policy refers to one of the characteristics that makes climate change a super-wicked problem mentioned earlier: *“Those seeking to put an end to the problem are also causing it”* (see section *“2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition”* of the same chapter).

The final beneficiaries of climate mitigation policy are inhabitants of small island states and southern countries that are already experiencing the impacts of climate change, future generations and, of course, our planet. As said before, the geographic and temporal distance from the final beneficiaries of GHG emissions reduction policy does not encourage authorities of industrialized countries to implement ambitious mitigation policies. This is another aspect that makes climate change a super-wicked problem (i.e.: *“hyperbolic discounting”*).

Other actors could potentially benefit indirectly from the transition to a low-carbon society, depending on which transition pathway is taken. Some low-carbon niches and regime components are expected to develop, thus generating market opportunities and employment, but also, improved user services. Among the areas that will or could develop, we find renewable energy, nuclear power, geo-engineering, eco-friendly transports (e.g.: walking and cycling), public transport, freight transport by rail and inland waterway, sustainable building, and various grassroots innovations (e.g.: sharing economy and short food supply chains). Moreover, the low-carbon transition implies a reduction of vehicles with internal combustion engines' use, which should bring significant benefits in terms of public health, especially to households living in urban areas. Such vehicles currently emit a great quantity of pollutants that cause disease and premature death (European Environment Agency, 2018).

It appears that the big losers of the energy transition are the fossil fuels industries. The transition to a low-carbon society actually requires a reduction in the use of oil, gas and coal, whose combustion generates GHG emissions. Such reduction is more or less important depending on the chosen transition pathway (e.g.: energy sobriety *versus* carbon capture and storage *versus* inaction).

Between those who have everything to lose and those who have everything to win in the low-carbon transition process, we find a number of actors that may become winners or losers depending on their capacity to adapt. These include companies in the automotive sector. While some firms may be affected by a decline in car use, vehicle producers who invest in the development and production of electric or hydrogen vehicles could take advantage of the energy transition. The same applies to electric appliances, lighting devices, kitchens and heating systems producing. In addition, businesses and households that manage to decrease their energy consumption, and thereby reduce their energy bills are also winners. On the other hand, if policy instruments aimed at increasing the price of energy are implemented, those who cannot reduce their consumption could strongly suffer from the low-carbon transition. For many reasons, such as lack of access to information or financial resources, not all businesses and households have the capacity to adopt less energy-intensive practices (Bauler & Fransolet, 2014).

This overview of the targets groups, final beneficiaries, and potential winners and losers of the long-term climate mitigation policy allows for a better understanding of the many issues at stake. It shows that the low-carbon transition involves many actors whose interests differ and that the decisions taken today will have significant impacts of these actors. Depending on the actions implemented (or not) today, the consequences are indeed more or less favourable for this or that actor. As a result, each actor has its own perception of how to address the problem of climate change. Those actors attempt

to influence climate mitigation governance through various channels. This is why, in addition to political-administrative authorities, various big companies, energy market operators, business federations, trade unions, environmental and development NGOs, consumers associations, grassroots movements, scientists and media take part to the governance of low-carbon transition. Those stakeholders are indicated into the circles in the hereinabove figure [Figure 27] (Sovacool & Van de Graaf, 2018; Jordan & *al.*, 2015).

4.2.2. Coexistence of Traditional Top-Down Modes of Governance and Bottom-Up Approaches Involving Stakeholders

As said before, the presence of many actors whose values and interests differ is a specific characteristic of wicked problems that render them particularly challenging for policy-makers (see section “2.2.2. From traditional top-down modes of governance to bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders” of the same chapter). For many authors, this characteristic makes the classic top-down mode of governance inadequate to address wicked problems (Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). They consider that such unilateral approach excluding stakeholders from the formulation and implementation of policies can result in strong resistances from actors whose interests are ignored and tends to focus solely on the problem as perceived by public authority leading to sub-optimal solutions (Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). In that context, several authors state that wicked problems require more bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders (Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004). Climate mitigation governance increasingly relies on such modes of governance. However, those “new” modes of governance do not make traditional top-down approaches disappear (Jordan & *al.*, 2015). Diverse modes of governance actually coexist. The following figure crosses the continuums “top-down *versus* bottom-up steering mode” and “state intervention *versus* societal autonomy” [Figure 28]. This allows to distinguish four modes of governance: hierarchies (i.e.: top-down steering mode, dominance of public actors), markets (i.e.: top-down steering mode, dominance of private actors), networks (i.e.: bottom-up steering mode, dominance of public actors), and communities (i.e.: bottom-up steering mode, dominance of private actors). In the case of climate mitigation governance, we can see the coexistence of various hierarchies, market, networks and communities modes of governance.

Figure 28. Hierarchies, markets, networks and communities modes of governance for mitigating climate change

Hierarchies correspond to the traditional “*model of democratic government and the public bureaucracy*” (Pierre & Peter 2000, p. 15). Under this mode of governance, public authorities directly influence the range of options available to target groups by limiting or excluding certain behaviours with command and control instruments. Example of such regulatory instruments in climate mitigation policy are building performance standards, eco-design standards, energy efficiency standards for industrial installations, and ban on incandescent and halogen bulbs. Those regulations apply in EU Member States. Another example of command and control instrument are the low- and zero-emission zones that are areas where some or all vehicles with internal combustion engines are banned. Many cities like Brussels, Berlin, London or Stockholm have already implemented this system.

Under markets-based governance, public authorities intend to indirectly influence target groups behaviours by using pricing, taxes and subsidies to encourage or discourage certain behaviours. Even if they allow the market to solve the problem, public authorities are still behind the decision that can be imposed on private actors against their will (Hall, 2011). Using the market as a governance mechanism was popularized under the Kyoto protocol that was ratified in 1997 and which relied on three flexible mechanisms, namely Emissions Trading, Clean Development Mechanism and Joint Implementation. A carbon market was also implemented in 2005 at the European level with the European Emissions Trading System (ETS). Another market-based policy tool is the Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+) mechanism which allocate price to carbon stored in forest as an incentive to reduce deforestation. Besides these market instruments, a number of states including Scandinavian countries have adopted carbon taxes. In addition, some economic instruments specifically target certain behaviours. Those are, for instance, home insulation subsidies, renewable energy subsidies, electric car subsidies, or CO₂-based motor vehicle taxes. A last example of economic instrument is the urban or road tolls that are implemented by public authorities to reduce car traffic.

At the opposite, first of two bottom-up modes of governance there are the networks. This “new” mode of governance aims at integrating private actors into joint projects on a voluntary basis (Hall, 2011). In that context, public authorities turn to various policy instruments like collaborative agreements, official labels, accreditation schemes, codes of practices or information and awareness campaigns. In the case of climate governance, several governments negotiate sectoral agreements with industry, in which different sectors commit themselves to reduce their GHG emission, while public authorities undertake not to implement binding regulations or carbon taxes. Public authorities also propose various official labels, accreditation schemes and codes of practices for the firms wishing to improve and/or promote their environmental performance, including energy efficiency and carbon intensity. Those are for instance the EU Eco-label, the EU-US Energy Star, the EU Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS), and the EU Code of Conduct for Data Centre Energy Efficiency. In addition, public authorities develop and broadcast information and awareness campaigns to business and citizens with a view to encouraging energy efficient behaviours.

The last mode of governance, which is equally based on a bottom-up approach, are the communities. This is a mode of “governance without government” which directly involves target groups in the quest of solutions to the problem (Hall, 2011; Pierre & Peter 2000). There are various more or less innovative modes of governance based on communities. Among them, grassroots innovations are increasingly observed. Such initiatives conducted by groups of citizens can take various forms like community energy projects, eco-housing neighbourhoods, urban agroecology, community currencies, repair cafés, hackerspaces and makerspaces (Smith & *al.*, 2015; Smith & *al.*, 2014). In the world of business, firms who want to do so can improve and/or promote their energy performance with labels or voluntary standards proposed by various non-governmental organisms, like the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) with its ISO 14000 and 50001. *In fine*, many private actors, like environmental and development NGOs, make information and awareness campaigns to promote less carbon intensive behaviours.

4.2.3. Development of Subnational Actions and Transnational Cooperation in a Polycentric System

The problem of climate change is not limited to national borders and the configuration of a low-carbon society goes beyond the levers of public action available for national governments. Consequently, in addition to the horizontal fragmentation of responsibilities between public and private actors, we also note that the authority is divided vertically among different political-administrative levels (Andonova & *al.*, 2009). Such multilevel governance framework is considered as a polycentric system, which is characterized by “*multiple governing authorities at differing scales rather than a monocentric unit*” (Sovacool & Van de Graaf 2018, p. 317). As stated before, the lack of central authority is a characteristic that makes climate change a super-wicked problem (see section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter). In the multilevel framework of climate change, we usually distinguish subnational, national, supranational and international authorities. The previously mentioned UNFCC, Kyoto Protocol and Paris Agreements are the most famous results of the international cooperation promoted by the United Nations. Supranational authorities, like the European Union, legislate in the area of climate energy. National authorities formulate and implement climate mitigation policy, sometimes under the umbrella of international and supranational climate change regime. Finally, subnational authorities (e.g.: cities and regions) also act in favour of the low-carbon transition (Andonova & *al.*, 2009).

According to many observers, subnational authorities – just like private actors – are increasingly gaining in power in climate governance (Gordon & Johnson, 2018; Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Sovacool & Van de Graaf, 2018; Hale, 2016; Jänicke, 2015; Andonova & *al.*, 2009). Cities can actually greatly contribute to the low-carbon transition inasmuch as urban activities are responsible for a significant portion of GHG emissions – e.g.: 80% of emissions in EU. Moreover, cities have a number of

political levers to reduce GHG emissions, like housing, mobility, infrastructures, land-use and urban planning, and waste management (Jänicke, 2015). Many of the cities that are implementing ambitious climate mitigation actions are part of national or transnational networks (Gordon & Johnson, 2018; Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Jänicke, 2015). Among them are the Covenants of Mayors, Local Governments for Sustainability (ICLEI), C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group, Carbon Neutral Cities Alliance, City Energy Project (USA), Low-Carbon Eco-Cities (China), or 100%-Renewable Energy (Germany). Such networks aim to promote greater “*interaction, exposure, and communication*” as a way to increase the mobility of good practices among the cities that join them (Gordon & Johnson, 2018, p. 35). While they emerged in the early 90’s at the margin of the global climate regime, city-networks now have a much more important role in climate governance. Those networks are, for instance, increasingly mobilized for lobbying at the United Nations level, enabling cities to take part to global response to climate change (Gordon & Johnson, 2018; Hale, 2016).

In addition to city-networks, many other forms of transnational networks aiming to contribute to climate mitigation have started to emerge from the mid-2000s (Jordan & al., 2015; Andonova & al., 2009). Transnational networks are defined by Keohane & Nye as “*contacts, coalitions, and interactions across state boundaries that are not controlled by the central foreign policy organs of governments*” (Keohane & Nye 1971, p. 6). These public, private or hybrid networks are active at different scales, ranging from local to global (Bulkeley & al., 2014; Andonova & al., 2009). They intend to tackle the problem of climate change by different ways, such as information-sharing, capacity building and implementation, and rule-setting (Andonova & al., 2009). Example of transnational networks are the Cities for Climate Protection program (CCP), the Regional Greenhouse Gas Initiative (RGGI), the Climate Group (TCG), the Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Partnership (REEEP), the Chicago Climate Exchange (CCX), the Gold Standard, and the Clinton Climate Initiative. Transnational networks are not specific to climate change governance. Nevertheless, several characteristics of climate change problem were apparently conducive to the proliferation of transnational networks. Those are, among other, the presence of many civil society organizations whose activities span borders and scales, the structuration of the interests around a great variety of narrowly defined climate-related issues (e.g.: carbon market, renewable energy, reporting, climate justice), the implementation of the Kyoto flexibility mechanisms that required different skills and capacity, and the variable involvement of national authorities in international climate cooperation which encourage actors from countries with limited commitments to form “*coalitions of the willing*” (Andonova & al. 2009, p. 58).

In a nutshell, we observe a strong development of subnational actions and transnational cooperation in a polycentric system. The following figure illustrates the vertical and horizontal interactions between public and private actors at the subnational, national, supranational and international levels [Figure 29].

Figure 29. Vertical and horizontal interactions in the multi-level governance framework of climate change

4.3. How to Govern the Low-Carbon Transition: A Knowledge Gap

As previously explained, the low-carbon transition can be considered as a governance challenge (See section “2.2.2. From traditional top-down modes of governance to bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders” of the same chapter). The fact that, despite the resources invested for governing climate change, the continuously growing GHG emissions diminish every day the chances of limiting global temperature rise below 2°C is a symptom of the challenging nature of climate mitigation (Meckling & *al.*, 2015; Jordan & *al.*, 2015). Aykut & Dahan (2016), who have extensively analysed the international governance of climate mitigation, describe this discrepancy between, on the one hand, the will to reduce GHG emissions demonstrated at the world climate summits, and, on the other hand, the “reality” marked by the lack of measures that could enable to efficiently mitigate climate change as a “schism of reality”. Conceptualizing climate change as a super-wicked problem has enabled to better comprehend the difficulties of policy-makers in understanding and responding to climate change. I explained that, just like any wicked problem, climate change is a highly complex problem involving various actors whose interests and values differ. It therefore cannot be addressed with traditional top-down modes of governance. With the four extra challenges that make climate change a super-wicked problem, governing the low-carbon transition becomes even more difficult. As a reminder, those challenges are the urgency that reduces the room for manoeuvre to ensuring the low-carbon transition by 2050 as time passes; the lack of central authority that raises the question about the coordination among states, but also among multiple political domains and levels of power within each state; the absence of well-defined protagonists and antagonists as that those seeking to end the problem are also causing it; and the hyperbolic discounting that incites human beings to make irrational decisions that discount the future welfare in favour of present satisfaction (see section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of the same chapter).

In view of all these challenges, several scholars and various political actors believe that the low-carbon transition requires to deeply rethink, reshape and reform governance (Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Termeer & *al.*, 2016; Jordan & *al.* 2015; Urpelainen, 2013; Kunchornrat' & Phdungsilp 2012; Montini, 2011; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Foxon & *al.*, 2009; Boulanger, 2008). This is formulated as follow by the IPCC: “*The design of institutions affects the choice and feasibility of policy options as well as the sustainable financing of climate change mitigation measures. By shaping appropriate incentives, creating space for new stakeholders in decision making, and by transforming the understanding of policy choices, institutions designed to encourage participation by representatives of new industries and technologies can facilitate transitions to low-emission pathways, while institutions inherited unchanged from the past can perpetuate lock-in to high-carbon development paths.*” (IPCC 2014b, p. 1147). It is now widely acknowledged that the low-carbon transition will not happen with the traditional modes of governance.

I have shown in the previous sections that “new” modes of governance are appearing in the field of climate change (see sections “4.2.2. Coexistence of traditional top-down modes of governance and bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders” and “4.2.3. Development of subnational actions and transnational cooperation in a polycentric system” of the same chapter). We indeed observe the emergence of more bottom-up approaches involving private actors, namely markets, networks and communities. Confronting the limits of traditional command and control instruments, alternative policy instruments such as emission trading systems, collaborative agreements between governments and industries, carbon-energy labelling schemes, or grassroot innovations have arisen. Some of these new instruments are private initiatives. Various private actors like NGOs, business or grassroot movements have actually initiated actions to develop innovative policies for reducing GHG emissions. Moreover, just like private actors, subnational authorities are increasingly gaining in power in climate governance. *In fine*, partly due to the inability of international climate regime to mitigate climate change, a great variety of public, private or hybrid transnational networks have emerged with a view to fostering the low-carbon transition.

Even if the presence of “new” forms of governance for addressing climate change has been empirically shown by many authors, we don’t know much about the emergence, the functioning, the performance and the diffusion of these steering modes (Sovacool & Van de Graaf, 2018; Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Jordan & al., 2015; Meckling & al., 2015; Bulkeley & al., 2014; Hoffmann, 2011). As very rightly stated by Jordan & al. (2015), *“Achieving the emission reductions that are factored into many low concentration pathways arguably requires new forms of governance. But where will these new forms originate, how will they diffuse, and what factors will shape their ability to perform as hoped?”* (Jordan & al. 2015, p. 2). There is actually a lot of uncertainty surrounding those new modes of governance: How and why do various private and subnational actors start to act in favour of the low-carbon transition? How and why do “new” policy instruments emerge? Through which mechanisms are such “new” modes of governance maintained, diffusing and scaling up? What is the role of public actors in maintaining, diffusing and scaling up them? How can these modes of governance generate and accelerate the low-carbon transition? Are they filling the gap left by the weakness of traditional modes of governance? How do various modes of governance interact with each other? What are the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats inherent in these different modes of governance? Which alternative is the best regarding this or that criteria? Etc.

Apart from the general question of their respective efficacy, each of the new forms of governance previously mentioned raise a number of specific questions. For instance, the increasing role of private actors in climate governance is view as a potential threat by some (Hall, 2011; Bäckstrand 2008; Dredge, 2006; Pierre & Peters, 2000). Bäckstrand explains that it *“can lead to a ‘hollowing out’ of the state, reinforce neo-liberalism and accelerate privatization of environmental governance, [...] increased business influence, power inequalities and skewed representation of stakeholders, fragmentation of global governance, reinforcement of elite multilateralism and the retreat of state responsibility in the production of public goods”* (Bäckstrand 2008, p. 78). Moreover, while the development of subnational actions and transnational cooperation is seen as an opportunity for fostering experimentation, innovation, lesson-drawing, and diffusion of best practices, the polycentric approach also generates the problem of final responsibility (Jänicke, 2015; Bulkeley & al., 2014; Happaerts, 2013). As stated by Jänicke, *“if everyone is responsible, in the end there might be a situation in which nobody actually takes responsibility”* (Jänicke 2015, p. 5794). Some researchers have carried out analyses to better understand the “new” modes of governance for mitigating climate change (see Sovacool & Van de Graaf, 2018; Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Cadman & al., 2017; Jordan & al., 2015; Meckling & al., 2015). However, there is much that we still do not know about how to govern the low-carbon transition – all the more so as climate governance is constantly evolving.

5. Low-Carbon Scenarios and Governance

5.1. Scenarios for Knowing and Governing the Low-Carbon Transition: A Twofold Perspective

In the previous sections, I showed that, as a super-wicked problem, climate change cannot be addressed with traditional forms of knowledge production and modes of governance (Wright & *al.*, 2018; Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Batie, 2008; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994) (see section “2.2. Forms of knowledge production and modes of governance to address super-wicked problems” of the same chapter). Addressing such a complex problem requires to go beyond traditional normal sciences and hierarchical top-down steering modes. In this context, I presented scenario analysis as a suitable approach for *knowing* super-wicked problems like climate change (Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Head, 2014; Kok & *al.*, 2011; Fobé & Brans, 2013; Sardar, 2010; Marien, 2010; Levin & *al.* 2009; Kosow & Gaßner 2008; Mulder, 2007) (see section “3.2. Scenarios tackling super-wicked problems” of the same chapter). The increasing number of low-carbon scenarios reveals that this approach is recognized by many actors as a suitable decision support and orientation tool for long-term climate mitigation policy (Torrie & *al.*, 2013; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Hughes & Strachan, 2010) (see section “3.3. Low-carbon scenarios” of the same chapter). Through the analysis of climate mitigation governance, I then highlighted the development of more bottom-up modes of governance increasingly involving private actors, subnational entities and transnational networks, but also the knowledge gap surrounding the emergence, the functioning, the performance and the diffusion of these “new” modes of governance (Sovacool & Van de Graaf, 2018; Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Jordan & *al.*, 2015; Meckling & *al.*, 2015; Bulkeley & *al.*, 2014; Hoffmann, 2011) (see section “4.3. How to govern the low-carbon transition: A knowledge gap” of the same chapter).

The final section of this chapter aims at connecting low-carbon scenarios and governance. The link between those two objects of study is explored under a twofold perspective. As illustrated in the following figure, this twofold perspective involves two levels of analysis, namely the governance and the low-carbon scenarios [Figure 30]. The analysis thus focuses, on the one hand, on the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance (i.e.: “low-carbon scenarios in governance”), and, on the other hand, on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (i.e.: “governance in low-carbon scenarios”). Those two lenses are guiding the review of the literature presented in the rest of the chapter (see sections “5.2. Interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance” and “5.3. Making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios” of the same chapter).

Figure 30. Knowing and governing the low-carbon transition with scenarios: A twofold perspective

5.2. Interactions between Low-Carbon Scenarios and Governance

The following section discusses the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance. It explores the role of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making [Figure 31]. In the light of the increasing number of low-carbon scenarios and the resources invested to carry out such analyses, it seems relevant to ask if and how those scenarios contribute to mitigate climate change. With this in mind, I first provide an overview of the main literature on the role of knowledge in policy-making emphasizing the importance of looking beyond purely instrumental use of knowledge to devise policy. I then focus more specifically on the use and influence of scenarios in the policy process. I finally highlight the research gap on the interactions between scenarios and governance.

Figure 31. Low-carbon scenarios in governance

5.2.1. Knowledge and Governance: Beyond the Rational Knowledge-Based Policy-Making Model

The role of knowledge in policy-making have been an important research area in social sciences since the 1970s (Hezri, 2006). It falls within the broad field of “knowledge utilization literature” (see Landry & *al.*, 2001; Amara & *al.* 2004; Henry & Mark, 2003; Cash & *al.*, 2002; Rich, 1997; Weiss, 1979). The present section does not aim at providing a detailed discussion of the various branches of this very dense literature. Instead, it presents the conception of the relationship between knowledge and governance as well as the knowledge role typology under which this research is based. For the reader

interested, extended reviews of the knowledge utilization literature are provided by Gudmundsson & al. (2009) and Hezri (2006).

As previously mentioned, the normal science's underlying idea that new knowledge leads to less uncertainty, which in turn leads to improved decision doesn't apply to wicked problems because of their inherent irreducible uncertainties and high stakes (Batie, 2008) (see section "2.2.2. From traditional top-down modes of governance to bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders" of the same chapter). In the knowledge utilization literature, this model implying a linear relationship between "good" knowledge and "good" decisions can be referred to as "rational-positivist model" (Boulanger, 2007), "comprehensive rationality model" (Howlett & Ramesh, 2003) or "problem-solving model" (Weiss, 1979). Such model is based on the enlightenment rationalism and positivist philosophy that consider policy-makers as rational actors (Hezri, 2006). It assumes that when facing with uncertainty, policy-makers use knowledge to identify and select appropriate solutions to solve a problem (Weiss, 1979). The very first researches in the field of knowledge utilization used to focus on such direct use of knowledge to design policy (Gudmundsson & al., 2009; Amara & al., 2004). However, the linear rational knowledge-based policy-making model has scarcely been empirically observed. It actually appears that political actors hardly ever use knowledge to support the formulation of policy (Fobé & Brans, 2013; Bauler, 2012; Gudmundsson & al., 2009; Hezri & Dovers, 2006; Weiss & al., 2005; Henry & Mark, 2003; Weiss, 1978). As stated by Weiss (1978), "*the prevailing expectations for use of social science knowledge and research are much higher than reported use*" (Weiss 1978, p. 27).

The little use of knowledge for policy-making is related to the fact that the policy process is also guided by other factors, including power relations and organizational procedures. Under an institutional perspective, a policy is indeed the result of dynamic interactions between power-relations, organizational procedures and knowledge. Policy is often the outcome of power relations, coalitions, political bargaining and compromises among various actors whose ideologies, values and interest differ (i.e.: *politics*). Those complex interactions between political actors are embedded in organizational structures (i.e.: *polity*), which in turn influence policy-making (Van der Steen & van Twist, 2012). Path dependence mechanisms actually generate "*positive feedback of existing structures and previous decisions in future decisions*" (Van der Steen & van Twist 2012, p. 478). As a result, knowledge is rarely used in a rational manner to devise policy. The linear rational knowledge-based policy-making model is all the more far from empirical reality since it implicitly assumes a distinction between those who make science and those who use it, isolating science from policy-making, and society in general (Batie, 2008). Yet, the boundaries between knowing and governing are fuzzy, especially when it comes to wicked problems like climate change. As stated by Voß & Freeman, "*as in the question of climate change, the close and complex relationship between scientific problems and political problems makes for a widely discussed 'scientization of politics' – and a corollary 'politicization of science'*" (Voß & Freeman 2016, p. 1-2).

The little evidence of using knowledge as the direct basis for decisions doesn't mean that knowledge doesn't contribute to policy-making. The researches on knowledge utilization have revealed "unintended" uses and influences of knowledge in policy-making. In 1979, Carol Weiss defined six forms of knowledge role¹⁷ (see Weiss, 1979). This knowledge role typology has been adapted and complemented over time by different contributions (Gudmundsson & al., 2009). Today, three types of knowledge role in policy-making are generally distinguished. Those are the instrumental, the conceptual, and the political roles (Lehtonen & al., 2015; Bauler, 2012; Gudmundsson & al., 2009; Hezri, 2006; Weiss & al., 2005; Amara & al., 2004; Henry & Mark, 2003; Shulha & Cousins, 1997).

¹⁷ In the present research, the term "role" covers the "use" and "influence" of knowledge.

Instrumental Role

The instrumental role corresponds to the direct use of knowledge as an orientation tool to devise policy. As previously explained, such translation of knowledge into political action is not common (Weiss & *al.*, 2005). Pure instrumental use of knowledge can potentially be observed when the problem addressed entails low societal or political impact or high level of technicality (e.g.: specific policy instrument calibration) (Bauler, 2012).

Conceptual role

The conceptual role is more indirect and diffuse than the instrumental role (Amara & *al.*, 2004). It assumes that new knowledge percolates into the political arena (Weiss, 1999). Knowledge can thus contribute to expand the knowledge base, introduce new ideas or concept in the policy system, or alter the attitude of various actors regarding the problem. This can be referred to as collaborative learning, that is now broadly acknowledged as being a source of policy change (Bauler, 2012; Gudmundsson & *al.*, 2009). In contrast to the instrumental role, the conceptual role occurs “*in decision situations where stakes tend to be high and where information cannot be directly translated into policy action for a series of reasons: too much complexity, divided opinions, contrasting positions, lack of opportunity*” (Bauler 2012, p. 39). Such decision situations that are, according to Bauler (2012) very common, correspond to the political context within which wicked problems are addressed. When considering the use and influence of social science research in policy-making, it is now widely known that the conceptual role is much more important than the instrumental role (Amara & *al.*, 2004).

Political Role

The third type of role is the political role. It includes three sub-categories: legitimation, tactical and symbolic use. We speak of legitimation use when knowledge is used to justify political decisions that have already been taken. Tactical role is when knowledge is commissioned to postpone or avoid decision concerning emerging problems. *In fine*, in case of symbolic use, knowledge is commissioned to create the appearance that actions are carried out to solve the problem in order to reassure stakeholders (Bauler, 2012, Gudmundsson & *al.*, 2009).

Process Role

In addition to the instrumental, conceptual, and political roles, several authors consider the process role (Bauler, 2012, Gudmundsson & *al.*, 2009; Henry & Mark, 2003; Shula & Cousins, 1997). Such role is associated not to the result of a knowledge production activity, but to the process of knowledge production. It thus corresponds to the effects from the actors’ interactions and learning process that can occur as part of deliberative activities (Bauler, 2012; Henry & Mark, 2003). Some authors see the process role more as a factor affecting knowledge influence and prefer not considering it on the same level as the instrumental, conceptual, and political roles (Weiss & *al.*, 2005). In the present research, I have decided to include the process role because of the importance of participatory process in foresight activities that will be further discussed in the section devoted to the role of scenario analyses in policy-making (see section “5.2.2. Role of scenario analyses in policy-making” of the same chapter).

Distortive Role

A last type of role considered in the present thesis is the distortive role. We speak of distortive role when insufficient, wrong or biased knowledge is used to confuse or derail the policy process (Gudmundsson & *al.*, 2009). This can result from deliberate dissimulation (“abuse”) or manipulation (“misuse”) of data (Lehtonen & *al.*, 2015; Cousins, 2004).

5.2.2. Role of Scenario Analyses in Policy-Making

The knowledge utilization literature has explored the role of different science-based artefacts in policy-making, including evaluation (Weiss & *al.*, 2005; Henry & Mark, 2003; Van der Meer, 1999; Weiss, 1999; Shulha & Cousins, 1997) and, more recently, indicators (Lehtonen & *al.*, 2015; Sébastien & Bauler, 2013; Bauler, 2012; Gudmundsson & *al.*, 2009; Hezri, 2006; Rosenström, 2006). Nevertheless, we observe that, with some exceptions like Fobé & Brans (2013), scholars in the field of knowledge utilization literature have shown little interest in scenario analyses. More generally, the interactions between scenarios and the social context have received little academic attention from social sciences, whether they are political science, sociology, philosophy of science or science and technology studies (STS) (Fobé & Brans, 2013; European Environment Agency, 2009; Garb & *al.*, 2008; Aligica, 2003). Social sciences research on the social “work” of scenarios – i.e.: the scenarios’ influence on policy-making, from the plain instrumental use to conceptual and political roles (see above); the creation of “actor–network” (see Akrich & *al.*, 2006) or “epistemic communities” (see Haas, 1990) around scenario exercises; or the exploration of scenarios as “boundary objects” connecting different social worlds (see Jasanoff, 1990; Star & Griesemer 1989) – are virtually non-existent. So to speak, the discussion of scenarios as social objects has not entered the mainstream debates within social sciences (Garb & *al.*, 2008; Aligica, 2003).

When looking at the scenario literature, we note that methodological issues have been broadly discussed, while less attention has been paid to understanding the way scenarios products and processes influence what political actors know, say and do. In comparison with the importance given to methodological developments at the level of the calculus or data-sets, the interactions between scenarios and the social context are indeed overlooked by foresight practitioners and theorists (Kaljonen & *al.*, 2012; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; European Environment Agency, 2009; Garb & *al.*, 2008; De Smedt, 2006). It leads to a *“growing imbalance between the increasing technical sophistication of the modelling elements of scenarios and the continued simplicity of our understanding of the social origins, linkages, and implications of the narratives to which they are coupled”* (Garb & *al.* 2008, p. 1). This observation is particularly striking for the role of foresight studies that are geared to serve public policy: It has been studied less than the role of foreknowledge in some private sectors (Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; European Environment Agency, 2009). The relatively low importance of research on the social “work” of foresight doesn’t mean that this field is virgin of any investigation. Some have noticed growing attention to the use and influence of foresight in policy-making (Kunseler & *al.*, 2015; Johnston, 2012; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009). This emerging field is referred to as *“evaluative scenario literature”* by Volkery & Ribeiro (2009), who have contributed to the realization of a review of academic and non-academic studies on the issue (see European Environment Agency, 2009).

Use of Scenario Analyses in Policy-Making

For many authors, foresight is by its very nature a decision support tool. These authors consider that informing strategic decision is the main function of scenario analysis (Ramos, 2006; De Smedt, 2006; Aligica, 2005; Mermet, 2005; Lévêque & Urien 2005). As previously explained, non-predictive future-oriented analyses can help decision-makers to react to anticipated changes (i.e.: “preactivity”) and to act with a view to achieving desired changes (i.e.: “proactivity”) (Godet, 2004). Even if the added value of scenario analyses in public policy is obvious – especially in complex decision contexts involving many uncertainties and a lot of actors with different interests –, its practical use is anything but that (Van der Steen & van Twist, 2013; van der Duin & *al.*, 2009). The knowledge produced through foresight exercise are hardly used to support the formulation and implementation of policy – excepted selectively and strategically (i.e.: political role) (Rijkens-Klomp 2012; Van der Steen & van Twist, 2012). Facing the low use of foresight products, Volkery & Ribeiro consider scenarios as *“hollow diamonds that sparkle alluringly but fail to contain real value to the decision-making process”* (Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009). The persistent implementation gap between scenario analyses and policy-making is widely acknowledged in the literature (Van der Steen, 2017; Olsson & *al.*, 2015; Banister & Hickman, 2013;

Fobé & Brans, 2013; Van der Steen & van Twist, 2013 and 2012; Rijkens-Klomp, 2012; Yoda, 2011; van der Duin & *al.*, 2010; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; European Environment Agency, 2009; De Smedt, 2006; Stevenson, 2001; Kapoor, 2001).

The low use of scenario analyses is not that surprising since, as explained in the previous section, the relationship between knowledge and policy is neither linear, nor mechanical – the rational knowledge-based policy-making model being hardly ever empirically confirmed (see section “5.2.1. Knowledge and governance: Beyond the rational knowledge-based policy-making model” of the same chapter). However, compared with other science-based artefacts like evaluation and indicators, scenario approach presents a number of characteristics that impede its use by policy-makers. According to Van der Steen & van Twist, “*policy-makers do not ‘choose’ to neglect or decline future oriented notions, but find it problematic/impossible to apply them to their reality (...) in day-to-day practice of making public policy*” (Van der Steen & van Twist 2012, p. 477). Many scholars point a mismatch between foresight and policy-making (Van der Steen, 2017; Kunseler & *al.*, 2015; Van der Steen & van Twist, 2013 and 2012; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009). Van der Steen and van Twist summarize the disconnected relation between foresight and policy-making as follow: “*Futures studies tend to complicate things, instead of resolving them. Policy makers know futures thinking is important, but futures thinking gets lost in the process of creating clear policy texts (...). Policy-makers need clarity, while foresight provides them with new complexity. They seek solutions, while foresight reframes or even adds problems. They are troubled by present-day crises, while foresight downplays those in the light of future developments. And although policy-makers know that futures studies are often right, they can hardly make use of them because of their contextual requirements*” (Van der Steen & van Twist 2012, p. 482). More fundamentally, the main purpose of foresight that is to cope with uncertainties appears to be incompatible with policy-making, since, according to Van der Steen & van Twist (2012), policy-makers are intolerant toward uncertainties – even if their environment is uncertain, fuzzy and ambiguous. In addition, at a more individual level, some authors identify moral impediments to the use of foresight products (Riedy, 2009; Hayward, 2003; Glenn & *al.*, 2001). Those psychological factors include, *inter alia*, the lack of consideration of future generations’ needs, caring only for the well-being of one’s own group or state, and the absence of holistic thinking about the world (Glenn & *al.*, 2001). In that context, Van der Steen claims that the link between foresight and policy-making “*needs to be forged – and sometimes perhaps forced*” (Van der Steen 2017, p. 194). Several works have been done to understand how to connect further foresight and policy-making. Those works provide various suggestions either for improving foresight practice in order to increase its use for policy-making (i.e.: “policy-oriented foresight”), or for reconfiguring policy-making or resolving moral impediments to foresight use in order to create a governance system more permeable to foresight (i.e.: “future-oriented policy” or “anticipatory governance”) (Kunseler & *al.*, 2015; Brunet, 2014; Hughes, 2013; Van der Steen & van Twist, 2013 and 2012; Rijkens-Klomp 2012; Habegger, 2010; van Asselt & *al.*, 2010; Fuerth, 2009; Da Costa & *al.*, 2008; Riedy, 2009; Chermack, 2004; Hayward, 2003; Glenn & *al.*, 2001).

Note that all the authors do not paint such a bleak picture of the applications of scenario analyses in policy-making. Certain authors have identified “success stories”. Use of scenarios by public authorities to formulate policy have been observed in the case of science and technology foresight in countries where this practice is institutionalized (e.g.: United Kingdom, Sweden, Finland, United States, China, or Japan) (Riedy, 2009; Calof & *al.*, 2006; Hayward, 2003). Calof & *al.* (2006) have identified the common features of such “success stories”. Those features relate both to institutional aspects and to the characteristics of foresight exercises: Foresight practice has to be integrated into organizational procedures and the scenario analyses should connect the future and today’s policy agenda, involve main stakeholders and present clear communication strategies (Calof & *al.*, 2006). Riedy (2009) and Wynberg (2003) add that science and technology foresight works fit better into the policy process than other types of foresight because they tend to reduce the levels of complexity and to diminish the uncertainties regarding future developments, rather than exploring alternative futures. As summarized by Riedy (2009), “*the successful examples tend to be close to government, with a clear*

focus on policy relevance. They apply foresight to a limited set of science and technology issues and tend to employ linear or systemic methods, reducing the complexity that decision-makers need to deal with” (Riedy 2009, p. 44). A last reason explaining the use of science and technology foresight is that it doesn't challenge dominant worldviews and related assumptions, contrary to sustainability foresight for instance. By ignoring radically different futures, those analyses presuppose that current power relations and societal objectives (e.g.: competitiveness, economic growth) are maintained, which resonates with policy-makers and incumbents. It is therefore less probable that science and technology foresight triggers the existing moral impediments to the use of scenario analyses results identified by Glenn & al. (2001) (Riedy, 2009; Hayward, 2003; Kapoor, 2001). Considering that one of the foresight's riches is its ability to embrace uncertainty, complexity and alternative worldviews, Riedy sees the success of science and technology foresight as *“an example of sacrificing quality, breadth and depth of analysis for the sake of influence”* (Riedy 2009, p. 44-45).

Beyond Use: Influence of Scenario Analyses in Policy-Making

Besides the low use of foresight for supporting policy formulation, several scholars highlight diffuse and indirect roles of foresight in policy-making (Fobé & Brans, 2013; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009). Many authors state that, by affecting the cognitions of individuals and groups, scenarios can help, among others, to awareness raising, agenda setting, and issue framing, which can, in turn, contribute to policy formulation and implementation (i.e.: conceptual role) (Fobé & Brans, 2013; Johnston, 2012; Rijkens-Klomp 2012; Van der Steen & van Twist 2012; Quist & al., 2011; van der Duin & al., 2009; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; European Environment Agency, 2009; Riedy, 2009; Paillard, 2006; Ladikas & Decker, 2004). We indeed observe that a number of publications that have helped to raise awareness on environmental problems are future-oriented. Examples of such publications are *“Silent Spring”* from Rachel Carson (1962) that have fostered the development of the ecological movement in the Western world and *“The Limits to Growth”* of the Club of Rome (Meadows & al., 1972) which enabled political actors and society to become aware of the dangers associated with economic and population growth (Riedy, 2009; Glenn & al., 2001). Those classic works have indirectly fostered the development of environmental policies (Glenn & al., 2001). More recently, in the 90's, the first IPCC report that explores possible future developments of climate system and associated impacts, has contributed to put the problem of climate change on the political agenda (Riedy, 2009; Tonn, 2007). According to Agrawala (1998), the adoption of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) at the Earth Summit in 1992 would probably not have been possible without this report. The subsequent IPCC reports have helped to keep climate change on the political agenda and to frame the debate on the issue (Riedy, 2009). Scenario analyses can also help political actors to gain a better understanding of the future developments of the problem, but also on its present state (Rijkens-Klomp 2012; Glenn & al., 2001).

In addition to the conceptual role, the process role of participatory foresight exercises is highlighted by many authors (Fobé & Brans, 2013; Rijkens-Klomp 2012; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; European Environment Agency, 2009; Riedy, 2009; De Smedt, 2006). Scenarios coproduction process can potentially contribute to facilitating collective learning, constructing a common cognitive frame of reference, promoting empowerment, developing a network of actors, fostering dialogue and exchange of opinion among different actors, enabling engagement and participation of stakeholders in the policy-process, creating negotiating space helping to the construction of consensus among stakeholders, or building a common future vision and a shared sense of commitment (Miller & al., 2015; Gunnarsson-Östling & al., 2012; Rijkens-Klomp 2012; Quist & al., 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Svenfelt, 2010; Habegger, 2010; Da Costal & al., 2008; Garb & al., 2008; de Smedt, 2006; Georghiou & Keenan, 2006; Paillard, 2006; Lévêque & Urien, 2005). Because of the potential influence of participatory process, an increasing number of foresight exercises attach more importance to the process than to the products (e.g.: Miller & al., 2015; Hisschemöller & Bode, 2011). Da Costa & al. (2008) observe a shifting emphasis from informing policy with foresight products to facilitating policy implementation

and enabling change through foresight processes. They explain that while foresight was initially intended to provide concrete guidelines and policy recommendations, process-oriented foresight aiming at promoting linkages, communication and cooperation between various actors have been more and more carried out since the 90's (Da Costal & *al.*, 2008).

5.2.3. On the Need for Empirical Research on the Role of Scenario Analyses in Policy-Making

Foresight products and processes are claimed as potentially contributing to policy-making. Basically, however, up to here, relatively little empirical efforts have tried to explore the fundamentals of the role of the scenario analyses in policy-making. Empirical insights of the use and influence of scenarios have been provided, among others, by Fobé & Brans (2013), Rijkens-Klomp (2012), Quist & *al.* (2011), Yoda (2011) and van der Duin & *al.* (2009). The other contributions on the interactions between scenarios and governance previously mentioned are mostly theoretical and conceptual research papers. In that context, several authors call for additional empirical research to better understand how scenario products and processes affect the social context (Rijkens-Klomp 2012; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; European Environment Agency, 2009; Georghiou & Keenan, 2006; Chermack, 2004). One of the conclusions drawn by Volkery & Ribeiro on the basis of the review of the evaluative scenario literature previously mentioned is related to *“the need for broadening the empirical base to better understand how and to which effect scenario planning is used and how it can deliver to its promises”* (Volkery & Ribeiro 2009, p. 1206).

Such empirical investigations on the role of scenarios in policy-making would, in my opinion, benefit from resting on theory and methodologies developed in political science, sociology, philosophy of science or STS. As said before, with a few exceptions like Fobé & Brans (2013), the discussions of scenarios as social objects have not yet penetrated the mainstream debates in social sciences, confining themselves to the evaluative scenario literature. Yet, the conceptual frameworks and methodological tools drawn from social sciences that have been proven to be effective for analysing the role in policy-making of other science-based artefacts could greatly contribute to shed light on the social aspects of scenarios (Garb & *al.*, 2008). Exploring the role of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making on the basis of the conceptual frameworks and methodological tools developed in the knowledge utilization literature is one of the objectives of the present thesis. A first research question is therefore formulated in the following manner:

“How do low-carbon scenarios interact with governance?”

This general question is divided into four sub-questions:

- I. How are low-carbon scenarios used by political actors?
- II. Beyond the purely instrumental use, how do these foresight exercises influence policy-making?
- III. How do the different actors appropriate the representations of the future developed through these scenario analyses?
- IV. What are the factors that affect the use and influence of these foresight exercises in policy-making?

5.3. Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios

While the previous section has explored the role of scenarios in the governance system, this section reverses the perspective in order to focus on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios [Figure 32]. We thus move from an exploration of “knowledge *in* political practices” to an investigation of “knowledge *of* political practices” (Voß & Freeman, 2016). The following section first highlights the under-representation of low-carbon scenario analyses addressing governance issues compared to purely technical-economic analyses. Then, on the basis of a review of low-carbon scenarios including dimensions of governance as variables, I explore what knowledge about governance is produced in low-carbon scenarios and how such knowledge is produced. I finally emphasize the need for further research on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios.

Figure 32. Governance in low-carbon scenarios

5.3.1. Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios

By conceptualizing the low-carbon transition as a socio-technical transition, I have shown that the policy process and its outputs (i.e. *policy*), the constellation of actors and their role in the policy process (i.e. *politics*) as well as the mode of political steering and the institutional arrangements (i.e. *polity*), can significantly impede or facilitate the transition towards a low-carbon society (Nilsson & al., 2011). Indeed, according to the socio-technical approach, a transition is a fundamental shift resulting from the coevolution between the different sub-systems of the socio-technical system, the activities of the actors and the system of rules and institutions (Foxon & al., 2010; Geels, 2004) (see section “1.2.1. Socio-technical approach” of the same chapter). A change in one of those components can therefore not be considered independently of the other components (Wangel, 2011a). As stated by Miller & al., 2015, “the transitions confronting us are not just whether and where we build new power plants but rather what kind of world we inhabit, what kind of climate we enjoy, and who prospers and who thrives” (Miller & al. 2015, p. 73). I have also demonstrated, that a number of characteristics make the low-carbon transition a super-wicked problem, which cannot be addressed with traditional top-down modes of governance (see section “2.2.2. From traditional top-down modes of governance to bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders” of the same chapter). The low-carbon transition will actually not happen without deeply rethinking, reshaping and reforming governance (Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Termeer & al., 2016; Jordan & al. 2015; Urpelainen, 2013; Kunchornrat & Phdungsilp 2012; Montini, 2011; Nilsson & al., 2011; Söderholm & al., 2011; Foxon & al., 2009; Boulanger, 2008). The development of “new” modes of governance call for further investigations: “Achieving the emission reductions that are factored into many low concentration pathways arguably requires new forms of governance. But where will these new forms originate, how will they diffuse, and what factors will shape their ability to perform as hoped?” (Jordan & al. 2015, p. 2) (see section “4.3. How to govern the low-carbon transition: A knowledge gap” of the same chapter).

In that context, many authors argue that low-carbon scenarios should include and explore governance dimensions as variables (Li & al., 2016 ; Olsson & al., 2015; Fortes & al., 2015; Schubert & al., 2015; Miller & al., 2015; Kalnins & al., 2014; Foxon, 2013; Hughes, 2013; O' Mahony & al., 2013; Nilsson &

al., 2011; Svenfelt & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Hughes & Strachan, 2010; Foxon & *al.*, 2010). They consider that low-carbon scenarios should not only represent in a clear and structured manner the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance, but also embrace the co-evolving nature of technology and society (Li *al.*, 2016; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Such scenarios would enable to better capture the socio-technical essence of the low-carbon transition (Li *al.*, 2016; Wangel, 2011a). Moreover, in light of the limits of traditional modes of governance for addressing the low-carbon transition, many argue that governance should be considered in scenario analyses as an object of (fundamental) change, in the same way as the modes of energy production and consumption (Kiraly & *al.*, 2013; Wangel, 2011a; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011). Low-carbon scenarios should indeed explore the functioning and the performance of alternative modes of governance, but also how those “new” steering modes emerge, diffuse and scale up. Governance changes are likely to be hampered by mechanisms that encourage institutional stability and inertia (e.g.: lock-in and path-dependence) and it is necessary to understand how to overcome those mechanisms (Wangel, 2012; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011).

However, we note that even if most of the low-carbon scenarios provide a high level of detail for the technical and economic dimensions, they do not or hardly address the governance issues. The scenarios are most of the time the outputs of quantitative models which allow analysing the technical and behavioural changes in producing and consuming energy required to reduce GHG as well as the costs associated with such a transition pathways (Li & *al.*, 2016; Fortes & *al.*, 2015; Schubert & *al.*, 2015; Miller & *al.*, 2015; Király & *al.*, 2013; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Svenfelt & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Hughes & Strachan, 2010; Foxon & *al.*, 2010). After reviewing a number of backcasting studies for sustainable development, Josefin Wangel concludes that “*even though there are some exceptions, there is a general lack of explicit, explorative and reflexive approaches to the question of agency and social structures*” (Wangel 2012, p. 62.) In most of the low-carbon scenarios, *policy* is generally external to the analysis. Through their methodological review of low-carbon scenarios, Hughes & Strachan observe “*a strong tendency to treat the two key variables of technology and behaviour as (...) controllable phenomena capable of being switched on or off in a somewhat binary fashion, by an exterior lever known as ‘policy’*” (Hughes & Strachan 2010, p. 6063). In many scenario analyses, the authors simply state that ambitious policies should be implemented to promote the technological and behavioural changes required to achieve GHG targets (Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). This assertion presupposes that policy affect technology and behaviour in a linear fashion, ignoring the co-evolving nature of society and technology (Li & *al.*, 2016; Foxon, 2011; Hughes & Strachan, 2010; Elzen & *al.*, 2004). It also assumes that policy-makers can formulate and implement policy at will. As a result, the low-carbon scenarios neglect the obstacles and limitations imposed by the societal context, such as the social acceptability or the institutional constraints (Hughes & Strachan, 2010). The scenarios are therefore not necessarily feasible from a social and political point of view (Schubert & *al.*, 2015). Regarding the *politics* dimensions, the modelling approach generally assumes a high level of economic rationality of actors and do not take into consideration – or only in a very limited way – the different values, perspectives and interests of the many stakeholders (Li *al.*, 2016; Foxon & *al.*, 2010). As a consequence, the resulting low-carbon scenarios do not really enable to understand the effects of actors’ decisions and actions on the socio-technical system (Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Finally, *polity* is hardly ever addressed in low-carbon scenarios, at least not explicitly. Most of the models often assume implicitly hierarchical steering modes according to which a central authority outside the system formulate and implement policy in order to foster technological and behavioural changes. The low-carbon scenarios elaborated with this type of model therefore maintain the modes of governance according to status quo (Kiraly & *al.*, 2013; Wangel, 2011a).

According to Mike Hulme (2011), the asymmetrical incorporation of technological and social change into future-oriented analyses of climate change results from the rise of a powerful epistemic community of earth system modellers in climate change studies combined with the lack of theory-making about the interactions between climate and society. The limited consideration of the social

dimensions of climate-energy issues is not unique to scenario analyses. In climate change studies, social sciences are globally under-represented and analyses integrating natural and human sciences are rare (Holm & Winiwarter 2017; Miller & al., 2015; Holm & al., 2013). There is indeed a “*poorly developed and a-theoretical understandings of climate-society relationships in the social sciences*” (Hulme 2011, p. 26). Holm & Winiwarter (2017) illustrate the marginal position of social sciences in climate change studies by analysing the disciplinary composition of the IPCC Working Group (WG) III. The mandate of the main epistemic authority on climate change is to assess in a comprehensive way scientific, technical and socio-economic knowledge. It should therefore include natural and social sciences perspectives. With 46% of the 468 authors of the WGIII coming from social sciences, we could think that the IPCC fulfil this objective. However, if we look at it closer, we can see that among those 46%, the great majority comes from the field of economy. The IPCC Assessment Reports actually provide substantial economic perspectives on climate change, with little regard to the rest of the social sciences spectrum (Holm & Winiwarter, 2017). Holm & Winiwarter conclude that “*despite the multitude of calls for interdisciplinarity, the need to encourage the integration of human sciences in climate change research remains*” (Holm & Winiwarter 2017, p. 115).

The technical-economic analyses are clearly of crucial importance, particularly to better understand the interactions between energy demand and supply, and to demonstrate that the low-carbon transition is physically feasible and not prohibitively expensive (Nilsson & al., 2011; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Yet, for the reasons previously mentioned, an analysis ignoring the interactions between technical, economic, social and political factors is too narrow and is based on several biases assumptions that reduce its robustness (Fortes & al., 2015; Kiraly & al., 2013). In addition to their inherent ontological and epistemic problems, purely technical-economic scenarios might also fail to provide relevant inputs into governance processes (Nilsson & al., 2011). Hughes (2013) claims that “*If such scenarios are to be effective and tractable tools in their intended public policy area, they must achieve two things. First, they must provide a convincing description of a low-carbon transition, to demonstrate that this is feasible prospect (in technological and social terms), and not just ‘wishful thinking’. Second, they must clearly identify decisions and actions of particular system actors upon which the transition is contingent. The latter aim is particularly crucial to ensuring that long-term goals and targets are translated back into near term action requirements*” (Hughes 2013, p. 689). Schubert & al. (2015) have a slightly different point of view regarding the policy-relevance of low-carbon scenarios. They assert that technical-economic scenarios used to be policy-relevant when the question of whether the low-carbon transition is possible was on the table, but the authors maintain that we are currently witnessing a shift of attention from *if* to *how* could we manage such transition (Schubert & al., 2015). The question of *how* encompasses, among others, the governance issues – i.e.: *How to steer the low-carbon transition? What public policies to implement? At what levels of power? By who? What are the institutional changes required to ensure such transition?* Etc. Against that background, many scholars consider that low-carbon scenarios including governance issues as variables might be perceived by policy-makers as being more relevant than the purer technical-economic studies (Schubert & al., 2015; Hughes, 2013; Nilsson & al., 2011; Söderholm & al., 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Such socio-technical scenarios might simply contribute to bridge the above mentioned implementation gap between scenario analyses and policy-making, bearing in mind that, besides their perceived relevance, many other factors influence the use of scientific objects in policy formulation and that the role of science in the policy process is not limited to instrumental use (Olsson & al., 2015; Schubert & al., 2015) (see section “5.2.2. Role of scenario analyses in policy-making” of the same chapter).

Nevertheless, including governance variables into low-carbon scenarios is a significant methodological challenge (Li & al., 2016; Prehofer & al., 2014; Kiraly & al., 2013). The development of scenarios capturing the socio-technical essence of the energy transition is indeed extremely complex, since it requires taking into consideration the co-evolution of many interrelated social and technological variables (Hughes, 2013). As we will see later, this raises, among others, the question of the level of

integration of social variables in energy models (see section “5.3.2. On the need for further investigation on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios” of the same chapter). In that context, several authors call for further research to develop new approaches to include social dimensions in low-carbon scenarios (Miller & *al.*, 2015; Király & *al.*, 2013, Nilsson & *al.*, 2011, Söderholm & *al.*, 2011, Wangel, 2011a; Hughes & Strachan, 2010).

5.3.2. On the Need for Further Investigation on the Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios

Even if the great majority of low-carbon scenarios are the result of technical-economic analyses, we can still observe a few foresight studies addressing governance issues. During the academic year 2014-2015, I have identified and analysed 24 energy foresight studies including at least one dimension of governance – i.e.: *policy*, *politics* and *polity* (see section “4.1.2. Policy, politics and polity dimensions of governance” of the same chapter). For each study, I have analysed the making of knowledge about governance, both in term of product and process. I have looked at “*what is this knowing or knowledge of, exactly, and how is it made?*” (Voß & Freeman 2016, p. 11). This review highlights the need for further investigation on the making of knowledge about governance – or “knowing governance” (see Voß and Freeman, 2016) – in low-carbon scenarios.

Overview of the Low-Carbon Scenarios Reviewed

The review has provided some insights into the knowledge about governance produced in low-carbon scenarios as well as a glimpse of the range of approaches and methodologies that are used to produce such knowledge. The table below summarizes the main features of the low-carbon scenarios reviewed [Table 6]. For the interested reader, a list with the complete references of these studies is given in appendix [Appendix 1].

REFERENCE	SCOPE			APPROACHES			Dimensions of governance included in low-carbon scenarios			Methodology used to include governance in low-carbon scenarios
	Temporal	Spatial	Material	Scenario type	Quantification	Participation	Politics	Polity	Policy	
(1) Au & al., 2011	2010-2020	Global	Energy and climate system	External scenarios	Qualitative and quantitative (each qualitative scenario is associated with an IPCC scenario, which enables to evaluate the rise in temperature in 2100)	Experts and stakeholders	x	x	x	Windows of opportunity in which the decisions of actors can shift climate governance from one scenario to another + development of storylines
(2) Bibas & al. 2012	2050	National	Energy production, transports, building, industry, agriculture and waste	Strategic scenarios	Quantitative (evaluation of energy production and consumption, and associated GES)	Experts and stakeholders (workshops)			x	Energy system model integrating policy instruments
(3) CLIMACT & al., 2015	2050	Region, multilevel perspective	Energy production, transports, building, industry, agriculture and waste	External scenarios (+ one target-orientated backcasting scenario)	Qualitative	Experts and stakeholders (consultation)		x	x	Structural analysis + morphological analysis + development of storylines
(4) Bruggink, 2005	2005-2050	National, multilevel perspective	Energy production and consumption	External scenarios	Qualitative	Experts	x	x	x	2X2 axes + development of storylines
(5) Carlsson-Kanyama & al., 2008; Carlsson-Kanyama & al., 2005	2010-2040	City	Households	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Qualitative and quantitative (evaluation of energy consumption)	Experts and stakeholders (workshops)	x	x	x	2X2 axes + qualitative backwards-looking analysis of the governance changes required for reach alternative future visions + development of storylines
(6) Ciscar & Soria, 2002	2000-2020	Global	Energy and climate system	Strategic scenarios	Qualitative (evaluation of GHG emissions and resulting temperature rise)	Experts	x	x	x	Integrated assessment model of climate system and economy based on a sequential game framework
(7) Elzen & al., 2004	2000-2050	City	Transports	Socio-technical scenarios	Qualitative	Experts	X	x	x	Multi-level perspective on transition + development of storylines

REFERENCE	SCOPE			APPROACHES			Dimensions of governance included in low-carbon scenarios			Methodology used to include governance in low-carbon scenarios
	Temporal	Spatial	Material	Scenario type	Quantification	Participation	Politics	Polity	Policy	
(8) Foxon & al., 2013	2050	National	Energy production, transports, building, industry, agriculture and waste	Socio-technical scenarios	Qualitative and quantitative (evaluation of energy production and consumption, and associated GES)	Experts and stakeholders (workshops and interviews)	x	x	x	Multi-level perspective on transition + action space + development of storylines
(9) Geurs & van Wee, 2004	2030	National	Transports	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Quantitative (evaluation of energy consumption and associated GES)	Experts			x	Energy system model integrating policy instruments
(10) Gomi & al., 2011	2005-2030	City	Energy production, transports, building, industry, agriculture and waste	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Quantitative (evaluation of energy production and consumption, and associated GES)	Experts			x	Energy system model integrating policy instruments
(11) Gomi & al., 2007	2000-2030	Region	Energy production, transports, building and industry	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Quantitative (evaluation of energy production and consumption, and associated GES)	Experts	x		x	Energy system model integrating policy instruments
(12) Hisschemöller & Bode, 2011	Not specified	National	Hydrogen production and use in building and transports	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Qualitative	Experts and stakeholders (workshops)	x		x	Constructive Conflict Methodology
(13) Hulme & al., 2009	2010-2040	Europe, multilevel perspective	Energy production, transports, building and industry	Strategic scenarios	Quantitative (evaluation of energy production and consumption, and associated GES and temperature rise)	Not specified	x	x	x	2X2 axes + integrated assessment modelling
(14) Leppänen & al., s.d.; Neuvonen & al., 2014	2050	Europe, multilevel perspective	Households	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Qualitative and quantitative (evaluation of environmental and social boundaries indicators)	Experts and stakeholders (Delphi survey, focus groups and workshops)	x	x	x	2X2 axes + qualitative backwards-looking analysis of the governance changes required for reach alternative future visions + development of storylines

REFERENCE	SCOPE			APPROACHES			Dimensions of governance included in low-carbon scenarios			Methodology used to include governance in low-carbon scenarios
	Temporal	Spatial	Material	Scenario type	Quantification	Participation	Politics	Polity	Policy	
(15) Murphy & al., 2008	2012-2050	Global	Not specified	Strategic scenarios	Qualitative	Experts		x	x	Development of storylines
(16) Ornetzeder & al., 2012	2050	National	Energy production and consumption (sectors not specified)	External scenarios and pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Qualitative	Experts and stakeholders (workshops)	x	x	x	Ex-post inclusion of social context in existing scenarios
(17) Prehofer & al., 2014	2050	Region	Energy production, building	External scenarios	Quantitative and qualitative (hybrid scenario resulting from the combination of a quantitative energy scenario and a qualitative context scenario)	Experts		x		Cross-impact-balance analysis
(18) Robèrt & al., 2007	2030	City	Transports	External scenarios and pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Quantitative (evaluation of energy consumption)	Experts			x	Transport system model integrating policy instruments
(19) Russ & al., 2007	2005-2050	Global	Energy production, transports, Building, industry, agriculture, waste and land use, land use change and forestry (LULUF), and climate system	Strategic scenarios	Quantitative (evaluation of energy production and consumption, and associated GES)	Experts			x	Energy system model integrating policy instruments
(20) Selin & VanDevee, 2009	Not specified	National, multilevel perspective	Not specified	Strategic scenarios	Qualitative	Not specified		x	x	2X2 axes
(21) Svenfelt & al., 2011	2050	National	Building	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Qualitative	Experts and stakeholders (focus groups)	x		x	Qualitative backwards-looking analysis of the governance changes required for reach alternative future visions

REFERENCE	SCOPE			APPROACHES			Dimensions of governance included in low-carbon scenarios			Methodology used to include governance in low-carbon scenarios
	Temporal	Spatial	Material	Scenario type	Quantification	Participation	Politics	Polity	Policy	
(22) Thollander & al., 2013	2020	National	Industry	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Quantitative (evaluation of energy consumption)	Experts			x	Energy system model integrating policy instruments
(23) Vergragt & Brown, 2007	2050	City	Transports	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Qualitative and quantitative (evaluation of energy consumption and associated GES)	Experts and stakeholders (workshops)			x	Not specified
(24) Wangel & al., 2013; Wangel and Gustafsson, 2011	2010-2060	City	Transports	Pathway-orientated backcasting scenarios	Qualitative and quantitative (evaluation of energy consumption and associated GES)	Experts and stakeholders (focus groups)	x		x	Qualitative backwards-looking analysis of the governance changes required for reach alternative future visions + development of storyline

Table 6. Main features of the studies analysed

The approaches used are summarized in the following figure [Figure 33]. We observe that the low-carbon scenarios analysed originate from two distinct research areas, namely futures studies and transition studies. The great majority of the scenarios come from the area of futures studies. Those analyses involve the development of explorative scenarios (external and strategic), visionary scenarios (pathway- and target-orientated backcasting), or sometimes a combination of both (see scenario typology presented in the section “3.1.2. Scenarios for envisioning and exploring alternative images of the future” of the same chapter). In addition to the foresight works carried out in the area of future studies, I have identified two scenario analyses built on the socio-technical transitions literature using a multi-level perspective on low-carbon transition (see section “1.2.2. Multi-level perspective on transition” of the same chapter). The low-carbon scenarios reviewed are based on a great variety of quantitative, qualitative and mixed approaches. Regarding the level of participation, I found as many desk researches conducted entirely by experts as participatory foresight exercises involving stakeholders. The analyses also vary regarding their temporal scope (from 2020 to 2060), their geographical scope (from local to global scale) and their material scope (from the households, to one specific sector, to the entire energy-climate system).

Figure 33. Approaches used to develop low-carbon scenarios including governance. Each number corresponds to an energy foresight analysed.

Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios

The review reveals that very few low-carbon scenarios provide comprehensive representation of governance. If we take a closer look at the three dimensions of governance, we see that the *policy* dimension is addressed in most of the scenario analyses, while the *polity* and *politics* dimensions are missing in many analyses. In light of the challenges posed by the vertical and horizontal interactions in the multi-level governance framework of climate change, the under-representation of *polity* and *politics* dimensions in low-carbon scenarios is questioning. We can actually wonder why the constellation of actors and their role in the policy process (i.e. *politics*) as well as the mode of political steering and the institutional arrangements (i.e. *polity*) are less represented than the policy process

and its outputs (i.e. *policy*). Are those issues less relevant for policy-makers? If not, why are they less addressed in scenario analyses? Is it too difficult from a methodological point of view to include those dimensions in low-carbon scenarios? Or do the scenarios producers simply not perceive the policy-relevance of the *polity* and *politics* issues? As explained by Cash & al. (2002) “*what the scientist considers relevant information may not be the same as what the decision maker considers relevant, and vice versa*”. They add that “*there must be some way that the expert can know what kinds of questions to ask in order to produce knowledge that is salient to the decision maker*” (Cash & al. 2002, p. 2). Assessing the knowledge needs of political actors for governing the low-carbon transition constitutes the second objective of this thesis. It involves the following research question:

“What do political actors need to know to steer the low-carbon transition?”

This question is divided into two sub-questions:

- I. What knowledge about governance do political actors need to devise long-term mitigation policies?
- II. Is foresight a suitable approach to provide this knowledge?

Modes of Production of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios

When looking at how the knowledge about governance is made in the scenario analyses reviewed, we note that each methodology is essentially unique. Yet, some constants regarding the methods used are observed. The most widely used methods are models integrating dimensions of governance, soft modelling methods like cross-impact / structural analysis and morphological analysis considering governance variables, qualitative backwards-looking analysis of the governance changes required for reach alternative future visions, 2X2 axes crossing two critical governance variables to create four possible future social contexts through which the scenarios are built, and the development of narrative stories or “storylines” exploring alternative future developments. Those quantitative and qualitative methods are sometimes combined to form quite elaborated methodologies. The scenario analyses reviewed can thus be placed on a continuum between purely quantitative approaches that fully integrate governance variables within models (i.e.: integrated assessment model-based analysis) (e.g.: Robèrt & al., 2007; Gomi & al., 2011) and exclusively qualitative studies (Hisschemöller and Bode, 2011; Elzen & al., 2004). Between these two poles, we find different hybrid approaches combining to various extent quantitative and qualitative scenarios techniques (e.g.: Neuvonen & al., 2014; Foxon & al., 2013; Wangel & Gustafsson, 2011).

The distinction between those three approaches for developing low-carbon scenarios representing governance reflects a broader discussion of the relations between quantitative models and social sciences. The question at the root of the discussion is the extent to which social dimensions should be integrated into models (see Geels & al., 2016). This debate opposes three conceptions of the relations between quantitative modelling and social sciences. A first perspective consists in advocating a full integration of social dimensions in models. The proponents the integrated approach consider that modelling tools should be based on social sciences theories and concepts, and fully integrate social dimensions as variables. Such integrated models are part of the larger area of integrated assessment which aims at combining knowledge, analyses and insights from the natural sciences and social sciences in a sort of meta-discipline in order to address wicked problems (Hamilton & al., 2015; Weyant, 2009). An opposing point of view is that quantitative simulation and social analyses are incommensurable and should be applied separately (Geels & al., 2016). Those in favour of pluralism consider that integrated assessment model-based analyses fail to capture the complexity of social dynamics. For Castree & al. (2014) integrated approaches “*reveal a limited conception of social science and virtually ignore the humanities. They thereby endorse a stunted conception of ‘human dimensions’ at a time when the challenges posed by global environmental change are increasing in magnitude, scale and scope*” (Castree & al., 2014). Finally, an intermediate view is that quantitative models and

social science concepts and theories should not be completely integrated, but rather combined. The defenders of this perspective argue that these different approaches are complementary, but hardly integrable. Instead, they suggest making alignment, bridges and iterations between quantitative simulations and social analyses with a view to combining their respective strengths (Robertson & *al.* 2017; Geels & *al.*, 2016; Turnheim & *al.*, 2015).

We observe that most of the low-carbon scenarios addressing governance issues are based either on quantitative models integrating governance variables (i.e.: integrated approach), or on purely qualitative analyses (i.e.: pluralistic approach). Approaches combining quantitative modelling and qualitative methods (i.e.: complementarity-based approach) for exploring low-carbon futures are indeed pretty rare¹⁸ (Robertson & *al.* 2017; Fortes & *al.*, 2015). Yet, as explained by Robertson & *al.* (2017), “*the combination of the qualitative and quantitative analysis in this way subsequently formed the cornerstone of wider interdisciplinary research, helping to harmonize assumptions, and facilitating ‘whole system’ thinking*” (Robertson & *al.* 2017, p. 293). Many authors claim that combining quantitative modelling and qualitative methods can increase the policy-relevance and the robustness of low-carbon scenarios (Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Geels & *al.*, 2016; Turnheim & *al.*, 2015; Fortes & *al.*, 2015; McDowall, 2014; Trutnevyte & *al.*, 2014; O' Mahony & *al.*, 2013; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Kowalski & *al.*, 2009; Alcamo, 2008). The integrated and the pluralistic approaches have actually inherent limits and are potentially fraught with bias (Robertson & *al.* 2017; Turnheim & *al.*, 2015; Fortes & *al.*, 2015, Söderholm & *al.*, 2011). Some limits of purely qualitative approaches are quite evident – especially in the case of visionary low-carbon scenarios. An exclusively qualitative analysis does not allow to know if the scenarios developed reach the quantitative GHG reduction targets, are cost-effective, or even technically feasible. Quantitative modelling is therefore necessary to make sure that the low-carbon scenarios are consistent (Robertson & *al.* 2017; Fortes & *al.*, 2015, Söderholm & *al.*, 2011). The remaining question is thus whether quantitative models and social science concepts and theories should be completely integrated or only combined. The last objective of this thesis is to contribute to the debate on the relations between quantitative modelling and social sciences. Positioning myself in favour of the complementarity-based approach, I aim at consolidating the foundations of this approach. My hypothesis is that the approaches attempting to fully integrate social science concepts and theories and the quantitative models-based analyses are not suitable to capture the complexity of the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition; and that, in this respect, complementarity-based approaches are more effective. The main research question is the following:

“What are the limits of scenario analyses based on integrated modelling in addressing the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition?”

This question involves three sub-questions:

- I. Which dimensions of governance are included in integrated energy models?
- II. Which approaches are used to integrate these social dimensions?
- III. What are the limits of integrated energy models in addressing governance issues?

¹⁸ An example of low-carbon scenario developed on the basis of a complementarity-based approach combining quantitative modelling and qualitative methods has been presented in the general introduction of the thesis (see Scenario “Thousand Flowers” developed as part of the Transition Pathways to a Low-Carbon Economy” (Foxon & *al.* 2013)).

Conclusion to the Chapter

Through this chapter, we navigated across various literatures, making bridges between research areas that are usually considered separately. Those are sustainability transitions, wicked problems, (evaluative) scenario, (climate) governance, and knowledge utilization literatures. The following figure displays the literature mobilized as part of this research [Figure 34].

Figure 34. Literature mobilized as part of this research

One of the objectives of the present chapter was to set the conceptual and theoretical framework of the research. In that context, I conceptualized the low-carbon transition as a socio-technical transition. It enabled to highlight the crucial role of society in reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% in 2050 – a socio-technical transition consisting in a multi-dimensional shift resulting from the coevolution between the different sub-systems of the socio-technical system, the activities of the actors and the system of rules and institutions. I then presented the characteristics that make climate change a super-wicked problem. Defining climate change as a super-wicked problem pointed out the difficulties of policy-makers in knowing and governing the low-carbon transition. This allowed to understand the need to go beyond classic ways of producing knowledge – here referred to as normal sciences – and traditional top-down modes of governance. I then presented foresight or scenario approach as a suitable tool for tackling super-wicked problems. It was defined as a policy-oriented approach assuming that the future is multiple, uncertain and potentially radically different from the present, and aiming at envisioning and exploring in a systemic and holistic way alternative images of the future. After defining this concept and demonstrating its relevance for tackling super-wicked problems like climate change, I focused more specifically on low-carbon scenarios, showing the great diversity of approaches for envisioning and exploring alternative images of low-carbon futures. I then moved on to the governance of the low-carbon transition. The concept of governance was defined as every mode of political steering involving public and private actors, including various modes of coordination, from traditional top-down to bottom-up steering modes of coordination. I then presented the three dimensions of governance considered in the present thesis, namely *policy*, *politics* and *polity*. Following

this conceptual clarification, I provided an insight on the governance of the low-carbon. I showed the coexistence of traditional top-down modes of governance and bottom-up approaches involving stakeholders, but also the recent development of subnational actions and transnational cooperation in a polycentric system. This analysis pointed out major knowledge gap about the governance of the low-carbon, highlighting the need for exploring this issue. At this stage, low-carbon scenarios and governance had been considered separately. The objective of the last part of the chapter was therefore to connect those two objects of study. This connection was explored under a twofold perspective focusing, on the one hand, on the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance (i.e.: low-carbon scenarios in governance) and, on the other hand, on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (i.e.: governance in low-carbon scenarios). Such twofold perspective guided the literature review, which highlighted the need for of social sciences research on scenarios. Against that background, three research questions were formulated.

DESIGN OF THE RESEARCH

DESIGN OF THE RESEARCH

1. Research Questions

Three main research questions and associated sub-questions were identified in the chapter devoted to the literature review (see section “5. Low-carbon scenarios and governance” of Chapter I). Through this review of the literature, I have highlighted their theoretical and conceptual basis as well as their relevance regarding the state of the art. Each main research question corresponds to one research axis that structure the present thesis. The three research axes as well as their corresponding questions are summarized below.

Research axis n°1. How do low-carbon scenarios interact with governance?

This research question is divided into four sub-questions:

- I. How are low-carbon scenarios used by political actors?
- II. Beyond the purely instrumental use, how do these foresight exercises influence policy-making?
- III. How do the different actors appropriate the representations of the future developed through these scenario analyses?
- IV. What are the factors that affect the use and influence of these foresight exercises in policy-making?

Research axis n°2. What do political actors need to know to steer the low-carbon transition?

This research question is divided into two sub-questions:

- I. What knowledge about governance do political actors need to devise long-term mitigation policies?
- II. Is foresight a suitable approach to provide this knowledge?

Research axis n°3. What are the limits of scenario analyses based on integrated modelling in addressing the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition?

This research question is divided into three sub-questions:

- I. Which dimensions of governance are included in integrated energy models?
- II. Which approaches are used to integrate these social dimensions?
- III. What are the limits of integrated energy models in addressing governance issues?

The three research axes can be situated in relation to the twofold perspective exposed in the previous chapter (see section “5.1. Scenarios for knowing and governing the low-carbon transition: A twofold perspective of Chapter I) [Figure 35]. As a reminder, the link between low-carbon scenarios and governance is explored through two lenses corresponding to (1) the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance (i.e.: “low-carbon scenarios in governance”), and (2) the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (i.e.: “governance in low-carbon scenarios”). While the research axes n°1 and n°3 corresponds respectively to the perspective 1 and 2, the research axis n°2 encompasses the two perspectives. It focuses on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (i.e.: perspective 2), but by assessing its policy-relevance, it considers this knowledge in the context of policy-making (i.e.: perspective 1).

Figure 35. Overview of the research

2. Empirical Studies

Through these three research axes, the present thesis aims at providing a social analysis of low-carbon scenarios. The three research axes are based on empirical studies – here understood as research resting on the observation of historical or contemporary objects of study, in contrast to theoretical or conceptual research. Each individual study has its own methodology and empirical material. The chapters devoted to one study can therefore be read independently of the others. The present section provides an overview of the three empirical studies that compose the thesis, introducing their specific methodology and empirical material.

Interactions between Low-Carbon Scenarios and Governance: A Multiple Case Study (Chapter III)

The aim of the research axis n°1 is to contribute to fill the gap on the social “work” of foresight by providing empirical insights to the state-of-the-art on the roles of scenario analyses in policy-making. With this in mind, I have undertaken a multiple case study analysing the role in policy-making of four energy foresight studies carried out for the Walloon Region (Belgium). This analysis has been carried out on the basis of an analytical framework developed in the knowledge utilization literature (see Gudmunson & al., 2009). It considers the five above-mentioned types of knowledge role in policy-making, namely instrumental, conceptual, political, process and distortive roles (see section “5.2.1. Knowledge and governance: Beyond the rational knowledge-based policy-making model” of Chapter I). The exploration of the use and influence of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making is based on documentary analysis and 74 semi-structured interviews with the actors involved in the long-term climate mitigation policy in Wallonia. Those actors are political authorities, political advisors, administrative authorities, employers’ federations, workers’ unions, environmental and development NGOs, advisory councils, energy market operators, public transport operators, public research institutes, consultancy agencies and universities. The important empirical material collected was analysed with the method of thematic coding. After exploring the role in policy-making and the level of appropriation per actor for each of the four studies, I have conducted a cross-case analysis in order to highlight the similarities and differences between the four studies.

Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios: A Needs Assessment (Chapter IV)

The research axis n°2 develops on an empirical study aiming to apprehend and compare the perceptions of different actors of the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition. Just like in the research axis n°1, the actors are those involved in the long-term policy process of GHG-emissions’ mitigation in the Walloon Region (Belgium). The needs assessment is carried out with a Q methodology, a qualitative but statistically supported survey method that allows understanding the variety of discourses around a given topic (see Barry & Proops, 1990). As part of the Q-survey, 54 participants sorted a set of potential research questions covering the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance according to their relevance to devise mitigation policies. A principal component analysis of the data led to the identification of three factors that are ideal-typical versions of the way to perceive the subject of study shared by a number of participants. The analysis of the similarities and differences between the factors allowed to highlight the areas of consensus and the terms of the debate regarding the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition.

Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios: A Critical Review of Socio-Technical Energy Transition Models (Chapter V)

The final research axis intends to contribute to the debate on the relations between quantitative modelling and social sciences. Positioning myself in favour of the complementarity-based approach, I aim at consolidating the foundations of this approach. My hypothesis is that the approaches attempting to fully integrate social science concepts and theories into quantitative models-based analyses fail to capture the complexity of the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition and that, in that respect, complementarity-based approaches are more effective. With a view to confirming this hypothesis, I attempted to highlight the inability of integrated modelling to effectively address governance issues. I carried out a critical review of fifteen socio-technical energy transition (STET) models. They correspond to “*formal quantitative energy models (...) [that capture] the elements of socio-technical transitions, including societal actors and the co-evolutionary nature of policy, technology and behaviour*” (Li & al. 2015, p. 291). I analysed if and how those integrated models make knowledge about governance through a framework allowing to assess the way they address the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance. This analysis revealed a number of limits regarding the way STET models address governance. After identifying the factors that might explain the failure of STET models in representing the “reality” of governance, I discuss the need to combine complementary approaches to address governance in low-carbon scenario analyses.

CHAPTER II.

Contextual Background

CHAPTER II. Contextual Background

Introduction

This chapter aims at providing the contextual background for the field study presented in the two new chapters (see Chapters III and IV). The field study has been carried out in Wallonia, one of the three regions that make up Belgium. In the first section, I introduce the main characteristics of the Walloon region. I then focus more specifically on the domestic GHG emission by presenting historic and projected emissions. Afterwards, I move on to the presentation of the climate mitigation governance in Wallonia. The governance is addressed in a multi-level perspective. I will indeed introduce climate mitigation governance in Wallonia by taking into consideration the interactions with other levels of power (i.e.: Belgian national, European and international), but also the implication of private actors. The section devoted to the governance of the low-carbon transition is divided into five sub-sections. The first sub-section provides an overview of the Belgian political system. I then expose the sharing out of the competence regarding climate mitigation policy between the federal state and the regions. I subsequently focus on the energy market governance. Afterwards, I explain how the civil society participate in the policy-making process. The last sub-section on governance aims at presenting the main climate mitigation policies starting from the emergence of climate mitigation governance and the first commitment period of the Kyoto Protocol to the post-2012 policy which is currently implemented. I close the chapter by providing some insight on climate-energy foresight in Wallonia. After discussing the institutionalization of foresight in Walloon public action, I focus more specifically on foresight in the field of climate-energy. In this context, I present the main actors that carry out such foresight studies, as well as some example of recent climate mitigation scenario analyses developed for Wallonia other than those analysed in the next chapter (see Chapter III).

1. Walloon Region

Wallonia is one of the three regions that make up Belgium, the other two regions being Flanders and the Brussels-Capital Region [Figure 36]. Located in the south of the country, the Walloon Region covers an area of 16,844.3 km², which equates to 55.2% of the national territory (IWEPS, 2017a).

Figure 36. Map showing the three Belgian regions. Wallonia is indicated in yellow

Wallonia is the least densely populated Belgian region. With 3 602 216 inhabitants registered on 1 January 2016, it has a population density equivalent to 214 inhabitants/km² while Flanders and the Brussels-Capital Region have respectively a population density of 479 and 7,361 inhabitants/km². As shown in the map below, these inhabitants are not evenly distributed in Walloon territory [Figure 37]. The northern part of the territory which includes the main Walloon cities is much more populated than the South. With the migratory movement, the number of inhabitants increases from year to year. In 2015, the population growth rate was 3.4% (IWEPS, 2017a). According to the latest projections from the Federal Planning Bureau, this growth rate should increase in the coming years. The Walloon population is expected to reach 3 815 265 inhabitants in 2030 and 4 014 896 in 2050 (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2018d).

Figure 37. Map of population densities by commune for Wallonia (IWEPS 2017a, p. 11)

In economic terms, Walloon gross domestic product (GDP) in 2015 amounted to 88.6 billion euros, that being 23% of the national GDP. While industrial activity, and especially heavy industry, was particularly developed in Wallonia, the tertiarization of the economy and the crisis of 2008 which caused the closure of the hot phase sites of the steel industry led to a decline in the contribution of this sector of activity to the total economy. In 2014, the share of industry in GDP was 23%, while that of services was 76% of GDP. In comparison, the industry in Flanders and Brussels represent respectively 26% and 8% of GDP. Walloon economic activity is particularly specialized in the pharmaceutical industry (IWEPS, 2017a).

Still in terms of the economy, in 2016 Wallonia had an unemployment rate of 10.6%. This relatively high rate is higher than the European average (9.2%). The unemployment rate in Wallonia is much higher than that of Flanders (4.9%), but lower than that of the Brussels-Capital Region (16.9%) (IWEPS, 2017a).

2. Domestic GHG Emissions

2.1. Historic GHG Emissions

In April 2018, Wallonia submitted its annual inventory of GHG which covers the GHG emitted from 1990 to 2016. This inventory is combined with those of the Flemish and Brussels Regions to form the national inventory of GHG emissions which is communicated every year by Belgium to the European Commission in accordance to the EU Regulation No 525/2013. The latest inventory shows that in 2016 Wallonia emitted 36.1 million tons of Carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂eq) (excluding the forestry sector) (AWAC, 2018). It corresponds to 31% of Belgium's annual emissions that amount to 177.7 million tons of CO₂eq (Service fédéral Climat, 2018).

Different types of gas are counted in annual inventory of GHG. As shown in the figure below, carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the main GHG [Figure 38]. It accounts for 82% of total emissions. Methane (CH₄), just like nitrogen dioxide (N₂O), accounts for 8% of total GHG emissions. Fluorinated gases (F-gas) contribute 2% of total GHG emissions.

Figure 38. Distribution of GHG emissions by type of gas in Wallonia in 2016 (AWAC, 2018)

Looking at the sectoral distribution of Walloon GHG emissions [Figure 39], the industry is the biggest source of GHG. This sector, which contributes 30%, is followed by the transport and residential sectors, which respectively account for 25% and 15% of total emissions. The remaining GHG emissions are divided between agriculture (13%), electricity generation (8%), tertiary (5%) and waste (1%).

Figure 39. Sectoral distribution of Walloon GHG emissions (AWAC, 2018)

Between 1990 and 2016, Wallonia reduced its GHG emissions by 35%. As shown in the figure below, the different sectors contributed in a very varied way to this reduction of emissions [Figure 40].

Although industry is the largest source of emissions, this sector is responsible for reducing total emissions by 27%. The emission decreases from the industrial sector is due to closures of steel plants and increased use of gas or alternative fuels. With the switch from coal to natural gas or wood and the closure of coking plants, the electricity generation sector also contributed to a reduction in emissions of around 7%. Emissions from the residential, waste and agriculture sectors also declined. On the other hand, the transport sector caused an increase in global emissions of 4%. This growth in emissions generated by transport is the result of an increase in the number of cars, in their engine capacity and in the kilometers traveled. Finally, tertiary sector emissions have also slightly risen.

Figure 40. Evolution of GHG emissions by sector in Wallonia between 1990 and 2016 (KT CO₂eq) (AWAC, 2018)

It also seems interesting to point out that between 1990 and 2016, the total GHG emissions of Wallonia did not decrease linearly. These interannual variations are generally due to the conjunction of several factors. The figure below shows a series of events that influenced the GHG emission reduction trajectory [Figure 41]. These events include, among others, the economic crises of the early 1990s and 2008 that caused the closure of some industries, but also milder than average winters that led to a reduction in heating requirements.

Figure 41. Main events that have influenced the evolution of GHG emissions in Wallonia between 1990 and 2016 (AWAC, 2018)

2.2. Projections of GHG Emissions

As part of the foresight study “towards a Wallonia Low-Carbon in 2050” conducted in 2012 by CLIMACT (2012), a business as usual scenario has been developed. This reference scenario, developed with the accounting model OPE²RA (for more information about the OPE²RA model, see section “3.1.2. Presentation of the study” of Chapter III), considers a successful implementation of GHG emission reduction policies adopted at European, Belgian and Walloon levels for 2020. With 45 million tons of CO₂eq in 2050, it leads to a reduction of GHG emissions of 17% compared to 1990 level. By highlighting the gap between projected emissions and the goal of reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% in 2050, the analysis shows the extent of efforts needed to ensure the transition towards a low-carbon society. The graph below illustrates the evolution of Walloon GHG emission between 2010 and 2050 in the reference scenario in comparison with low-carbon scenarios [Figure 42].

Figure 42. Evolution of Walloon GHG emission between 2010 and 2050 in the reference scenario (in red) in comparison with low-carbon scenarios (in green) (in kilo-tons of CO₂eq) (CLIMACT 2012b, p. 10)

In the reference scenario developed by CLIMACT, the evolution of GHG emissions varies from one sector to another. This is notably the case for the industry, which, thanks to the improvement of its carbon intensity, is seeing its GHG emissions decrease. On the other hand, GHG emissions generated by the transport sector are increasing. According to CLIMACT analysis, the improving vehicle energy efficiency is indeed unlikely to offset the increase in emissions caused by the growing demand for mobility per capita and the rise in road freight transport. GHG emissions from electricity generation should also increase after 2025 as a result of the closure of nuclear power plants and their partial replacement by gas-fired power plants. Emissions for heating are also increasing very slightly due to a rise in energy demand that is not offset by improvements in the energy efficiency of buildings and equipments. This rise in the energy demand of buildings is the result of an increase in thermal comfort, in the number of housing units and in tertiary demand (CLIMACT, 2012).

More recently, projections have been made for Wallonia to develop a 2030 energy-climate reference scenario. These projections are based on a simulation exercise conducted by ECONOTEC with the Energy Policy Model (EPM) (DGO4, 2017). EPM is an accounting model similar to the OPE²RA model used by CLIMACT (2012) (VITO, 2012a). The analysis covers the following sectors: residential, tertiary, industry and electricity generation. The document published on the DGO4 website does not include the projections for the transport sector. By considering the main existing policies and by extending them until 2030, the EPM model have evaluated the evolution between 2012 and 2030 of the final energy consumptions, of the development of renewable energies and of GHG emissions. Overall, the analysis shows that, assuming unchanged policy, GHG emissions should remain relatively stable for the period considered.

Figure 43. Evolution of Walloon GHG emission between 1990 and 2030 for the sectors of energy, industry, residential and tertiary (in kilo-tons of CO₂eq) (DGO4 2017, p. 6)

As shown in the graph above [Figure 43], only the energy production sector should see its emissions increase significantly after 2025 following the closure of nuclear power plants and their partial replacement by gas-fired power plants. On the other hand, the analysis reveals that, despite growth in the buildings stock, GHG emissions from the residential and tertiary sectors are expected to decrease very slightly between 2012 and 2030. This reduction in emissions is the result of improvement of the energy efficiency of buildings and equipment. Finally, the GHG emissions generated by the industry should remain relatively stable (DGO4, 2017).

The 2030 Walloon energy-climate reference scenario was used to sketch the Belgian projections of greenhouse gas emissions for the period 2015-2035. These are presented in the Reporting on projections approved in March 2017 by the National Climate Commission and submitted to the European Commission in accordance to the EU Regulation No 525/2013. In this report, a scenario with existing measures (WEM) and a scenario with additional measures (WAM) were developed on the basis of bottom-up projections made for the three regions of the country. The WAM scenario includes two additional measures: an increased blend of biodiesel in the transport sector and a more extensive development of off-shore wind power. The scenarios resulting from the compilation of regional projections were compared with national projections developed by the Federal Planning Bureau (FPB) with the top-down macro-econometric model HERMES. The evolution of emissions for WEM and WAM scenarios is illustrated in the graph below [Figure 44]. The modelling shows that with 114 million tons of CO₂eq in 2030, GHG emissions in the WEM scenario remain more or less stable between 2014 and 2030. The WAM scenario results in a very slight decrease in GHGs emissions from 114 million tons of CO₂eq in 2014 to 112 million tons GHGs in 2030. The GHG emissions in the macro-economic scenario decrease slightly more to reach 109 million tons of CO₂eq in 2030. The variations between the scenarios elaborated with the top-down and the bottom-up modelling tool can be explained by

differences in the ways those simulation tools respond to assumptions – the macro-econometric models being for instance more sensitive to price variations than accounting models.

Figure 44. Evolution of Belgian GHG emission between 2014 and 2035 in WEM and WAM scenarios (in million tons of CO₂eq) (National Climate Commission 2017, p. 45)

That being said, whatever the model used, the scenario analysis highlights a considerable gap between the projected emissions and the policy objectives for 2020 and 2030. It shows that Belgium will not achieve the target for reducing GHG emissions by 15% in 2020 set for the non-ETS¹⁹ sector under the EU effort sharing decision (for more information about the climate-energy objectives of Belgium, see section “3.5. Main climate mitigation policies” of the same chapter). While this target amount to 67,7 tons of CO₂eq for the non-ETS sector in 2020, the WEM and WAM scenarios lead respectively to 71 and 70,2 tons of CO₂eq. The scenario analysis reveals that the gap is widening between projected emissions for the non-ETS sector and the envisaged policy objectives for the next period that will go for 2021 to 2030. The graph below illustrates the gap between projected emissions and GHG emission reduction pathways to achieve the 2020 and 2030 targets [Figure 45].

Figure 45. Evolution of Belgian GHG emission for non-ETS sectors between 2014 and 2035 in WEM and WAM scenarios in comparison with effort sharing decision path (in million tons of CO₂eq) (Service fédéral Climat, 2018)

Finally, by drawing attention to the considerable efforts that are needed to engage in a low-carbon transition trajectory, this analysis is in keeping with the conclusions set out earlier by CLIMACT.

¹⁹ Emissions Trading System

3. Climate Mitigation Governance in a Multi-Level Perspective

3.1. Overview of the Belgian Political System

3.1.1. Belgian Federalism

Due to the 1993 institutional reform, Belgium has become a federal state made up of three political-administrative levels. At the top level, one finds the federal government and two types of federated entities that do overlap, namely the regions (Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels) and the communities (Flemish, French and German) (Reuchamps, 2013) [Figure 46]. A specificity of Belgian federalism is the absence of hierarchy between the federal state, the regions and the communities. In addition, the competences are divided on an exclusive basis between the three political-administrative levels. Therefore, a given competence can only be exercised by a single entity. In accordance with the principle of *in foro interno, in foro externo*, the exclusivity of competences is also applied in foreign policy (Happaerts, 2013). In Belgium, the power and the competences of the federated entities are relatively broad and the Sixth state reform, which has been implemented between 2011 and 2014, provides for the transfer of additional competences from the federal state to the regions and communities. As some policy domains go beyond the scope of a single entity, several cooperation and coordination mechanisms have been developed. These include cooperation agreements that can be signed between the federal state, the regions and the communities with a view to increasing collaboration between these entities (Reuchamps, 2013).

Figure 46. Belgian federated entities (www.belgium.be)

At the middle and inferior political-administrative levels, we find respectively the provinces and the communes, which are under the supervision of the higher authorities, depending on the powers exercised.

3.1.2. Partitocracy

Another fundamental characteristic of the Belgian political system is that it is a partitocracy (Peters, 2006; Seiler, 1999). This implies that the majority parties – and more specifically the authorities of these parties – hold most of the power (Vigor, 2010). In the Belgian partitocracy, the main actors in policy-making are the ministerial cabinets, which are composed of the political advisors of each minister (Brans, 2005). In such a system, after the elections, the parties called to form a majority define the coalition government agreement. Built on the basis of a compromise between the programs of the different political parties, this agreement takes up, for each ministerial department, the main orientations of the public policy that the government undertakes to carry out during the legislature. In addition, the development of a public policy often leads to negotiations between the main leaders of the majority parties. A first version of a bill drafted by the competent minister's office is actually discussed at an inter-cabinet meeting gathering the representatives of majority parties. When these parties have reached an agreement, the bill is submitted to parliament. It is unlikely that the project will be challenged by parliament, especially because parliamentarians most often vote in favour of the policy developed by the authorities of their party (Vigor, 2010). Moreover, the parties not only hold most of the power in the political sphere, but also in the administrative sphere. Political parties indeed intervene in the recruitment of senior officials whose appointment depends on a politicized distribution (Vigor, 2010; Jacob, 2005).

3.1.3. Corporatism

The relationship between policy and society is based on a corporatist model (Petit Jean, 2016). Belgium has actually a long tradition of social dialogue. Through advisory bodies, the Government consults social partners when making decisions on social and economic matters. The social dialogue developed after the Second World War (CESW, 2018). Initially, it involved a triangular relationship between the Government, the employers and the workers' unions (Arcq & Marques-Pereira, 1991). With the emergence of new types of political issues, such as environmental and North-South problems, other civil society organizations joined the advisory bodies – i.e.: development and environmental NGOs. The involvement of civil society in climate-energy policy is presented in greater detail later (see section “3.4. Involvement of Civil Society in Climate-Energy Policy-Making” of the same chapter).

3.1.4. Pillarization

The Belgian political system is defined as a pillarized system. Pillarization is a system of social and political organization based on pillars. A pillar is "*a set of organizations that share a common ideology and that ensure its influence in the organization of society*" (CRISP, 2018). It can gather a political party, a trade union, a mutuality, cooperatives, youth and permanent education movements, private or public schools and other socio-cultural, socio-economic or sports organizations that share the same ideology. Political parties are only one component of the pillars (CRISP, 2018, Delwit, 2011). The development of a system of pillarization assumes the existence of cleavages that significantly structure the society. In Belgium, this system developed at the end of the 19th century with the emergence of an opposition between the socialist and the Christian pillars. On the eve of the First World War, the liberal pillar joined the political landscape to form the three-pillar system that we know today (Delwit, 2011). These three pillars correspond to the three traditional parties. Note that some parties such as the extreme right-wing are not associated with any pillar. In addition, other parties like the ecologists reject the system of pillarization while their emergence is the result of interactions between various organizations sharing a common ideology (CRISP, 2018).

3.2. Climate Mitigation: A Shared Competence between the Federal State and the Regions

In Belgium, climate mitigation competences are fragmented between the federal state and the regions, but also, between different political and administrative authorities within each of these entities. The complex multi-level architecture of the Belgian climate-energy governance was illustrated as follows by the Belgian cartoonist Pierre Kroll [Figure 47]. According to Happaerts (2013), such a complex multi-level architecture often leads to policy features. A typical and memorable example of policy failure was the inability of political authorities to reach a political agreement on intra-Belgian burden sharing before the COP21 in Paris, which led environmental NGOs to award the "Fossil of the day" title to Belgium (RTBF, 2015). The present section aims at presenting the vertical and horizontal division of competences in the area of climate-energy policy.

Figure 47. Belgian political authorities at COP21 in Paris (Kroll, 2015)

3.2.1. Vertical Integration

Even if the environmental policy is mostly a regional competence, climate mitigation is a shared competence between the federal state and the regions. The issue of climate change mitigation goes actually well beyond environmental policy and concerns other policy areas such as energy, transports or even taxation. The competences are therefore fragmented between the federal state and the regions. The following table illustrates the Division of competences for climate mitigation policy between the federal state and the regions [Table 7]. Except for education, the communities have no real political levers to carry out a climate-energy policy. As they have a number of political levers, including mobility and urban planning, local entities (i.e.: provinces and communes) have an important role to play in the climate mitigation policy. Yet, as part of this study, I have decided to focus on the federal and Walloon levels.

	FEDERAL STATE	REGIONS
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coordination of the international policy (including climate policy) ▪ Products' standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Air quality
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Energy foresight ▪ Nuclear fuel cycle ▪ Energy production, including offshore ▪ Major infrastructures of production and storage of energy ▪ Transport of energy ▪ Policy regarding final prices of energy for the consumer ▪ Energy efficiency of federal buildings ▪ Aspects of taxation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Distribution and local transport of electricity through networks with a nominal voltage of 70,000 volts or less ▪ Rational use of energy ▪ Distribution rates (gas and electricity) ▪ Public distribution of gas ▪ Use of firedamp and blast furnace gas ▪ Distance heat distribution networks ▪ Valorisation of slag heaps ▪ New sources of energy with the exception of those related to nuclear energy ▪ Energy recovery by industries and other users ▪ Rational use of energy
Transports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ National airport and railway lines ▪ Taxation on fuels ▪ Vehicles' technical standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Motorways, waterways, ports and regional airports ▪ Public transport and school transport ▪ Taxation on vehicles

Table 7. Division of competences for climate mitigation policy between the federal State and the regions (adapted from Service fédéral Climat, 2018)

Some structures have been put in place to coordinate the actions of the regions and the federal state. These are the National Climate Commission (CNC), the Interministerial Conference for the Environment (CIE), the Coordinating Committee for International Environmental Policy (CCIEP), the Interregional Environment Committee (CELINE) and the State-Regions Concertation Committee on Energy (CONCERE). These structures bring together political and / or administrative authorities from the federal and regional levels (Service fédéral Climat, 2018). However, since decision-making requires consensus among the different governments, some observe that national climate policy "*is always pulled down*" (interview, former adviser to the Walloon Minister for the Environment) and when the different entities cannot agree, no decision is made. These vertical coordination issues are, among other things, the source of difficulties in drawing up an intra-Belgian agreement on burden sharing.

3.2.2. Horizontal Integration

The competences are also fragmented within each entity between different political and administrative authorities. In total, ten ministers and eleven administrations have levers for action to ensure the low-carbon transition. The table below lists the main political and administrative authorities having levers for action to ensure low-carbon transition [Table 8].

	FEDERAL STATE	WALLOON REGION
Political authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minister in charge of Energy, Environment and Sustainable Development ▪ Minister in charge of mobility ▪ Minister in charge of agriculture ▪ Minister in charge of employment and economy ▪ Minister in charge of Finances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minister in charge of budget, finances, energy, climate and airports ▪ Minister in charge of environment, ecology transition, territory planning, mobility and transports ▪ Minister in charge of Local Authorities and housing ▪ Minister in charge of agriculture ▪ Minister in charge of Economy, Industry, Research, Innovation, Digital, Employment and Training
Administrative authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment ▪ FPS Mobility and Transports ▪ FPS Economy ▪ FPS Finances ▪ FPS Employment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon Agency for Air and climate (AWAC) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Mobility and Waterways (DGO2) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Agriculture, Natural Resources and the Environment (DGO3) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Spatial Planning, Housing and Energy (DGO4) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Economy, Employment and Research (DGO6) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Taxation (DGO7)

Table 8. Political and administrative authorities having levers for action to ensure the low-carbon transition

3.3. Energy Market Governance

3.3.1. Liberalisation of the Energy Market

Until recently, the energy market in Wallonia was a controlled monopoly. The import, production, distribution, transport and supply of energy were in the hands of three companies (i.e.: Electrabel, Luminus and Distrigaz) and of the intercommunals (Comparateur-Energie.be, 2018). In Belgium, the energy market has been liberalized in 2007. This liberalization stems from a decision of the European Union to promote the free exchange of goods and services between Member States – i.e.: European Directives concerning common rules for the internal market in electricity (96/92/EC) and natural gas (98/30 /EC) (CWAPE, 2018). The purpose of this decision was to lower energy prices by promoting competition, but also to improve the quality of services offered to consumers. With this in mind, the EU have imposed a separation of the energy related activities. It implies that distinct companies have to deal with transportation, distribution and energy supply. The liberalization of the energy market has therefore led to the arrival of new actors. As we will see below, it has also driven to the emergence of other monopolies (Comparateur-Energie.be, 2018).

3.3.2. Energy Market Operators

Today, the main energy market operators are the producers, the importers, the suppliers, the transmission system operators (TSOs), the distribution system operators (DSOs) and the regulators. The figure below illustrates the interactions between these different actors [Figure 48].

Figure 48. Interactions between the energy market operators (Resa, 2018)

Energy Producers, Importers and Suppliers

Energy producers are either companies or individuals. In Belgium, electricity is produced in conventional power plants, in nuclear power plants or via devices that generate electricity from renewable sources (i.e.: onshore or offshore wind turbines, solar panels, geothermal power plants, biomass power stations or hydroelectric plants). Since Belgian soil doesn't have any natural gas deposit, this energy is imported from the Netherlands, Norway, and to a lesser extent from Great Britain and Russia. Electricity producers and gas importers sell their energy to suppliers who then resell it to consumers (CREG, 2018). With the opening of the market to competition, consumers can now choose their electricity and gas suppliers (CWAPE, 2018). Note that some companies such as Engie - Electrabel are both producers and suppliers of energy (Energide, 2018).

Transmission System Operators (TSOs)

The transmission system operators (TSOs) transport energy to local distribution networks and to large industrial consumers. In Belgium, two companies have a monopoly on the transport of energy: Elia and Fluxys. While Elia is responsible for the transmission of electricity from production sites via the high-voltage grid, Fluxys ensures the transport of gas from gas terminals via high-pressure pipelines. TSOs are also in charge of the interconnection of their network with neighbouring countries (CREG, 2018, Energide, 2018).

Distribution System Operators (DSOs)

It is then the distribution system operators (DSOs) that take the reins by transforming high voltage electricity and high-pressure gas into energy usable by the consumers. They bring this energy to homes and small businesses. The DSOs also ensure the development and the maintenance of the network of cables and pipes, as well as the connection of consumers to the network. In Wallonia, there are several DSOs. Each DSO is allocated an area of the regional territory and has the monopoly of the network in its area of activity (CREG, 2018, Energide, 2018). Note that the Operator of gas and electricity networks (ORES) ensures the transmission of energy in a large part of Wallonia.

Energy Market Regulators

The last type of actor is the regulator. This actor ensures the proper functioning of the energy market. To the extent that energy is a shared competence between the federal government and the regions (see previous section), there is a federal regulator and a regulator for each region. The federal regulator is the Commission for Electricity and Gas Regulation²⁰ (CREG) and the Walloon regulator is the Walloon Commission for Energy²¹ (CWAPE). The CREG performs various missions. One of its missions is to ensure transparency and competition in the energy market and to control that the market respects the interests of consumers, serves the public interest and is in line with the overall energy policy. The CREG is also responsible for approving TSOs' tariffs and for advising federal political authorities (CREG, 2018). The CWAPE, like the Brussels (BRUGEL) and Flemish (VREG) regulators, approves the tariffs of the DSOs and advises the regional political authorities. The CWAPE also monitors compliance with the applicable regulations in the regional energy market. Moreover, the regional regulator licenses suppliers who wish to sell electricity or gas in Wallonia. It is also the CWAPE that is responsible for the green certificate system. The regulator finally proposes a mediation service for consumers, producers, energy suppliers and DSOs (CWAPE, 2018).

²⁰ Commission de régulation de l'électricité et du gaz

²¹ Commission wallonne pour l'Énergie

3.4. Involvement of Civil Society in Climate-Energy Policy-Making

3.4.1. Civil Society organizations

Since climate-energy policy affects a lot of actors whose values and interests differs, a great number of civil society actors are involved in the decision-making process for climate mitigation. Civil society refers to a range of organizations such as business federations, trade unions, environmental and development NGOs and consumer associations. The main civil society organizations involved in the decision-making process for climate mitigation at the federal and Walloon levels are listed in a table Below [Table 9].

TYPES OF ORGANIZATION	ORGANIZATIONS
Business federations	Union wallonne des entreprises (UWE) Fédération des entreprises de Belgique (FEB) Groupement de la sidérurgie (GSV) Fédération de l'industrie du verre (FIV) Fédération de l'industrie cimentière (FEBELCEM) Fédération des industries extractives de Belgique (FEDIEX) Fédération belge des industries chimiques et des sciences de la vie (Essenscia) Association des fabricants de pâtes, papiers et cartons de Belgique (COBELPA) Fédération des industries transformatrices de papier et de carton (FETRA) Fédération de l'industrie du textile, du bois et de l'ameublement (Fedustria) Producteurs Belges de matériaux de constructions (PMC) Fédération belge de la brique (FBB) Confédération construction Fédération belge des industries graphiques (BEBELGRA) Fédération de l'industrie alimentaire belge (FEVIA) Fédération de l'industrie technologique (Agoria) Fédération belge de l'automobile et du cycle (FEBIAC) Fédération des consommateurs industriels d'électricité et de gaz naturel en Belgique (Febeliec) Union pétrolière belge (UPB) Fédération pétrolière belge (FPB) Fédération belge des négociants en combustibles et carburants (BRAFCO) Fédération belge des entreprises électriques et gazières (FEBEG) Fédération des énergies renouvelables (EDORA) Fédération des gestionnaires de réseaux électricité et gaz en Belgique (Synergrid) Fédération du commerce et des services (COMEOS) Fédération royale belge des transporteurs et des prestataires de services logistiques (FEBETRA) Union professionnelle du transport et de la logistique (UPTR) Fédération Wallonne de l'agriculture (FWA) Union des classes moyennes (UCM) Union des entreprises à profit social (UNIPSO)
Trade unions	Fédération générale du travail de Belgique (FGTB) Confédération des syndicats chrétiens (CSC) Centrale générale des syndicats libéraux de Belgique (CGSLB)
Environmental and development NGOs	Fédération inter-environnement Wallonie (IEW) World wide fund for nature (WWF) Greenpeace Associations21 Natagora Centre national de coopération au développement (CNDD-11.11.11) Climat et justice sociale Oxfam solidarités
Consumer associations	Association belge de recherche et d'expertise des organisations de consommateurs (AB-Reoc) Test-achats

Table 9. Main civil society organizations involved in the decision-making process for climate mitigation at the federal and Walloon levels

3.4.2. Involvement of Civil Society in Policy-Making

The organized civil society participate in different ways in decision and policy-making.

Consultation

Through consultative bodies, various civil society organizations discuss draft plans or legislation and transmit a joint opinion to the political-administrative authorities. The latter are required to give reasons for their decision if they deviate from the opinion of the advisory bodies. Consultative bodies exist at the federal and regional levels for the different matters addressed by the political authorities. At each level, an organization acts as a dome, providing coordination between councils specialized in different matters. At the Walloon level, it is the Economic and Social Council of Wallonia (CESW). At the federal level, this role is provided by the Central Economic Council (CCC). The specialized consultation bodies on climate-energy policies are the Walloon Council for the Environment and Sustainable Development (CWEDD) and the Federal Council for Sustainable Development (CFDD).

Concertation

In addition, dialogue between the government and some civil society organizations are also taking place. When developing some key policies, those organizations are invited to debate with the political authorities. Nevertheless, only representatives of companies and workers can participate in these debates. Environmental and development NGOs as well as consumer associations are not invited. Tripartite consultations involving business federations, trade unions and the government have been existing for many years in Belgium. Through these consultations, business federations and workers unions have acquired a tradition of dialogue that allows them to overcome their oppositions. It is the CESW and the CCE that organize the dialogue with the political authorities.

Other forms of participation

Civil society organizations also influence decision-making through informal forms of participation (lobbying), but also indirectly by mobilizing public opinion through awareness campaigns and the media.

3.5. Main Climate Mitigation Policies

Climate mitigation is a very recent political matter that is continuously evolving. The figure below summarizes the main policies taken from the emergence of the climate mitigation governance in the early 1990s until the ratification of the Paris Agreement in 2015 [Figure 49].

Figure 49. Main policies taken since the emergence of the climate mitigation governance until the ratification of the Paris at the international (in green) and Walloon (in blue) levels (adapted from AWAC, 2018)

In order to understand the origin and the context in which the current GHG reduction policies are developing, the first part of this section focuses on the emergence of climate mitigation governance and on the first commitment period of the Kyoto Protocol. We will then look at the post-2012 climate mitigation policy.

3.5.1. Emergence of Climate Mitigation Governance and First Commitment Period of the Kyoto Protocol (2008-2012)

Climate change problem has been institutionalized between the late 1980s and the early 1990s. The **Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)** was established in 1988 by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). This panel, which brings together the world's leading experts on climate issues, published its first report in 1990. On the basis of an extended literature review, the first IPCC report recognized and highlighted the anthropogenic origin of climate change.

Climate policy emerged at the European level in 1990, shortly after the publication of the first IPCC report. The issue of climate change has been debated for the first time within the European Council to prepare for international negotiations on the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). In June 1990, the European Council adopted its first climate target. This aimed to stabilize GHG emissions at the 1990 level by 2000 (European Council, 1990). By adopting such a target, the EU intended to send a signal to the international community about its ambitions. The European decision to stabilize emissions at the 1990 level has led to discussions on the policies and measures to be implemented with a view to achieving this objective. Very quickly, the discussions on the climate-energy policy were structured around the three areas that one knows today: the reduction of GHG emissions, the development of renewable energy and the improvement of energy efficiency (Climate policy info hub, 2018).

At the instigation of the EU, climate policy has also developed in the Member States. At the Federal Council of Ministers held on 6 June 1991, Belgium adopted its first goal of reducing CO₂ emissions. The aim was to reduce CO₂ emissions by 5% by 2000 compared to 1990 level (Ministère des Affaires sociales, de la Santé publique et de l'Environnement, 1997). The same objective has also been adopted at the Walloon level (DGRNE, 1995). It was at this time that Belgian climate policy emerged with the development of the National Program for the Reduction of CO₂ Emissions. This plan, approved in 1994 by the federal and regional governments, proposed a series of measures to achieve the 5% emission reduction target by the year 2000 (Service fédéral Climat, 2018).

The **United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)** was adopted during the Earth Summit held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992. The main objective of this convention was *“to achieve, in accordance with the relevant provisions of the Convention, stabilization of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system”* (United Nations 1992, p. 4). To achieve this goal, the UNFCCC urged industrialized countries to implement policies and measures to reduce GHG emissions. By stipulating that *“these policies and measures will demonstrate that developed countries are taking the lead in modifying longer-term trends in anthropogenic emissions consistent with the objective of the Convention, recognizing that the return by the end of the present decade to earlier levels of anthropogenic emissions of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases not controlled by the Montreal Protocol would contribute to such modification”* (United Nations 1992, p. 6), the Convention doesn't set any quantitative targets nor specific measures. That is why it was completed a few years later by the **Kyoto Protocol** (see United Nations, 1998). This international agreement, ratified in 1997 and entered into force in 2005, aimed to reduce GHG emissions by 5% compared to 1990 level between 2008 and 2012. It included for the first time concrete and mandatory GHG reduction targets for industrialized countries, a monitoring and reporting obligation, and flexibility mechanisms (i.e.: Emissions Trading, Clean Development Mechanism and Joint Implementation) (Service fédéral Climat, 2018).

For the first commitment period of the Protocol (2008-2012), the EU committed to reducing its GHG emissions by 8% compared to 1990. It was the most ambitious objectives adopted under the Kyoto Protocol (Climate policy info hub, 2018). In order to ensure that the EU fulfills its commitments, the European Commission launched in 2000 the First European Climate Change Program (ECCP). This

program that aimed at identifying the most efficient policy instruments that can be taken at European level to cut GHG emissions has resulted in the adoption of several policies and measures for reducing GHG, developing renewable energy and improving energy efficiency. One of the most noteworthy instruments that have been adopted following the ECCP is the European Emissions Trading System (ETS). The ETS system, which was launched in 2005 and which entered its third phase in 2013, is based on the definition of a declining cap corresponding to the maximum amount of GHG emissions produced by all installations covered by this system. In accordance with the Directive 2003/87/EC, these installations can exchange emission allowances within the limit of the cap in order to return each year a number of allowances equivalent to the emissions they have generated. The system covers emissions from large industrial and electrical installations as well as the aviation sector (European Commission, 2018).

The EU Kyoto objective has been divided among the different Member States under a legally binding **burden sharing agreement** that is included in the Council Decision 2002/358/EC approving the Kyoto Protocol (European Commission, 2018). Belgium has been assigned a target of reducing GHG emissions by 7.5% by 2012. The Belgian target was in turn divided among the three regions of the country in the 8 March 2004 Agreement on the distribution of national burdens (Service fédéral Climat, 2018). This agreement assigned Wallonia a target of reducing GHG emissions by 7.5% by 2012. A series of policies and measures have been implemented by federal and regional authorities to fulfill the obligations of the Kyoto Protocol. These are included in the National Climate Plan 2009-2012 (Commission Nationale Climat, 2008) and in the Walloon Air Climate Plan 2008-2012 (DGRNE, 2008). Among the measures implemented by the Walloon Region figures the creation of the Walloon Agency for Air and Climate that have been established in 2008 (AWAC, 2018).

3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate Mitigation Policy

EU Climate and Energy Package and Intra-Belgian Burden Sharing

Besides the objective of reducing GHG emissions by 80% by 2050 defined in the Roadmap to a low-carbon economy that was mentioned earlier (see section “1.1. Context” of Chapter I), the EU also has shorter-term targets for climate-energy policy. With a view to gradually reducing emissions, the EU has adopted targets for 2020 and 2030 under the Climate and Energy Package. They concern the three historic areas of European mitigation policy, namely, the reduction of GHG emissions, the increase share of renewable energies in the energy mix and the energy efficiency improvements. In addition to these three areas, there is the interconnection of electricity networks. The **“2020 Climate and Energy” Package** adopted in 2007 aims to achieve the “20-20-20”. This plan aims to reduce GHG emissions by 20%, achieve 20% renewable energy in energy consumption and increase energy efficiency by 20%. Note that the renewable energy target includes a specific target for the transport sector – i.e.: 10% renewable energy by 2020. Finally, the interconnection target amounts to 10%.

The **“2030 Climate and Energy” Package** adopted in 2014 is in line with the Package for 2020. The objectives for 2030 are the following: at least 40% less GHG than in 1990, at least 27% renewable energies in the energy mix, an improvement of energy efficiency equal to or greater than 27%, and an interconnection equivalent to 15% (European Commission, 2018). These objectives as well as some of the measures to achieve them are included in the Renewable Energy Directive 2009/28/EC and in the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EU. The figure below summarizes the objectives adopted in the EU Climate and Energy Packages for 2020 and 2030 [Figure 50].

Figure 50. Objectives adopted in the EU Climate and Energy Packages for 2020 and 2030 (Service fédéral Climat, 2018)

As shown in the figure below [Figure 51], the GHG emission reduction targets are divided between the ETS and the non-ETS sectors. As a reminder, the ETS system covers emissions from large industrial and electrical installations as well as the aviation sector. These sectors, which account for approximately 45% of the EU GHG emissions, are expected to reduce their emissions by 21% in 2020 and by 43% in 2030 compared to the 2005 level. GHG not covered by the ETS system comes principally from the housing, transports (aviation excluded), agricultural and waste sectors. In order to achieve the overall emission reduction target adopted under the Climate and Energy Packages, emissions from these sectors will have to decrease by 10% in 2020 and by 30% in 2030 compared to 2005 (European Commission, 2018).

Figure 51. GHG emissions reduction targets in non-ETS and ETS sectors for 2020 and 2030 (Service fédéral Climat, 2018)

The target of reducing emissions from the non-ETS sector by 10% in 2020 has been divided into binding national targets in accordance with Decision No 406/2009/EC on **burden sharing**. In the framework of this decision adopted jointly by the European Parliament and the Council, national objectives have been defined according to the relative wealth level of the Member States. As illustrated in the figure below [Figure 52], the targets vary between -20% GHG compared to 2005 for the richest Member States and +20% GHG for the poorest Member States. Belgium has been assigned a target of reducing GHG emissions by 15% by 2020 (European Commission, 2018).

Figure 52. EU Member States specific GHG emissions reduction targets in non-ETS sectors for 2020 (European Commission, 2018)

Recently, on 14 May 2018, the EU adopted national targets for the period 2021-2030. Those targets range from 0% to 40% GHG reduction. Just like in the previous period, the distribution of effort among the Member States is based on the GDP per capita. In accordance with this allocation key, Belgium must reduce its GHG emissions from non-EST sectors by 35% by 2030. In order to guarantee a reduction of emissions at the lowest cost, the new regulation introduces two mechanisms of flexibility. Some Member States are now allowed, under certain conditions, to achieve their national targets by covering some emissions with EU ETS allowances or with credits from the land use sector (European Commission, 2018). The following figure illustrates the Member States specific GHG emissions reduction targets in non-ETS sectors for 2030 including new flexibility mechanisms [Figure 53].

Figure 53. EU Member States specific GHG emissions reduction targets in non-ETS sectors for 2030 including new flexibility mechanisms (European Commission, 2018)

The objective of achieving 20% renewable energy in the energy mix in 2020 has also been split between the different Member States. These binding targets have been defined for each Member State considering their initial situation in terms of renewable energy production and their ability to increase

the share of renewable energy in their energy mix (European Commission, 2018). In this context, Belgium must reach 13% of renewable energy in 2020 (Service fédéral Climat, 2018).

As the climate change mitigation policy is the responsibility of the federal government and the regions, the objectives attributed to Belgium via the European Climate and Energy Package must be divided between the various competent entities. After six years of negotiations, the federal, Walloon, Flemish and Brussels ministers in charge of climate have agreed on the distribution of the Belgian climate-energy objectives for the 2013-2020 period. On 4 December 2015, during the COP21 in Paris, the Political Agreement on **intra-Belgian burden sharing** was adopted. The legislation focuses on four areas: the GHG emissions from non-ETS sectors, the deployment of renewable energy, the sharing of revenues from auctioning allowances and the international financing. In terms of GHG emissions reduction, the objective of reducing national emissions by 15% in 2020 is divided as follows between the three regions: -15.7% for Flanders, -14.7% for Wallonia and -8.8% for the Brussels-Capital. Regarding the renewable component, to reach 13% of renewable energy in Belgian final energy consumption by 2020, the various authorities have committed to achieving the following objectives: 2.156 million tons of oil equivalent (Mtoe) for Flanders, 1.277 Mtoe for Wallonia, 0.073 Mtoe for the Brussels-Capital and 0.718 Mtoe for the federal government (Service fédéral Climat, 2018).

The target of reducing emissions by 35% by 2030 recently allocated to Belgium has not yet been distributed among the various entities (Service fédéral Climat, 2018).

EU Clean Energy Package and National Energy and Climate Plans

In 2016, the European Commission proposed a new package of measures to enable the EU to meet its Paris Agreement commitments. The **“Clean Energy for All Europeans” Package** aims at stimulating investments in the clean energy transition by *“putting energy efficiency first, achieving global leadership in renewable energies and providing a fair deal for consumers”* (European Commission, 2018). Presented as the backbone of energy-climate policy for 2030, the Clean Energy Package includes eight legislative proposals that cover energy performance in buildings, renewable energy, energy efficiency, Energy Union governance, electricity regulation, electricity directive, risk preparedness and Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER). Note that some of the proposals of the EU Clean Energy Package are still under discussion and should be adopted by the end of 2018 (European Commission, 2018).

The Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union resulting from this legislative package requires, among others, the Member States to produce integrated **National Energy and Climate Plans (NCEP)** and to report on the progress they make in implementing those plans. The NCEP cover a period of 10 years – the first period stretching from 2021 to 2030. They must integrate five major dimensions of the EU Energy Union strategy: decarbonisation, energy efficiency, energy security, organization of the energy market, as well as research, innovation and competitiveness (European Commission, 2018). For each of these dimensions, objectives, policies, measures and projections must be provided. The Member States are required to submit a draft plan by the end of 2018 and the final version by the end of 2019. In Belgium, the federal authorities and the three regions are currently preparing the NCEP (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2018b). Two phases of consultations with civil society organizations were conducted by the competent administrations between March and April 2017 and between February and March 2018. A public inquiry should be held soon (DGO4, 2018). The Impact assessment of the policies, measures and projections of the Belgian NCEP were carried out by Federal Planning Bureau in May 2018 (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2018b).

Another noteworthy aspect of the EU Clean Energy Package concerns the new targets for 2030. On 14 June 2018, the Commission, the European Parliament and the Council have agreed on a binding renewable energy target of 32% and on an energy efficiency target of 32.5%, both with an upwards revision clause by 2023. These new targets are more ambitious than those adopted in 2014 under the EU Climate and Energy Package.

Interfederal Energy Pact

At the Belgian national level, the Interfederal Energy Pact complements the integrated National Energy and Climate Plan. Developed at the initiative of the four Belgian ministers of energy, this pact aims to "*guarantee a secure, affordable and sustainable energy future*" (CONCERE, 2017). On 26 April 2017, the Federal and Regional Ministers in charge of Energy decided to build, in consultation with civil society actors, a clear and long-term vision of Belgian energy policy. A State-Regions Concertation Committee on Energy (CONCERE) gathering members of administrations and ministerial cabinets responsible for energy is currently working on the development of the Energy Pact. Two consultations already took place: a first involving stakeholders (from 3 May to 30 June 2017) and a second involving citizens (from 17 October to 5 November 2017). The draft Energy Pact was approved by the four energy ministers in December 2017. In April 2018, after stormy discussions on the maintenance of the nuclear phase out in 2025, it was also approved by the federal, Walloon, Flemish and Brussels Governments (L'Echo, 2018). By defining a series of medium- and long-term objectives and measures, the draft Energy Pact provides a political framework for the low-carbon transition. The various measures aim at decarbonising the energy mix, improving energy efficiency, reducing energy demand, developing transmission and distribution networks adapted to decentralized electricity production, and ensuring the security of electricity supply. The draft Energy Pact also includes quantified targets, including 100% renewable electricity in 2050 (Le Soir, 2017). Note that the legal value of this text is not yet known (IEW, 2018a).

Federal Climate Mitigation Policy Mix

The Federal authorities have implemented different types of policy instruments to reduce GHG emissions. These instruments mainly target emissions from the non-ETS sector. According to the impact assessment of the Federal climate mitigation policy mix carried out by ICEDD & al. in 2017, "*the five most important policy and measures in terms of emission reduction are the Energy label, tax incentive to promote energy efficiency in households, biofuels, offshore wind energy and tax deduction for energy saving*" (ICEDD & al. 2017, p. 9). The following figure summarizes the main policies and measures implemented at the federal level in the non-ETS sector and the cumulative reduction of GHG emission that they generate between 2013 and 2020 [Figure 54].

Politiques et mesures (PAMs)	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total (2013-2020)
EC-B01 Incitants financiers pour l'utilisation rationnelle de l'énergie	2.170	2.226	2.226	2.226	2.226	2.226	2.226	2.226	17.755
EC-A05 Label sur l'efficacité énergétique	657	914	1.169	1.469	1.773	2.097	2.401	2.682	13.162
TR-D01 Promotion des biocarburants	1.036	1.235	1.299	1.333	1.366	1.370	1.374	1.945	10.959
Règlement gaz fluorés	-	-	185	378	567	807	1.071	1.305	4.313
IP-A06 Réduction fiscales pour les investissements économiseurs d'énergie pour les entreprises	246	267	297	327	344	355	322	312	2.473
Green loan	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	121	980
Ecochèques	66	79	92	106	119	132	145	158	897
OB-B02 efficacité énergétique dans les bâtiments fédéraux	38	43	44	48	52	57	61	66	409
TR-B05 Eco driving	33	40	47	53	53	53	53	53	387
TR-C01 Déduction fiscale véhicules propres	123	113	80	30	2	0	0	0	348
TR-A02 Amélioration et promotion des transports publics (SNCB)	32	27	26	24	23	21	20	18	190
Sous-total	4.524	5.067	5.588	6.117	6.648	7.241	7.796	8.886	51.873
Divers autres PAMs	65	88	102	136	159	185	208	218	1.154
TOTAL	4.589	5.155	5.690	6.253	6.807	7.426	8.004	9.104	53.028

Figure 54. Main policies and measures implemented at the federal level in the non-ETS sector and cumulative reduction of GHG emission that they generate between 2013 and 2020 (in kilo tons of CO₂eq) (Service fédéral Climat, 2018)

In addition, the federal authorities are currently evaluating the ways and means of implementing a carbon tax for non-ETS sectors. In January 2017, the Federal Climate Service launched, at the request of Minister of energy, a **national debate on carbon pricing** in the transport and building sectors. This debate, which involved the participation of a large number of stakeholders and which ended in June 2018, led to the definition of various implementation options for a carbon tax in Belgium (Climact, 2018). A public inquiry was also conducted to understand the perception of Belgian citizens regarding the implementation of such an instrument. The survey shows that citizens are generally in favour of the introduction of a carbon tax and of the redistribution mechanisms proposed in the national debate on carbon pricing (Profacts, 2018).

Walloon Climate Mitigation Policy Mix

One of the central elements of the Walloon mitigation policy is the **Walloon Climate Decree** (see Gouvernement wallon, 2014). Adopted on 20 February 2014 by the Walloon Parliament, this decree sets targets for reducing GHG emissions in the short, medium and long term. The objectives anchored in the Walloon Climate Decree are a GHG emissions reduction of 30% by 2020 and of 50% by 2050 compared to the 1990 level. In order to achieve these objectives, the Decree provides for the adoption of emission budgets for a period of 5 years. In accordance with the Climate Decree, a Committee of Experts has been charged with establishing emission budgets and monitoring their compliance. The central instrument for implementing the decree is the Air-Climate-Energy plan. This plan brings together all the policies and measures to be implemented to respect the emission budgets. The Walloon Climate Decree provides for the development of such a plan on a five-year basis (AWAC, 2018).

The last **Walloon Air-Climate-Energy Plan** (see AWAC, 2016) was adopted by the Walloon government on 21 April 2016. This plan, which covers the period 2016-2022, lists all the policies and measures that exist or have to be implemented in order to stay within emissions budget set for this period. The main measures in force in Wallonia are energy / CO₂ branch agreements between the Walloon Government and the main industrial sectors via their federations, the green certificate system, the investment

premiums for the purchase of renewable energy facilities, the "Sustainable construction" Employment-Environment Alliance, the Walloon Strategy for long-term energy renovation of the buildings, the system of energy and rehabilitation bonuses for housing, the economic instruments encouraging the purchase of low-emission vehicles, the per-kilometer charging system for trucks, and awareness and information campaigns (AWAC, 2016).

4. Climate-Energy Foresight in Wallonia

4.1. Foresight: A Scarcely Institutionalized Practice

In the Walloon Region, foresight is a quite recent and scarcely institutionalized practice. Maxime Petit Jean, who studied the institutionalization of foresight in Wallonia, distinguishes three phases in the development of foresight in public action: "the emergence of foresight (1974-2004)", "the rhetorical public practice of foresight (2004-2009)" and "the effective public practice of foresight (2009-2016)" (Petit Jean, 2017). The following section traces the process of emergence and integration of foresight into Walloon public action via the three phases identified by Petit Jean (2017). The section also presents the two main Walloon foresight actors, namely the Destrée Institute and IWEPS, as well as the actors who gravitate around them.

4.1.1. Emergence of Foresight (1974-2004)

As mentioned in the section devoted to foresight (see section "3.1.1. Foresight: conceptual clarification" of Chapter I), this practice developed after the Second World War in the USA and in France as a tool for military and territorial planning. However, it was only in the 70s that foresight emerged in Wallonia. Between 1970 and 1980, some Walloon professors from different disciplines imported the concepts and methods of foresight developed in the USA and France within their university research centers. These include Claire Lejeune (Professor of Philosophy at University of Mons), Raymond Collar (Professor of Economics and Social Sciences at the University of Namur), Paul Duvigneaud (Professor of Ecology at the Free University of Brussels and at Gembloux Agro-Bio Tech), Gilbert de Landsheere (Professor of Education at the University of Liège), Jacques Berleur, Georges Thill and Gérard Fourez (professors in the field of science, technology and society at the University of Namur). Foresight activities have also developed outside academic circles with the "Walter Nova" Project led by Emile Nols and Georges Vandersmissen, the Commission "Economic future of Belgium" launched by the King Baudouin Foundation, and the "Wallonia 2020" dossier produced by the Socio-political Research and Information Center (CRISP) and the Belgian Radio-Television of the French Community (RTBF) (Destatte, 2014).

The first foresight exercises at the public policy level were conducted in 1976 by the **Destrée Institute** as part of a reflection on the cultural future of Wallonia (Petit Jean, 2017; Destatte, 2014). The Destrée Institute is a non-profit association founded in 1938. In addition to its foresight activities, this pluralistic and independent association plays a role in permanent education. It also conducts research on the history, identity and development of Walloon territory. The historian and prospectivist Philippe Destatte is since 1987 general director of the institute (Institut Destrée, 2018). The Destrée Institute is partially financed by the public authorities (Petit Jean, 2016).

In 1978, for lack of partners to launch an economic foresight of Wallonia, the Destrée Institute had to wait along 10 years before carrying out its second prospective exercise. This second exercise was part of the "Wallonia of the Future" initiative. Launched in 1986 by Philippe Destatte and Michel Quévit, professor of political and social sciences at the Catholic University of Louvain and Walloon activist, the "Wallonia in the Future" approach brought together a series of actors – including political authorities – to discuss the future of their region (Destatte, 2014). In this context, five forward-looking congresses on issues such as education and employment were organized until the Minister-President of the Walloon Government Jean-Claude Van Cauwenberghe put an end to this financing in 2004 to transfer it to the IWEPS budget (see below) (Petit Jean, 2016).

The "Wallonia in the Future" approach has resulted in a number of initiatives, including the creation of the **Walloon Society for Evaluation and Foresight**²² (SWEF). Following the fourth "Wallonia in the Future" Congress held in 1998 and that was entitled "Coming out of the 20th Century: Evaluation, Innovation, Prospective", the Destrée Institute initiated dynamics aimed at creating a platform to promote the prospective and evaluation in order to contribute to the improvement of Walloon public governance (SWEF, 2018). This independent space of exchange between public, private and academic actors of the evaluation and foresight was charged with the following missions: organizing methodological and ethical reflections on evaluative and foresight approaches, calling on the decision-makers to encourage them to support and undertake this type of approach and, more generally, promoting dissemination of the evaluation and foresight culture among decision-makers and citizens (SWEF, 2018, Petit Jean, 2016). In 2018, SWEF decided to end its activities (SWEF, 2018). It seems that it suffered from a lack of expertise, especially in foresight (Petit Jean, 2016).

During this period, the Destrée Institute also played a foresight supporting role in the service of the Walloon Government. In the framework of the "Prospective Wallonia 21" Mission, the Institute ensured, among other things, the animation of a foresight reflection on the future of Wallonia, the methodological watch, the detection of heavy trends, and an advisory function especially concerning the "Future Contract for Wallonia". In addition to the "Prospective Wallonia 21" Mission, the Destrée Institute has conducted other foresight activities for the Government, such as the prospective reflection on business policies in Wallonia "ProspEnWal". In order to have the necessary expertise to carry out the missions entrusted to it by the Government, the Destrée Institute has developed a Prospective Pole within it (Destatte, 2014).

These multiple foresight activities have led the Minister-President Jean-Claude Van Cauwenberghe to perceive the strategic interest of foresight and to consider integrating this practice into a public entity placed under the responsibility of the Government. It is in this context that the idea of creating the Walloon Institute for Evaluation, Foresight and Statistics (IWEPS) has emerged (Petit Jean, 2016).

4.1.2. Rhetorical Public Practice of Foresight (2004-2009)

The creation of the **Walloon Institute for Evaluation, Foresight and Statistics**²³ (IWEPS) in 2004 put an end to the quasi-monopoly of the Destrée Institute on foresight (Petit Jean, 2016). IWEPS is a public scientific institute that helps public authorities to make decisions. As the statistical authority of the Walloon Region, IWEPS develops, amongst other things, the official statistics program of the Walloon Region. In addition to producing statistics and indicators, this institute provides economic, social, political and environmental analyses. IWEPS is composed of three Departments, namely the Anticipation of Socio-Economic Phenomena Department, the Data and Indicators Department and the Research and Evaluation Department. Sébastien Brunet, professor at the Faculty of Law and Political Science at the University of Liège, has been the general director of IWEPS since 2011 (IWEPS, 2018). IWEPS is statutorily an organization of public interest under the tutelage of the Walloon Minister-President (Petit Jean, 2016).

Compared to other decision support tools provided by IWEPS, foresight analyses were – and remain – marginal. When the Institute was set up, following requests from a range of political actors, the statistical mission was considered to be prioritized over foresight and evaluation missions. Then, under the influence of the EU, evaluation became a priority of IWEPS, relegating foresight to the rank of IWEPS poor relation. With less than one full-time equivalent in charge of foresight for the entire period

²² Société wallonne de l'évaluation et de la prospective (SWEF)

²³ Institut wallon de l'évaluation, de la prospective et de la statistique (IWEPS)

2004-2009, the human and financial resources allocated to this practice were extremely limited. During this period, IWEPS did not launch any prospective studies.

In 2007, at the request of the Minister-President, IWEPS began to devote reflection to the evolution of its foresight mission (Petit Jean, 2016). As part of this reflection, IWEPS was, among other things, responsible for exploring possible collaborations with the Destrée Institute in order to combine their skills for the benefit of regional foresight (Petit Jean, 2016; Destatte, 2014). The establishment of such collaboration was particularly difficult because of the competition between the two institutes. This competition is materialized financially since some of the Destrée Institute's funding has been transferred to IWEPS, but also in terms of how they conceive foresight. While the Destrée Institute practices normative foresight, IWEPS advocates an exploratory approach (Petit Jean, 2017).

On its side, the Destrée Institute continued its foresight activities by creating the **Regional Foresight College²⁴ (CRP)** and **IntelliTerWal**. Launched in 2004, the CRP is a place for debating and collective learning involving about thirty members from the public sphere, the corporate world and the civil society. The future-oriented reflections conducted by the CRP focus on how to remove the barriers to the development of Wallonia. In this context, numerous seminars and two symposiums were organized. In 2010, the CRP launched the project "Wallonia 2030: Anticipating future bifurcations and choosing positive behaviour". This vast project of participatory foresight addressed many issues, including governance, education, employment, the environment, energy, health or poverty (Institut Destrée, 2017, Destatte, 2014). During the period 2004-2009, it is, with a few exceptions, the only foresight exercises carried out on the scale of Wallonia (Petit Jean, 2016). It should be noticed that foresight work has been carried out at the local level, with, for example, "Luxembourg 2010", "Charleroi 2020" or "Liège 2020". These multiple initiatives have led to the establishment of IntelliTerWal. IntelliTerWal was developed by the Destrée Institute in 2006 at the request of the Walloon Minister André Antoine who was in charge of territorial development. It is a platform for sharing information and experience on territorial foresight. In this sense, IntelliTerWal lists the territorial foresight exercises conducted by local Walloon actors, but also foresight initiatives carried out in other European municipalities. It thus provides a methodological expertise that local actors can use to conduct such exercises within their territory (IntelliTerWal, 2017). Moreover, since part of the public financing of the Destrée Institute was transferred to the IWEPS budget to enable it to fulfill its foresight missions, the Destrée Institute was forced to look for other sources of funding. In this perspective, it participated in various French and European foresight projects (Petit Jean, 2016). These included the project "Millennia2015: Women actors of development for global issues" developed by the Destrée Institute in collaboration with its international partners (Institut Destrée, 2017; Destatte, 2014). These initiatives, carried out outside the Walloon context, contributed to forging the reputation of the Destrée Institute abroad (La Libre, 2013).

4.1.3. Effective Public Practice of Foresight (2009-2016)

In 2009, the partnership between IWEPS and the Destrée Institute encouraged by the Minister-President during the previous period led to the creation of the **Walloon Regional Prospective Research and Watch System²⁵ (SRPW)**. The aim of this platform was to bring together foresight practitioners and, more generally, people interested in foresight in order to develop a Walloon centre of expertise in that field. Around thirty university research teams and ten members of the Walloon administration have joined the network (Guyot & Rieppi, 2014). It should be noted that most members of the SRPW were more interested in the long-term and the anticipation than they practiced foresight (Petit Jean,

²⁴ Collège régional de prospective (CRP)

²⁵ Système régional de recherche et de veille prospective wallon (SRPW)

2016). The activities of SRPW were structured around four axes: the transfer of knowledge and experience on foresight, the foresight watch, the promotion of the foresight approach and the realization of joint projects (Guyot & Rieppi, 2014). The SRPW only lived for two years. It ceased its activities in 2012, partly because of the low participation of academic actors in the network (Petit Jean, 2016, Destatte, 2014).

It is only in 2012 that IWEPS have started to develop prospective exercises (Petit Jean, 2016). The Institute commissioned two studies on issues identified as main prospective issues for Wallonia after a consultation with SRPW members. One focused on aging (SONECOM & al., 2016) and the other on energy transition (see CLIMACT & al., 2015). This last study is one of the four foresight studies analysed as part of this doctoral thesis (see section "4.4. Case Study n°4. Prospective study: energy transition" of Chapter III). IWEPS also funded a prospective study on business transfer. This study was conducted by a consortium including the Destrée Institute (see Destrée Institute & al., 2016). The last two foresight studies funded by IWEPS focused on poverty (see Boulanger & al., 2017) and energy networks (see ICEDD & al., 2018). IWEPS has also begun conducting foresight activities internally. This work focused on the analysis of the digitalisation of the Walloon economy (see IWEPS, 2017b). The resources allocated to the foresight mission of IWEPS have increased to allow scenario analyses to be carried out internally and externally. To date, two full-time equivalents are in charge of foresight (Petit Jean, 2016). The financial and human resources granted to the prospective mission remain, however, lower than those allocated to other IWEPS missions (source: interview).

IWEPS is also developing its prospective mission with activities other than studies. In 2012, IWEPS devoted its methodological conference to foresight (IWEPS, 2012). In addition, with the IWEPS PhD Research Activity Program (IPRA), IWEPS has been funding doctoral scholarships since 2012 in connection with its missions. One of those scholarships financed the thesis on the institutionalization of foresight in the Walloon Region mentioned in this section (see Petit Jean, 2016). The latest initiative of IWEPS is the establishment of an interuniversity certificate in prospective analysis. This training launched in 2014 in collaboration with SWEP, the Catholic University of Louvain and the University of Liège, targets primarily actors from the political or administrative world and aims to disseminate foresight methods within the Walloon public sector (Petit Jean, 2016). The thirty or so participants from the Public Service of Wallonia attending the 2018 edition of this training illustrate the growing interest in foresight within the administration observed by Petit Jean (2017). The certificate also aims to foster the anchoring of foresight as a scientific discipline (Petit Jean, 2016). Note that today, foresight is little rooted within the Walloon universities. Petit Jean observes "*a weak involvement of the academic world in the theorization of Walloon prospective practice and in the establishment of an epistemic community linked to it*" (Petit Jean 2016, p. 321). He actually identified only one theoretical work on territorial foresight (see Stassart & al., 2007). With, to my knowledge, a course given by Sébastien Brunet (general director of IWEPS) at the University of Liège as part of the Master in Political Sciences and another course given by Pierre Stassart to the students of the Master in Science and Management of the environment of the same university, foresight is also not much present in the training programs of the Walloon universities.

The second major actor of Foresight, the Destrée Institute, has continued its foresight activities in Wallonia and abroad, for instance in the framework of the "Millennia2025" Project, which is a continuation of the future-oriented work on gender equality and women's empowerment previously carried out by the Institute (Institut Destrée, 2017). In January 2018, the Institute also organized in collaboration with the University of Mons and the Open University of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation the first edition of its certificate in operational foresight.

Foresight activities were also conducted by other actors during this period. In the area of climate-energy, we find, among others, the studies "Territory and energy 2050" carried out by the Permanent

Conference of Territorial Development²⁶ (CPDT) (Bréchet & *al.*, 2014), "Our energy future" conducted by 3E for environmental NGOs (3E, 2014) and "Towards a low-carbon Wallonia" undertaken by CLIMACT on behalf of the Walloon Air and Climate Agency (AWAC) (CLIMACT, 2012). The latter is one of the four foresight studies analysed as part of my thesis (see section "3.1. Case study n°1. Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050" of Chapter III).

The period 2009-2015 is also characterized by the emergence of structures labeled "prospective" within Walloon public institutions. These include the Foresight and Scientific Intelligence Unit developed within the Agricultural Strategy Committee as well as the Strategy and Foresight Council created within the Walloon Agency for Health, Social Protection, Disability and Families (Petit Jean, 2016).

Despite these recent advances, foresight keeps a relatively marginal place in the Walloon political and administrative system, particularly in comparison with other entities such as the Netherlands or the United Kingdom. This practice is still little known by the political-administrative authorities and the term "foresight" is often confused with the notion of "forecast". A number of actors also question the legitimacy and the relevance of foresight as a tool for decision support. It should be noted that this low level of institutionalization also applies to the Belgian context. The prospective activity is indeed also very limited at the federal and Flemish levels. At the federal level, the main institution in charge of foresight is the Federal Planning Bureau (FPB). However, foresight analyses are underrepresented compared to the work on indicators, evaluation and projections. The foresight activity of the FPB is mainly concentrated in the Sustainable Development Task force, which have developed the Federal 2050 Strategic Vision for Sustainable Development (see Task force développement durable, 2007) and which took part in the prospective study "Energy transition" financed by IWEPS (see CLIMACT & *al.*, 2015) (Petit Jean, 2016).

4.2. Foresight on Climate-Energy Issues

The following section focuses more specifically on foresight on climate-energy issues. We'll first look at the main actors who carry out this kind of studies. Then, to the extent that the four studies analysed are not the only prospective analyses on the climate-energy problems carried out at the scale of Wallonia, we will review other recent studies.

4.2.1. Main Contractors of Foresight Studies on Climate-Energy Issues

The scenario building process commonly involves a client-contractor relationship. In the selected case studies (see Chapter III), the client is a public authority and the contractor is a consortium of research institutes or consultancy agencies (Schubert & *al.*, 2015). The following table shows the clients and the contractors of the four studies analysed as part of the Chapter III [Table 10].

²⁶ Conférence Permanente du Développement Territorial (CPDT)

STUDY	CLIENTS	CONTRACTORS
Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon agency for air and climate (AWAC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ European Climate Foundation (ECF)
Scenarios for a Low-Carbon Belgium by 2050	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Federal public service (FPS) health, food chain safety and environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO)
Towards 100 renewable energy in Belgium by 2050	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Federal, Walloon, Flemish and Brussels ministers in charge of energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Team Energy and Transport of the Federal Planning Bureau (FPB) ▪ VITO ▪ Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development (ICEDD)
Prospective study: Energy transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon institute for evaluation, prospective and statistics (IWEPS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ Institute for a Sustainable Development (IDD) ▪ Center for Operations Research and Econometrics (CORE) of the Catholic University of Louvain (UCL) ▪ Faculty of Architecture, Architectural Engineering, Urban Planning of UCL ▪ Sustainable Development Task force of the FPB ▪ ICEDD ▪ Laboratory of Studies on New Technologies of Information, Innovation and Change (LENTIC) of the University of Liège (ULg)

Table 10. Clients and contractors of low-carbon scenarios for Wallonia

It has to be acknowledged that it is often the same consultancy agencies or institutes that carry out climate-energy foresight studies for public authorities. Among them are found CLIMACT, the Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development (ICEDD), the Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO) and the Federal Planning Bureau (FPB).

CLIMACT

CLIMACT participated in the development of three of the four studies analysed. It is a consultancy agency based in Louvain-la-Neuve (Wallonia). Specialized on the issues of energy efficiency, renewable energy and climate change, this agency advises public and private stakeholders in the development of their strategies for reducing GHG emissions in the short, medium or long term. The team has about twenty members (CLIMACT, 2018). Founded in 2007, CLIMACT has quickly become a key player in the network of climate-energy actors. The study "Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050" carried out for AWAC in 2012 was the first foresight analysis carried out by CLIMACT. Since then, Climact has produced the study "Scenarios for a Low-Carbon Belgium by 2050" for the Federal Climate Service (Cornet & *al.*, 2013), as well as other initiatives carried out under the 2050 Project of the Federal Climate Service, namely, the macroeconomic analysis of the low-carbon scenarios (see CLIMACT & *al.*, 2016), the development of the webtool My2050²⁷, and the national debate on carbon pricing (see CLIMACT & *al.*, 2018). Moreover, CLIMACT supported the Walloon region in the elaboration of its Strategy for long-term energy renovation of the buildings (see CLIMACT & *al.*, 2017), in the development and exploitation of the TIMES optimization model at the regional scale and, more recently, in the development of its 2030 Energy and Climate Plan. CLIMACT was also part of the consortium that developed the foresight studies on energy transition (see CLIMACT & *al.*, 2015) and on energy networks (see ICEDD & *al.*, 2018) financed by IWEPS. At the level of the private sector, CLIMACT has supported a number of federations of companies such as the federations of the technological (Agoria), graphic (FEBELGRA), paper and cardboard (COBELPA and FETRA), textile, wood and furniture

²⁷ <http://www.my2050.be>

(FEDUSTRIA), glass (FIV) and steel (GSV) in the realization of the 2050 sectoral roadmaps they had to submit to the Walloon government under the second generation branch agreements (Wallonie, 2018). In addition to these initiatives carried out at the scale of Wallonia and Belgium (including the Flemish and Brussels regions), in ten years CLIMACT has participated in a number of other projects from the local level (e.g.: Action Plan for sustainable energy for the municipality of Ottignies-Louvain-la-Neuve (see CLIMACT, 2017)) to the international level (e.g.: The Global Calculator²⁸).

Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development (ICEDD)

Another important actor who participated in the development of two of the four studies analysed (i.e.: "Towards 100 renewable energy in Belgium by 2050" and "Prospective study: Energy transition") is the Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development²⁹ (ICEDD). Based in Namur (Wallonia), ICEDD is a consultancy agency specialized on sustainable development issues. Its multidisciplinary team of about thirty experts carries out studies on natural resources and waste, mobility and territory, climate and energy transition, and building and sustainable industry for public and private actors. Foresight is one of the four activities of ICEDD, the other three being diagnosis and evaluation, support of the transition, and training and participation (ICEDD, 2018). Note that in its "Prospective" activity, ICEDD includes projections and medium or long-term analyses that are not necessarily based on foresight approaches. Foresight studies are only a small part of these activities. Founded more than 50 years ago, ICEDD has been for many years the key interlocutor for Walloon stakeholders on sustainable development issues. Since 1980, ICEDD has been entrusted with the production of the Walloon annual energy balance. On climate-energy issues, ICEDD recently participated in several projects in collaboration with CLIMACT. Those include the technical support for the elaboration of the 2030 Energy and Climate Plan, the development and operation of the TIMES model at the Walloon scale, and the two prospective studies on energy-related issues financed by IWEPS. Like CLIMACT, ICEDD also carried out some 2050 sectoral roadmaps, including those of the brick (FBB and FEDICER), the extractive (FEDIEX) and the food (FEVIA) industries (Wallonia, 2018). It should be noted that most of the ICEDD projects focus on Wallonia, the Brussels-Capital Region and Belgium.

Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO)

The Flemish Institute for Technological Research³⁰ (VITO) was part of the consortium for two of the studies analysed (i.e.: "Scenarios for a Low-Carbon Belgium" by 2050 and "Towards 100 renewable energy in Belgium by 2050"). VITO develops advice and technological innovations that aim at fostering the sustainable transition in the fields of chemistry, materials, land use, health and energy. This center of expertise, which is based in multiple sites in Flanders and which has 842 employees (including 111 international employees) is the Flemish reference institute on environmental issues. Just like ICEDD in Wallonia, VITO provides the annual energy balance for the Flemish Region. VITO also has a solid reputation outside Belgium. With projects in China, India and Middle East countries, VITO has many international activities (VITO, 2018). Recently, much of VITO's research on energy has been integrated into EnergyVille, which brings together researchers from VITO, the Catholic University of Leuven, the University of Hasselt and IMEC working in the field of sustainable energy and intelligent energy systems. The work on energy carried out at EnergyVille covers a very wide scope: building and districts, storage, networks, power control and conversion, solar, and strategies and markets. Foresight is only a small part of this work. When it comes to long-term energy system analyses, VITO/EnergyVille

²⁸ <http://www.globalcalculator.org>

²⁹ Institut de conseil et d'études en développement durable (ICEDD)

³⁰ Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (VITO)

experts base themselves primarily on the TIMES modeling framework (EnergyVille, 2018). This optimization model was used by VITO, ICEDD and the Federal Planning Bureau in the study "Towards 100 renewable energy in Belgium by 2050" (for more information about the TIME model, see the section "3.3.2. Presentation of the study" of Chapter III). Because of its expertise on the TIMES model, VITO is also involved in adapting this model to the scale of Wallonia.

Federal Planning Bureau (FPB)

The Federal Planning Bureau (FPB) participated in two of the analysed studies. Based in Brussels, the FPB is a public interest organization that provides indicators, ex-post and ex-ante evaluations of public policies, forecasts and foresight analyses at the Belgium scale. However, as mentioned in the previous section (see section "4.1. Foresight: A scarcely institutionalized practice" of the same chapter), few prospective analyses are undertaken by the Plan Office. Only the Sustainable Development Task force, which took part in the prospective study on energy transition financed by IWEPS and whose mission is to develop the federal vision and scenarios for sustainable development by 2050 (see Task force développement durable, 2007) carries out foresight exercises. However, this is not its main activity. For its part, the Energy and Transport team of the FPB, which took part in the "Towards 100 renewable energy in Belgium by 2050" study, is not used to carrying out foresight analyses. This team provide forecasts rather than foresight studies. The experts from the Energy and Transport team actually produce the national forecasts on the evolution of the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions. To make such projections, they use mainly the PRIMES model, a partial equilibrium model of the energy system similar to TIMES (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2017). This FPB team is also working with the three actors mentioned above to adapt the TIMES model to the scale of Walloon region. The members of this team also carry out public policy evaluations. They are the ones who were responsible for carrying out the impact assessments of the Interfederal Energy Pact (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2018a) and of the National Climate Energy Plan (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2018b).

4.2.2. Climate Mitigation Scenarios for Wallonia

Many studies focus on the long-term evolution of the energy landscape and of the GHG emissions across the Walloon Region and Belgium. However, most of those analyses consist of projections to define the likely evolution of the climate-energy system. Some of these projections were already presented previously. In the section devoted to the evolution of GHG emissions (see section "2.2. Projections of GHG emissions" of the same chapter), I mentioned the Walloon Energy-Climate reference scenario in horizons 2020 and 2030 developed on the basis of the work done by ECONOTEC with the bottom-up model EPM (DGO4, 2017) and the Belgian projections of greenhouse gas emissions for the period 2015-2035 (National Climate Commission, 2017). In addition, in the previous point, I alluded to the 2050 projections made with the partial equilibrium model of the energy system PRIMES by the Energy and Transport team of the FPB (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2017). It seems interesting to mention that another team of the FPB, the Macroeconomic Projection and Analyses team, produces, on the basis of the national top-down macro-econometric model HERMES, projections of the evolution of energy consumption and GHG emissions in the shorter term (5 years horizon) as part of its economic outlook report (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2018). These medium-term national perspectives are disaggregated by the FPB, in collaboration with the research departments of the three Belgian regions (IWEPS, IBSA & Statistiek Vlaanderen) to provide regional projections. To do this, HERMREG, a multi-regional variant of HERMES, is used (Bureau du Plan & *al.*, 2018). The projections of the FPB are published on an annual basis. The energy market regulators also make projections. In its annual reports, CREG, the federal regulator, provides the probable evolution of the demand for natural gas in Belgium for the next 10 years (CREG, 2017). For its part, CWAPE, the Walloon regulator, has estimated, at the request of the Minister of Energy, projections of the evolution of the electricity prices by 2020 (CWAPE, 2011). More recently, Elia, the electricity transmission system operator, has, at the request

of the Federal Minister of Energy, sketched projections to assess the need for flexibility of the Belgian electricity system for the period 2017-2027 (Elia, 2016).

Besides these numerous forecast analyses, some recent foresight studies on climate-energy issues other than those analysed in this thesis have been identified. One of them was mentioned in the previous point. This is the prospective study on energy networks commissioned by IWEPS with the support of the Energy Department of the Public Service of Wallonia (DGO4). The study was carried out by ICEDD, CLIMACT, The University of Liège, the Institute for a Sustainable Development (IDD) and the Federal Planning Bureau. It aims to analyse how energy distribution networks could evolve in Wallonia in the 2030 and 2050 horizons. On the basis of a participatory approach combining qualitative and quantitative methods, four exploratory scenarios were elaborated. As shown in the figure below [Figure 55], the scenarios were developed along two axes: “market concerns *versus* non-market concerns” and “centralized network structure *versus* decentralized network structure”. The different scenarios (that are illustrated by a character) are titled "European Copper Plate", "European Energy Citadel", "Wallonia of Blockchainized Energy", and "Autonomous Energy Territories" (ICEDD & al., 2018). An analysis of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the scenarios lead to the definition of a number of recommendations regarding the regulatory framework, investments, research and development, communication, training, and democratic functioning. Short-term priority areas were also identified (Marenne, 2018).

Figure 55. Scenarios developed in the prospective study on energy networks commissioned by IWEPS (Marenne 2018, p. 30)

This prospective exercise sponsored by a public actor meets criteria used for selecting the cases studies (see the section “2.1. Multiple case study” of Chapter III). However, as the study was still under development when I conducted the survey, it would not have been possible to evaluate its role in policy-making.

Foresight studies on climate-energy issues have also been carried out by stakeholders, starting with Elia. In the study “Electricity scenarios for Belgium towards 2050: Elia’s quantified study on the energy transition in 2030 and 2040”, the Electricity Transmission System Operator developed on the basis of a simulation tool (i.e.: ANTARES) a reference scenario (“Base Case”) and two alternative scenarios (“Decentral” and “Large scale”). While the “Decentral” scenario assumes a transition based on the

production of renewable electricity from decentralized renewable sources (i.e.: photovoltaic) and the development of storage devices, the scenario “Large scale” assumes a transition based on the production of renewable electricity from decentralized renewable sources (i.e.: onshore and offshore wind power). The scenarios developed by Elia are illustrated in the following figure [Figure 56]. Through the scenario analysis, Elia highlights, amongst others, the ecological and economic benefits from investing in additional electrical interconnectors, the need for supplementary adjustable thermal generation capacity with a view to coping with the shock of the 2025 nuclear phase-out and to guaranteeing security of supply, and the necessity of implementing targeted auctions before 2020-2022 to ensure that those required replacement capacities will be built (Elia, 2017).

Figure 56. Scenarios developed by Elia (Elia 2017, p. 28)

In addition, the Federation of Belgian industrial energy consumers (Febeliec) commissioned a foresight study at VITO/EnergyVille to evaluate the costs generated by different energy transition pathways. Based on the TIMES model, five scenarios at horizon 2030 have been developed. These scenarios represent different possible evolutions of the Belgian energy mix. These include a baseline scenario based on the extrapolation of current trends (“Central scenario”), a scenario assuming that electricity import is limited to 10% of aggregated power generation (“10% import restriction”), a scenario assuming a low price level trend for fossil fuel price (“Low fossil fuel price”), a scenario assuming a high price level trend for fossil fuel price (“High fossil fuel price”), and a last scenario assuming ten-year extension of 2 GW nuclear power capacity beyond 2025 (“Nuclear extension”). The net electricity imports, the system costs and the CO₂ emissions have been estimated for each scenario. The figure below summarizes the key results of the study [Figure 57] (EnergyVille, 2017).

Scenario Power sector	2016	Central	10% Import restriction	Fuel price high	Fuel price low	Nuclear extension 2 GW
Capacities (GW)	19.9	25.8	27.2	27.7	25.3	25.8
RES total	6.1	19.1	18.2	23.5	17.4	18.9
solar PV	3.0	7.9	7.0	12.1	6.2	8.3
wind onshore	1.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6
wind offshore	0.7	2.2	2.2	2.5	2.2	1.6
nuclear	5.9	0	0	0	0	2.0
fossil	7.9	6.7	9.0	4.1	7.9	4.9
import	3.5	6.5	6.5	7.5	6.5	6.5
Production Belgium (TWh)	78.3	71.0	79.1	55.7	78.0	72.2
RES	11.0	35.8	34.9	40.9	34.2	34.2
nuclear	43.0	0	0	0	0	15.0
fossil	24.3	35.1	44.2	14.8	43.9	23.2
net import	6.3	15.6	6.2	28.4	7.9	14.4
Annual electricity system cost 2030 (billion Euro)	/	6.18	6.19	6.43	4.82	5.57
Additional annual ele. system costs (2030 to 2016, billion Euro)	/	4.49	4.50	4.74	3.13	3.88
CO ₂ emissions (Mton)	15.4	19.3	22.5	11.6	22.9	14.7

Figure 57. Comparative overview of key scenario results in 2030 in the study ordered by Febeliec (EnergyVille 2017, p. 32)

It is interesting to note that costs in the scenario assuming ten-year extension of 2 GW nuclear power capacity beyond 2025 are lower compared to other scenarios. This is because the costs of investing in new gas plants are reported: *“From 2035 onwards, after the complete closure of the nuclear generation, other technologies will have to fill the gap”* (EnergyVille 2017, p. 4). However, when Febeliec presented the results at a press conference held in January 2017, the lobby did not mention this aspect and stated that the study concluded that *“the extension of nuclear life reduces the overall cost of the transition as well as CO₂ emissions”* (Febeliec 2017, 9). Febeliec, just like the federations of chemistry and technological companies, actually defends a pro-nuclear vision (Agoria & al., 2017). This is why the Belgian environmental NGOs Bond Beter Leefmilieu (BBL), Greenpeace and Inter-Environnement Wallonie (IEW) asked EnergyVille to undertake a sensitivity analysis of the scenarios. In this new version of the study, the hypotheses were reviewed on the basis of updated data and the time horizon was fixed at 2040 in order to be able to compare the cost of a nuclear output in 2035 and 2025. The sensitivity analysis of the scenarios shows that the economic advantage of the partial postponement of the nuclear phase-out is temporary and much less important than expected. (EnergyVille, 2018; Greenpeace & al., 2018). This example illustrates the issues linked to the methodological choices in scenario analyses and the importance of how the results of the foresight studies are interpreted and communicated.

In addition to this sensitivity analysis of the study ordered by Febeliec, Belgian NGOs also commissioned their own foresight climate-energy study. This is the study *“Our Energy Future 2016: On the way to a Belgian renewable energy system”*. Conducted by the 3E consulting firm for the Belgian NGOs Bond Beter Leefmilieu (BBL), Inter-Environnement Wallonie (IEW), Greenpeace and World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF), this study explores how to reduce efficiently GHG emissions of the electricity generation sector while leaving the nuclear power behind by 2025. On the basis of a model, two scenarios were developed: a reference scenario and a low-carbon scenario called *“Our Energy Future scenario”*. The analysis shows that Belgium could produce 54% of its electricity from renewable sources by 2030. It also highlights that this renewable energy development trajectory will not be more expensive in terms of subsidies than the reference scenario. The scenarios have been adapted to the scale of Wallonia and Flanders (3E, 2016).

Conclusion to the Chapter

This chapter intended to provide the contextual background for the field studies contained in the next two chapters – i.e.: the Walloon region. After offering an insight into the geographical and economic characteristics of Wallonia, I presented its historic and projected GHG emissions. I showed that between 1990 and 2016, Wallonia reduced its GHG emissions by 35%. Although industry is the largest source of emissions, this sector has contributed the most to the reduction of GHG emissions. On the contrary, the emissions associated to the sector of transports have risen. Taking a look at the projections, several forecasts indicate that without additional measures, the domestic GHG emissions should in a first stage slightly diminish and increase from 2025 following the closure of nuclear power plants and their partial replacement by gas-fired power plants. As a result, the GHG emissions should remain relatively stable between now and 2030. This pointed out a considerable gap between the projected emissions and the policy objectives for 2020 and 2030. I then went to the presentation of climate mitigation governance in Wallonia, starting with an overview of the Belgian federalism system. After introducing the particularly complex multi-level architecture of Belgium, I mentioned three other fundamental characteristics of the Belgian political system: the partitocracy, the corporatism and the pillarization. I then focused more specifically on climate mitigation governance. I showed that, climate mitigation competences are fragmented between the federal state and the regions, but also between different political and administrative authorities within each of these entities – highlighting that, in total, ten ministers and eleven administrations have levers for action to ensure the low-carbon transition. After defining the institutional framework, I moved on to the energy market governance. I mentioned the recent liberalization of the Belgian energy market and introduced the main energy market operators, namely the producers, importers, suppliers, transmission system operators (TSOs), distribution system operators (DSOs) and regulators. The next section was devoted to the involvement of civil society in climate-energy policy. Since climate-energy policy affects a lot of actors whose values and interests differs, a great number of civil society actors are involved in the decision-making process for climate mitigation. In order to illustrate the density of the constellation of private actors involved in climate-energy governance, I listed the main business federations, trade unions, environmental and development NGOs and consumer associations involved in the decision-making process for climate mitigation at the federal and Walloon levels. I then exposed the three principal ways by which those actors participate in decision and policy-making, namely consultation, concertation and lobbying. The last point of the section devoted to climate mitigation governance covered the policy dimension. Starting with the emergence of climate mitigation governance and the first commitment period of the Kyoto Protocol (2008-2012), it showed the recent character of climate mitigation governance. I conclude the section by presenting the main climate mitigation policies adopted at the European, national and Walloon levels. It reflected the great variety of policy implemented to reduce GHG emissions. The last section of the chapter was devoted to climate-energy foresight in Wallonia. Through the presentation of the institutionalization process of foresight in Wallonia, I showed the marginal place of this practice in the Walloon political and administrative system. I concluded the chapter by presenting the main “producers” of foresight on climate-energy issues – i.e.: CLIMACT, ICEDD, VITO and Federal Planning Bureau – as well as some recent climate-energy foresight studies developed for Wallonia other than those analysed in the next chapter (Chapter III).

CHAPTER III.
**Interactions between Low-Carbon Scenarios and
Governance: A Multiple Case Study**

CHAPTER III. Interactions between Low-Carbon Scenarios and Governance: A Multiple Case Study

Introduction

As shown in the literature review on the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance, foresight products and processes are claimed as potentially contributing to policy-making (See section “5.2. Interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance” of Chapter I). Basically, however, up to now rather few empirical efforts have tried to explore the fundamentals of the role of scenario analyses in policy-making. Empirical insights on the use and influence of scenarios have been provided, among others, by Fobé & Brans (2013), Rijkens-Klomp (2012), Quist & *al.* (2011), Yoda (2011) and van der Duin & *al.* (2009). In that context, several authors call for additional empirical research to better understand how scenario products and processes affect the social context (Rijkens-Klomp 2012; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; European Environment Agency, 2009; Georghiou & Keenan, 2006; Chermack, 2004).

Furthermore, with a few exceptions like Fobé & Brans (2013), the discussions of scenarios as social objects have not yet penetrated the mainstream debates in social sciences, confining themselves to the evaluative scenario literature, which is a branch of scenario literature. The interactions between scenarios and the social context have indeed received little academic attention from social sciences, whether they are political science, sociology, philosophy of science or science and technology studies (STS) (Fobé & Brans, 2013; European Environment Agency, 2009; Garb & *al.*, 2008; Aligica, 2003). Yet, the conceptual frameworks and methodological tools drawn from social sciences that have been proven to be effective for analysing the role in policy-making of other science-based artefacts like evaluations or indicators could greatly contribute to shed light on the social “work” of scenarios. In that context, Garb & *al.* (2008) emphasize the need to carry out social sciences research on scenarios.

The objective of this chapter is to provide an empirical contribution to social sciences research on low-carbon scenarios by exploring the role of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making on the basis of the conceptual frameworks and methodological tools developed in the knowledge utilization literature. The main research question is thus formulated quite straightforwardly:

“How do low-carbon scenarios interact with governance?”

This general question is divided into four sub-questions:

- I. How are low-carbon scenarios used by political actors?
- II. Beyond the purely instrumental use, how do these foresight exercises influence policy-making?
- III. How do the different actors appropriate the representations of the future developed through these scenario analyses?
- IV. What are the factors that affect the use and influence of these foresight exercises in policy-making?

To address those questions, I have undertaken a multiple case study analysing the role in policy-making of four energy foresight studies carried out for the Walloon Region (Belgium). This analysis has been carried out on the basis of an analytical framework developed in the knowledge utilization literature (see Gudmunson & *al.*, 2009). It considers the five above-mentioned types of knowledge role in policy-making, namely instrumental, conceptual, political, process and distortive roles (see section “5.2.1. Knowledge and governance: Beyond the rational knowledge-based policy-making model” of Chapter I). The exploration of the use and influence of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making is based on documentary analysis and 74 semi-structured interviews with the actors involved in the long-term

climate mitigation policy in Wallonia. Those actors are political authorities, political advisors, administrative authorities, employers' federations, workers' unions, environmental and development NGOs, advisory councils, energy market operators, public transport operators, public research institutes, consultancy agencies and universities. The important empirical material collected was analysed with the method of thematic coding. After exploring the role in policy-making and the level of appropriation per actor for each of the four studies, I have conducted a cross-case analysis in order to highlight the similarities and differences between the four studies.

The following chapter includes six sections. In the first one, I present the framework I have used to analyse the role of energy foresight studies in policy-making. The second section is devoted to the methodology. I discuss the choice of the cases studies, the data collection methods (i.e.: documentary analysis and semi-structured interviews), and finally the approach I used to analyse the empirical material (i.e.: thematic coding). Afterwards, I move on to the presentation of the four case studies. For each of them, I detail the emergence of the study, its process and results, its communication, follow-up and reception, and *in fine* its role in policy-making. In the fourth section, I present the cross-case analysis, discussing the similarities and differences between the case studies regarding their roles in policy-making as well as their appropriation and use per actor. The fifth section is devoted to the discussion of the results. In the last section, I expose the limits of this research.

1. Framework to Analyse the Role of Foresight Studies in Policy-Making

The analysis of the role of scenarios in policy-making have been carried out on the basis of a conceptual and methodological framework developed in the knowledge utilization literature. More specifically, I'm using the analytical framework developed by Gudmundsson & al. (2009) as part of the "Policy use and influence of indicators" (POINT) project. It considers the five above-mentioned types of knowledge role in policy-making, namely instrumental, conceptual, political, process and distortive roles (see section "5.2.1. Knowledge and governance: Beyond the rational knowledge-based policy-making model" of Chapter I). As shown in the following figure, this framework explores the role of science-based artefacts in policy-making through a "knowledge pathway" [Figure 58]. This pathway involves four stages: the emergence of the science-based artefacts, its uses, its influence and finally its role in policy-making. Obviously, in reality, the knowledge pathway is neither a linear nor a unidirectional process – the process being linearly sequenced for an analytical purpose (Gudmunson & al., 2009).

Figure 58. Framework to analyse the role of foresight studies in policy-making (adapted from Gudmundsson & al., 2009)

Each of the four steps of the knowledge pathway are depicted in order to characterize the interactions between the science-based artefact and governance. The following tables summarizes the variables took into consideration for characterizing those four steps [Tables 11, 12, 13, and 14]. The first step is the emergence. It corresponds to the stage where a scenario exercise originates and is developed with some interactions to policy-making. Several dimensions can characterize this initial phase of interactions with policy-making [Table 11].

EMERGENCE OF THE SCENARIO ANALYSIS	
Origin of the study	
Official function	
Clients	
Contractors	
Budget	
Scenario process	

Table 11. Variables characterizing the emergence of the scenario analysis (adapted from Gudmundsson & al., 2009)

The use of scenario analysis corresponds to a direct application of its product. It is explored at four levels ranging from simple reception to more extensive use [Table 12].

USE OF THE SCENARIO ANALYSIS	
1. Reception	
Receive, notice, observe	
Forward to others (no change)	
2. Internal application	
Use for own work (calculation/text)	
Use in internal communication	
3. External application	
Communication with other policy institutions	
Communication with stakeholders	
4. Decision support	
Use in official policy plan/report/document	
Use for making a judgment and decision	

Table 12. Variables characterizing the uses of the scenarios (adapted from Gudmundsson & al., 2009)

The influence concerns the direct or indirect effects of the scenario product or process. It is analysed at the individual, interpersonal and collective levels [Table 13].

INFLUENCE OF THE SCENARIO ANALYSIS	
1. Individual level	
Attitude change	Affect state policy-makers' opinions about feasibility or <i>acceptability</i> of implementing program
Saliency	Raise the importance of the issue or social problem
Elaboration	Stimulates individuals to think more about the program and their expectations for its outcomes
Priming	Make an issue appear more important by highlighting
Skill acquisition	New skills, such as collaboration or survey techniques, are learned through participation in scenarios process
Behaviour change	Adopting new practice following showing positive results
2. Interpersonal level	
Persuasion	Communication of scenarios through credible organization persuades policymakers that program should be supported
Justification	Scenarios are used to justify political decisions
Change agent	Results influence an individual to work for organizational change
Minority-opinion influence	Opinion minorities use findings to counter widely held attitudes
Social norms	Information makes new behaviour seem appropriate
<i>Network building</i>	<i>Scenario process led to the establishment of a community of scenarios producers and users</i>
<i>Consensus building</i>	<i>Scenario process facilitate the construction of consensus among different actors</i>
<i>Dialogue</i>	<i>Scenario process or product facilitate dialogue among different actors</i>
3. Collective level	
Agenda setting	Media reports of study findings helps put an issue onto the political agenda
Policy-oriented learning	Advocacy coalition modifies policy recommendation based on evidence of success of several program alternatives
Policy change	Study findings lead to changes in the representation of the societal problem, policy goals or instruments
Diffusion	Evidence of policy success stimulates adoption elsewhere

Table 13. Influence of the scenarios (adapted from Gudmundsson & al., 2009). New types of influence compared to the initial analytical framework are written in italic.

The last “step” of the knowledge pathway is the role in policy-making. It is a broader concept encompassing use and influence. By analysing the role, we move from a descriptive to an interpretative task. As previously explained, the present study considers five types of role of knowledge in policy-making [Table 14].

ROLE OF THE SCENARIO ANALYSIS	
Instrumental role	Scenarios helping to perform intended policy function in a way that confirms the scenarios as a tool for problem solving
Conceptual role	Scenarios contributing to expand knowledge base and introduce new ideas or concept in the policy arena
Political role	Scenarios serving to justify decisions already taken or to improve someone's relative position in the policy process or system compared to 'opponents'
Process role	Scenarios process contributing to policy-making
Distortive role	Scenarios confusing or derailing policy process because of wrong, insufficient or biased information, or because of induced strategic behaviour, gaming ...

Table 14. Role of the scenario analysis (adapted from Gudmundsson, 2009).

The analytical framework further considers that the knowledge pathway can be influenced by three types of factors, namely scenarios, users and institutional factors. The scenarios factors correspond to the internal characteristics of the scenario product and processes (e.g.: methodology, outcome, communication, follow-up, resources). The users factors covers the characteristics of the intended users that can potentially influence their propensity to demand, respond to, or apply foresight studies (e.g.: repertoire, educational background, familiarization with foresight). Finally, the institutional factors include the policy-process to which the scenario analysis is intended to contribute (i.e.: *policy*), as well as the system of rules and organizational structures within which the intended users operate. Those three factors form groups of potential independent variables for explaining if and how scenarios influence policy-making (Gudmundsson & *al.*, 2009).

2. Methodology

2.1. Multiple Case Study

2.1.1. Case Selection

The chapter develops on a multiple case study analysing the role in policy-making of four energy foresight studies carried out for the Walloon Region (Belgium). The criteria used for selecting the cases studies are the following:

- (1) The study corresponds to the definition of foresight presented previously, i.e.: a policy-oriented approach assuming that the future is multiple, uncertain and potentially radically different from the present, and aiming at envisioning and exploring in a systemic and holistic way alternative images of the future (see section “3.1.1. Foresight: Conceptual clarification” of Chapter I)
- (2) The study explores at least one low-carbon scenario. Such scenario results in a low-carbon regime in 2050. The low-carbon regime can be described quantitatively (i.e.: reduction of GHG emissions of 80-96%) or qualitatively.
- (3) The geographical scope of the study covers all or part the Walloon Region, without exceeding the Belgian territory.
- (4) The study has been commissioned by a public actor.

Four foresight studies meeting those criteria were found. The studies analysed are the following: “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050” (CLIMACT, 2012), “Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050” (CLIMACT & VITO, 2013), “Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050” (VITO & *al.*, 2012) and “Prospective study: Energy transition” (CLIMACT & *al.*, 2015). Two of them are limited to the regional territory (i.e.: “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050” and “Prospective study: Energy transition”) and the other two consider the whole country (i.e.: “Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050” and “Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050”). It appears that no study has been conducted at the local level in Wallonia.

2.1.2. Main Features of the Foresight Studies Analysed

Besides the geographical scope, the chosen studies differ *inter alia* in terms of clients, contractors, year of publication (i.e.: between 2012 and 2015), normative and material scopes (i.e.: from the energy system to the entire socio-technical system), approach (i.e.: forecasting or backcasting), methodology (i.e.: bottom-up modelling, top-down modelling or qualitative methodology inspired by the work of the French *prospectivists* Hugues de Jouvenel and Michel Godet), level of participation and actors involved (i.e.: from expert-based analysis to participative exercises), extent to which governance issues are addressed (see next section), product, communication strategy, but also regarding the follow-up. The table below summarizes the main features of the studies analysed [Table 15].

	CASES SELECTED			
	Case study 1: Low-carbon Wallonia	Case study 2: Low-carbon Belgium	Case study 3: 100% renewable	Case study 4: Energy transition
Full title	“Towards a low-carbon Wallonia by 2050”	“Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050”	“Towards 100 renewable energy in Belgium by 2050”	“Prospective study: Energy transition”
Emergence	Publication of the EU Roadmap 2050 and emergence of the Walloon energy-climate partly at the instigation of Green party	Publication of the study “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia by 2050”	Fukushima nuclear disaster	Identification of the energy transition as one of the main prospective issues for Wallonia through a consultative process with academics and members of Walloon administration launched by IWEPS
Clients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon agency for air and climate (AWAC) at the request of the Minister of environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate Change Section of the Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Federal, Walloon, Flemish and Brussels ministers in charge of energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon institute for evaluation, prospective and statistics (IWEPS)
Contractors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ European Climate Foundation (ECF) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development (ICEDD) ▪ Federal Planning Bureau ▪ Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ Institute for a Sustainable Development (IDD) ▪ Catholic University of Louvain (UCL) ▪ Federal Planning Bureau ▪ Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development (ICEDD) ▪ University of Liège (ULg)
Budget	145.200 €	?	?	200. 000 €
Publication	February 2012	November 2013	December 2012	March 2015
Normative scope	Reduction of GHG emission by 80-95%	Reduction of GHG emission by 80-95%	100% renewable energy	-
Temporal scope	2050	2050	2050	2050
Geographical scope	Walloon Region	Belgium	Belgium	Walloon Region
Material scope	Energy system	Energy system	Energy system and economy	Socio-technical system (energy system, economy, society and policy)
Scenario type³¹	Feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios	Feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios	Feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios	External scenarios
Methodology	Bottom-up modelling representing the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions (OPE ² RA)	Bottom-up modelling representing the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions (OPE ² RA)	Top-down macro-economic modelling representing the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions (TIMES)	Qualitative methodology inspired by the work of the French prospectivists Hugues de Jouvenel and Michel Godet

³¹ As defined in the low-carbon scenario typology previously presented (see section “3.3.2. Typology of low-carbon scenarios” of Chapter I)

Participation	Many consultations of stakeholders and administrations (more than 100 persons consulted)	Many consultations of stakeholders and administrations + bilateral meetings (more than 120 persons consulted)	Two consultations of stakeholders and administrations (50-60 persons consulted)	One consultation of stakeholders and administrations (6 persons consulted)
	CASES SELECTED			
	Case study 1: Low-carbon Wallonia	Case study 2: Low-carbon Belgium	Case study 3: 100% renewable	Case study 4: Energy transition
Knowing governance	-	-	List of policy recommendations in the concluding chapter	Policy and polity dimensions included as variables
Product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report ▪ Executive summary ▪ Web tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report ▪ Executive summary ▪ Web tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report ▪ Executive summary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report ▪ Executive summary
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation to the cabinet of the Walloon Minister in charge of environment ▪ Presentation to an inter-cabinet meeting of the Walloon Government ▪ Presentation to a conference organized by AWAC and the cabinet of the Walloon Minister in charge of environment ▪ Press release (Sudpresse, LaLibre...) ▪ Presentation to the CESW 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of the preliminary results of the study to the Annual Forum of the CFDD ▪ Presentation to the cabinet of the Federal Minister in charge of Energy ▪ Press conference with the Federal Minister of energy and the FPS Climate change ▪ Press release (LaLibre, L'Echo, RTBF, De Redactie, Vilt...) ▪ Presentation to the Annual Forum of the CFDD ▪ Presentation to the cabinet of the "new" Federal Minister in charge of Energy ▪ Presentation to the Belgian House of Representatives ▪ Many presentations to different institutions and organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation to the stakeholders ▪ Press release (LaLibre, LeSoir, L'Echo, RTBF...) ▪ Presentation to a joint meeting of Commissions from Federal, Walloon, Flemish and Brussels' Parliaments ▪ Many presentations to different institutions and organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation to the cabinet of the Walloon Ministry of Energy ▪ Presentation to the Walloon Parliament ▪ Presentation to the Energy department of the Walloon administration ▪ Presentation to the Energy Commission of Ecolo
Follow-up	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Web tool My 2050 ▪ Macro-economic study ▪ National debate on carbon pricing 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Foresight study on electrical networks

Table 15. Main features of the foresight studies analysed

2.1.3. Making of Knowledge about Governance in the Foresight Studies Analysed

Among the four climate-energy foresight studies analysed, only two studies address governance issues. They are the “Energy transition” and the “100% renewable” studies. “Energy transition” is the study that proposes the more in-depth analysis of the governance issues. As explained in the section devoted to the presentation of the study (see section “3.4.2. Presentation of the study” of the same chapter), the scenarios were built on the basis of a qualitative methodology exploring the possible evolutions of a system through an analysis of the interactions between the variables which compose this system. Among the variables analysed, we find several variables related to the *policy* and *polity* dimensions of governance. They cover the steering mode and various policy instruments – i.e.: Infrastructures, regulatory framework, fiscality, land use planning, information and awareness, and educational and vocational training. Those variables have different states from one energy transition scenario to another. Note that the question of the role of the different publics and private actors (i.e.: *politics*) is not analysed as part of this study.

The study “100% renewable” doesn’t provide such an extensive analysis of governance issues. While the governance dimensions are included as variable in the scenarios developed in the “Energy transition” studies, the scenarios built in the present study doesn’t include any social dimension as variable. Such dimensions were addressed in an ex-post analysis aiming at identifying the policies and measures to be implemented to meet 100% renewable energy in 2050. The analysis, which is mostly in an exploratory nature, concerns the policy mix needed to reach the renewable energy target (i.e.: *policy*) as well as the institutional framework required so make this portfolio of policy instruments effective (i.e.: *polity*). The analysis of the *policy* and *polity* dimensions of governance is presented in the form of recommendations. Just like in the “Energy transition” study, the question of the actors (i.e.: *politics*) is not addressed.

For their part, the studies “Low-carbon Wallonia” and “Low-carbon Belgium” are purely technical-economic studies that address neither governance issues, nor any other social dimensions.

2.2. Data Collection

The analyses of “what happened with?” is based on the one hand on a documentary analysis and on the other hand on extensive semi-structured interviews. The following section describes these two modes of data collection.

2.2.1. Documentary Analysis

The first mode of data collection is a documentary analysis. I looked for references or mentions to the studies analysed in different types of sources. The sources include policy plans and legislations from the Walloon and Belgian Governments; records of the Walloon and Belgian Parliaments; advisory councils’ notices; press articles; as well as documents, reports, communications and websites from various political actors. I have actually analysed the websites of the actors involved in the long-term policy process of GHG-emissions’ mitigation in the Walloon Region. Such desk research allowed me to highlight a number of references and mentions to the foresight studies under consideration. The sources collected on the internet were completed by various documents not available on the Net that the respondents gave me during the interviews (e.g.: internal notes, confidential documents).

2.2.2. Semi-Structured Interviews

Besides the documentary analysis, I conducted extensive semi-structured interviews with the actors involved in the long-term policy process of GHG-emissions’ mitigation in the Walloon Region – i.e.: the producers and the intended users of scenarios. The transcriptions of the interviews are the main source of information for analysing the use and influence of the four prospective studies. The rest of

the section presents the sampling approach, the composition of the sample, the interview process and the system of code I used to anonymize the collected data.

Constitution and Composition of the Sample

A purposive sampling approach was adopted to identify the respondents. The actors involved in the long-term decision-making process for climate mitigation can be split in three groups, namely the authors, the sponsors and the intended users of low-carbon scenarios. The former corresponds to the actors in charge of the production of the foresight study, the second to the public authorities that order the study, and the last to the political actors that are their intended users. Note that the borderline between these groups is not fixed: from one study to another or even in a same study, some actors may be sponsors as well as users.

With a view to identifying the actors, I mobilized a **social network analysis (SNA)** approach (see Hermans & Thissen, 2009). This method consists in identifying and representing with sociograms the relation between different actors. The actors and the relationships that bind them together are respectively represented by points and lines. SNA sounds particularly interesting because it provides a good understanding of the role of different actors, allows identifying important actors, yet highlights also informal relations (Ramalingam, 2006). Furthermore, this approach is particularly suitable for complex object of study (e.g.: intricate interactions between different level of power).

I conducted the SNA in an iterative way. I firstly made an inventory of the authors, the sponsors, the steering committee members and the scenario workshop participants of the four foresight studies analysed. I completed this list with other actors playing a role in the long-term decision-making process for climate mitigation who were not directly involved in these studies. Those actors are competent political and administrative authorities in the area of climate-energy policy, members of civil society organizations that represent the position of their organization on those issues in advisory councils, and actors of foresight. On this basis, I outlined an initial version of the network of actors. The actors identified in this way constituted the first survey participants. During the interviews, I presented them the initial version of the network of actors and they were asked to complete it by adding the missing actors and relations.

This snowball sampling approach enabled to identify 105 actors. The following figure represents the network of actors involved in the long-term decision-making process for climate mitigation in Wallonia [Figure 59]. In view of the large number of actors, I used organizations instead of individuals as nodes. The network includes different types of organizations, namely political authorities, political advisors, administrative authorities, employers' federations, workers' unions, environmental and development NGOs, advisory councils, energy market operators, public transport operators, public research institutes, consultancy agencies and universities. Most of the organizations have been introduced in the chapter devoted to the contextual background (see Chapter II). The objective in including the representation of the network of actors is to illustrate the complexity of such a network: there is a lot of actors at the federal and Walloon levels and intricate relations among those actors.

Figure 59. Network of actors involved in the long-term policy process of mitigation in Wallonia. The political and administrative authorities are coloured in blue, the civil society in green, the energy market operators in orange, the public transport operators in pink and the actors of (climate-energy) foresight in red. The arrows correspond to foresight studies production and the lines correspond to relations between actors

For each organization, I identified a contact person. I attempted to identify the persons likely to be able to discuss the foresight studies analysed, starting with those who contributed to these studies as authors, sponsors, steering committee members or workshop participants. For the organizations that were not involved in the development of the studies analysed, depending on the organizational structure, I contacted the person responsible for foresight and long-term planning or the reference persons in the matter of energy and climate policy. Since most of the energy and climate policy actors know each other, the identification of reference persons was done without too much difficulty through the snowball sampling approach.

Note that although they have an important role to play in the low-carbon transition, local actors have not been invited to participate in the study. The number of people to meet and the quantity of material to be analysed would have been too large given the time allotted.

I contacted the identified persons by email. In those emails, I presented the research project (i.e.: study on the political use of the low-carbon scenarios), the objectives of the interview (i.e.: to understand the impacts on policy-making of different energy foresight studies carried out for Wallonia / Belgium) and the reason why I wanted to meet those persons (i.e.: participation in the scenario process and/or expertise on climate-energy issues / foresight). I specified the time required for the interview (+/- 1h30). The persons contacted were also informed that the interview would be anonymous, implying that neither their name nor their organization name would be mentioned. I finally explained that the interview requires no preparation, but I sent to those who asked for a list of topics to be addressed. If the person did not answer, a first reminder email was sent, then a second one.

Among all the persons contacted, twelve did not answer my emails and thirteen declined the invitation, referring me most of the time to another contact person. Between January and September 2017, I have interviewed 74 persons, among which five political authorities, fifteen political advisors, seven administrative authorities, eleven employers' federations, three workers' unions, eight environmental and development NGOs, one advisory council, eleven energy market operators, one public transport operator, five public research institutes, five consultancy agencies and two universities [Table 16]. To guarantee the anonymity of the respondents, the complete list of the interviewed persons is kept confidential. Note that I met some people twice. I indeed also met the persons strongly involved in the development of studies (authors and sponsors) during exploratory interviews released in spring 2016. Most of the interviews were conducted face to face. However, at the request of the respondents, four interviews were conducted with one or more colleagues to them.

CATEGORY OF ACTORS		LEVEL		TOTAL
		WALLONIA	BELGIUM	
Intended users of scenarios	Political authorities	2	3	5
	Political advisors	6	9	15
	Administrative authorities	5	2	7
	Employers' federations	3	8	11
	Workers' unions	1	2	3
	Environmental and development NGOs	2	6	8
	Advisory councils	0	1	1
	Energy market operators	5	6	11
	Public transport operators	0	1	1
Producers of scenarios	Public research institutes	3	2	5
	Consultancy agencies	0	5	5
	Universities	2	0	2
TOTAL		29	45	74

Table 16. Number of respondents for each category of actors

Note that I closed the survey when actors from every category have been interviewed and when the additional interviews did not provide me any new data (i.e.: principle of data saturation).

Conduct of the Interviews

During the interview, the participants were invited to speak personally, and not in the name of their organization. I specified again the anonymous nature of the interview. With the permission of the respondent, the discussion was recorded. Only two interviews were not recorded. Apart from three interviews conducted in English, the discussions took place in French.

To lead the discussion, I was basing myself on an interview guide. I developed this guide on the basis of the analytical framework presented in the previous section (see section “1. Framework to analyse the role of foresight studies in policy-making” of the same chapter). The following table summarizes the main points of the interview guide as well as some examples of questions [Table 17]. A full version of the interview guide is available in appendix [Appendix 2]. The questions varied from one respondent to another, depending on the implication of the respondent in the studies (i.e.: client, authors, scenario workshop participant and/or intended user). Inasmuch as the interview was semi-directed, the order of questions was not predetermined, and the themes arose at the turn of the discussion. At a first step, in order to help put interviewee at ease, I usually asked him to introduce himself. We then talked about his perception and his experience with regard to foresight before focusing on the studies analysed.

THEME	EXAMPLES OF QUESTIONS
Presentations	Could you briefly introduce your organization and your role within it?
Foresight	Are you familiarized with foresight? What do you think about foresight as a decision support tool?
Reception of the study	Do you know these different studies? How did you become aware of the study? Did you or your organization react when the study was published (i.e.: press, advisory boards...)? Did you disseminate the study?
(Non)-Use of the study	Did you use the study for your own work? Did you use the study for the communication within your organization or with other actors? Did you use the study for the elaboration of reports, documents or plans? Did you use the study for decision making?
Beyond use: Influence of the study on policy-making	Did the study influence your opinion regarding the feasibility / acceptability of the low-carbon transition? Where you surprise by some aspects of the study? Did you learn something? What do you remember? Did the study lead to a discussion / debate among different actors? Did the study contribute to put some issues on the political agenda?
Process role: Influence of the scenario building process on policy-making	How did the scenarios workshop go? Do you feel that you have been listened to? Did you learn something during the scenario workshops? Do you think that the scenarios workshops fostered the dialogue among different actors
Evaluation of the studies regarding their credibility, legitimacy and salience	

Table 17. Examples of questions asked during the interviews

Note that I brought with me a printed version of the four foresight studies analysed. The respondent was allowed to skim through the documents during the interview.

I took some notes during the interview and I transcribed the entire discussion with the Transcribe³² software after the meeting.

System of Code to Anonymize the Collected Data

In order to guarantee the anonymity of the participants, I used a code system that anonymize the collected data. Each respondent was assigned a code. The code assigned reflects two dimensions: the type of actor and the political level. I have also allocated a number to each respondent. The system of

³² <https://transcribe.wreally.com>

code I used to anonymize the collected data is presented in the table below [Table 18]. For instance, the code “POL-BE-1” corresponds to a Belgian political authority.

DIMENSIONS	CARRACTERISTICS	CODE
(1) Type of actor	Political authorities	POL-
	Political advisors	PA-
	Administrative authorities	ADM-
	Employers’ federations	BUS-
	Workers’ unions	WU-
	Environmental and development NGOs	NGO-
	Advisory councils	AC-
	Energy market operators	ENG-
	Public transport operators	TRA-
	Public research institutes	PRI-
	Consultancy agencies	CA-
(2) Level	Universities	UNI-
	Belgian	BE-
	Walloon	RW-

Table 18. System of code used to anonymize the collected data

Note that I removed the number at the end of the code for the quotations in order to avoid identification of the author of the quotation by cross checking.

2.3. Data Analysis

The transcription of the interviews provided a considerable amount of empirical material. To draw conclusions from such a vast amount of unstructured raw information, different qualitative data analysis approaches exist (see Paillé & Mucchielli, 2016; Fallery & Rodhain, 2007; Quivy & Van Campenhoudt, 2011). Miles & Huberman (1994) identify three simultaneous tasks in a qualitative data analysis process. Those are (1) the data reduction that consists in “*selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstracting and transforming*” the empirical material, (2) the data display that aims at developing “*an organized, compressed assembly of information that permits conclusion drawing*”, and (3) the conclusion drawing/verification which implies to “*decide what things means (...) noting regularities, patterns, explanations, possible configurations, causal flows, and propositions*” (Miles & Huberman 1994, p. 10-11). A great variety of techniques can be mobilized to carry out those tasks. We will see in this section that these three components are articulated in a continuous and iterative way throughout the analysis (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

Thematic coding is the method I used to reduce the empirical data. This method consists of assigning one or more codes to portions of texts depending on the theme they cover. According to Miles & Huberman, “*codes are tags or labels for assigning units of meaning to the descriptive or inferential information compiled during a study. Codes are usually attached to ‘chunks’ of varying size – words, phrases, sentences or whole paragraphs*” (Miles & Huberman 1994, p56). Thematic analysis is an appropriate method to highlight what the empirical material is about, or, in other words, to identify the themes raised in the material (Paillé & Mucchielli, 2016).

There are two types of coding: the inductive coding and the theoretical or deductive coding. In the case of inductive coding, the researcher did not define a list of themes beforehand, the codes being determined as and when the material is analysed. This type of thematic analysis is data-driven inasmuch as the researcher doesn’t try to integrate the data into a predefined framework (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Conversely, in the case of deductive coding, the researcher has drawn up a list of themes before beginning the analysis of the material. This list is defined on the basis of, among other things, the conceptual framework, research questions, assumptions, problem areas and key variables of the study (Miles & Huberman, 2003). The deductive coding is more analyst-driven in that it is led by the theoretical or analytical interests of the researcher (Braun & Clarke, 2006). In this research, the thematic analysis of the interview transcripts has involved both deductive and inductive coding. As the

interviews were semi-structured, the main themes to be addressed were predetermined. A list of codes could thus be defined before starting the analysis of the empirical material (i.e.: deductive coding). However, to the extent that some of the themes relevant to the research question that were not included in the theoretical framework used emerged during the interviews, the initial code list had to be reviewed afterwards (i.e.: inductive coding).

The first step of the analysis was therefore to define a list of codes on the basis of the interview guide (see the section "2.2.2. Semi-structured interviews" of the same chapter) and of the conceptual framework on which the interview guide is built (See the section "1. Framework to analyse the role of foresight studies in policy-making" of the same chapter). This list of codes was completed a first time over the transcription process of the interviews. Although it is time-consuming and not very stimulating, this task is an excellent way to become familiar with the material and to begin the analysis of it. The transcription process is indeed *"an interpretative act, where meanings are created, rather than simply a mechanical act putting spoken sounds on paper"* (Braun & Clarke 2006, p. 87-88).

As I transcribed the interviews, I also gradually identified the main elements that structure the history of each study (ex.: emergence, publication, communications, follow-up...). To get an overview of the process, these elements have been represented on a timeline. This representation which seeks to better understand the process under study is a form of what Miles & Huberman (1994) consider as data display. The time lines tracing the history of each study are integrated into the section devoted to the presentation of case studies (see section "3. Case studies" of the same chapter).

In addition, the process of transcribing the interviews also resulted in the writing of a first draft of the section devoted to the case studies (see section "3. Case studies" of the same chapter). This corresponds to the third and final component of a qualitative analysis as conceived by Miles & Huberman (1994), namely the conclusion drawing/verification. In the section devoted to the case studies, four points were developed for each of the four studies analysed: Emergence; presentation of the study; communication, follow up and reception; and role of the study in policy-making.

I then coded the interview transcripts. This task involves reading the transcripts carefully in order to assign one or more codes to portions of texts depending on the theme they cover. There are different techniques for identifying themes within a text. Among these techniques, we find the identification of repetitions, indigenous typologies or categories, metaphors and analogies, transitions, similarities and differences, linguistic connectors, missing data and theory-related material (see Ryan & Bernard, 2003). I mainly based on the identification of transitions and of theory-related material. The technique based on thematic transitions consists in identifying the changes of subjects using different hints such as breaks in speech or the presence of typical expressions (e.g.: "Otherwise..." or "it is also interesting to mention that..."). In semi-structured interviews, transitions are also created by the researcher when he asks questions. The technique for identifying themes based on theory-related material aims to identify expressions that correspond to theoretical issues of research. It is to find in the material the passages that echo the codes that have been previously defined on the basis of the conceptual framework.

The coding of the interview transcripts can be done manually or with the help of a computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (Lejeune, 2017; Wong, 2008). Given the large amount of empirical material to be processed, I chose the second approach. The computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software can actually process a large amount of material in an iterative way (Fallery & Rodhain, 2007). I choose the Dedoose³³ software. It is a web application for analysing qualitative and mixed methods research developed by researchers from the University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA) (Dedoose,

³³ <https://www.dedoose.com>

2018). I chose Dedoose for its competitive price. Its price is actually low compared to other coding software such as NVivo.

The coding of transcripts has led to the redefinition of certain codes, but also to the identification of new codes (i.e.: inductive coding). The processing of the data using the Dedoose software allowed me to enrich the text presenting the four case studies as well as the timelines tracing their history that I had sketched previously. I included a series of relevant elements that were not highlighted during the interview’s transcription phase as well as quotes. Software such as Dedoose is a great help as it allows to quickly gather all portions of text related to one or more specific themes. A particularly useful feature proposed by Dedoose is the code co-occurrence matrix. As shown in the figure below, this matrix indicates for each code crossing the number of text portions relating to the two selected codes and provides a one-click access to all these quotes [Figure 60].

Figure 60. Code Co-occurrence matrix in Dedoose software

After determining the role of each of the four studies in policy-making, I conducted the cross-case analysis. In order to highlight the similarities and differences between the four studies, I have drawn comparative charts (i.e.: data display). Charts comparing the role of the four studies in policy-making as well as the appropriation per actors are available in the section presenting the observations resulting from the cross-case analysis (see section “4. Cross-case analysis” of the same chapter).

3. Case Studies

3.1. Case Study n°1. Towards a Low-Carbon Wallonia in 2050

3.1.1. Emergence

The Study “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050” was initiated in 2010. Wallonia is one of the first European regions to have developed low-carbon scenarios – the United Kingdom having initiated this dynamic with the 2050 Energy Calculator released by the UK Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC)³⁴. At the request of the Walloon Minister in charge of environment, Philippe Henry (Ecolo), AWAC sponsored a study with a view to elaborating a long-term strategy towards a low-carbon society. Minister Henry wanted the Walloon Region to develop its own 2050 Roadmap, just like the European Commission did at the time with the help of the European Climate Foundation (ECF) (see European Commission, 2011). By providing information on the measures to be adopted in the Post-2012 Air Climate and Energy Plan, the objective of the study was indeed to inform the Walloon long-term mitigation strategy.

«C'était dans le but d'alimenter le contenu du Plan Air-Climat-Energie qui lui reprend des mesures. Parce que pour savoir quel type de mesures on allait prôner, ça valait la peine de savoir vers quel type de scénario on allait, quelles étaient les grandes options qu'il fallait trancher.» (POL-RW)

In addition to developing a low-carbon strategy for Wallonia, the study also had a more political objective. The second motivation of the Minister of the Environment was to demonstrate that the objective of reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050 was realistic. The Minister intended to include this ambitious long-term objective in the Walloon Climate Decree. He and his cabinet esteemed that a robust and independent study demonstrating the feasibility of the objective would be helpful in convincing other members of the Government to include it in the Decree.

«C'était plus une étude pour montrer que c'est faisable (...) et notamment pour inscrire les fameux objectifs 2050 dans le Décret, puisque c'est ce qu'on voulait politiquement faire.» (PA-RW)

In autumn 2010, AWAC launched the request for proposals. In the specification, AWAC requested that were developed two scenarios: a baseline scenario and an alternative scenario sketching a path towards a low-carbon Wallonia. The demand also involved identifying priority areas and measures to be implemented in the short (5 years), the medium (15 years) and the long term (beyond 20 years) with a view to reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050. AWAC received five proposals and selected the one elaborated by CLIMACT in collaboration with ECF.

3.1.2. Presentation of the Study

Methodology

CLIMACT responded to AWAC's order by supporting the idea that there isn't a single path towards a low-carbon society, but several possible routes. Therefore, they proposed to develop not one, but several low-carbon scenarios. The scenarios were developed on the basis of a bottom-up model representing the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions for the sectors of energy production, building, transports, industry, agriculture and wastes. The modelling exercise has been achieved using the model Open-source Prospective Energy and Emissions Roadmap Analysis (OPE²RA). This model is a variation of the DECC 2050 Energy Calculator at the Walloon level. In collaboration with the DECC,

³⁴ <http://2050-calculator-tool.decc.gov.uk/#/home>

CLIMACT adapted the model to Walloon data and improve it, particularly by refining the modeling of industrial sectors. The model has since been adapted to many other regions, including Belgium as we will see in the next section, but also China, South Korea, Taiwan, India, South Africa and Japan. A Global Calculator³⁵ was also developed on the basis of this model by an international team composed, among others, of CLIMACT to explore pathways to reduce GHG emissions worldwide.

The OPE²RA model is based on an equilibrium backcasting approach between demand and energy supply. The model integrates four types of parameters: the fixed parameters (demography and historical demand, energy sources potential), the parameters on which the influence of Wallonia is limited (industrial production), the GHG emissions reduction parameters in the sectors of energy demand over which the region has a lot of influence (behaviour changes, improvement of carbon intensity, electrification and application of carbon capture and storage (CCS) in the industry), and the parameters of decarbonization of energy supply (energy mix, electrical mix and import levels) [Figure 61]. For each parameter, four levels of ambition have been defined. While the level 1 corresponds to the business as usual evolution, the level 4 amount to the maximum technical potential. The maximum technical potential has been defined on the basis of literature and expert’s consultations.

Figure 61. Energy balance model used in the study “Low-carbon Wallonia” (CLIMACT 2012, p. 11)

In total, over 100 experts from the administration, the ministerial cabinets, the industry, the civil society, and the academic world were consulted through a committee of experts and sectoral workshops. The sectoral workshops covered the sectors of transport, buildings, lime, cement, glass, steel, paper, chemical, energy transmission and distribution renewable energy and biomass. The consultative approach is a fundamental characteristic of the study to which CLIMACT attaches great importance. By involving a large number of experts, CLIMACT intended to benefit from the knowledge of actors on the ground, to allow everyone to express themselves, but also to enhance the transparency of the study.

«L’approche participative, c’est une de mes convictions fortes. Il faut être capable d’exposer en toute transparence. Il y a beaucoup de modèles qui existent et qui sont opaques, je pense que ça ne marche pas. Ils sont opaques parce qu’ils sont complexes aussi, donc il faut respecter la complexité et en même temps il faut veiller à simplifier et à être transparent,

³⁵ <http://globalcalculator.org>

donc ça c'est vraiment quelque chose de puissant chez nous. Alors l'exposer parfois c'est un peu désagréable, mais au moins quand on expose, ça permet d'entendre et de laisser de la place à toutes les opinions. Ça ne veut pas dire qu'on est d'accord sur toutes les opinions, mais au moins elles s'expriment. Et ça c'est, je pense, puissant dans notre méthodologie parce qu'elles s'expriment et nous on en tient compte. Ça veut dire que les gens ont envie de participer et les gens se sentent aussi reconnus.» (Author of the study)

The participatory approach also aimed to guard against possible questioning assumptions when the final results would be presented.

«C'est très important d'avoir consulté beaucoup de monde, parce qu'au moins, tu connais toutes les options et, à tout moment, tu peux dire "Attendez on vous a impliqués, donc il fallait le dire dans les groupes de travail". Donc ça, ça nous a donné un grand confort après, en disant "Attendez, nous on a été ouvert. Si vous avez une meilleure hypothèse, donnez-la nous, on est preneur".» (Author of the study)

During the consultations, in order to have technical discussions, participants were invited to speak as experts and not as representatives of their organizations. Note that it was not a co-construction exercise, in that the consultant constructed the hypotheses and submitted them to the experts who were then invited to react and give their opinion. The choice of whether or not to take into account the opinion of the experts belonged to the consultant. Incidentally, CLIMACT points out that the experts don't necessary validate the hypothesis used in the model and that the conclusions of the study are its sole responsibility.

Once the hypotheses were defined, the scenarios have been developed. By combining different levels of ambition for each parameter, CLIMACT, in collaboration with the steering and expert committees, has developed five balanced scenarios resulting in a reduction of GHG emissions of 80% in 2050. They are qualified as balanced, since they involve efforts in all sectors and avoid using the maximum level of ambition for a particular sector. These five scenarios differ according to the level of energy demand reduction and the level of decarbonization of the energy supply [Figure 62]. The lower is the demand, the less the energy supply needs to be decarbonized with a view to reaching the 80% emission reduction target. CLIMACT has also developed a scenario leading to 95% GHG reduction. This implies a maximum level of ambition in all sectors. Finally, a business as usual scenario was also elaborated. This trend-based scenario resulted in a reduction of GHG emissions of 17% compared to 1990.

Figure 62. Scenarios developed in the study "Low-carbon Wallonia" (CLIMACT 2012, p. 11)

For each scenario, CLIMACT assessed the impacts on the environment, on the socio-economic components and on the energy security.

Results

The technical-economic study showed that Wallonia could reduce its emissions by at least 80% in 2050 and that there were several ways to meet this objective. However, the low-carbon transition required high efforts in all sectors, but also a proactive attitude on the part of the Walloon public authorities.

CLIMACT highlighted a series of key elements for the transition to low-carbon Wallonia. The consultant stated the importance of improving energy efficiency and processes in the industries, but also the need to equip certain industrial facilities with CCS. Behavioural changes would also play a key role in reducing the demand for energy in the transport and building sectors. For these same sectors, improved energy efficiency and massive electrification were also required to significantly reduce GHG emissions. The essential character of the decarbonization of the energy supply was also highlighted. This decarbonization requires the development of renewable energies and the equipment of CCS in gas and coal power plants. Land-use planning that includes limiting the geographic spread of activities would also help to reduce energy consumption.

The scenario analysis showed that, in addition to reducing GHG emissions, the low-carbon transition leads to a decrease in Wallonia's energy dependence. Nevertheless, a significant portion of electricity generated from intermittent sources in the energy mix requires adapting the electricity grid to ensure security of supply.

In addition, the analysis revealed that reduction of GHG emissions by 80 to 95% by 2050 requires considerable investment. That being said, the scenario study showed that the total cost of a transition to a low-carbon economy might be lower than the cost of inaction.

Note that even if the AWAC's initial demand involved identifying measures to be implemented in the short, the medium, and the long term with a view to reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050, the study didn't provide such policy recommendations.

«Finalement, on n'a pas de mesures concrètes. C'est plutôt des lignes directrices, par exemple, électrification des véhicules.» (ADM-RW)

3.1.3. Communication, Follow-Up and Reception

The study was completed at the end of 2011. The results were presented in the form of an executive summary and a report. It should be noted that initially only the executive summary was distributed, the full report being available only on request. A simplified version of the model used by CLIMACT has been made public allowing everyone to develop their own low-carbon scenarios. The results of the study were also communicated via several newspapers, including LaLibre, but also Sudpress which published a complete special dossier on the subject.

Besides the consultations that allowed a number of stakeholders to become aware of the study, several presentations were organized to communicate the results of the study to a larger number of actors. Following a presentation in the cabinet of the Minister in charge of the environment, who welcomed the results with enthusiasm, CLIMACT presented the study at an inter-cabinet meeting. During this presentation, the study was apparently strongly criticized by the members of other ministerial cabinets. The critics – considered as unfounded by the sponsors of the study I met – related rather to the form than to the substance of the study. The political context of the time was apparently unfavourable to the Ecolo party. The initiatives of the Greens were constantly torpedoed by the partners of the majority who feared that the actions of Ecolo in favour of climate mitigation, and more globally in favour of sustainable development, would undermine the Walloon economy. The study was not an exception to that rule.

«Il y a eu des soucis. De toute façon, c'était un moment où quoi qu'Ecolo propose, c'était mauvais. Moi j'ai assisté à certains intercabinets, ce n'étaient pas des insultes, mais pratiquement qui volaient (...) mais voilà, c'était le contexte qui voulait ça.» (ADM-RW)

«Nous étions dans un rapport de force très difficile dans le gouvernement sur ce genre de questions. Ecolo avait obtenu en 2009 dans l'Accord du gouvernement beaucoup d'éléments en matière de développement durable, de climat, etc. Il y avait le Programme d'énergie renouvelable, la Stratégie de développement durable, le Décret climat et le Plan Air-Climat-Energie etc. Il y avait vraiment beaucoup d'éléments et ça nécessitait de prendre des mesures quand même assez ambitieuses de la part du Gouvernement et on peut dire que les autres parties du Gouvernement ont été un peu résistantes à ça pendant toute la durée la législature. Il avait une crainte infondé et démesurée de faire peur aux secteurs économiques et de mettre en difficulté certains secteurs économiques en étant trop orienté environnement, développement durable etc. Je pense qu'il y avait une difficulté pour eux à intégrer ce qui est notre conviction profonde, c'est-à-dire que la politique climatique est une opportunité d'orienter l'économie différemment, de redéployer d'autres économies, de créer de nouveaux emplois etc. (...) Ce n'est pas du tout surprenant que ça a été tendu en intercabinet – pas tellement par rapport à l'étude elle-même, mais probablement par rapport à ce qu'elle allait pouvoir déboucher après dans le Plan Air-Climat-Energie, parce que l'étude, elle n'implique aucune décision en fait.» (POL-RW)

The Greens mentioned the study in the Walloon Parliament, but it didn't generate a debate about the low-carbon transition. Climate mitigation was actually not considered a primary concern by most of the deputies. Only few deputies were interested in this issue.

«On en a parlé [au sein du Parlement], il y a une certaine publicité. Beaucoup, non, parce que c'est quand même pas un sujet qui est la préoccupation permanente et unique des parlementaires. Même si c'est un problème parce que encore aujourd'hui, ça reste vraiment très très urgent, très très élevé. Pas que l'enjeu en Wallonie, mais l'enjeu plus globalement au niveau mondial. C'est ce constat-là que je fais de manière générale. Quand on voit les élections françaises maintenant, le climat est totalement absent de la discussion. Les élections américaines, n'en parlons pas parce que là on va carrément dans le négationnisme scientifique. Donc voilà. C'est une très grande préoccupation. On la retrouve aussi au niveau du Parlement wallon. Il y a certains parlementaires qui sont attentifs et qui reviennent régulièrement, mais bon ce n'est pas l'obsession permanente de tous les parlementaires.» (POL-RW)

Note that the study was largely criticized by the MR who was in opposition. The liberal party accused Ecolo of carrying out too many studies, leading to unnecessary spending of public money. The Greens who wanted to base the design of environmental policy on scientific knowledge had indeed commissioned many studies during this legislature with a view *inter alia* to develop the Regional Space Development Scheme³⁶ (SDER), the Wind Plan and more generally the renewable energy development policy, as we will see later with the study "Towards a 100% renewable Belgium" that was commissioned by the Walloon Minister of Energy, Jean-Marc Nollet.

Shortly after the study was published, the 20th January 2012, AWAC, in collaboration with the cabinet of the Minister in charge of environment, organized a conference at the Aula Magna in Louvain-la-Neuve. The conference entitled "Let's draw today the low-carbon Wallonia of 2050" devoted one morning of reflection on the study. Following the intervention of Minister Henry and Prof. van Ypersele, who was at the time Vice-President of the IPCC, the study was presented by CLIMACT. These presentations were followed by a round table with civil society actors. At this conference, which welcomed 200 participants mainly from civil society, the study was rather well received. This was also the case when the study was presented and discussed in October 2012 at the Energy Commission of the CESW which brings together business and trade unions.

In contrast to the political authorities who strongly criticized the study, the civil society actors seemed to reflect favourable positions with regard to the CLIMACT analysis. By demonstrating that the transition to a low-carbon Wallonia was technically feasible, some stakeholders such as environmental or development NGOs and trade unions who had been advocating for the low-carbon transition for several years basing their argument on the need to drastically reduce GHG emissions could, for the

³⁶ Schéma de développement de l'espace régional (SDER)

first time, support their discourse with the argument of feasibility. Inter-environment Wallonia (IEW) had published on its website an article presenting the study and other organizations had disseminated it through their website or mailing list.

For their part, business federations had also welcomed the study, but for different reasons. In a context where the energy-climate policy was treated by two green ministers, Jean-Marc Nollet and Philippe Henry, the companies could fear that the study would be politically connoted, yet the fact that it was carried out by CLIMACT consultancy seemed to reassure them. With its portfolio of clients from the business world and its ability to work with private actors, it appears that CLIMACT was generally well perceived by the federations of companies.

«J'ai souvenir qu'on n'était pas si mécontent que ça de cette étude, pour différentes raisons, mais ça va vous paraître extrêmement subjectif. On était avec un ministre Ecolo qui avait en charge le climat, un ministre Ecolo qui avait en charge l'énergie et le développement des énergies renouvelables, et la manière dont le gouvernement était en train de gérer le développement des énergies renouvelables, l'explosion de la bulle Solwatt... Ça n'a pas été terrible, les années Nollet, pour ça (...) Donc, on avait un ministre Ecolo qui gérait ces matières et on a vu arriver sur le marché des consultants de CLIMACT qui était des gens qui avait un bon CV parce qu'ils avaient tous travaillé dans des gros bureaux de consultance, alors qu'on craignait de voir arriver des gens avec des gros pull de laine de mouton, donc une bande d'énergumènes écolo gaucho. Et, c'est vrai que quand on voit nos amis de CLIMACT, (...) il ne donne pas l'impression...alors qu'ils ont des convictions écolo, enfin pas écolo au sens politique, mais ils ont une conscience environnementale certaine. Je les connais bien et je ne peux pas douter de leur conscience environnementale. Et donc, ça a été plutôt rassurant (...) C'est comme leurs collègues de CO2logic, c'est le même type de personnage. Ce sont des gens qui ont des clients, qui travaillent pour l'industrie. Et donc, c'était plutôt bien ; moi, j'étais assez content de la dynamique qu'ils avaient faite.» (BUS-RW)

Besides the good reputation of CLIMACT, the involvement of a wide range of stakeholders had also helped to shape the positive perception those actors had of the study.

«Ils ont aussi une méthodologie assez professionnelle. Ils ont entendu beaucoup de monde, il y a eu beaucoup de groupes de travail, il y a eu beaucoup de dynamique. On n'a pas toujours le temps d'aller dans tous ces groupes de travail, mais tout le monde était là... La méthode aussi était bonne et je pense que la manière dont les stakeholders ont été associés n'était pas mal du tout. Ça c'était bien passé.» (BUS-RW)

Despite this generally positive reception, a number of criticisms were made about the study. These criticisms focused on the normative (no alternative scenario to low-carbon) and material (non-integration of economic and political dimensions) scopes, the hypothesis (too much or too little ambitious depending on actors' sensitivity) but also on the inherent limits in approaches to modelling the possible evolutions of complex systems. That said, such criticisms that arose mostly from civil society organizations didn't make a lot of noise.

3.1.4. Role of the Study in Policy-Making

Instrumental Role

The study "Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050" was used by AWAC to elaborate the first draft of the Air-Climate-Energy 2016-2022 Plan (see section "3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate mitigation Policy" of Chapter II). As mentioned earlier, the initial function of the study was to support the development of the post-2012 plan. By providing a detailed and comprehensive analysis of current and past GHG emissions by sector, AWAC members responsible for the development of the Air-Climate-Energy plan used the study to set the context of the plan. They also used the work of CLIMACT to define the GHG reduction measures proposed in the plan. In this context, it was mainly the modelling tool that had been used. The tool was actually used to assess the relative impact of different technical and behavioural levers on total GHG emissions. The measures to be implemented were then defined. However, there are very few traces of the study in the final version of the Air-Climate-Energy Plan published in 2016. Between the first draft proposed by AWAC and the final version, the plan was the subject of many debates which have lasted over two legislatures. The draft plan had to be reworked several times following many discussions in inter-cabinet meeting, several readings by the Government,

a notice from the advisory bodies and a public inquiry. Globally, the level of ambition of the measures of the first draft developed by AWAC had been lowered – the final version including a large number of existing measures.

«Je ne pense pas qu'il a été énormément utilisé pour le Plan Air-Climat-Energie, parce qu'on est resté à des mesures très terre-à-terre. (...) C'était la première occurrence du Plan Air-Climat-Energie, sachant que les émissions de gaz à effet de serre en Wallonie ont diminué quand même assez vite sans beaucoup de besoin d'intervention publique, vu qu'il y a eu une série de fermeture d'entreprises. Donc, ça n'a pas été à court terme une grande difficulté d'identifier des mesures.» (POL-RW)

It appears that the study hasn't been used by political authorities to devise low-carbon policy. Minister Henry, who originally instigated the study, hasn't used it as a basis for developing climate mitigation policies. He explained that in 2011 the development of such policies was premature. The climate mitigation governance had just started to emerge at the Walloon level, and he considered that a number of prerequisites had to be met before developing low-carbon pathway. As previously mentioned, one of the prerequisites was to convince other political actors that the low-carbon transition is feasible.

«On voulait l'utiliser pas tellement pour déterminer la trajectoire à 2050, parce que c'était complètement prématuré, il y a beaucoup de choses à faire avant et, de toute façon, il y a beaucoup trop d'inconnues.» (POL-RW)

Today, the transition towards a low-carbon society is considered as feasible by most of the actors, but it appears that the political authorities don't use the study to develop climate mitigation policy. One explanation put forward is that mitigating climate change is far from being a priority for political authorities.

«C'est pas du tout leur priorité. Ils n'ont pas remis en cause le Décret et le Plan Air-Climat-Energie, mais maintenant ils sont un peu à la traîne. Par exemple, sur le renouvelable ils ont reporté tous les objectifs de 2020 à 2030. Ils n'ont rien fait d'autre en matière renouvelable sauf un appel à projet pour une grosse centrale biomasse, ce qui me paraît une très mauvaise idée. Donc, il n'y a pas vraiment de dynamique enclenchée. Sur l'efficacité énergétique, ils ont essentiellement diminué les primes aux particuliers pour l'isolation des maisons. (...) Ils annoncent qu'ils vont faire un programme de soutien au prêt à taux zéro pour les bâtiments publics et le non-marchand en isolation des bâtiments. Mais voilà, c'est toujours pas fait. Ils ne sont pas du tout dans l'urgence. C'est pas du tout une priorité dans leur politique à eux. Je ne suis pas très objectif pour dire ça, mais comme je considère que la politique climatique n'est vraiment pas leur priorité, je pense que les scénarios de long terme non plus.» (POL-RW)

In the same vein, the discrepancy between the temporal scope of the study and the time horizon of political action is also mentioned.

«Vous avez vu comment les gouvernements fonctionnent? Avec des gens qui ont des échéances à 5 ans, maximum à 10 ans. Il n'y a pas un homme politique qui a des échéances à 10 ans. On ne va jamais mettre en place des politiques qui risquent de coûter cher, qui pourraient ne pas être populaire» (BUS-RW)

Another explanation for the implementation gap between low-carbon scenarios and policy concerns the share of competences between different entities that cannot agree on strategy to reduce GHG.

«Le gros problème en Wallonie, c'est que chacun tire la couverture à soi, les compétences sont dispersées et personne n'arrive à se mettre d'accord sur quelque chose. La Belgique est comme ça. C'est une mentalité décentralisée où chacun veut avoir ses petits avantages. Je pense qu'en France, tout n'est pas parfait, mais il y a une vision de l'intérêt collectif où on s'organise pour mettre en place des projets avec différents acteurs. La gouvernance, pour moi, c'est le point faible, ce qui empêche de mettre en place une stratégie bas-carbone.» (WU-RW)

Finally, the study published in 2011 is considered by some actors as outdated. The contextual background has evolved and some aspects of the study, such as developing CCS, are no longer relevant. Other actors have simply forgotten the study exists.

«Elle devient ancienne et les gens ne savent plus qu'elle existe» (PA-RW)

Conceptual Role

In comparison with the minor instrumental role, the study had great impact at the conceptual level. As this was the first scenario analysis of the low-carbon transition in Belgium, and also one of the first ones at the European level, the actors of the world of energy drew a number of lessons from this study, starting with the issues regarding the feasibility of the low-carbon transition. Thanks to the study, many actors have indeed become aware of the fact that the transition to a low-carbon Wallonia is technically and economically realistic.

«il y a 5 ans, dire on va réduire de 80% les émissions de GES par rapport à 1990, les gens te prennent pour des fous. Or aujourd'hui on démontre que c'est possible. C'est possible, mais pas facile.» (Author of the study)

They also realized that there is not only one path, but several possible avenues to achieve the GHG emission reduction target. In this sense, the study has led to a significant shift in stakeholders' perceptions of the low-carbon transition, moving from a vague and distant political goal to an achievable objective.

«Je ne pensais pas qu'il y allait avoir tant de scénarios en matière de climat qui allaient pouvoir être possibles et qu'on allait avoir le choix. J'aurais pensé qu'il n'y en avait qu'un qui était possible. Après, pour faire du moins de 95%, il y a très peu de variables potentielles, on est bien d'accord. Mais, on est bien d'accord que pour le moins 80-95%, il y a encore des possibilités. Donc, on n'est pas obligé de dire oui à la liste qui est là sans pouvoir un peu discuter. Il reste encore des variables politiques éventuelles. Et ça, je ne m'attendais pas à voir ça. Je m'attendais à ce qu'il y ait un seul chemin possible. E donc, ça c'est vraiment quelque chose qui m'avait un peu étonné. Ça je trouve que c'est très positif de voir ça, d'apprendre ça» (PA-BE)

If the study enabled the actors to realize that reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% in 2050 was a reachable target at the Walloon scale, it also enabled them to become aware of the extent of the efforts needed to ensure the low-carbon transition, but also of the urgency of the situation. The analysis of the scenarios shows that ambitious measures must be implemented as of now, which resulted in a change in the perception of some actors regarding the actions that need to be carried out.

«Elle m'a fait changer d'avis... pas changer d'avis, c'est plutôt un changement de la perception de l'urgence de la situation» (ENG-BE)

Moreover, the study enabled some actors to become aware of the technical issues inherent in the low-carbon transition, including challenges related to the intermittent nature of renewable energies, but also the importance to massively electrify the transport and residential sectors which implies the need to equip gas and coal power plants with CCS whatever the scenario envisaged.

«Je me rappelle qu'il y avait une chose qui m'avait frappé parce qu'on n'en parlait pas beaucoup à ce moment-là c'était l'intermittence, le fait que les renouvelable ne soient pas une source d'énergie continue... Maintenant, ça paraît un peu évident, mais je pense qu'à cette époque-là, pour moi, c'était un truc qui était ressorti, le fait qu'il faille gérer ça en fait. (...) c'est vrai que c'était le tout début. Il y avait des scénarios qui avaient été faits en Angleterre, en Europe, et la Wallonie était fort en avance. C'est vrai qu'on ne pensait peut-être pas à ça à l'époque.» (PA-RW)

«Ils prônaient beaucoup l'électrification du secteur du transport et du résidentiel. Ça, ça m'a surpris. Je ne m'attendais pas trop à ça, mais c'est vrai que maintenant, on y va de plus en plus, mais au moment où on l'a fait, pour moi, c'était quelque chose d'assez nouveau. (...) Ça a des implications importantes, parce que qui dit électrification, dit consommation d'électricité, et donc production d'électricité qui ré-augmente, alors qu'on ferme les centrales. Donc il faut la produire de façon verte, enfin plus verte en tout cas. Ou alors, mettre les dispositifs pour qu'il n'y ait plus... D'où la raison pour laquelle ils ont utilisé le CCS. Parce qu'il produisait plus d'électricité et qu'il fallait enlever le carbone qui était émis en trop dans l'atmosphère.» (ADM-RW)

«Il y avait un autre point qui était assez intéressant dans l'étude, c'était de montrer qu'à l'horizon 2050 pour aller entre 80 et 95%, on ne savait le faire qu'avec des techniques de stockage du CO₂, quels que soient les scénarios qui avaient été

retenus. Et ça, c'est un élément très intéressant parce qu'on se dit "Qu'est-ce qu'on fait? Est-ce qu'on s'engage vers le stockage?"» (BUS-RW)

These issues are now known and widely debated, but at the time, as the discussions on the low-carbon transition had just penetrated the political sphere and as there were very few foresight studies exploring technical innovations to implement to ensure this transition, the issues of intermittency and electrification were new for a number of actors. The study "low-carbon Wallonia" has thus highlighted a number of key questions and helped to increase the level of knowledge of energy stakeholders on these technical issues underlying the low-carbon transition.

More fundamentally, the study also enabled some actors to better understand the functioning of the Walloon energy system. By offering a systemic analysis of the interactions between the different sectors of energy production and consumption, and the GHG emissions associated with them, the study provided a better understanding of the Walloon energy balance to the actors who were not yet or barely familiar with these issues.

«[Ca m'a permis] de me rendre compte aussi de l'état des lieux, puisque je ne connaissais pas non plus très bien le bilan énergétique, donc ça m'a permis de rentrer dedans et de faire connaissance, enfin d'avoir une idée plus précise de l'impact de chaque secteur sur les émissions. On voit bien ainsi que c'est l'industrie le plus important (...) C'était une étude qui m'a appris beaucoup, puisque je ne connaissais pas grand-chose à ce niveau-là, mais là, c'est moi personnellement.» (ADM-RW)

Political Role

While the study was hardly used in a purely instrumental way to inform the design of public policies to reduce GHG emissions, it was used for more political purposes by different actors, starting with the Cabinet of Minister Henry who used the study to promote the development of a climate mitigation policy at the Walloon level.

«On voulait l'utiliser pour changer les références politique, se dire dans quel cadre on devait se mettre, et justifier que les objectifs étaient accessibles et qu'ils seraient accessibles de différentes façons. C'est pour ça que cette étude était très utile de ce point de vue-là, parce qu'elle était ouverte en permettant différents scénarios. (POL-RW)

In a context in which energy-climate policy emerged, partly at the instigation of Ecolo party who was in power, Minister Henry used the study to present to other political actors a coherent and positive vision of the Walloon mitigation policy.

«Moi je l'ai utilisée [ndlr. : l'étude] surtout pour présenter une vision positive, pour montrer la cohérence globale de la politique climatique qu'on avait voulu mettre en place. C'était novateur comme politique, on partait plus ou moins de rien. On avait les objectifs européens qui existaient, mais il n'était que pour 2020. Moi je suis arrivé en 2009, donc c'était quand même encore loin à ce moment-là, et dans la législature précédente, la politique climatique, ça n'existait pas. Il y avait les négociations internationales, mais au niveau wallon, il n'y en avait pas vraiment. Et donc, on a construit vraiment une nouvelle politique: Le Décret, le Plan, les scénarios. C'était une politique que je voulais présenter positivement, parce que je savais bien que le risque c'était que ce soit un repoussoir, que ça fasse peur, le retour à la bougie etc. (...) [L'étude s'inscrivait] dans une perspective de réalisation positive, mais sans qu'il y ait de réalisation immédiate difficile à assumer.» (POL-RW)

More specifically, the Minister also relied on the study to support the adoption in the Climate Decree of the objective of a 80-95% reduction in GHG by 2050 (see Gouvernement wallon, 2014). By showing that this goal was realistic from a technical and economical point of view, the study was indeed of great help for Minister Henry during the governmental debates that led to the adoption of the Climate Decree (see section "3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate mitigation Policy" of Chapter II).

«Le fait d'arriver à la conclusion que c'est tout à fait faisable et qu'il y a plusieurs scénarios possibles, ça pour moi, c'était vraiment un élément rassurant qui m'a aidé dans la défense des objectifs du système de Décret climat, du Plan Air-Climat-Energie, etc... qui n'ont d'ailleurs pas été contestés. Le Plan Air-Climat-Energie oui, mais le Décret et les objectifs à long terme, ils n'ont pas vraiment été contestés et encore aujourd'hui, ils sont d'application.» (POL-RW)

As it demonstrates that the low-carbon transition is feasible and requires to act as soon as possible, the study has been – and still is – used by a number of political actors who support this vision when defending their interests in dealing with other political actors. Environmental NGOs, trade unions, renewable energy actors and political-administrative authorities refer to the study to give credibility to their discourses in favour of ambitious mitigation policies.

«On les a utilisés dans le fait que ces scénarios indiquaient qu'il est possible. Ils tracent des chemins, donc ils montrent que c'est possible d'arriver entre -80 et -95% d'émission en 2050. C'est un objectif que nous on soutient, qui est aussi un objectif adopté à l'échelon européen. (...) Ça permet de crédibiliser ce discours-là. Il existe – ça c'est vraiment la première chose et sans doute une des plus fondamentales – des chemins; c'est possible techniquement et économiquement, mais aussi, il y aura beaucoup de détails opérationnels à préciser pour y arriver, mais il y a des chemins qui existent. Ces scénarios impliquent de maintenant prendre des décisions qui vont vers le long terme, et donc il y a une responsabilité politique à pouvoir un peu sortir d'une vision uniquement sur la législature et se projeter dans le long terme...» (NGO-RW)

In addition to communications with other stakeholders or political-administrative authorities, the study is also used by some people to convince their hierarchical superiors, their colleagues or the affiliate members of their organization that the low-carbon transition is technically and economically realistic. These are persons working for trade unions or "traditional" political parties who want to convince internally of the need to engage in a low-carbon transition pathway. These structures, subject to the weight of the past, often have a fringe that is resistant to environmental policies, and members who intend to change the position of their organization in relation to these questions refer among other to the CLIMACT analysis when facing those resistances.

«On doit convaincre à l'intérieur et ces études-là elles sont super importantes parce que d'une part, elles montrent que les choses sont possibles, elles vont en profondeur et d'autre part, elles sont un peu au-dessus de la mêlée, je dirais. Donc là, je parle en interne, mais à l'externe, ça joue aussi très fort.» (PA-RW)

These same actors who support a low-carbon vision also refer to the study to challenge decision-makers by showing them that the actions they are currently implementing are not in line with the GHG emission reduction pathways outlined in the study.

«Et donc en général, c'est plutôt pour dire "vous êtes bien mignons avec vos études, mais les décisions que vous prenez ne vont pas dans ce sens-là" et donc, c'est plutôt de faire la démonstration de pourquoi est-ce que les choix qui sont posés aujourd'hui ne permettent pas de le réaliser et d'essayer de développer du coup des alternatives et des choix qui permettraient de le faire.» (PA-RW)

Besides, members of the administration sometimes refer to the study during discussions with stakeholders who have participated in the scenario workshops. In these discussions, they support the argument that by participating in the study, these stakeholders have adhered to the goal of reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% in 2050.

«Vous vous en servez comme référence, pour évoquer l'adhésion des stakeholders (...) Donc on capte sur les adhésions en disant "attendez, vous avez bien participé à cette étude, et donc, nous avons bien convenu d'être arrivés là à ce stade". Pour moi, c'est le plus important. (ADM-RW)

Apart from the main conclusion of the study (i.e.: the feasibility of the low-carbon transition), a number of persons working for NGOs, trade unions, business federations, energy market operators or political parties extract very specific elements from the study to support their discourse. In most cases, they include precise numerical data or graph in written or oral communications addressed to other stakeholders or public institutions.

«Quand on a besoin d'un chiffre, on va voir dans l'étude. Mais voilà, vraiment analyser les différents scénarios, pour nous, compte tenu de notre charge de travail, c'est difficile.» (WU-RW)

«Dans les contacts politiques, c'est des études sur lesquelles on s'appuie (...) Il y a un graphique qui a beaucoup été utilisé, on voit les différents secteurs... Parce que ce genre de graph, ça fait se dire "waouh, ça va changer beaucoup, on n'est pas dans le statu quo, on est dans une mutation vraiment importante de la société, de différentes activités". Si moi, je suis actif

dans ce secteur-là, dans l'agriculture ou dans les transports, je ne vais pas me dire que les autres vont faire l'effort... En fait, tout le monde doit faire des efforts importants.» (NGO-RW)

Process Role

As mentioned in the presentation of the method, the scenario building process mobilized a large number of experts from public and private sphere. This consultative process seems to have had some influence on the policy-making process. Firstly, the consultation of a large number of stakeholders showed that there was a potential to mobilize the civil society in favour of the low-carbon transition. Benefiting from stakeholders' support was particularly crucial at a time when public action on climate change mitigation was taking place. The study has thus contributed to create a momentum with civil society in favour of the low-carbon transition.

«Pour moi, cette étude, plus que de démontrer la faisabilité, elle a démontré qu'il y a une mobilisation potentielle. (...) Une étude comme celle-là, pour moi elle a été basculante. Elle a permis effectivement de convaincre de cette nécessité un minimum de stakeholders, mais pas le stakeholder déjà convaincu, les stakeholders plus réticents au changement. Alors ce n'est pas que ça évidemment. À un moment, il faut prendre le contexte plus large de l'ensemble de l'influence que peuvent avoir la question du changement climatique et de la transition énergétique, mais on y a contribué. Et donc, on a mis notre pierre à l'édifice et on a pu, je trouve, assister à ce changement à ce moment-là. Qui a permis de créer, de renforcer en tout cas le bon état d'esprit belge au niveau des stakeholders. Et donc finalement, préparer ce qui a pu être la réponse de la Belgique à l'Accord de Paris et donc, d'apprécier son acceptabilité. Et donc ça, pour moi, c'est plus important que de voir les voies du possible. Après, il y a eu l'étude fédérale qui s'est fortement basée sur la même méthode, puisque c'est les mêmes acteurs qui l'ont conçue. C'est un peu le même truc, quoi. C'est-à-dire que ça et ça, on a réussi à mobiliser des acteurs derrière» (ADM-RW)

According to some persons I interviewed, the consultations fostered the dialogue between different stakeholders.

«B. C'est toujours intéressant d'être avec d'autres stakeholders qui ne partagent pas nécessairement notre vision.

A. Vous pensez que ce genre de consultation favorise le dialogue?

B. Oui-oui, parce que le fait qu'on soit tous amenés à réfléchir sur quelques questions qui nous sont posées, même si on n'a pas forcément le même intérêt... oui-oui, ça facilite le dialogue.

A. Vous pensez que vous compreniez mieux le point de vue des autres suite à ce genre d'exercice?

B. Oui, ça aide en tout cas.» (NGO-RW)

That said, several people I met also point out the limits of the participative approach developed by Climact in fostering the dialogue. The first limitation was related to the fact that in most consultations – and not only those organized as part of this study – it was always the same actors who come with the same well-honed speech. Each one presented his institutional discourse, leaving little room for the emergence of a real discussion.

«Quand tu rentres dans ce genre de lutte d'intérêts, t'es pas forcément prêt à faire un pas vers l'autre, à remettre en question le discours que tu as lissé pendant des mois et des mois et que tu as juste envie de te battre pour dire qui tu es. Un peu comme un politicien. On a peut-être raté un moment au départ où tu vois que les gens étaient plus consensuels, plus dans la volonté de comprendre le métier de l'autre. (...) En tout cas, moi je suis venu trois fois. En trois fois, c'était juste de ne pas se faire piéger. Tu regardes la methodo, tu regardes si tes chiffres sont corrects par rapport à ceux qu'ils utilisent. C'est tout. Tu as prévu un ou deux messages clés pour ta réunion. Si tu as un dialogue en plus, tant mieux, mais c'est pas du tout gagné. Et là, on n'a pas fort dépassé... moi, je me suis évertué à essayer d'appuyer la démarche de mes autres collègues régulateurs, en disant, si au moins, entre régulateurs des trois régions, on peut afficher une cohérence, je trouvais que c'était un beau message pour le secteur privé et les GRD.» (ENG-RW)

«On va là parce qu'on est invité et qu'on doit y aller, et que malgré tout, c'est intéressant. Mais ça ne développe pas vraiment le dialogue. (...) On arrive, on a un programme. Et donc, on écoute les exposés, on participe au groupe de travail qui sont organisées par le consultant et chacun arrive avec son discours habituel qui est son discours institutionnel.» (WU-RW)

The second limit pointed by some workshop participants was that we often hear more the voice of those who say “no”. This is true in the consultations, where participants who are against are going to be more vocal than others, but also in the discussions to prepare the position of the organization within inter-professional organizations such as FEB, UWE or trade unions. As a result, these important actors supported most often a conservative position on environmental policies that was not representative of the sensitivity of all the members.

«C'est la limite quelque part de toutes ces consultations. On entend surtout ceux qui disent non. Mais même au sein de Fédérations interprofessionnelles comme la FEB ou comme l'UWE, ou comme le VOKA, c'est surtout la voix des gens qui sont contre qu'on va entendre. Et donc, on a sans doute un discours assez conservateur, alors que peut-être il y a des entreprises qui justement font leur mue et qui s'inscrivent dans ce changement-là, et pour qui les idées climatiques et de développement durable sont surtout des challenges et l'occasion de développer de nouveaux produits, d'apporter des solutions technologiques nouvelles. Il y en a encore beaucoup qui n'ont pas fait ce chemin, peut-être parce que c'est pas possible, peut-être parce qu'ils n'ont pas encore eu l'idée, mais c'est ceux-là qu'on entend surtout.» (BUS-RW)

Another impact of the consultation process connected to the fact that the study took place in a context in which climate governance was emerging has been that it incited some new actors to structure themselves and to define their position. During the workshops, the actors in the renewable energy sector found themselves facing actors such as business federations, trade unions and energy market operators who defended a well-honed speech. Those confrontations encouraged the actors of the renewable energy sector to gather together and to develop an effective external communication strategy in order to make their voice heard.

«Ca structure les intérêts. Typiquement, après ça, ou peut-être à la même période, les producteurs renouvelables se sont rendus compte qu'ils devaient se structurer de manière un peu plus costaud, qu'ils devaient adopter une stratégie de communication vers l'extérieur, qu'ils devaient constituer une espèce de groupe homogène avec un intérêt bien compris qui puisse balancer des recommandations avant les élections, qui puisse aller faire du lobby. Ils se rendaient compte de ça parce qu'en face il y avait les GRD, le réseau (...) Ce que je veux dire, c'est déjà un microcosme très serré. Alors qu'en face, les renouvelables, c'était nouveau. Donc eux, se sont formés au fur et à mesure. (...) C'est là que j'ai vraiment vu le discours évoluer, notamment d'Edora.» (ENG-RW)

Finally, at a more individual level, the consultation process enabled some persons to acquire new knowledge on the operation of the energy system.

«Pour moi, c'est intéressant les groupe de travail auxquels j'ai participé, parce que, je ne suis pas une spécialiste, je ne suis pas ingénieur réseau, parce qu'on ne connaît pas non plus toutes les contraintes techniques liés à des changement de technologie. Pour moi, c'est intéressant d'apprendre certaines choses, au niveau des réseaux notamment.» (NGO-RW)

3.1.5. Key Lessons

The last section aims at summarizing the key lessons that emerge from the analysis. For each foresight study analysed, I have built two radar charts. The first chart shows the role of the study in policy-making [Figures 63, 67, 71 and 76] and the second one the level of appropriation per actor for the study [Figures 64, 68, 72 and 77]. It is by no means an attempt to quantify the impact of the study. The aim of such graphs is to display in a clear and structured way the main features of each case study. The radar chart display will also be helpful to compare the four case studies in the next section (see Section “4. Cross-case analysis” of the same chapter). Still with a view to providing an overview of the principal findings, I have sketched timelines illustrating the history of each study [Figures 65, 69, 73 and 78].

The intended function of the study “Low-carbon Wallonia” was quite ambivalent. The official function of the study – which materialized in the bill of specification – was to inform policy-makers in the development of a low-carbon strategy for Wallonia (i.e.: Air-Climate-Energy Plan). The study also had a more political objective. Minister Henry wanted a robust and independent study demonstrating that the objective of reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050 is realistic with a view to convincing other members of the Government to include this objective in the Climate Decree. While the later function

has been successfully performed, the function of informing the design of the Walloon low-carbon roadmap has been barely fulfilled.

Figure 63. Role of the study “Low-carbon Wallonia” in policy-making. Each axis corresponds to a type of role. The centre of the chart equates to a minor role and the extremity to an important role.

Inasmuch as it was used by AWAC to develop the first draft of the Air-Climate-Energy 2016-2022 Plan, the study “low-carbon Wallonia” has an instrumental role. This role is however quite limited. The first draft proposed by AWAC on the basis of the study had actually been substantially amended after long political negotiations. Such negotiations resulted in a far less ambitious plan (see section “3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate mitigation Policy” of Chapter II). The study hasn’t been used by political authorities to devise low-carbon policy. Minister Henry, who originally instigated the study, hasn’t used it as a basis for developing a low-carbon roadmap stating that in 2011 the development of such strategy was premature. Today, the non-use of the “low-carbon Wallonia” study by political actors appears to be mainly related to the very nature of both climate mitigation issue and foresight. While climate mitigation is not seen as a priority issue by many political authorities, the temporal scope of foresight doesn’t match with the time horizon of political action.

The study has however an important political role. Because it demonstrates that reducing domestic GHG emissions by 80-95% in 2050 is feasible and that it requires the implementation of ambitious policy as of now, the study was – and still is – used by several political actors in favour of the low-carbon transition to endorse their discourse. Minister Henry relied on the study to support the adoption within the Climate Decree of the objective of 80-95% reduction in GHG by 2050. Such decree is a corner stone of the Walloon climate mitigation policy (see section “3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate mitigation Policy” of Chapter II). Moreover, various actors – mainly environmental NGOs, trade unions, renewable energy actors and political-administrative authorities – refer to the study to give credibility to their discourses in favour of ambitious mitigation policies.

The study also has a conceptual role. As this was the first scenario analysis of the low-carbon transition in Belgium, but also one of the first at the European level, the actors of the world of energy drew a number of lessons from this study. It concerns the feasibility of the low-carbon transition, the existence of several pathways to achieve the GHG emission reduction target, the extent of the efforts needed to ensure such transition, the urgency of the situation, the technical challenges associated with the low-carbon transition, and the functioning of the Walloon energy system.

By mobilizing a large number of actors for the scenario analysis, the study has had a process role. Inasmuch as it was the first participatory process that gathered so many various actors to discuss the long-term mitigation policy in Wallonia, it showed that there is a potential to mobilize the civil society in favour of the low-carbon transition. In addition, by confronting them with incumbents, the

consultations incited emerging actors (i.e.: renewable energy actors) to structure themselves and define their position. The consultative process also fostered, to a certain extent, the dialogue between different stakeholders.

When looking at the analysis per actor [Figure 64], we observe, not unexpectedly, a high level of appropriation for the actors who were behind the study – i.e.: The Greens and AWAC. The other administrations as well as the employer’s federations, the workers unions, the NGO’s and the energy market have moderately appropriated themselves the study. Most of them know the existence of the study and its main conclusions. Apart from a few persons who have some knowledge of the study, the advisors of the traditional political parties have very limited or no knowledge of the analysis performed by CLIMACT. Finally, the level of appropriation of political authorities from traditional party seems to be virtually nil. Because it was commissioned by a Green Minister at a time where all the initiatives of the Green Party were torpedoed by the other majority parties, the study was strongly criticized – more on the form than on the substance – by members of other political parties and did not penetrate the political sphere.

Figure 64. Level of appropriation per actor for the study “Low-carbon Wallonia”. Each axis corresponds to a type of actor. The centre of the chart equates to a low level of appropriation and the extremity to a high level of appropriation.

Figure 65. Timeline illustrating the history of the study "Low-carbon Wallonia"

3.2. Case Study n°2. Scenarios for a Low-Carbon Belgium by 2050

3.2.1. Emergence

The study "Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium" follows the study "Low-carbon Wallonia". After having participated in the elaboration of the study for Wallonia as a member of the support committee, an expert in climate policy within the Climate Change Department of the Federal Public Service (FPS) Environment, wished to carry out the same analysis at the level of Belgium. He was indeed seduced by the approach developed by CLIMACT because it allows to quantify, but also to think out of the box.

«J'avais entendu parler du travail qui avait été finalisé en 2012 par la Région Wallonne. (...) J'ai trouvé cette démarche particulièrement appropriée par rapport à l'exercice qu'on voulait faire nous au niveau de l'administration publique et qui avait comme caractéristique que d'une part c'était suffisamment quantifié (...) qu'on avait la possibilité d'analyser les choses de manière quantitative, ce qui me semblait assez indispensable pour la matière qui est traitée – je ne dis pas qu'il faut nécessairement le faire, non pas pour tout, mais pour la matière qui est traitée, je trouvais ça assez important –; et d'un autre côté, d'avoir un outil qui était suffisamment flexible et ouvert que pour pouvoir "think out of the box", c'est vraiment élargir les possibilités en étant également conscients des limites de l'analyse économique et en particulier des modèles calculables.» (ADM-BE)

Unlike the Walloon study which had been commissioned by an administration at the request of a ministerial cabinet, the Belgian study was thus ordered on the administration's own initiative.

«Ce n'est pas quelque chose qui est directement demandé par le politique ou par les élus politiques. En tout cas c'est nous qui nous disons qu'on voit bien qu'à ces réflexions il y a un manque, c'est nous qui devons avoir ces discussions au niveau des scénarios, de voir à quoi ça va ressembler et à quantifier les choses. Il y a ce manque et on y va, et on le fait, et voilà, on a initié des choses.» (ADM-BE)

The objective pursued by the Federal Climate Service in developing such an approach was also a bit different than the objective pursued by AWAC in building the low-carbon scenarios for Wallonia. While the AWAC study was result-oriented, for the FPS Climate Change, the scenario building process was as important as the results of the study. With this study, the federal administration wanted to develop a transition management approach. They drew inspiration from this mode of governance that emerged in the Netherlands and that aims to facilitate sustainable transition by setting up a participatory process involving different societal actors (see Boulanger, 2008). The objective of the study was therefore to develop a process of learning and dialogue with the Belgian stakeholders. This is why, in comparison with the Walloon study, the participatory dimension has been reinforced, as we will see in the description of the methodology.

«Le processus comptait autant que le contenu et le résultat. On était inspiré par ce concept de gestion de la transition dans l'esprit d'essayer de faire parler les acteurs, mais en s'assurant qu'on ait un échantillon d'acteurs qui ont des avis et des expertises disons contrastées pour pouvoir refléter un peu différents équilibres. (...) [la gestion de la transition], c'est vraiment ce qui nous anime clairement. (...) On se rend bien compte que pour discuter de manière intelligente de la question des changements climatiques et de la réduction des émissions, il faut le faire dans le long terme (ADM-BE)

«I think that was mainly interesting for the federal public service also to assemble the most important stakeholders in the low-carbon transition around this study to discuss with them» (Author of the study)

Another difference with the study "Low-carbon Wallonia" is that, still in this perspective of developing a transition management approach, the study "Low-carbon Belgium" is part of broader project aiming to develop a continued reflection with the stakeholders around the transition to a low-carbon Belgium by 2050. As we will see later, the study was followed by other initiatives undertaken by the Federal Climate Service, including the webtool My2050, the macro-economic study and the national debate on carbon pricing. All these initiatives form the "Project 2050".

«Ici, on a essayé de cadrer autour d'une multitude de projets en 2050. Ca, c'est un peu la différence avec l'étude Wallonie bas-carbone.» (ADM-BE)

Finally, while an analysis of the measures to be implemented in the short, the medium and the long term was part of AWAC's specifications, the Federal Climate Service didn't want to address the issue of public policies at this stage.

«[Il ne s'agissait pas d'être] trop précis sur les politiques qui pourraient faire en sorte que ces leviers atteignent les niveaux 3 ou 4 selon les scénarios. Donc voilà on dit la mobilité va diminuer, mais pas à quoi c'est dû. Je ne veux pas rentrer dans cette discussion-là maintenant, c'est trop tôt. D'abord regardons les quantités et puis on pourra regarder comment ça se met en place. Parce que là il y a tous les intérêts, on se cabre, et donc il faut être un peu dans ce flou au départ pour permettre la réflexion avec les acteurs.» (ADM-BE)

The Federal Climate Service launched the request for proposals in 2012. Following the tender, it was CLIMACT again, but this time in collaboration with VITO, which has won the bid.

3.2.2. Presentation of the Study

Methodology

The approach used to construct and analyse the scenarios has been the same as that the one used by CLIMACT in the "Low-carbon Wallonia" study (see "Section 3.1.2. Presentation of the study" of the same chapter). The model OPE²RA and its assumptions were adapted at the Belgian level. Again, a considerable number of experts from the administration, the ministerial cabinets, the industry, the civil society, and the universities were consulted. Since the aim of the study was to develop a dynamic of learning and dialogue with the stakeholders through the consultations, the participatory approach was strengthened in comparison with the Walloon study. With more than 120 people consulted, the number of participants was larger. Several actors who had not been consulted in the context of the Walloon study participated in the Belgian study. This is particularly the case for the refinery sector. The study also gave rise to more interactions with the stakeholders. In addition to the about twenty workshops, several bilateral meetings and discussions with the stakeholders were held. Moreover, the preliminary results of the study were presented and discussed on the 20 November 2012 at the Annual Forum of CFDD that gathered many different political actors. Finally, compared to AWAC, the Federal Climate Service was more involved in the consultations. For instance, the administration sent the invitation emails itself and most often participated in the consultation process.

«On a encore accentué ce côté-là [ndlr.: l'aspect consultatif]: plein de workshop, des discussions, des rencontres informelles pour équilibrer les choses. Et donc, ça on l'a vraiment utilisé comme instrument de dialogue. Ça, c'était très poussé. (...) Un exemple: tous ces workshops c'est nous qui envoyions un mail d'invitation aux acteurs avec nos signatures. On marquait l'importance politique des choses. Là-bas [ndlr.: Wallonie bas-carbone], c'était plus les consultants qui avaient leur réseau et qui organisaient ça. Donc ici on essaye de faire peut-être davantage pénétrer les travaux dans le processus politique» (ADM-BE)

It is interesting to note that some consultations were difficult in the sense that federations of companies, including the Petroleum Federation, strongly questioned the assumptions of the study and lobbied the authors and the sponsors to influence the scenario building process. The sometimes-stubborn defence of the interests of certain sectors during the scenario building process represented a difficulty in which CLIMACT, VITO and the FPS Climate change have had to face which was not or at least much less present when carrying out the study "Low-carbon Wallonia".

« Il y a eu à différents moments dans le projet des lobbys virils de la part de la fédération des raffineries. La Fédération du pétrole est allé voir [les auteurs de l'étude], a essayé de les influencer. Ils ont estimé qu'ils n'avaient pas été suffisamment attentifs à leur sensibilité. La Fédération du pétrole n'étant pas satisfaite au niveau des coûts du pétrole et a reflété ça au niveau de la FEB.»

«Certaines consultations ont été difficiles. Quand les résultats ont été présentés à la FEB, ça, ça a été très difficile. (...) Beaucoup de questions, pas toutes constructives. Beaucoup de défenses d'intérêts particuliers aussi.»

The analysis resulted to the development of five low-carbon scenarios [Figure 66]. Of these scenarios, three led to an emission reduction of around 80% by 2050: "Behaviour and Societal Organization", "Core" and "Technology" scenarios. As their names suggest, the "Behaviour and societal organization" scenario achieves a reduction in GHG emissions based largely on social innovations (i.e.: levers for reducing transport demand, meat consumption (...) pushed to the maximum level), while the "Technology" scenario is based on technological innovations (i.e.: levers for electrification, improvement of energy efficiency (...) pushed to the maximum level). The core scenario is halfway between "Behaviour" and "Technology" insofar as it involves both social and technological innovations – the levels of ambition for all the parameters being set at an intermediate level (+/- 3 on a scale of 1 to 4). A fourth scenario results in a 95% reduction in GHG emissions by applying the maximum level of ambition for all parameters. The fifth scenario is entitled "EU integration". It includes a massive deployment of intermittent renewable energies supported by the development of an integrated European grid, increased imports of electricity and the construction of back-up plants. This scenario, which is more focused on energy production, reduces GHG emissions by 87% in 2050. Finally, the business as usual scenario leads to a 15% reduction in emissions by 2050.

Figure 66. Scenarios developed in the study "Low-carbon Belgium" (CLIMACT & VITO 2013, p. 44)

Results

The results of the "low-carbon Belgium" study are quite similar to those of the study conducted for Wallonia (see section "3.1.2. Presentation of the study" of the same chapter). The scenario analysis shows that the low-carbon transition is technically feasible at the national scale and that there are several ways to reduce domestic GHG by 80-95% in 2050. Such transition constitutes however a major challenge that requires efforts from every sector.

Diminishing the GHG by at least 80% in 2050 requires, among others, a reduction of the demand for mobility, an electrification of transport and heat facilities, a massive renovation of buildings, an improvement of energy efficiency in industries, a reduction of meat consumption, and, more globally, a decrease in energy demand in every sector through behavioural changes and social innovations. On the production side, the share of electricity in the energy mix is required to increase substantially. The electricity sector should decarbonize almost in its entirety by resorting to renewable sources – intermittent (i.e.: solar and wind) or not (i.e.: geotherm and sustainable biomass). The CCS is seen as an option to reduce the GHG of power stations and industries, but the authors are showing caution because of the concerns regarding the feasibility and the risks of carbon leakages associated with this technology. Compared to the "Low-carbon Wallonia study" that applies the CCS in all the low-carbon scenarios, the "Low-carbon Belgium" shows that a low-carbon transition is possible with no CCS. The "Behaviour" scenario actually leads to a reduction of GHG by 80% without having to resort to CCS. Finally, a development of interconnected energy networks and energy demand management measures are required to deal with the increase in intermittent renewable energy.

The authors highlight the opportunity offered by the low-carbon transition such as the implementation of “no regrets” measures – i.e.: renovating buildings, improving energy efficiency or developing energy infrastructures.

Finally, from an economic point of view, the study shows that the low-carbon scenarios involve costs in the same order of the business as usual scenario. The low-carbon transition requires additional investments, but they are balanced by reduced expenditures in fuel.

3.2.3. Communication, Follow-Up and Reception

The final report was published in November 2013. Like the Walloon study, the report was accompanied by an executive summary and the model has been made available online.

The study was presented to the cabinet of the Federal Secretary of state in charge of Energy, Melchior Wathelet (cdH) who, although he had not initiated the study, had monitored progress on the project. He welcomed the conclusions of the analysis with a lot of interest and enthusiasm, and he has strongly appropriated himself the scenarios and the web tool.

«Il a vraiment adoré l’outil, le concept et donc il s’est lancé dedans. Il a été un très bon ambassadeur de ces travaux. On avait fait un scénario central et je l’entends encore dire “et vous imaginez bien en tant que Cdh, c’est le scénario central que je préfère”. Il y a une forme d’appropriation. (...) Il faisait référence [à l’étude] très régulièrement dans ses speeches, dans ses réflexions, dans ses allocutions par rapport aux questions climat et énergie» (ADM-BE)

«Ca, il aimait bien. Il aimait bien parce que c’est très concret, et puis, ce qui en a découlé, c’est-à-dire le tool, ça permettait vraiment alors au consommateur de s’approprier les scénarios, de les calibrer selon la sensibilité de tout un chacun.» (PA-BE)

On 6 November 2013, Minister Wathelet, members of the Federal Climate Service and the authors of the study presented the project to a press conference organized at the Brussels School of Journalism and Communication (IHECS). The information was published in various newspapers both in the South (RTBF, La Libre and L’Echo) and in the North (De Redactie, and Vilt) of the country. A number of environmental and development NGOs, trade unions and renewable energy actors have also relayed the results of the study via their website or newsletter.

Shortly thereafter, the 26 November 2013, again in the presence of the Federal Secretary of state in charge of Energy, the study was presented to the Annual Forum of CFDD. For two consecutive years, the federal advisory body has devoted its annual forum to the study – the preliminary results having been presented at the 2012 edition, as stated before. In addition to this huge meeting, which brings together each year a lot of stakeholders and which gave lots of visibility to the CLIMACT and VITO analysis, the study was presented on multiple other occasions by members of the Federal Climate Service. They have presented it to organizations such as FEB and IEW, but also at various events related to the mitigation policy, both at Belgian and international levels. For example, the study was presented during a side event at COP 19 in Warsaw to show the actions taken by Belgium to reduce GHG emissions. During these numerous presentations, the Federal Climate Service has widely disseminated the executive summary set up in brochure form available in French, Dutch and English.

«Nos clients font beaucoup aussi. Vincent van Steenberghe (Service fédéral Climat) en particulier a beaucoup travaillé avec son équipe pour que les résultats soient visibles. (...) Il est capable de répondre à toutes les questions, il connaît vraiment bien le sujet, et il est très convaincant et très juste.» (Author of the study)

The reception of civil society was rather mixed when presenting the results of the study. The study of the Federal Climate Service has generated a lot of negative criticism and opposition from federations of companies and dominant energy market operators. During the presentations, members of organizations such as FEB or the federations of petroleum and chemical brought a series of arguments aimed at discrediting the study.

«Il y a eu de la pression dans tous les forums, dans toutes les présentations. La fédération du pétrole a interpellé les auteurs de l'étude, et ce sont des gens qui sont intelligents, qui ont des moyens. Donc ils ne font pas de remarques... Ils sont toujours bien argumentés. Il y a une forme de questionnement et à partir de là on essaie de discréditer l'étude.»

«J'ai vu le porte-parole de la Fédération pétrolière, il a pratiquement enguirlandé l'administration et le bureau d'étude en disant que c'était totalement irresponsable de faire des scénarios qui ne prennent pas en compte le fait que ça va avoir des répercussions extrêmement négatives sur le secteur de la pétrochimie anversoise. Et donc, eux sont proches des fédérations Essencia, qui sont des grosses fédérations industrielles qui ont des procédés qui reposent largement sur les énergies fossiles aujourd'hui. Et donc, ils voient ça d'un mauvais œil.» (NGO-RW)

The well-constructed arguments of these lobbies related to different points that are summarized in a note developed by FEB. On 17 February 2014, FEB sent the Secretary of state a note setting out its position on the study. The FEB's two main criticisms of the "low-carbon Belgium" study concerned the failure to take into account the economic reality – and particularly the question of competitiveness –, and the poor analysis of the aspects related to the security of supply. The companies advocated a rebalancing of the objectives pursued in climate-energy policy involving integration of industrial objectives, competitiveness and security of supply alongside environmental objectives. Another important criticism concerned the geographical scope of the study. FEB considered that a reflection on the evolution of technologies should be framed in a larger context taking into account the European and global frameworks in order to optimize efforts and ensure an international level playing field. Furthermore, some technological choices of the study were criticized. This included the decision to phase out nuclear power in 2025. Since nuclear could help to ensure security of supply while reducing GHG emissions, the companies stated that this technology should be considered as an option in low-carbon scenarios. The important role of CCS in low-carbon scenarios was also seen as a weak point of the study. The realism of the implementation of this technology was indeed questioned. Finally, after highlighting a series of limitations of the economic analysis carried out as part of the study (e.g.: uncertainties about the long-term evolution of costs and prices, level of ambition of the reference scenario, discount rate, impact of shale gas on fuel prices), the note defended the idea that the conclusions drawn from the comparison of the costs of different scenarios are not valid (FEB, 2014).

The objective with such a note was to qualify the main study's conclusion that the low-carbon transition was feasible. The private actors had concerns regarding the way such conclusion would be communicated in the media and the lessons that political authorities would draw when hearing it.

«Après, je crois que les gens s'emballent un peu sur ce genre de modèle. Ça reste des modèles, c'est des scénarios. Il y a quatre scénarios, je crois... Il y a un moment, la grosse crainte, c'était au niveau de la com', qu'est-ce que les médias vont en faire et comment vont réagir les politiques. C'est surtout ça en fait. Parce que finalement, sur la façon dont s'est modélisé, aussi bien les ONG que les fédérations sectorielles savaient bien qu'il y a des hypothèses là-dedans qui vont mener sur un résultat. Mais le gros souci, c'est quelle communication on va faire? Comment est-ce qu'il va être présenté dans la presse et qu'est-ce qui va être retiré après, par les différents partis, ou un ministre, au régional ou au fédéral.» (BUS-BE)

«Le politique, il ouvre l'étude, il va directement à la conclusion et qu'est-ce qu'il lit? "Oui, c'est possible d'atteindre - 80% de réduction pour le secteur industriel", sans autre nuances.» (BUS-BE)

It may seem surprising that this study has led to such major oppositions from business world, while the Walloon study – which is based on the same approach and which leads to almost the same conclusions – has elicited few negative reactions from incumbents. Several factors can explain this difference, starting with the configuration of the Belgian industrial sector. With a larger number of big companies located on its territory, the industrial sector is of greater importance in Flanders than in Wallonia. Refineries and most of the Belgian chemical industries are located in Antwerp, which is a world-class petrochemical cluster. This is why, during federal discussions on energy-climate issues, Flemish industrial lobbies are generally much more reactive and vocal than Walloon organizations.

«C'est entre nous, mais l'industrie flamande est beaucoup plus importante que l'industrie wallonne. Alors est-ce que quand les Flamands ont reçu ça [ndlr.: Étude Belgique bas-carbone] sur leur assiette, est-ce qu'ils ont eu plus peur, ou est-ce qu'ils

ont plus réagi, ils ont plus critiqué. C'est ça, beaucoup plus de critiques, mais qui c'est qui la critique? (...) le secteur industriel pèse plus lourd. Ce sont des entreprises beaucoup plus grandes. Tout le secteur chimique... Quand on voit des réunions, des réactions au niveau fédéral, l'industrie flamande et généralement quand même beaucoup plus présente et plus active. Donc probablement qu'ils ne connaissent pas celle-là [ndlr.: Étude Wallonie bas-carbone] (...) Peut-être que les critiques s'appliquent aux deux, mais qu'ils ne connaissent que celle-là [ndlr.: Étude Belgique bas-carbone].» (BUS-BE)

These oppositions to the study could also be explained by the way in which the comments of the stakeholders who participated in the consultations were addressed by the consultants. While the final report of the Walloon study includes a section presenting the main remarks of the stakeholders and the CLIMACT's responses to these comments, the stakeholders' feedbacks does not appear anywhere in the Belgian study. Several members of business federations that have been involved in the development of the low-carbon scenarios for Belgium are frustrated because they feel they have not been listened to.

«On en a beaucoup parlé notamment au sein de la FEB. [L'étude] a provoqué dans plusieurs Fédération pas mal d'émoi. On s'est dit que c'est quand même important pour le futur de nos secteurs et on n'a pas l'impression qu'on a été écouté. (...) [Un membre] du SPF environnement, est venu présenter l'étude. Je pense que c'était en présence de CLIMACT. Là, ils sont venus présenter le final report. Il y a eu beaucoup de réactions venant de la salle, en disant "on vous a donné du feedback, manifestation, vous n'avez pas pris en compte dans l'étude telle que présentée"» (ENG-BE)

«Aujourd'hui on a deux ou trois fédérations qui nous disent "on a participé à ça, et l'impression qu'on a c'est qu'on a un peu parlé dans le vide, qu'on n'en a pas tenu compte". Alors, moi je trouve que leur rôle peut être de ne pas tenir compte, mais je trouve qu'ils devraient s'expliquer, donc expliquer à une fédération x ou y "nous vous avons bien entendu, voici ce qu'on a entendu et voici pourquoi on n'en a pas tenu compte".» (BUS-BE)

Of course, not all members of civil society reacted negatively to the study. Insofar as the scenario analysis shows that reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% in Belgium by 2050 was technically and economically feasible, the actors who support a low-carbon vision welcomed the study with enthusiasm. This was particularly the case of development NGOs which, more active at national than regional level, had little or no knowledge of the Walloon study. As we will see in the point devoted to usage, this study was particularly useful for them to give credibility to their speeches in favour of the low-carbon transition.

«C'est là que petit à petit, on a pu commencer à construire – pas seulement nous, mais avec d'autres ONG, syndicats etc. – un discours sur la faisabilité de la chose et le fait qu'il y avait même des opportunités économiques importantes. Il y avait quand même déjà eu, si je me souviens bien, dans les années précédentes, l'un ou l'autre rapport du réseau européen Climate Action Network, qui allait dans ce sens-là, mais qui ne s'appliquait pas à la Belgique et qui rendaient donc les éléments plus difficilement traduisible en "chiffres belges".» (NGO-BE)

The members of civil society discussed the study within advisory bodies. The Federal Climate Service actually suggested to Secretary of state Melchior Wathelet to request the opinion of the civil society concerning the study. On 17 December 2013, Melchior Wathelet asked the Regional and Federal Councils to submit a joint notice on the best way to achieve the transition towards a low-carbon society in 2050. The stakeholders discussed the main conclusions of the study within the CFDD and this dialogue led to a compromise on the levers to be implemented with a view to reaching a low-carbon transition (see CFDD & al., 2014). The CFDD members agreed on all points except the nuclear issue.

«On a discuté ensemble pour essayer d'arriver à un compromis et, si je me rappelle bien, on a un compromis sur tout, sauf le point que j'ai rajouté par après qui est le nucléaire. Je trouve qu'on a fait un bel effort de consensus. (...) et là, on a une base, on va dire sociétale, sur lequel on peut construire. (...) Et donc, l'avantage de celui-ci [ndlr.: "Belgique bas-carbone"] (...) c'est que pour finir, avec le CFDD, les stakeholders se sont mis – je ne dis pas que c'est exhaustif – d'accord sur des moyens. Et donc, on est déjà allé quelque part assez loin. Par contre, on ne s'est pas encore mis d'accord sur les outils. C'est déjà plus compliqué. Mais, on a déjà franchi les deux premières étapes. Je ne suis pas sûr qu'au niveau des gouvernements ils aient déjà franchi même la première.» (BUS-BE)

Since the report was published in 2013, the Federal Climate Service continued to present the study. After the 2014 federal election and the establishment of the new government, they presented the

study to the cabinet of the new Federal Minister in charge of Energy, Marie-Christine Marghem (MR). The reception was less favourable than in the Wathélet Cabinet. Minister Marghem and her staff seem to have less appropriate the study.

«Maintenant c'est Marghem qui est aux commandes. Elle s'est tout à fait enthousiasmée pour l'étude, mais elle n'a pas pris la peine de comprendre ce qu'il y avait derrière».

In addition, the study has raised some apprehension within the cabinet because it does not address the impacts of the scenarios on the economy. A demonstration that the low-carbon transition would not affect economic growth was needed to convince this Government to support such transition.

«B. Il a fallu une étude macroéconomique pour convaincre ce gouvernement que la transition ... [Le Service fédéral Climat] a d'abord présenté celle-là [ndlr.: Scénarios pour une Belgique bas-carbone] au tout début et puis effectivement, Marghem était ok pour qu'on fasse un impact macroéconomique de ces scénarios. Mais les scénarios en eux-mêmes, justement, ça a fait peur à plein de gens parce que ça ne dit pas quelle est la portée économique. Maintenant, on sait qu'il y a une bonne portée économique (...) En tout cas, ce n'est pas une mauvaise. Il n'y a pas plus de croissance, mais il n'y en a pas moins. Donc, ça ne devrait pas faire peur. Mais ça ne doit pas non plus faire booster le truc.

C. On n'est pas obligé de parler de décroissance.

A. Et au début, c'était un peu une peur des membres du cabinet?

B. Est-ce que c'était une peur? On va parler pour nous, non.

C. On va parler pour nous, non. Et pour le cabinet en général, on va dire qu'une peur, c'est peut-être un peu trop fort, mais il y avait une sorte de réticence ou appréhension en tout cas.

A. Et l'étude macroéconomique a convaincu en quelques sortes?

B. Oui.» (PA-BE)

In order to answer a series of fears and questions on the economic impacts of low-carbon scenarios formulated by the Cabinet, but also by certain stakeholders, the Federal Climate Service commissioned a macroeconomic analysis of the scenarios.

«Des questions fondamentales ont été posées par les stakeholders, et je pense qu'il faut les entendre, notamment par la FEB. C'était de dire "vous nous dites que ça c'est possible techniquement même si on n'a pas encore vu le politique derrière, mais qu'est-ce que ça implique en termes de développement économique? Est-ce que ça veut dire que si on va vers un développement économique c'est super on va créer de l'emploi et si on va vers un scénario comportemental c'est l'inverse, c'est de la décroissance?" Je simplifie de nouveau. (...) Les commanditaires ont décidé de compléter cette étude par une approche macro-économique.» (Author of the study)

This complementary study carried out by CLIMACT in collaboration with UCL, the Federal Planning Bureau and Oxfords Economics has again involved the participation of many stakeholders. Published in October 2016, it shows that the low-carbon transition should not only involve a growth level similar to the Business as usual scenario, but also generate a net job creation (CLIMACT & al., 2016).

In addition to the macro-economic study, the Federal Climate Service has developed other follow-up to the study, including the webtool My2050³⁷. This is a simplified version of the online modelling tool for young people aged 16-18 and more largely for non-specialists. My2050 is an initiative led by the Federal Climate Service in collaboration with CLIMACT, Climate Media Factory, Cronos/Legioen, WWF and GoodPlanet. Launched in October 2016 by Minister Marghem, the webtool is now presented by climate coaches in Belgian schools.

In the continuity of the study "Low-carbon Belgium" and always in a dynamic of dialogue with the stakeholders, the Federal Climate Service launched the national debate on carbon pricing on 25

³⁷ <http://www.my2050.be>

January 2017. This reflection led by CLIMACT, PwC and SuMa Consulting has been achieved in June 2018 (CLIMACT & al., 2018) (see section “3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate mitigation Policy” of Chapter II). The study “low-carbon Belgium”, the macro-economic analysis of the scenarios, the webtool My2050 and the national debate on carbon pricing are part of the “Project 2050” promoted by the Federal Climate Service.

While the scenario analysis has elicited many reactions from stakeholders, it has not really had an echo among political authorities. Known only by a few deputies – primarily from the Green party – and by some political advisors specialized on energy-climate issues, the study seems to have barely penetrated the political sphere. Yet, the low-carbon scenarios were presented on 21 June 2016 to the Belgian House of Representatives. After discovering the study during a communication of a member of the FPS Climate Change at a conference at ULB, the deputy Jean-Marc Nollet (Ecolo) organized a presentation of the low-carbon scenarios to the Climate and Sustainable Development Commission of the Federal Parliament. Although the presentation has engendered fairly in-depth questions and exchanges (see Chambre des Représentants de Belgique, 2016), it does not seem to have made an impression.

«A. Il me semble que vous étiez à la présentation de celle-ci [Belgique bas-carbone]. C'était en juin ou en juillet cette année.

B. Moi je ne l'ai pas... Non-non, je ne la connais pas en tout cas.» (Federal Deputy who reacted to the study during the presentation to Parliament)

3.2.4. Role of the Study in Policy-Making

Instrumental Role

Except for a member of a federal administration who stated having the intention to use the study to elaborate the integrated Energy-Climate 2030 Plan required by the EU (see section “3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate mitigation Policy” of Chapter II), the study didn't seem to have been used as a decision support tool by policy makers.

«Est-ce que je peux te dire que grâce à notre étude, par exemple, ce dont je rêverais, on a pris une mesure significative pour limiter l'utilisation des véhicules de société? Eh bien non.» (Author of the study)

«Dans les faits, moi j'ai l'impression qu'il y a peu de chose qui en a été fait. On a parfois repris un point par ci, un point par là, mais le politique n'en a pas fait grand-chose. Évidemment, et c'est ça la difficulté du politique, c'est qu'il y a des aspects qui sont fédéraux et des aspects qui sont régionaux» (BUS-BE)

The most cited reason for not using the study in devising climate mitigation policies is the Federal government's lack of competence in this matter.

«Elle [Belgique bas-carbone] ne mène pas à beaucoup de réalisations non-plus et ça, c'est dû à la répartition des compétences. (...) Le Fédéral a la compétence de faire des études, mais il n'a pas les leviers pour mettre en œuvre des politiques en climat en particulier, et en énergie. Tous les grands axes, l'efficacité énergétique et le renouvelable, c'est des compétences régionales. (...)» (POL-RW)

«Il y a beaucoup de compétences qui n'appartiennent pas au SPF. LE SPF, sa volonté, c'est de continuer d'influencer le ministre fédéral sur ce qu'on doit faire sur les compétences qui sont encore disponible et puis après, les régions font ce qu'elles veulent.» (Author of the study)

«The department that ordered the study is not the department that is in charge of all the different measures that have to be taken to make it reality» (Author of the study)

Another reason that help explaining the non-use of the study is the absence of political momentum favourable to the development of climate mitigation policy.

«C'est un peu compliqué (...) Il faut informer des décideurs évidemment, mais on n'informe pas en arrivant avec ce document et en disant "voilà ce que ça donne, maintenant décidez". On a beau avoir des recommandations, ça a l'air robuste et relativement partagé, ça ne se passe pas comme ça. Il faut qu'il y ait un momentum politique; il faut qu'il y ait convergence de points de vue; il faut que dans les partis ils se soient mis d'accord; il faut des choses qui puissent bouger.» (ADM-BE)

An additional explanation concerns the contents of the study. Some actors believe that it doesn't inform on how to reach the low-carbon target. They explain that the study doesn't provide information neither on the policy measures to be implemented to reduce GHG emission, nor on the milestones required to guide and monitor the low-carbon transition.

«Si je prends une étude comme les scénarios bas-carbone pour la Belgique, je regarde ce que je peux en tirer concrètement, ce n'est pas très clair. C'est extrêmement complexe. Moi, ça ne m'intéresse pas, de voir un scénario Behaviour, CORE, Technology et EU intégration. Je préférerais qu'on en fasse un seul, avec des hypothèses réalistes en matière de comportement des individus, de déploiement de la technologie et qu'on regarde, derrière, quels sont les outils à mettre en place, avec des deadlines, avec une vraie roadmap. Ca, ça m'intéresse. Le reste...» (BUS-BE)

On the contrary, other actors consider that with studies like "Low-carbon Belgium", the political authorities have all the information needed for developing climate mitigation policies and that all that is missing today is the political courage to implement such policies.

«Quand on voit les discussions politiques qui sont actuellement menées par Marghem sur la vision énergétique et le pacte énergétique, c'est extrêmement laborieux alors que tout est sur la table. Il faut "juste" décider maintenant. On sait vers quoi on doit aller, comment on va le faire, (...) Tout est là, il faut juste avoir le courage de passer à l'acte. Et ça, ça prend du temps.» (WU-BE)

It seems interesting to point out that the French-speaking and Flemish Greens have used the study to draft a 2016-2020 climate budget. Mainly based on the online modeling tool, they have developed ten measures to implement for the reinforcement of Belgian climate policy (Ecolo & Groen, 2016). However, being in opposition, Ecolo and Groen did not submit these measures in the form of a proposal for a law.

«On s'en est beaucoup servi. Par exemple, on a fait une note sur un budget climat au niveau fédéral. Décliner le budget climat régional au niveau fédéral, pour en faire éventuellement une proposition de loi. On n'est pas allé jusque-là parce qu'on est dans l'opposition. Faire une proposition de loi, c'est faire un document qui ne va pas être pris en considération par la majorité.» (PA-BE)

Conceptual Role

While it has not led to breakthroughs in public policy, the study served as a basis for elaborating of a consensual vision of the low-carbon transition for the stakeholders. As mentioned before, the members of civil society discussed the study within advisory bodies, and this led to the approval of the Regional and Federal councils' joint notice on the concretization of the transition towards a low-carbon society in Belgium. The study has thus helped to move the societal debate on the climate energy issue.

«[Les membres de la société civile] se sont penchés dessus, ils ont regardé, ils ont lu, ils y ont réfléchi. Donc ça, c'est des façons de faire progresser le débat politique.» (ADM-BE)

Furthermore, just like the Walloon study, the scenario analysis affects the opinion of several actors about the feasibility of the low-carbon transition at the Belgium scale, about the existence of several pathways, but also about the challenge posed by such a transition. The many activities of communication carried out by the Federal Climate Service to promote the study fostered the appropriation of study findings by the actors of the world of energy.

«[J'ai appris] premièrement, que c'était faisable et, deuxièmement, que le défi était à la rigueur énorme, beaucoup plus important que je pouvais l'imaginer au départ.» (PA-BE)

«Ce qui m'a étonné, c'est que c'était faisable. Au départ, je ne pensais pas qu'on puisse imaginer d'y arriver. Je pensais que c'est une sorte de concept fixé notamment par les Nations Unies, mais quand on devait le ramener à la pratique, à moins d'arriver à des aménagements du style CDM, achat de permis de polluer et des choses pareilles. Une économie bas-carbone belge, moi ça m'a d'abord surpris. Je me dis "Ouwaw c'est possible !". C'est possible et ça demande un changement de paradigme assez considérable, mais qui est encore possible et encore faisable. Ça va coûter de l'argent, ça va être un changement assez brutal, mais pas aussi dramatique qu'on pourrait l'imaginer si on s'y prend aujourd'hui.» (WU-BE)

Political Role

Insofar as it leads to the same conclusion as the Walloon study, the study has been – and still is – used by actors in favour of the low-carbon transition to support their speech, either in internal communications or in communications with other stakeholders or institutions. As it demonstrates that the low-carbon transition is technically and economically feasible and requires to implement ambitious policy as of now, actors supporting this vision refer to the study when supporting actions to mitigate climate changes. However, in some arena, several actors prefer not – or not much – base their arguments on this study because of the counter-expertise elaborated by incumbents that I previously mentioned.

«Ca [ndlr.: Les études "Belgique bas-carbone" et "100% renouvelable"] reste des références... Je siège dans beaucoup de conseils consultatifs, que ce soit au CFDD, mais aussi au CCE, ou à la CREG, et ça reste, des documents... "Comme l'étude X l'a prouvé, c'est faisable...". Mais de nouveau, ça reste très général, parce que ça permet d'éviter les réponses de certains [qui diraient] "oui, mais méthodologiquement c'est critiquable, ces études, ils ont pris des hypothèses sur lesquels on n'est pas tout à fait d'accord au départ...". Donc, on reste sur les grandes conclusions.» (WU-BE)

Also, just like the Walloon study, various actors extract from the report very specific elements such as figures or numbers to give credibility to their communications.

«On avait montré des résolutions dans le cadre de la COP 21 et des choses comme ça. Si on a besoin de se baser sur des chiffres, en général, ce sont des chiffres de la meilleure qualité qui existe et donc ce sont des bons arguments et donc on les utilise.» (PA-RW)

Process Role

As mentioned in the presentation of the study, the Federal Climate Service attached as much importance to the scenario building process as to the results of the study. It appears that the significant involvement of stakeholders in the construction of the scenarios and in the development of spin-off (i.e.: macroeconomic study and national debate on carbon pricing) have contributed to create this dynamic of dialogue and learning with the stakeholders that the administration wanted to initiate. This process, initiated in 2012 with the first consultations on the scenarios, appears to have elicited a thinking process on the low-carbon transition and contributed to creating a common language and frame of reference among the stakeholders.

«Évidemment, c'est toujours utile quand ça suscite de la réflexion. Il ne faut pas me faire dire ce que je n'ai pas dit. Je n'ai jamais dit que c'était inutile. On a eu d'excellentes réflexions avec eux. (...) On a revu une série d'hypothèses avec les gens des raffineries, parce que ça concernait essentiellement les raffineries. Puis, on a eu des réflexions en interne» (BUS-BE)

Regarding the development of a substantive dialogue during the workshop, the participatory approach developed in this study faced the same problem that the one developed in the "Low-carbon Wallonia". The fact that most of the actors present their institutional discourse and that those who are in disagreement are more vocal than others did not favour the emergence of a meaningful dialogue on the low-carbon transition.

3.2.5. Key Lessons

When looking at the chart summarizing the role in policy-making of the study “Low-carbon Belgium”, we observe that it has no instrumental role [Figure 67]. To explain the non-use of the study by policy-makers to devise climate mitigation policies, some actors mention the gap between the information provided by the study and what policy-makers’ need to know. The study actually doesn’t provide information neither on the policy measures to be implemented to reduce GHG emission, nor on the milestones required to guide and monitor the low-carbon transition. However, all the actors don’t share that view. Some consider that the non-translation on the study in political action is the result of governance problem. Such problems concern the Federal Government’s lack of political levers in climate-energy matters, the absence of political momentum favourable to the development of climate mitigation policy, and the failure of political courage to implement such policy.

That said, developing a climate mitigation policy on the basis of the study was not the main objective of the sponsor of this study. With the study “Low-carbon Belgium” and more generally with the entire “Project 2050”, the Federal Climate Service aimed at developing a process of learning and dialogue with the Belgian stakeholders. The significant involvement of stakeholders in the scenario analysis and in the development of spin-offs (i.e.: macroeconomic study and national debate on carbon pricing), but also the many activities of communication carried out by the Federal Climate Service to promote the study have contributed to create the intended dynamic of learning and dialogue. All of these initiatives have indeed elicited a thinking process on the low-carbon transition and contributed to creating a common language and frame of reference among the stakeholders. In that context, we can consider that the study has a rather important process and conceptual roles.

Inasmuch as the discussions of the study within advisory bodies served as a basis for elaborating a consensual vision of the low-carbon transition for the stakeholders, the study has contributed to move the societal debate on climate-energy issues. This strengthens the conceptual role of the study.

The study also has a political role. Just like the Walloon study, the study “Low-carbon Belgium” has been – and still is – used by actors in favour of the low-carbon transition to support their speech. Those are principally environmental NGOs, trade unions, renewable energy actors and political-administrative authorities. However, because of the counter-expertise promoted by the incumbents, some actors prefer not – or not much – base their speech on this study. The study has indeed generated a lot of negative criticism and opposition from federations of companies and dominant energy market operators who developed a series of arguments aimed at discrediting the study.

Figure 67. Role of the study “Low-carbon Belgium” in policy-making. Each axis corresponds to a type of role. The centre of the chart equates to a minor role and the extremity to an important role.

Regarding the level of appropriation by actors, the sponsor of the study (i.e.: Federal Climate Service) has, of course, strongly integrated its content [Figure 68]. The other administrations, just like workers unions and environmental and development NGOs are aware of the study and know its main conclusions. An interesting aspect is the high level of appropriation of employers’ federations and dominant energy market operators. Many incumbents actually know very well the main conclusions of the study, but also more specific elements mentioned in the report (e.g.: model's parameters, scenarios’ assumptions, conclusions per sector). They have examined carefully the study to develop counter-expertise. Then, just like the “Low-carbon Wallonia” study, the analysis at the Belgian scale has barely penetrated the political sphere. It is known only by a few deputies – primarily from the Green party – and by some political advisors specialized on energy-climate issues. Such knowledge is often limited to the main conclusions of the study. Conversely to the Walloon study, the scenario analysis is known by the current Federal Minister in charge of Energy and her cabinet. This is the result of the many communication activities and the spin-offs carried out by the Federal Climate Service. That said, the level of appropriation of the Minister and her cabinet appears to be not yet very high.

Figure 68. Level of appropriation per actor for the study “Low-carbon Belgium”. Each axis corresponds to a type of actor. The centre of the chart equates to a low level of appropriation and the extremity to a high level of appropriation.

Figure 69. Timeline illustrating the history of the study "Low-carbon Belgium"

3.3. Case Study n°3. Towards 100% Renewable Energy in Belgium by 2050

3.3.1. Emergence

The study "Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050" emerged in a particular context. It was initiated under the impulse of the Walloon Minister of Energy Jean-Marc Nollet (Ecolo) following the nuclear disaster of Fukushima which occurred on 11 March 2011. In his first speech a week after the disaster, Jean-Marc Nollet invited his Brussels, Flemish and federal counterparts to set up a reflection group with a view to contributing to the implementation of the nuclear phase-out scenario by 2025 and to the definition of the 100% renewable energy roadmap by 2050. In his communication, the Minister affirmed his willingness to submit this nuclear phase-out scenario to an independent review.

«Je suis prêt à soumettre mes chiffres à un examen indépendant! Voyons-nous pour étudier cela. Et si j'arrive à démontrer que c'est effectivement possible, je ne vois pas pourquoi on se priverait de sortir du nucléaire. D'autant qu'avec le signal qui nous vient du Japon, celui qui votera la prolongation des centrales portera dans ce cas une lourde responsabilité à l'égard des générations futures» (Ministre Nollet, in the 19 March 2011 edition of the newspaper Le Soir)

A few days after, on 28 March 2011, the four Belgian ministers of energy, Jean-Marc Nollet, Evelyne Huytebroeck (Brussels Minister, Ecolo), Freya Van Den Bossche (Flemish Minister, SPA) and Paul Magnette (Federal Minister, PS) got together and jointly decided to meet regularly, especially in order to progress in the development of the energy efficiency Plan and of the national renewable energy Plan. With this in mind, they decided to develop a number of initiatives, one of them consisting in studying the feasibility of a 100% renewable based energy system in Belgium by 2050 using a backcasting exercise. This mission was entrusted to the Federal Planning Bureau in collaboration with similar regional institutes, namely ICEDD and VITO. They were asked to propose a methodology for June 2011 and to provide the final report by end 2011-early 2012. The joint decision of the four ministers to order the study has been mentioned in several presses.

The purpose of this study was primarily political. Minister Jean-Marc Nollet took advantage of the collective emotion caused by the nuclear disaster to embark the other Belgian energy ministers in the realization of a study assessing the feasibility of the transition towards a fossil and nuclear free Belgium by 2050. The fact that other ministers, and particularly the socialists who were in charge of energy at the Federal and Flemish levels, support the study was very important for Minister Jean-Marc Nollet, because it allowed to crystalize the position of the Walloon and Flemish socialists in favour of the transition towards 100% renewable energy.

«Politiquement, elle était intéressante au moment où les quatre ministres se sont mis d'accord pour la commande et, ça veut dire, constatait la position des socialistes. Pour moi, stratégiquement, c'est ça qui est important. C'est que, en travaillant sur le court terme, on n'arrivait pas à être d'accord. Eux voulaient prolonger Tihange 1, nous, on estimait que ce n'était pas nécessaire, qu'il y avait moyen de s'en sortir. Mais en sortant de l'objectif 2020, et en allant jusqu'à 2050, on pouvait se rejoindre. (...) Et donc, tant que c'était cette position-là, moi je trouvais intéressant de la figer au niveau belge aussi et de pouvoir faire référence.» (POL-BE)

In addition to freezing the position of the socialists in favour of the replacement of nuclear and fossil energy by renewable energy, the study also aimed to support the energy policy of Jean-Marc Nollet. The study, if it succeeded in demonstrating that 100% renewable is feasible, could enable him to defend his own vision of a Belgium without fossil and nuclear energy with regard to other political actors.

As it was a mission, and not a tender, there were no specifications as such. The only injunction of the sponsors was to study the feasibility of the transition to a 100% renewable system using a backcasting approach involving a first consultation with the transmission system operators and a second one with the whole stakeholders. Apart from that, the consortium had free rein on the choice of the method to be used, but also on the definition of the scope of the study – i.e.: the choice of components of the energy sector to integrate.

3.3.2. Presentation of the Study

Methodology

The development of the methodology took almost six months. This task has been particularly difficult for several reasons. As mentioned above, the order did not specify guidelines for the definition of scope and the choice of methodology. In delimiting the scope, the consortium decided to set the bar high by considering all sources of energy production (electricity, heat and fuels) and all energy consumption sectors, with the exception of intercontinental shipping and air transport because they were conscious that there was no technical alternative to fossil fuels for these modes of transport.

Once the scope was delimited, the aim was to define the scenario building method. When defining the method, the consortium encountered difficulties associated with working for four ministers and four administrations with different sensitivities, political agenda and visions.

«Il y avait les autres régions – deux personnes par région –, plus le fédéral, plus les consultants. Il y avait la DG Energie et une autre équipe équivalente en Flandre et à Bruxelles. Avec la difficulté que chaque région a sa vision politique et essaye de la faire passer dans l'étude» (ADM-RW)

More particularly, the Cabinet Nollet was reluctant to use a modeling tool because it feared that the model would lead to the conclusion that the transition to a 100% renewable energy Belgium was not feasible.

«Le cabinet Nollet était relativement, on ne va pas dire craintif, mais se méfiait de ce genre de résultats qui sortent d'un modèle parce que c'est moins facile, je pense, d'orienter le résultat vers ce vers quoi tu veux aller quand même. Il avait quand même bien compris qu'une fois qu'on a défini la méthode de calcul, la cible (...) et les hypothèses de travail, après c'est le modèle qui parle. Tu peux après interpréter les résultats du modèle mais tu ne peux plus rien faire d'autre. Si le modèle te dit "c'est pas possible", eh bien, c'est pas possible. En fait au départ on ne savait juste rien.»

Nobody knew what the model run would come up with. Most of the consortium members were actually skeptical and thought that the modeling would lead to the conclusion that it was unfeasible.

«[Certains membres du consortium] étaient relativement sceptiques en disant "c'est juste pas possible, ça va pas marcher ce truc, on va arriver à des résultats unfeasible!". (...) Je me suis dit "Eh bien on va prendre le risque, on va y aller, on va tester et si c'est pas réalisable, eh bien, le modèle nous dira c'est pas possible, mais au moins on aura la réponse."» (Author of the study)

The consortium finally convinced the sponsors to use the Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System (TIMES), a partial equilibrium model of the energy system that was already at the disposal of VITO. This model was chosen so that the results would be more credible in the stakeholders' eyes. The first version of the TIMES model was developed in 1981 by about twenty countries who joined their forces as part of the Energy Technology Systems Analysis Program (ETSAP), an implementing agreement of the International Energy Agency (IEA). Ever since, it has been used and proven by many modelers around the world. It enjoys a certain notoriety and is reputed to be reliable and robust. The TIMES models have been adapted at the Belgian scale in the early 2000's by VITO and the University of Leuven (KU Leuven) within a project financed by the Belgian Science Policy Office (Belspo) (see CES-KU Leuven & VITO, 2001).

The principal purpose of TIMES is to analyse comparatively alternative scenarios. Basically, this modelling involves first defining the energy services and the technology that can supply such services. Demand drivers, such as the evolution of GDP, population or size of families, allow to define pathways of development for the different energy services. Based on a cost optimization, the computer program then finds out the way to get these service levels at minimal global cost. The cost covers investment costs, fixed and variable operating costs, fuel costs and environmental taxes. Besides environment taxes, the model can include other *policy* components such as GHG emissions restrictions, nuclear phase out, technology portfolios, subsidies, emission trading systems etc. A distinctive feature of TIMES over other energy model is the way it grasps the time dimension. While most of the simulation tools "cover periods from 30 to 100 years, divided into a number of sub-periods, each of them covering

a couple of years”, TIMES provides a higher time resolution that enables “to consider typical conditions determining supply and demand conditions”. For instance, the model allows to take into consideration the fluctuations in solar energy availability between day and night, but also between summer and winter.

Once the method was established, a new difficulty arose in defining the hypotheses. This phase of the project was indeed a source of tension on the side of the Cabinet of Minister Nollet – and to a lesser extent from the Cabinet of Minister Huytebroek – who understood that the choice of hypotheses would be decisive on the outcome of the modelling exercise and tried to influence such choice to maximizing the chance of demonstrating that the transition to a 100% renewable energy based system is feasible.

«Ce qui est aussi étonnant, c'est que j'ai trouvé que les Ecolos, évidemment c'était Nollet qui était à la démarche d'investigation de l'étude, pour moi, il y a eu une vraie tentation de sa part d'instrumentaliser l'étude et d'instrumentaliser le consortium pour faire dire ce qu'ils voulaient entendre. (...) A la limite en comité d'accompagnement, ce sont eux qui ont généré le plus de discussions sur la fixation de certaines hypothèses. (...) Je pense que derrière, ils avaient peur des résultats qui allaient sortir, et donc ils voulaient avoir des hypothèses les plus favorables possibles pour maximiser les chances de réussite. (...) Le prix du pétrole, chacun tirait dans son sens: "Ouais mais non ce ne sera pas possible. 150 dollars le prix du baril ce ne sera jamais plus, ça c'est sûr, on sera à 300 dollars sans aucun problème", et l'autre disait "Non ça c'est pas possible". Même chose pour la courbe de décroissance du photovoltaïque. Donc toutes ces tensions ont dû être arbitrées au sein du comité d'accompagnement».

At this stage of the project, stakeholders were also consulted. Given the very controversial nature of the issue, the consortium decided not to set up a real exercise of co-construction of scenarios. In a plenary session, the research team presented the method and the assumptions, and the participants were invited to provide feedback.

«Le scope de l'étude était tellement problématique. Les fantasmes que chacun des stakeholders avait sur ces questions-là étaient tellement divergents que si on avait voulu travailler de façon plus consensuelle, ça aurait été extrêmement compliqué. Et donc on a été obligé de prendre la posture de l'étude académique en disant "Nous, on fait une étude, on nous paye pour faire ça, on a défini une méthode ; on a fait valider notre méthode par le comité d'accompagnement ; on a fait valider les hypothèses ; maintenant on vous les présente. Vous pouvez donner vos commentaires et, le cas échéant, on ajustera les hypothèses, on retravaillera certains résultats". Mais ce n'était pas un forum où chacun y allait... Ceci n'a pas été co-construit avec les stakeholders». (Author of the study)

The consortium has delegated the regional and federal advisory bodies to select the participants. Around fifty people from business federations, environmental NGOs, trade unions and energy network operators participated in this plenary session.

Once the model assumptions were established, one reference scenario and five scenarios compatible with the objective of 100% renewable energy in 2015 were elaborated: DEM, GRID, BIO, PV and WIND. Those 100% renewable energy differ in term of energy mix. The main characteristics and the assumptions of the scenarios are represented in the following figure [Figure 70].

Scenario name	Main characteristics	Variants	General assumptions		Technology assumptions		
			CO ₂ price	Energy price	Nuclear	CCS	Renewable target
REF	Reference scenario 2020 EU climate-energy package	NO	15€/ton in 2020 and 51€/ton in 2050	EU Roadmap Ref.	Phase out	No CCS	13% in 2020 and beyond
DOM	100% Renewable Energy by 2050; DOMestic check	NO					100% in 2050 (intermediate targets 13% in 2020, 35% in 2030 and 65% in 2040)
DEM	Low energy services demand	NO					
GRID	Flexible electricity imports	NO					
BIO	More biomass imports	Low price					
		High price					
PV	More solar PV	Low price					
		High price					
WIND	More Wind (onshore and offshore)	NO					

Figure 70. Main characteristics and assumptions of the scenarios in the study “100% renewable” (VITO & al. 2012, p. 13)

The consortium then assessed the socio-economic impacts of the scenarios, which included the electricity prices, the investments, the external fuel bill, the security of energy supply and, to a lesser extent, the job creations. This socio-economic analysis was based on the modelling tool completed with an extensive literature review.

They finally defined the policies and measures that could be implemented to materialize the different scenarios.

Results

The main result of the study is that the transition to 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050 is feasible. Model runs showed that all the scenarios were feasible, excepted for the DOM scenario. It suggested that it was not possible to meet the energy needs of the country with 100% local renewable energy unless reducing energy demand below the level projected – just like in the DEM scenario.

The simulation pointed out that the investments to be made with a view to developing a 100% renewable energy-based system amount between 300 and 400 billion euros. In comparison with the reference scenario, the increase in the energy system cost was estimated at 2% of the GDP in 2050 whichever scenario was adopted. Those additional cost didn't take into consideration neither the cost associated with a reduction of energy service demand, nor the benefits engendered by a reduction of GHG emissions resulting from the transition towards 100% renewable energy system. The analysis also showed that such transition should create between 20 000 and 60 000 jobs compared to the reference scenario.

Moreover, the authors highlighted the importance of improvement in energy efficiency, energy saving and massive electrification if it would be decided to embark on a pathway towards 100% renewable energy. They also demonstrated that since that long-term energy storage should be extremely expensive, “in a cost optimal modelling approach, a transformation of energy system towards abandoning strict equilibria and replacing it by installing overcapacity in intermittent renewable energy sources is to be preferred” (VITO & al., 2012, p. 13). This could involve a shift towards seasonal

production in the industrial sectors implying using energy during the cheapest period of the year. The development of such flexible energy consumption pattern required to rethink completely our relationship with energy.

3.3.3. Communication, Follow-Up and Reception

The "Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050" is arguably the most talked about study. Almost every people I met have at least heard about it. Called "the backcasting study" by many persons, it has aroused a lot of reactions from various actors, starting with its sponsors, and more specifically the Ecolo cabinets. Minister Nollet's Cabinet was apparently surprised on the downside when hearing that the simulation shows that the transition to a 100% renewable energy-based system by 2050 should cost between 300 and 400 billion euros.

«Nollet était celui qui a lancé l'étude et à la limite je pense que c'était lui qui était le moins content des résultats. (...) Je le vois encore: "M'enfin qu'est-ce que c'est ça? 300 - 400 milliards? J'ai vu d'autres études... en Allemagne ou au Danemark ils ont fait des études où on montre que ça rapporte de l'argent"»

Minister Nollet's Cabinet also regretted that the scenarios maintained the current economic paradigm of growth and did not imply a reduction in energy consumption. The consortium had indeed decided to show that we can reach 100% renewable without necessarily being part of a dynamic of degrowth in order to guard against criticisms of actors who would consider that such paradigm change was not feasible or desirable. A few criticisms also came from the cabinet of Brussels minister Evelyne Huytebroek, who would have liked the scenarios to make more use of biomass. Conversely, the cabinets of the Flemish and Federal minister tended to have little reaction. It should be noted that between the launch of the study in March 2011 and the finalization of the project, Minister Magnette was replaced by Melchior Wathelet (cdH), appointed Secretary of state for the Environment on 6 December 2011.

The study was published on 12 December 2012. The final report in English included an executive summary translated into French and Dutch. On the occasion of the publication of the report, a presentation of the final results to the stakeholders who took part to consultation was organized. A press release was broadcasted and relayed in many French language and Flemish newspapers. The study was also widely disseminated by several actors, including by environmental NGOs (IEW, WWF, Greenpeace), renewable energy actors (Edora and APERe) and other organizations in favour of the 100% renewable energy vision.

The study generated some interest and the authors were invited to present it on various occasions. It was presented to many different institutions and organizations, including the Walloon and Flemish Parliaments, public administrations, political parties, advisory bodies, civil society organizations like FEB, Agoria and FGTB. Even nowadays, the study is still presented.

«We presented this study at least 20 times, if not 30 times. Everybody was interested when it came out. This study has really paid a lot of attention. And, with [ICEDD], we presented this study three weeks ago in Eupen. It was a surprise for me that he still asks me to present another time the study.» (Author of the study)

The reactions from civil society organizations following the release of the study have been rather lukewarm.

«A part nous, personne n'était très content.» (Author of the study)

The most vocal actors were again the employer's federations and the dominant actors of the energy market. The incumbents have indeed strongly criticized the study. Note that those criticisms have been made more by Belgian than Walloon actors.

«Les positions les plus tranchées, les plus oppositionnelles, c'était plutôt le camp patronal, plus la FEB que l'Union Wallonne d'ailleurs. L'Union Wallonne était plus ouverte. Je ne sais pas, peut-être qu'ils avaient moins compris les enjeux.»

«La fin ne s'est pas bien passée, parce qu'il y a eu un manque d'interaction, un manque de considération d'une série de remarques, ce qui fait que nous, on est sorti avec ça [ndlr.: note de la FEB sur l'étude], ça a même été dans la presse.» (BUS-BE)

In a detailed note, FEB – who opposed this analysis more than the “Low-carbon Belgian” – sets out a series of arguments against the study. The note points out a number of fundamental limitations of the analysis that “*question the foundations and the conclusions of the study... and thus raise the question of its legitimacy to support decision regarding our energy future*” (FEB 2013, p. 1). First, the employers’ federation questions the normative scope of the study: should we reach 100% renewable energy in 2050? For them, the development of renewable energy is a mean, and not an objective – the objectives being, as said before, the security of supply, the business competitiveness and the environmental protection. Secondly, beside questioning the object of the study, the companies state that the conclusion that ensuring economic growth and comfort is compatible with the transition towards 100% renewable energy is not valid. This statement is based on the identification of several limits of the analysis. A first limit is that by not taking into account neither the integration of energy markets at the European level, nor the European and global competitiveness facing Belgian industries, the study considers the country “*like an island*”, which leads to non-credible results. Then, the biomass is an important source of energy in the scenarios, but the study doesn’t take into account the competition with other uses for biomasses products (i.e.: food and material manufacturing). The shift towards seasonal production in some industries proposed to cope with the intermittent nature or some renewable energy is also criticized. This solution proposed by the model is seen as not very credible inasmuch as it requires strengthening industrial production capacities, organizing flexible work conditions, but also implementing such solution abroad for not cripple Belgian industries. Other criticisms regarding the parameters and hypothesis of the model are formulated in the note. They concern, among other, the low discount rate, the non-consideration of nuclear and coal energy in the business as usual scenario that leads to an overestimation of the costs associated with such scenario, the overly optimistic assumptions regarding the renewable energy potential and the reduction of the investments-costs to develop renewable energy. Finally, considering that the policy to be implemented to reach 100% renewable energy is a political choice that should not be made by scientists, the note criticizes the inclusion of policy recommendations in the rapport (FEB, 2013).

This FEB’s note was sent to several parliamentarians. The socialist deputy Edmund Stoffels (PS), expert from his party on energy issues, addressed to Minister Nollet a number of questions raised by the companies in a parliamentary question (see Parlement Wallon, 2013b). For his part, David Clarinval (MR), a liberal deputy closely interested in energy policy and agreed with the companies’ position about the study, relayed the arguments of the FEB in the press and in his book “Energy fiasco” (see de Salle & Clarinval, 2014). In an article published on 12 April 2013 in the newspaper L’Echo, the deputy made public a series of arguments set out in the FEB note.

«A l’époque, on disait que c’était utopique de croire qu’on pouvait comme ça en très peu de temps remplacer complètement les énergies fossiles par des énergies vertes. Et puis, cette étude est arrivée. Ça a participé au fait de dire que c’était possible, d’autant plus que les présentations qui ont été faites à l’époque ne parlaient pas du tout du coût. C’est pour ça que moi j’avais fait une sortie à l’époque pour bien dire “oui-oui c’est possible, mais ça va coûter un pont”. Et donc, on masquait une partie de la vérité, puisque le but des commanditaires de cette étude, ou en tout cas d Ecolo, c’était de démontrer que c’était possible par rapport à ceux qui disait que c’était techniquement pas possible. Et donc, ça participait de cette mouvance et lors de la présentation, les gens n’ont pas retenu que ça coûte très très très cher. Ils ont juste retenu que c’était possible.» (POL-BE)

David Clarinval is not the only one to have publicly opposed the study. Two days after the publication of the report, in the 14 December 2012 edition of the Flemish newspaper De Morgen, André

Oosterlinck, former rector of the Catholic University of Leuven (KUL), strongly criticized the study in an opinion paper entitled “100% renewable energy by 2050? In some studies, only misprizes fit³⁸”.

«He didn't know the content of the study. He thought that we were projecting it, that we could have renewable energy system by 2050 - While in fact we investigate the conditions, so something completely different. Ronnie Belmans (KUL) was very unhappy with that reaction from Oosterling because he reacted without knowing what we did and basically he supported us in our fight with Oosterling.» (Author of the study)

Shortly after, on 8 January 2013, it was the turn of Luc Stercks, President of the Federation of Belgian Industrial Energy Consumers (Febeliec), to speak about the study in a *carte blanche* for the newspaper *Le Soir*. With this position paper, the President of Febeliec intended to counterbalance the idea that the transition towards a 100% renewable energy system was feasible and that we must quickly embark on such path – a message that was widely disseminated in the press following the publication of the study.

«Je crois qu'on n'avait pas réagi à l'étude elle-même. Mais après la parution de l'étude, il y a eu toute une série d'articles et de réactions de la presse qui disaient "Vous voyez que c'est possible, 100% renouvelable". Nous avons dit "Écoutez, cette étude ne dit pas que c'est possible, cette étude dit quel sera l'impact, si on le fait".» (BUS-BE)

In Summer 2013, Annemie Bollen and Peter Van Humbeeck from the Social and Economic Council of Flanders (SERV) published a paper entitled “100% renewable energy in Belgium? Everything can be done in wonderland³⁹” in the magazine of the Flemish Association for Environmental Law (Bollen & Van Humbeeck, 2013).

While the study aroused the anger of those actors, it generated little reaction from the associative world. Environmental NGOs welcomed the study, but they showed little enthusiasm for its conclusions. Like the Ecolo Cabinets, they regretted the high costs generated by the transition highlighted by the model and the absence of degrowth scenario.

For their part, the trade unions stayed in the background in the discussions about the study. The issue of the shift to seasonal industrial production and the implications that this could entail in terms of organization of work have of course drawn their attention. However, unlike the federations of companies, they were more open on this issue. They preferred not to come down for or against the study and ask the Secretary of state for Energy for a complementary study on the socio-economic impacts of the 100% renewable objective in order to better understand the impacts of such transition on sectoral employment, work organization and competitiveness.

«Cet élément [le shift vers une production industrielle saisonnière] nous avait fort interpellés sur le moment même, et j'en avais informé mes responsables. J'avais fait une note en disant que cette étude est intéressante, mais que ça demande un changement de paradigme, notamment en termes de structuration du marché du travail dans certains secteurs tel que l'acier. Il est question de période de chômage technique assez importantes aux périodes avec beaucoup d'ensoleillement, peu de vent ou que sais-je, et de périodes plus intensive au travail. Je croyais qu'ils allaient hurler et dire que c'est pas possible. Mais non, pourquoi pas, si on encadre ça suffisamment pour défendre l'intérêt des travailleurs, pour défendre les conditions de travail aussi, mais que ce soit bien clair, on peut imaginer ça. S'il faut y arriver, il faudra y arriver. Voilà, donc effectivement (...) j'avais eu un retour assez surprenant et qui, il faut être honnête, dépend fort je pense de la personnalité du responsable. Je ne suis pas sûr d'avoir les mêmes échos avec la présidence actuelle. Ils sont plus prudents.» (WU-BE)

The members of civil society discussed the study within the CFDD. They were indeed invited by the Secretary of state in charge of energy to provide a notice on the study. However, the study was the object of a very polarized debate and the stakeholders did not manage to agree. They submitted to

³⁸ Original title: “100% hernieuwbare energie tegen 2050? Bij sommige studies past alleen misprijzen”

³⁹ Original title: “100% hernieuwbare energie in België? Alles kan in wonderland”

the Secretary of state a non-consensual note presenting the positions of the different actors (CFDD, 2013).

Finally, compared to the other studies analysed, the "100% renewable" study seems to have penetrated more deeply into the political sphere. Most of the public authorities or political advisers I met, if they have not read the study, have at least heard of it. This may be explained by the facts that the study was ordered by four ministers, that it has been very much in the media and that some of the conclusion of the study were very controversial and triggered reactions.

«C'est parce que le Ministre Nollet à l'époque en a parlé et puisqu'il se vantait d'avoir été un des commanditaires de cette étude, je me suis dit "Maintenant tu vas te la procurer et tu vas la lire".» (POL-RW)

The penetration of the study in the political world is however limited to specialists of climate-energy issues. Those are the climate-energy advisors of different political party and a few deputies such as Jean-Marc Nollet (Ecolo), Edmund Stoffels (PS) and David Clarinval (MR) who specialized in climate energy policies. The great majority of political authorities haven't an expert knowledge of this particularly technical and complex question and don't know the study.

«C'est plutôt au sein des personnes qui dans le monde politique s'intéressent à ces questions. Ils sont une minorité. Vous avez pour chaque parti quelques personnes qui s'y connaissent un tout petit peu, mais je ne pense pas que si je parle de cette étude-ci [100% renouvelable] dans le parti, il y ait grand monde qui voit précisément de quoi il s'agit, à part les 4-5 parlementaires qui s'intéressent de plus près à ça.» (Conseiller parti politique)

This could help to explain the little discussion among decision makers generated by the study. Apart from the discussions that took place during the joint meeting of Commissions from Federal, Walloon, Flemish and Brussels' Parliaments organized the 9 July 2013 – event widely advertised in the press –, the study was not the subject of political debate.

It is interesting to note that this study has globally had more repercussions in Flanders than in Wallonia. In the North of the country, it has generated a lot of debate among people who are interested in energy, especially in the academic world.

« [Le Vito] a fait plein de présentations en Flandre. Ça a eu beaucoup plus de retentissement en Flandre qu'en Wallonie, cette étude-là. Il y a eu beaucoup plus de débat au sein des gens qui s'intéressent un peu à l'énergie. En Flandre, ils sont même passés à la télé. Nous on l'a fait juste le jour où l'étude a été publiée et ça été oublié dans le flot médiatique. (...) On sent que les intellectuels de l'énergie en Flandre, il y en a. En Wallonie, à part Damien Ernst... Hervé Jeanmart, il est très peu présent dans la presse. Tandis qu'en Flandre, tu as quand même Daseleer, Stef Proost, qui sont déjà des notoriétés très imposantes. Daseleer il a checké ça et il a dit "Ouais méthodologiquement, ça c'est bon". Quand il nous a dit ça, et il y a eu cette espèce d'in prima tour du monde académique flamand par rapport à la méthodologie.» (Author of the study)

3.3.4. Role of the Study in Policy-Making

Instrumental Role

Like the study "scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium", it seems that "100% renewable energy" has not been used as a tool for policy-making.

«Elle n'a jamais donné lieu à des résultats concrets» (PA-RW)

«Il faut bien se rendre compte que ça n'a pas été suivi des faits, sinon, je crois qu'on aurait déjà beaucoup plus d'éoliennes, de panneaux photovoltaïques, d'offshore et de biomasse» (ADM-RW)

Even though they order it, it appears that the Greens haven't used the study for developing climate mitigation policies. An argument made by Ecolo for not using the study to develop policies concerns its publication date. It seems that the study arrives too late in the legislature. Most of the decisions have already been taken and the policy were in the phase of finalization.

«2013 [ndlr.: année de publication de l'étude "100% renouvelables"], c'était déjà tard dans la législation, puisque nous, on a terminé en juin 2014. Donc, on était dans un rush tout à fait fou. Toutes les procédures étaient déjà enclenchées. C'était plus une question de consolider le discours et de faire référence à différents éléments. Les politiques étaient toutes en train de se finaliser, de se négocier en dernière étape au niveau du gouvernement. (...) Maintenant, s'il s'agit d'influencer les choix d'une législature, les choix concrets d'une législature, c'est vrai qu'il vaut mieux arriver au tout début de la législation, voire avant, puisque beaucoup se négocie déjà dans la déclaration de politique régionale, pour 5 ans. Mais bon, de toute façon, il n'y a pas de timing parfait.» (POL-RW)

Ecolo intended to translate the study into the Government's policy statement of the following electoral period, but since the Greens had lost the elections and were relegated to the opposition, they didn't participate in the elaboration of the policy statement.

«L'idée eut été – mais bon, ça n'a pas été possible – de l'implémenter dans la déclaration gouvernementale du gouvernement suivant. Mais là, on n'a pas été appelé à négocier» (POL-BE)

Apart from the Greens, the other political actors didn't use the study either. The most cited reason for not using the study to devise was that it didn't meet the information needs of those actors. It described broad visions of the future but didn't give any clues on how to reach those visions. This analysis didn't inform concretely on the policies to implement today and at the various stage of the pathway towards a 100% renewable energy system. The policy-makers were thus not able to translate it into political action.

«A l'époque, quand ça a été présenté [ndlr.: l'étude 100% renouvelable], et encore maintenant, ça peut se lire comme une espèce de roman de science-fiction, parce que ça manque quand même un peu de concret. Ce sont des grandes visions. Je peux formuler tous les objectifs du monde que je veux, si je ne trace pas le chemin comment y arriver, ça reste un rêve.(...) C'est un bon outil de communication. Ça peut être un outil entre les mains de parlementaires pour rappeler de temps en temps à un ministre qu'il faut être plus ambitieux, mais c'est pas là-dessus que je construirai une politique énergétique. (POL-RW)

«Pour que ce soit un véritable outil d'aide à la décision, ça doit répondre à des questions de quel est l'objectif? Quel est le rythme? Quel est le coût? Et qui paie? Et moi, tant que j'ai pas la réponse à ces quatre questions-là, je ne sais pas prendre de décision. (...) L'objectif est connu. Je ne connais pas le rythme – c'est-à-dire les milestones –, je ne connais pas le coût et je ne sais pas qui va payer. Donc, tant que je n'ai pas d'informations sur ces quatre éléments, je ne sais pas prendre de décision. (...) Une fois que vous avez décidé le rythme (...) il faut dans un second temps intégrer comment fait-on. Ici on ne répond pas à la question comment.» (ENG-BE)

«On fait une évaluation à l'horizon 2050 de 100% renouvelable. Mais, le problème, c'est qu'elle est extrêmement limitée. (...) Elle doit être certainement complétée pour pouvoir être un outil d'aide à la décision (...) [avec] les dimension sociétales, les dimensions de coût (...). Cette étude-là, en tant que telle, ne permet pas aux décideurs de prendre une décision. Elle répond à la question est-ce que oui ou non c'est possible. Et la réponse est oui. Mais, est-ce qu'elle permet de prendre une décision? La réponse est non, parce que en fait, il y a toute une série de questions auxquelles elle ne répond pas. C'était pas son objectif, mais si vous me dites est-ce que ça c'est un outil d'aide à la décision? Pour partie, mais ça ne suffit pas.» (ENG-BE)

Another reason advanced by political actors for not using the study was the mismatch between the temporal scope of the study and the time horizon of the binding objectives adopted by the Governments. The same applied to the other foresight studies.

«Prenons l'étude 100% renouvelable. Pour l'instant, nous avons les auditions sur le pacte énergétique. Il faut dire qu'on est plus dans une réflexion à 2025-2030 actuellement visant à mettre des balises intermédiaires, sachant effectivement que les objectifs climatiques 2050 impactent aussi notre politique énergétique. Mais c'est vrai qu'on a pour l'instant notamment un horizon qui est la sortie du nucléaire. Donc, même si on sait que ces études existent et qu'il faut aussi une vision à long terme, on est plutôt dans des chemins à moyen terme – même à court terme si on regarde en termes d'investissements – que dans des réflexions à 2050. Donc c'est pour ça peut-être que ces études sont connues, mais qu'on se base sur d'autres travaux – aussi d'universitaires ou de stakeholders – avec des horizons plus courts» (PA-BE)

More fundamentally, the distant temporal scope of studies such as 100% renewable energy is not aligned with the time horizon of political authorities.

«Le politique est très souvent plongé dans la gestion très quotidienne et il ne développe des visions à long terme que très rarement» (POL-BE)

The low level of priority given by Walloon and federal political authorities to the development of renewable energy is also mentioned to explain the implementation gap.

«Aujourd'hui, la priorité en Wallonie, n'est pas de dire "on veut faire du renouvelable à tout prix", et au fédéral, encore moins.» (POL-RW)

Note that a member of a Cabinet stated his intention of using the study to elaborate the integrated Energy-Climate 2030 Plan required by the European Union.

«Elle est quand même intéressante dans tous les impacts, dans toutes les conditions nécessaires au changement, dans les coûts. Il y a plusieurs scénarios qui sont examinés, et dans le coût que ça peut entraîner, si on choisit l'option plutôt biomasse ou forcément importer du combustible, ou plutôt électrique avec du photovoltaïque, éolien (...) Elle est un peu complexe quand même, mais, il y a beaucoup d'éléments utiles. Là [ndlr.: en désignant le rapport de l'étude sur son bureau], j'étais en train de vouloir la réutiliser comme base de réflexion pour voir comment faire évoluer système énergétique.» (PA-RW)

Conceptual Role

The study had a great impact at the conceptual level. It affected the opinion of several actors about the feasibility of a transition to 100% renewable in 2050 at the scale of Belgium. This conclusion was a real surprise for several actors – starting with the sponsors and the authors of the study themselves who, as said before, didn't know what the simulation would come up with.

«Il faut vraiment l'avouer qu'au début, le 100% renouvelable, on n'était pas sûr qu'on allait y arriver.» (PA-BE)

The conditions necessary to ensure the transition to a 100% renewable energy system – i.e. investments equivalent to 2% of GDP and labour flexibility – are perceived differently from one actor to another. This directly affects the perception of the actors of the feasibility of such transition. For some, the study has made them realize that the transition to 100% renewable energy required significant investments and social changes but was achievable with strong political and societal commitment.

«J'espérais qu'on arrive à un résultat favorable... Enfin c'est toujours possible, mais si on arrive à dire c'est possible, mais ça coûte trois fois le PIB chaque année, ben on aurait dit "non, c'est juste pas possible". Ici, non, on arrive à des conclusions qu'il faut mettre 2% du PIB chaque année. C'est cher, mais c'est pas 50% du PIB, c'est quelque chose qu'à un moment, s'il y avait une vraie volonté politique et sociétale de tendre vers ça, on pourrait le faire» (Author of the study)

«The big advantage of this study is that I think that we have at least a quantification – I mean it remains a little bit a utopic idea that we will do that, I mean by 2050 going by 100% renewable energy system. So I don't believe that any of these scenarios will ever be realized, but the interesting thing is that we came to the conclusion that the cost of such a scenario would not be extremely dramatic, because if we talk before, some people had the idea "if we do that, it's going to cost so much money that the whole country will be bankrupt". We have demonstrated that it's not the case although it remains very difficult.» (Author of the study)

For others, all the conditions necessary to ensure the transition highlighted by the analysis convinced them that this transition is unfeasible.

«Moi, autant je veux bien y croire de manière théorique, autant du point de vue pratique, j'ai l'impression que ça reste toujours pas possible. En terme d'impact sur le fonctionnement économique de la Belgique, je continue à avoir des gros doutes. Je veux bien croire que ce soit théoriquement possible d'avoir autant de gigas nécessaires... D'accord, mais concrètement, sur la vie des entreprises et des travailleurs, qu'est-ce que ça implique? Là, je reste dubitatif.» (WU-BE)

«Je crois que la chose la plus pertinente qu'on peut trouver, c'est que oui c'est possible, mais c'est franchement infaisable. On n'a pas les ressources suffisantes. C'est tout. Dans tous les scénarios, il y a toujours une frange plus ou moins

importante d'importation. Que ce soit en biomasse, puisque, je l'ai dit, il faudrait que le territoire de la Belgique augmente de façon substantielle si on voulait se fournir complètement en biomasse pour répondre à tous les besoins. Même dans tous les modèles électriques qu'ils ont développé, soit avec plus de photovoltaïque, soit avec plus d'éolien, dans tous les cas de figure, il y a toujours une partie d'interconnexion qui est nécessaire. On n'exportera rien, mais on aura besoin de l'extérieur pour importer. Ça, c'est une constante. On n'a pas les ressources nécessaires. (...) Mais ça, on va pas le dire très ouvertement non plus au grand public.» (ADM-RW)

At a more macro level, by making the goal 100% renewable accessible, this study – along with other analyses that go in this direction – has helped to change the frame of references. While 10 years ago, the transition to an energy system based 100% on renewable sources was inconceivable, this idea is now imaginable for most actors in the world of energy. For instance, in its current version, the Belgian inter-federal energy Pact includes the objective of a consumption covered by 100% renewable energies in 2050 (see section “3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate mitigation Policy” of Chapter II).

«Moi, d'une manière générale, ce que je retiens de ces différentes études, c'est que finalement, on est sorti des tabous où le développement du renouvelable, les objectifs climatiques apparaissaient comme inaccessibles et trop ambitieux. (...) Quand on se dit que maintenant l'objectif en matière de renouvelable c'est d'arriver à 100% d'énergie renouvelable, à un moment donné dans un certain terme, moi je me rappelle qu'il y a 10-15 ans d'ici, c'était complètement inimaginable comme discours. Donc, les choses ont quand même fort évolué et donc, le cadre de référence a fait évoluer.» (POL-RW)

«10 years ago, the grid operators from the transmission network operator thought that they could go with 5% renewable energy in the system without too many problems, but more than 5% renewable energy on the system, that would give problems, because of the intermittence challenge... Now, grid operators in Germany say that in area where there is much more renewable energy, I think we can deal with 80% of renewable energy in our system without any real big additional cost. So there is a mindset which is changing completely and this study contributed a lot to change this mindset.» (Author of the study)

Last, but not least, the study made some actors realize that a society with 100% renewable energy requires profound socio-economical changes. This was especially the issue of the shift towards seasonal production in some industries, which would imply radical changes in industrial organization and, by extension, in labour organization, that made a deep impression. Almost all the actors I met remember this conclusion of the study.

«Les stakeholders à qui on présentait les résultats de l'étude (...), quand je les rencontre, ils m'en parlent encore toujours. Ça a quand même marqué. Peter Claes de Febeliec, quand il me voit il dit "Oui, cette étude-là, mais c'était fou cette histoire que vous vouliez fermer les sidérurgies pendant l'hiver et laisser tourner uniquement l'été!"» (Author of the study)

«[L'étude] préconisait que la sidérurgie tourne que l'été... Ce sont des faits qui ont marqué. Les gens en rigolent encore, mais au moins, on continue à en parler. Personnellement, on arrive à se demander comment est-ce qu'ils ont osé écrire ça, où est-ce que ce n'était pas justement le petit électrochoc pour se dire "voilà, si on veut s'en sortir aujourd'hui, il faut faire comme ça."» (ENG-BE)

«[J'ai appris] que ça impliquait de profondes modifications sociétales. Ça, ça a été l'élément qui a été le plus éclairant pour moi. C'est possible, mais pas dans le système industriel tel qu'il existe maintenant, et pas avec, je dirais les modes de travail classiques. Ce sont les modifications sociétales pour moi qui ont été les plus emblématiques.» (ENG-BE)

This conclusion aroused very strong opposition from various actors, but it fostered reflection and helped to prepare mentalities regarding the paradigmatic changes that it implies.

«Certains éléments vont pouvoir rester et c'est sans doute ça la valeur. Celle-ci a posé la question avec la sidérurgie de l'organisation du travail. Ça commence à préparer les mentalités (...) on a eu les syndicats qui ont dit "oui, peut-être repenser l'organisation du travail"»(BUS-BE)

In fact, while the shift to a flexible industrial activity based on energy production seemed absurd for many in 2012, this idea is getting more and more interest among energy actors. This is for instance the

case of the Walloon Region, which ordered a research project on industrial flexibility to N-SIDE, ICEDD, UCL and ULg⁴⁰.

«On finance des recherches par exemple sur la flexibilité au niveau industriel. Ça, c'est une des conclusions du backcasting. D'ailleurs, ça m'a fait beaucoup plaisir, parce qu'ils ont fait beaucoup référence au backcasting.» (ADM-RW)

Political Role

The study was – and still is – used for political purposes. As mentioned before, one of the objectives of Minister Nolleet was to crystalize the position of the Walloon and Flemish socialists in favour of the transition towards 100% renewable energy in 2050. The study was useful to him during a number of meetings with socialists to remind them that their parties had participated in this initiative in favour of the 100% renewable target.

«Ca m'a déjà servi à plusieurs reprises, au fait qu'ils – les socialistes francophones et néerlandophones – avaient pris une position favorable à cette étude. Mais c'est plus l'acte politique du fait d'avoir demandé l'étude et puis d'avoir dit c'est possible, puisque le résultat disait que c'était possible (...) À l'époque, on l'a utilisée, évidemment, et dans les médias d'une part, dans les différents Parlements aussi et comme acte politique pour figer la position des socialistes. (...) [Je l'utilise] pour le fait qu'il y a eu une étude et que les socialistes sont là-dessus. J'ai dû rappeler cela à quelques socialistes à la veille de Paris en disant "vous savez, on avait initié ça avec Paul Magnette"» (POL-BE)

The other objective of Minister Nolleet study was also political – i.e.: demonstrating that the nuclear phase-out in 2025 and the transition towards 100% renewable energy in 2050 are feasible to give support to the policy in favour of a Belgium without nuclear and fossil energy that he wanted to implement. In that context, Minister referred to the study.

«J'ai systématiquement illustré mon propos autour de ça. Donc, j'étais ministre à l'époque, donc pour moi, c'était évidemment quelque chose d'important. À la fois au niveau wallon, à la fois dans mes contacts au niveau fédéral, à la fois aussi dans le Conseil des ministres européens, je me souviens avoir montré que c'était possible. Maintenant, c'est plus qu'une question de choix politique évidemment. Et l'idée eu été, mais bon ça, ça n'a pas été possible, de l'implémenter dans la déclaration gouvernementale du gouvernement suivant. Mais là, on n'a pas été appelé à négocier.» (POL-BE)

However, because of the economic and social requirements to be fulfilled to develop a renewable energy-based system highlighted in the study, Jean-Marc Nolleet and other members of his party preferred basing their discourse on other sources such as the study “Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium” which led to more favourable conclusions regarding the conditions for the energy transition.

«[J'utilise] surtout celle-ci [ndlr.: Belgique bas-carbone] et alors quand je regarde aussi les chiffres économiques puisque on voit que on n'est pas perdant. Et donc, en fonction du choix, ça c'est pour moi aussi important. Celle-ci, je l'utilise souvent en fait, plus que celle-là [100% renouvelable].» (POL-BE)

«Quand j'ai quelqu'un de chez nous en face de moi, de la communication qui me dit "il faut la [ndlr.: 100% renouvelable] mettre en avant", je lui ai dit "mais tu sais, dedans on travaille l'été et on se repose l'hiver (...) C'est fini les vacances!". (...) Je ramène toujours cet argument là en leur disant "molo molo avec l'étude".» (PA-BE)

While the former Minister who had commissioned this study as well as some members of his party have turned to other sources to support their speech, other actors refer to it to support an ambitious policy to replace nuclear power by renewable energy. Members of environmental NGOs, renewable energy sector, or even trade unions have used and still use the study to show that a vision of a Belgium without nuclear and fossil energy by 2050 is realistic.

⁴⁰ <https://www.industore-project.be>

«Encore maintenant elle est utilisée souvent comme référence, surtout par les mouvements écologistes qui s'en servent pour dire " Vous voyez, il faut aller plus vite et c'est possible et on n'a qu'à...". Dans des conseils, dans des débats politiques publics, dans des déclarations à gauche et à droite, on revient souvent avec.» (BUS-BE)

«On l'a utilisée aussi pour une position sur l'énergie pour indiquer que c'est possible la transition vers 100% énergies renouvelables sous telles ou telles conditions. Là, on a clairement utilisé ça dans notre positionnement interne.» (WU-BE)

«Par exemple, le 25, je me mobilise pour la chaîne humaine pour la sortie du nucléaire. C'est super d'avoir une étude du Bureau du Plan, car c'est impossible de les suspecter d'être des gauchistes qui démontrent qu'effectivement un scénario de sortie du nucléaire coûte moins cher qu'un scénario de poursuite dans le nucléaire. C'est un argument excellent par rapport à tout le lobby nucléaire qui existe. C'est très important. Et d'autre part, grâce à ces études-là, c'est scientifiquement prouvé qu'elle est possible, qu'elle est bénéfique... Et aussi qu'on a intérêt à se bouger pour que ça arrive, puisque c'est pas du tout les directions dans lesquelles on est actuellement.» (PA-RW)

The fact that study was carried out by the Federal Planning Bureau (FPB) renders the study even more useful to support 100% renewable vision. This public institute, and more specifically its team “Energy-Transport”, has actually the trust of almost all the actors in the field of energy. It enjoys a solid reputation for its long experience in providing data on current situation and forecasts and for its deep expertise on the energy system. Besides its experience and its expertise, its status as a public research institutes adds even more credibility to the FPB analysis. Several actors believe that public research institutes, just like universities, conduct analyses in the interests of the public good, while private consultants might not be neutral because of hidden agenda. In this context, the analyses of the FPB are rarely questioned.

«C'est vrai que lorsqu'on se réfère au Bureau du plan, on sait au moins qu'on s'appuie sur les chiffres qui seront difficilement remis en question par d'autres partis politiques ou par le citoyen ou par les fédérations.» (PA-RW)

That said, as explained previously, this study has prompted a lot of reactions and severe criticism from incumbents. Because of the counter-expertise developed by employers' federations, some actors prefer not to refer to this study in some circumstances.

«Souvent, c'est très difficile pour ces études d'avoir un soutien général de tous les stakeholders et ça rend l'utilité... La FEB a fort discrédité, surtout cette étude [ndlr.: 100% renouvelable]. Du coup, comme nous on utilise ces rapports et quand on doit le faire avec eux, ils disent que c'est pas suffisamment fondé et là... ils ne veulent pas en parler. Pour nous, l'étude devient aussi moins intéressante à ce moment» (WU-B)

Finally, the study was mentioned by David Clarinval (MR) and Corentin de Salle (Centre Jean Gol) in their book “Energy Fiasco” to illustrate the totalitarian dream of controlling all the components of the human beings' life proper to proponents of the sustainable development. They explain that, by developing sustainable development plans, some ecologists aim at controlling all the human activities around common principles and that this study is a classic example of such aspiration.

Process Role

I did not observe any process role for this study.

3.3.5. Key Lessons

The purpose of the study “100% renewable” was primarily political. Minister Jean-Marc Nollet took advantage of the collective emotion caused by the Fukushima nuclear disaster to embark the other Belgian energy ministers in the realization of a study assessing the feasibility of the transition towards a fossil and nuclear free Belgium by 2050. The Nollet's objectives were to crystalize the position of the Walloon and Flemish socialists in favour of the transition towards 100% renewable energy in 2050 and to promote his vision of a fossil and nuclear-free Belgium by demonstrating with an independent analysis that developing an energy system entirely based on renewable energy is feasible.

As shown in the chart below, this political role was more or less fulfilled. Minister Nollet referred to the study on the one hand to remind the socialists that they took part and supported this study in favour of the 100% renewable target, and on the other hand to support his discourse pro-renewable energy. Nevertheless, because of the economic and social conditions to be met to develop a 100% renewable energy-based system highlighted in the study, Jean-Marc Nollet and other members of his party preferred basing their discourse on other sources. Unlike the Greens, other actors – mainly members from environmental NGOs, renewable energy sector, or even trade unions – have used and still use the study to support an ambitious policy to replace nuclear power by renewable energy. That being said, owing to the counter-expertise developed by incumbents, some actors prefer not to refer to the study “100% renewable”. This is indeed the study that gave rise to most questions and criticism from the part of employers’ federations, dominant energy market operators, but also from political authorities including the deputy David Clarinval. The scenarios actually comprise a number of disruptive elements that trigger criticism and opposition – the most talked-about element being the shift towards seasonal production in some industries to cope with intermittent renewable energy production.

The disruptive character of the scenarios and the important communication on the study have contributed to strengthen its conceptual role. The study affected the opinion of several actors about the feasibility of a transition to 100% renewable in 2050 at the Belgium scale. Moreover, it made some actors realize that a society with 100% renewable energy requires profound social and economic changes. Even if it aroused very strong opposition from various actors, the shift towards seasonal production in some industries proposed by the economic optimization analysis made an impression, fostered reflection and helped to prepare mentalities regarding the important social and economic changes that it involves. At a more macro level, in synergy with other analyses that also lead to the conclusion that the transition to 100% renewable is feasible, the study has helped to change the frame of references. The idea of a transition to an energy system based 100% on renewable sources is now imaginable for most actors in the world of energy, while it was completely inconceivable 10 years ago.

It seems that the study has no instrumental role. An argument made by Ecolo for not using the study they ordered to devise renewable energy policy is that it was published at the end of the legislature, when most of the policy measures were already finalized and approved. The Greens were not able to use the study in the following legislature as they were relegated to the opposition after the election of 2014. The reasons set out for explaining the non-use of the study as decision support tools by members of the political majority are about the same that those cited for explaining the non-use of “Low-carbon Wallonia” and “Low-carbon Belgium” by political authorities. While some actors explain that the study doesn’t inform on the policies to implement today and at the various stage of the pathway towards a 100% renewable energy system, other highlight governance problem – i.e.: The low level of priority given by political authorities to reduce fossil and nuclear energy, and the mismatch between the temporal scope of the study and the time horizon of policy-making.

Figure 71. Role of the study “100% renewable” in policy-making. Each axis corresponds to a type of role. The centre of the chart equates to a minor role and the extremity to an important role.

Looking at the level of appropriation of the study per actor, it appears that Jean-Marc Nollet, who was at the origin of the study, and to a lesser extent the other three ministers of energy appropriate the findings of the study. The same applies to the administrations of energy which were involved in the project⁴¹. The other administrations, the workers unions and the environmental and development NGOs have usually heard about the study, know its main conclusions and remember the most talked-about issues – i.e.: the shift towards seasonal production in steel industry. Just like the “Low-carbon Belgium”, the content of the study is very well known by the employers’ federations and the dominant energy market operators who developed counter-expertise about the study. The “100% renewable energy” is the study that has penetrated the most the political sphere. Almost all the political authorities or political advisers I met, if they have not read the study, have at least heard of it. Some members of traditional political parties even reacted to the study at the Parliament or in the press. This may be explained by the facts that the study was ordered by four ministers, that it has been very much commented in the media and that some of the conclusions of the study are very controversial and triggering reactions. Nevertheless, the penetration of the study in the political sphere is limited to specialists of climate-energy issues. In each party, there are very few such specialists.

⁴¹ Note that I haven’t investigated the reception of the study in the Flemish and Brussels Capital Regions.

Figure 72. Level of appropriation per actor for the study “100% renewable”. Each axis corresponds to a type of actor. The centre of the chart equates to a low level of appropriation and the extremity to a high level of appropriation.

Figure 73. Timeline illustrating the history of the study "100% renewable"

3.4. Case Study n°4. Prospective Study: Energy Transition

3.4.1. Emergence

The last case studied is very different from the other ones, not only regarding the approach implemented, but also with respect to the sponsor. This is indeed the only study that has not been commissioned by a political or administrative authority in charge of energy or climate related matters. This is indeed IWEPS – a public scientific institute that helps public authorities to make decisions – which following a survey of administrations has identified the energy transition as a priority prospective issues for Wallonia and has decided to finance a study on this particular topic. Between May 2010 and April 2011, IWEPS, in collaboration with the Destrée Institute and the Spiral Research Center of the University of Liège, has actually consulted representatives of the different departments of the Public Service of Wallonia as well as research teams that are members of the of the Walloon Regional Prospective Research and Watch System (SRPW) with a view to identifying transdisciplinary and prospective research topics to be investigated as a priority. This co-production work involving producers and users of scenarios allowed to delimit five research topics: “Migration flows from Brussels to Wallonia and their consequences”; “Wallonia: towards a dual society or a more solidary model?”; “Welcoming and accompanying elderly people in Wallonia”; “The energy transition: risks and opportunities for Wallonia”; and “The evolution of the territorial configuration of Walloon public action” (Guyot & *al.*, 2012). In the light of these priority prospective issues for Wallonia, IWEPS has launched two studies, one on aging, and another one on the energy transition.

IWEPS launched the call for tender for the prospective study on the energy transition in October 2011. The initial objective of the request was to analyse the risks and opportunities engendered by the end of cheap oil for different components of the Walloon economy, the organization of work and the articulations between the private and the professional life. In the specifications, IWEPS insisted on the importance of carrying out this study on the basis of a participatory prospective approach. The need to evaluate long-term impacts of energy transition in a systemic and transdisciplinary perspective articulating qualitative and quantitative approaches was indeed clearly stated. The sponsor also requested to actively integrate the Walloon administration in the process, to produce policy-relevant results in order to help the decision-makers and to valorize them in the political sphere and in the scientific world.

This was a project proposal developed by a multidisciplinary consortium piloted again by CLIMACT that won the bid. For this project, CLIMACT worked in collaboration with the Sustainable Development Task force of the Federal Planning Bureau, ICEDD, the Institute for Sustainable Development (IDD), the Center for Operations Research and Econometrics (CORE) of the Catholic University of Louvain (UCL) and the Laboratory of Studies on New Technologies of Information, Innovation and Change (LENTIC) of the University of Liège (ULg). It is interesting to note that the researcher from LENTIC had never worked on energy issues before. Even if it caused some difficulties – specially to define the concepts – the diversity of the consortium members' backgrounds, as we will see in the presentation of the results, allowed to bring very different views on the issue.

The steering committee consisted of IWEPS, the Minister-President's Cabinet, the DGO4, the DGO6 and the Destrée Institute.

3.4.2. Presentation of the Study

Methodology

The scenarios were built on the basis of a qualitative methodology inspired by the work of the French prospectivists Hugues de Jouvenel and Michel Godet. This methodology aimed at exploring the possible evolutions of a system on the basis of an analysis of the interactions between the variables which compose this system. It led to the construction and the analysis of exploratory scenarios allowing, as their name suggests, to explore the range of possible futures. The study involved five steps:

the problem definition and the choice of time horizon; the identification of key variables; the exploration of the interactions between the variables and the development of the assumptions; the formulation of possible futures; and the comparison of the scenarios followed by the drawing up of recommendations.

Based on systems theory, the consortium identified 27 key variables for the Walloon energy system. The interactions between the variables were explored through a structural analysis. This was performed by resorting to a structural analysis matrix and the MICMAC⁴² (i.e.: Impact Matrix Cross-Reference Multiplication Applied to a Classification) method developed by Michel Godet. The structural analysis led to the development of a cartography of the variables regarding their motricity and dependence. While the variables with a high motricity have a significant influence on the evolution of the energy system, those with a high dependence have an evolution that is strongly dependent on other variables. The cartography enabled to classify the variables into three categories: “Prolog”, “Heart” and “Epilog”. The following figure illustrates the cartography of the variables forming the “Prolog”, the “Heart” and the “Epilog” in the motricity - dependence map [Figure 74].

Figure 74. Cartography of the variables forming the prolog, the heart and the epilog in the motricity - dependence map in the study “Energy transition” (CLIMACT & al. 2015, p. 34)

The possible evolutions of the variables that form the “Prologue” (i.e.: variables with a high motricity) were then explored. As showed in the figure below, the assumptions regarding the possible evolutions of each variable where combined [Figure 75].

⁴² Matrice d’Impacts Croisés Multiplication Appliqués à un Classement (MICMAC)

Figure 75. Combinations of the assumptions on the possible evolutions of the different variables that form the Prolog in the study "Energy transition" (CLIMACT & al. 2015, p. 38)

Those combinations of possible futures constitute the starting point of the scenarios. They are four scenarios. For each scenario, the evolution of the system has been defined by analysing the evolution of the variables that form the "Heart". Afterwards, the consortium analysed the consequences of each scenario on the variables that form the "Epilogue" (i.e.: variables with a high dependence). Finally, an analysis of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) was carried out for the different scenarios. The SWOT analysis concerned five issues, i.e.: social cohesion, security of supply, environmental protection, democratic participation and financial viability. This analysis led to the development of policy recommendations.

The present approach enabled to build four contrasted exploratory scenarios entitled "A decentralized Wallonia in a Kyoto + world", "An autonomist Wallonia, atypical in a 'petro-optimistic' world", "A technological and dual Wallonia" and "A follower Wallonia in a conscious world". These scenarios were presented as narratives, each story being divided into four chapters that correspond to the "Prolog", the "Heart", the "Epilogue" and the SWOT analysis. The scenarios didn't include transition pathways. According to the authors, the development of such pathways would have need further work.

A fifth scenario that did not result from the prospective analysis was added. Entitled "Sustainable development", this visionary scenario was built on the basis of a study carried out by the Sustainable Development Task force of the Federal Planning Bureau in 2007 (Task force développement durable, 2007). The "Sustainable Development" scenario was the result of the combination of the "Pyramid" and "Mosaic" scenarios presented in the study in question. These were built according to a backcasting approach based on sustainable development goals to be achieved by 2050.

The approach implemented was expert-based in the sense that it was mainly the members of the consortium who developed and analysed the scenarios. One consultation gathering six experts from administration, employers' federations, workers' unions and environmental NGO was organized. It was again not a scenario co-construction workshop as such. The consultation actually took place at the end of the process, when the scenarios were already almost completed. The purpose of this discussion with the stakeholders was to identify the opportunities, the risks and the potential consequences of these scenarios for the Region.

«Il y a eu des consultations des stakeholders, mais sur des scénarios déjà très aboutis, donc je ne pense pas que le débat ait vraiment pris dans ce cas. Ca a été communiqué trop tard.» (ADM-RW)

Results

The stories of each scenarios are pretty rich and multidimensional. It is thus quite complex to summarize the results of the study. A cross-analysis of the scenarios highlights a series of risks and opportunities related to the energy transition.

An important risk that emerges from the analysis concerns the social and territorial dualizations. It appears that the different scenarios generate various forms of impact on social cohesion – i.e.: dualizations cities *versus* countryside, producers *versus* consumers, energivore *versus* non-energivore firms, rich *versus* poor persons. Even if the authors suggest a few possible directions to reduce such impacts (i.e.: educational and vocational training), they state that the evolution of social and territorial dualizations represents a major uncertainty that requires further studies.

The issues of the costs and benefits associated with the energy transition also seems to be fundamental. The costs and their distribution among different actors (i.e.: households, firms, public authorities) vary from on scenario to another. It appears that the scenarios involving rational use of energy enable a less expensive energy transition. Conversely, transition pathways involving inaction or unsuitable measures can be extremely expensive. Furthermore, the authors encourage new forms of financing and the pooling of public and private resources. According to the authors; the question of the costs and financing of the energy transition should, just like the impacts on social cohesion, be studied more deeply.

More generally, a number of prerequisites for the energy transition are highlighted. They concern the need to develop a vision as well as a clear and stable regulatory framework to the horizon 2030 at the minimum and ideally at the horizon 2050. The necessity to mobilize and develop synergies between all the different society actors, but also the role of public authorities to facilitate the emergence of such alliances are emphasized.

3.4.3. Communication, Follow-Up and Reception

The study was published in March 2015 in form of a report and executive summary. There was no communication to the press and very few presentations. The study has generated almost no reaction and has been little relayed within the network of energy players. To my knowledge, only IEW, APERE and Etopia relayed the study. Of the people I met, very little knew about it.

When it was published, the study was presented to the Cabinet of Paul Furlan (PS) who was the Minister in charge of energy in Wallonia. The study received a rather lukewarm reception, the cabinet members showing little interest in it.

«Le rapport a été présenté à son cabinet. Dans son cabinet ils ont plusieurs matières. Il y a le logement social notamment, il y a l'énergie (...) Lors de cette présentation, ils ont dit " ça ne nous intéresse pas. De toute façon, tout est réglé par le marché ou par les normes européennes, donc nous, on n'a rien à faire. Donc, continuez à travailler sur l'énergie si ça vous intéresse, mais...". (...) Ce qui les intéresse, c'est simplement d'avoir des chiffres sur l'habitat, sur les logements sociaux.»

It actually appears that mitigating climate change was far from being a priority for the Cabinet Furlan.

«On est dans un contexte politique où la ligne de conduite, c'est on respecte ce que l'Europe nous dicte et on ne cherche pas à aller plus loin, à révolutionner les choses. (...) Ils ont choisi leurs combats, et l'énergie n'en fait pas partie.» (ADM-RW)

Shortly after, on the 24 March 2015, CLIMACT in the presence of IWEPS members presented the study to the Walloon Parliament. The presentation of the scenarios in the Energy Commission provoked little reaction: Only three parliamentarians expressed themselves concerning the study (Parlement Wallon, 2015). The Minister of Energy who was present at the hearing made no comments or questions.

«On est allé présenter ça au Parlement. Ça a été un petit peu un flop.»

«Philippe Henry (Ecolo) m'a dit que c'était lamentable. Et il m'a dit: "Je ne vais pas passer mon temps à poser des questions, je sais qu'il n'y aura pas de débat vu qu'il n'y a personne". Donc voilà, c'est dingue le désintéret qu'il y a dans la matière» (PA-BE)

It seems that the presentation to the Walloon Parliament hasn't left a mark in Deputies' memories.

«B. Celle-là, je ne la connais pas.

A. Pourtant, vous étiez à la présentation au Parlement. Vous ne vous en souvenez pas?

B. Ça se peut. J'en vois tellement...» (Walloon Deputy who reacted to the study during the presentation to Parliament)

However, during this presentation to the Parliament, the study provoked the interest of some members of IEW and Ecolo attending the assembly. While the member of the environmental NGO interviewed one of the authors of the study and published an article presenting it (see Warnant, 2015), the Ecologist invited one of the authors to come and discuss the study within the Energy Commission of the party. At this presentation, the study was greeted with a lot of enthusiasm.

«Ils m'ont contacté et j'ai passé une matinée avec eux à discuter. Eux étaient, semble-t-il, très intéressé.» (Author of the study)

«C'est un des documents que je trouve les plus intéressants qu'on ait écrits ces dernières années.» (PA-BE)

The study also aroused the interest of the Energy Department of DGO4 who was part of the study's steering committee. The DGO4 agent who had followed the study presented it in his Department. This presentation received a rather mixed reception. While some found that taking a sociological view of the energy transition brings a real added value, others considered that the approach is not serious.

«Je l'avais présenté à une réunion de département. Certain avaient eu une réaction: "c'est fumeux", "ce sont des scénarios qui n'iront jamais". C'est un peu science-fiction pour certaines personnes. D'autres avaient été assez ouverts et avaient trouvé ça intéressant comme démarche.» (ADM-RW)

The choice of a purely qualitative approach can contribute to explain the fact that several persons considered the study not very credible. It actually seems that quantitative approaches, like modelling, are often perceived as more robust and more objective.

«Le problème c'est qu'ici [ndlr.: Etude "Transition énergétique] tu mets beaucoup de tes projections mentales dans le résultat. (...) Tu définis toute une série de variables, tu les positionnes un peu comme tu veux. Moi, j'étais et reste assez perplexe. (...) et puis après, quand tu arrives dans la définition du scénario et dans le narratif du scénario, c'est quand même très fort tes projections. Je trouve que la part de subjectivité est beaucoup plus importante là-dedans [ndlr.: que dans les approches basées sur des modélisations]. De mon point de vue, ça manque de solidité ou de quantification sans doute.» (Author of the study)

«Je suis toujours fort attentif aux chiffres (...) parce que les chiffres crédibilisent le propos scientifique et ils y sont quasi inhérents.» (POL-BE)

The presentations to the Walloon Parliament, to the Cabinet Furlan, to the DGO4 and to Ecolo are to my knowledge the only activity of communication carried out to promote the study among the actors of climate-energy policy in Wallonia. Aside from the consultation during the scenario building process that gathered six persons, the study hasn't been presented to the stakeholders.

Finally, it has to be noted that the points of attention highlighted by the scenario analysis included among others the challenges related to the evolution of electricity networks. This study finding stimulated the Energy Department of DGO4 and IWEPS to order a new foresight study on that particular issue. The study carried out by ICEDD, CLIMACT, ULg, IDD and the Federal Planning Bureau differs from the study "Energy transition" in the sense that it is more participatory and that it involves both qualitative and quantitative approaches (ICEDD & al., 2018). This study is presented in the section devoted to the climate mitigation scenarios for Wallonia (see section "4.2.2. Climate mitigation scenarios for Wallonia" of Chapter II).

3.4.4. Role of the Study in Policy-Making

Instrumental Role

The study was not used to inform political decisions. As said before, it generated little interest within the Cabinet of the Minister in charge of energy and in the Walloon parliament. The study is, so to speak, unknown in the political sphere. Among the Walloon administration, the study aroused the interest of some agents of the Energy Department. However, those people did not use the study in their daily work. They considered that the report is hardly usable because it didn't lead to clear policy recommendations. Owing to its broad scope that include the entire socio-technical system, the study doesn't lead to the definition of concrete policy recommendations, but rather to the identification of opportunities and threats that should be taken into consideration when developing low-carbon policy (e.g.: potential impact on social cohesion). Furthermore, a member of the administration regretted that the study didn't identify among the possible futures analysed neither the scenario to be promoted, nor the policies to be implemented at the present time to make such scenario a reality.

«Ce qui manquait un peu, c'est qu'à la fin de l'étude, il y a eu plusieurs scénarios et on n'a pas déterminé lequel était le scénario à promouvoir. Et surtout, même si on avait défini cette situation idéale, l'étude n'étudie pas du tout comment y arriver à travers le temps. (...) Que doit-on faire en 2020, 2030 etc. pour y arriver? C'est dommage, s'il y avait eu cette approche-là dans l'étude, si on avait dit "voilà le scénario idéal et pour arriver là, voilà ce qu'il faut faire dès aujourd'hui et demain", on aurait pu avoir un peu plus de répercussions. (...) Mais je crois que ce "scénario idéal", on ne peut pas le décider nous sans le politique, et le politique n'est pas au comité d'accompagnement.» (ADM-RW)

The absence of quantitative data was also pointed out by the members of the administration as a reason for not using the study.

«Les scénarios etc., moi, je ne pense pas qu'on les utilisera. D'autant plus qu'ils ne sont pas chiffrés. (...) L'IWEPS a un peu plus de mal à intégrer la vision quantitative dans leurs démarches prospectives pour plusieurs raisons qui sont les leurs. Alors que nous, dans l'énergie, on a bien souvent besoin d'approches chiffrées: combien de consommation d'énergie, combien de renouvelable on va produire, etc.» (ADM-RW)

Quantitative data actually appears to be necessary in the field of climate-energy. Policy-makers need accurate quantitative data on the energy consumption and production, and on the GHG emissions generated by such activities.

«Oui, on a besoin de chiffres. Oui, on a besoin d'un monitoring. Oui, on a besoin de choses précises selon des scénarios qui tiennent le mieux possible la route. Sinon, le politique, il ne décidera jamais.» (PA-RW)

It is interesting to mention that, despite the lack of quantitative data and policy recommendation, the study is one of the main sources used by Ecolo to develop its new energy vision. The members of the Energy Commission of Ecolo who invited the authors to come and present the project are using a series of studies, including this one, to develop their vision of the transition towards a system based on 100% renewable energies by 2050. To elaborate this vision, they have been inspired by one of the scenarios of the study, namely "A decentralized Wallonia in a Kyoto + world". A certain number of elements developed in the study are reflected in Ecolo's text, including the question of the impact of energy choices on democratic structures (Commission Energie d'Ecolo, 2017).

«On est en train d'essayer de construire un scénario pluriannuel pour recoller avec l'objectif 100% renouvelable et donc, mis à jour par rapport à ce qui a été fait. Et dans ce cadre-là, c'était un des trois apports, je vais dire. Il y avait aussi les scénarios des Verts Européens (...)» (POL-BE)

«Le texte que j'ai fait sur la transition, il s'inspire quand même fort de l'étude de prospective. Il y a pas mal d'éléments qui sont dedans. (...) C'est vraiment celui-là [ndlr.: le scénario "Une Wallonie décentralisée dans un monde Kyoto +"] qui nous a guidés, parce que quand on voit que dans les autres [ndlr.: scénarios], nous, sur notre point de vue politique, sur nos valeurs, notre volonté de faire avancer les choses, on s'y retrouve pas. Soit, c'est plus d'inégalité, alors parfois c'est des inégalités territoriales. Quand on voit un des scénarios, je ne sais plus comment il s'appelle, on sent qu'il y a des territoires

qui vont d'abord être abandonnés, puis revenir... Tout ça ne va pas se faire sans dégâts sociaux extrêmement importants à certains endroits.» (PA-BE)

However, as the Green party is in the opposition, its vision has little influence on policy-making.

Conceptual Role

As the study is not known by many actors, its conceptual role is low. It did not really contribute to expand knowledge base and introduce new ideas or concept at the collective level. Its influence remains at the individual level. It has indeed impacted the attitude of some people who have read the study.

By exploring the interactions between technical and social variables on the basis of a cross-disciplinary approach, the study contributed to changes in the way some perceive energy issues. It made some actors realize that the low-carbon transition is not only a technical issue and that it can have important impacts on the social cohesion.

«Ca permet d'élargir notre vision qu'on a parfois ici [ndlr.: à l'administration], trop technique, trop terre à terre. De penser de façon un peu plus large aux conséquences de la transition énergétique. D'ailleurs, quand je l'avais présentée en réunion de département, ceux qui s'étaient montrés ouverts, ils avaient dit "Oui, on ne pense pas à ça... ça va avoir des répercussions sur autre chose"» (ADM-RW)

«Ce qui m'a frappé et que je trouvais très original, c'est toute la discussion sur les implications sociétale, la cohésion sociale. (...) Cette étude-là allait plus loin, c'était pas juste au niveau technique» (NGO-RW)

This particular issue – just like other issues that could not be addressed when analysing only the technical component of the socio-technical system – is not known by many actors in the field of energy who are primarily engineers or economists. If the study would have been communicated more widely, it might have had a stronger conceptual role. However, the communication and the appropriation of scenarios like those analysed in the “Energy transition” study are difficult. Such qualitative scenarios are indeed very dense and multidimensional, and therefore much more difficult to communicate and appropriate than purely quantitative scenarios.

«C'est la force du quanti. C'est que les données sont plus facilement utilisables, ça parle plus vite, ça a un côté plus opérationnel, plus vite appropriable. Le quali, en terme de communication et de réappropriation, c'est plus compliqué. (...) 50%, c'est facile à voir. C'est 50%. On se réapproprie le truc. Les scénarios, ils sont complexes, ils sont touffus, ils sont multidimensionnels, et donc, c'est pas évident d'avoir une vision claire» (Sponsor of the study)

Inasmuch as participation facilitates appropriation, involving the stakeholders earlier and more in the scenario building process could have also strengthen the conceptual role of the study.

Political and Process Roles

I did not observe any political or process role.

3.4.5. Key Lessons

The study “Energy transition” was intended to be a decision support tool. However, as we can see in the following chart [Figure 76], the instrumental role of the study is nil. Several reasons help to explain why the study hasn't reach its objective. The first reason is the lack of interest of Walloon political authorities for climate mitigation issues. This issue was apparently not a priority of Minister Furlan, who was in charge of energy at that time. It is more or less the same for the members that compose the Energy Commission of the Walloon parliament. The commissions are indeed composed with members from the majority parties and since the 2014 elections, the Greens are not part anymore of the majority. Another reason cited for explaining the non-use of the study in devising climate mitigation policy is that it sketches possible futures but doesn't inform on the policies to be

implemented today to reach such futures. Last but not least, the lack of quantitative data also contributes to explain the implementation gap.

The study “Energy transition” has a very limited conceptual role. Because the study is not known by many actors, its influence remains at the individual level. It has modified the perception of energy issues of some people who have read the study. By exploring, on the basis of a cross-disciplinary approach, the interactions between technical and social variables of the energy system, the study made those persons realize that the low-carbon transition is not only a technical issue and that it can have important impacts on the social cohesion.

Figure 76. Role of the study “Energy transition” in policy-making. Each axis corresponds to a type of role. The centre of the chart equates to a minor role and the extremity to an important role.

Globally, the level of appropriation of the study is extremely low, as illustrated in the figure below [Figure 77]. The study is known by one member of the administration who was part of the steering committee as well as some of his colleagues to whom he presented the study. Some members of IEW and Ecolo who discovered the study during the presentation at the Parliament have also appropriated themselves the study and communicated it in their organization. Apart from that, the study is so to speak unknown to the actors of the world of energy. As explained previously, the factors explaining this low level of appropriation concern the little interest of members of traditional political parties for climate energy issues, the low level of participation in the scenario building process, the lack of communication of the study’s findings, and the difficulties to communicate and appropriate the results of qualitative foresight analyses. Note that the present research might have slightly increased the appropriation of the study by the actors of energy. As explained in the presentation of the interviews process, I brought with me a printed version of the four foresight studies analysed and the respondent was allowed to skim through the documents during the interview (see section “2.2.2. Semi-structured interviews” of the same chapter). When discovering the study “Energy transition”, several persons seemed to be interested by the study and asked me to send them the report by email. I have met again some of them after the interview and a few of them told me that they looked over the report and that they drew relevant information on social implications of the energy transition.

Figure 77. Level of appropriation per actor for the study “Energy transition”. Each axis corresponds to a type of actor. The centre of the chart equates to a low level of appropriation and the extremity to a high level of appropriation.

Figure 78. Timeline illustrating the history of the study "Energy transition"

4. Cross-Case Analysis

4.1. Roles of the Studies in Policy-Making

In this first section devoted to the cross-case analysis, I present the similarities and differences between the studies regarding their role in policy-making. The radar chart below highlights those similarities and differences [Figure 79]. It places the role pattern of each case study on top of each other. In this chart, each axis corresponds to a type of role. The centre of the chart equates to a minor role and the extremity to an important role. A colour is assigned to each case study: “Low-carbon Wallonia” in blue, “Low-carbon Belgium” in green, “100% renewable” in red and “Energy transition” in yellow. Again, this is by no mean an attempt to quantify the role of the studies in policy-making. Such display simply intends to summarize in a single graph the main results of the analysis and facilitates comparison of the different case studies regarding their role in policy-making.

Figure 79. Role of the different studies in policy-making. Each axis corresponds to a type of role. The centre of the chart equates to a minor role and the extremity to an important role. A colour is assigned to each study, as indicate in the caption of the graph.

For facilitating the cross-case analysis, a timeline containing the main events associated with each study is also displayed hereunder [Figure 80].

Figure 80. Timeline illustrating the history of each study. "Low-carbon Wallonia" is coloured in blue, "Low-carbon Belgium" in green, "100% renewable" in red, and "Energy transition" in yellow.

4.1.1. Similarities between Case Studies

Instrumental Role

A first similarity concerns the instrumental role. The studies analysed have very limited or nil instrumental role. The “Low-carbon Wallonia” is the only study that has an instrumental role. AWAC actually used this study as a support tool to develop the first draft of the Walloon air climate energy Plan 2016-2022. Apart from that, the study doesn’t appear to be used as a tool to inform policy-makers when developing climate-mitigation policy. Such gap between low-carbon scenarios and policy is not surprising. As previously explained, the purely instrumental use of scientific knowledge in policy-making is generally quite limited because the **relationship between sciences and policy** is neither linear nor mechanical (see section “5.2.1. Knowledge and governance: Beyond the rational knowledge-based policy-making model” of Chapter I). This factor is not specific neither to foresight studies, nor to climate mitigation issues.

«Dans la plupart des pays, mais encore plus en Belgique, on peut pas dire qu’il y a un ministre qui commande une étude et puis il prend une décision sur la base de l’étude. Ça ne marche pas comme ça, il n’y a pas de lien direct.» (ADM-BE)

The low use of scientific knowledge to devise policy is particularly marked in Belgium. This is related to specific characteristics of the Belgian political system that have been presented previously: the *partitocracy*, the *pillarization* and the *corporatism* (see section “3.1. Overview of the Belgian political system”). It appears that those characteristics reduce the use and influence of scientific knowledge. On the one hand, against a background where majority parties hold nearly all the power, the main actors in policy-making are the ministerial cabinets. In Belgium, those actors don’t rely much on scientific knowledge. Instead, they use other bases to devise policy, including concertation and consultation of civil society (Petit Jean, 2016). In such highly politicized context, scientific knowledge is rather used to justify decisions already taken or to improve someone’s relative position in the policy systems compared to opponents (i.e.: political role).

«C’est sûr que si l’étude ne sert pas la politique, le politique s’en sert pas.» (PA-RW)

On the other hand, as explained by Petit Jean, “*the legacy of pillarization in Belgium tends to limit the circulation of certain knowledge that could undermine a fragile political balance between the different actors of Belgian politics*” (Petit Jean 2016, p. 259). In this type of system, the political debate is indeed merely about distribution of power, rather than the content of policies.

In addition to the public authorities’ relationship with knowledge, other types of factors emerge from the analysis of the interviews to explain the implementation gap. The first type of explanatory factor concerns the **characteristics of the studies** – i.e.: internal factor. Many actors claim that the studies don’t meet the policy-makers information needs. They actually don’t effectively inform on *how* to make the low-carbon transition happens – e.g.: *How to steer the low-carbon transition? What policies to implement? At what levels of power? How to ensure coherence with other sectoral policies? How to finance such transition? By whom?* Such information gaps have been highlighted for the four studies analysed. All those studies sketch different low-carbon scenarios and explore the implications of such scenarios regarding various components of the socio-technical system. On the basis of this analysis of the environmental, economic and/or social impacts of the scenarios, the authors either formulate recommendations on technology and behaviours that should be promoted to reduce GHG (e.g.: electrification of transports) or identify the opportunities and threats that should be taken into consideration when developing low-carbon policy (e.g. potential impact on social cohesion). Policy-makers can apparently not translate such information into political action.

«Ces études sont très bien, c’est très intéressant, mais le politique ne sait pas les traduire au niveau de l’action. (...) Ce qui m’intéresse moi, en tant que conseiller dans un parti politique, c’est qu’est-ce que le politique doit faire pour y arriver? Quels sont les outils juridiques et administratifs? Moi, je suis dans le cambouis ici.» (PA-RW)

Many actors think that foresight approaches could potentially be helpful in developing a low-carbon policy. To do so, such studies should inform on *how* to realize this transition. Some respondent think that a policy-relevant study should lead to the choice of one desirable low-carbon scenario. A backward analysis should then help to identify a number of milestones, as well as the policies to be implemented today and at the various stages of the pathway to make this desirable low-carbon scenario happens. Such analysis should be quantified. Defining one desirable low-carbon scenario raises the question of who is legitimate to decide which scenario is desirable. According to many actors, this is the role of political authorities. Political authorities do usually not participate to scenario building process. Such participatory approaches would require the political authorities' willingness to take part to the development of low-carbon vision. However, as mentioned before, neither the long-term, nor climate issues appear to be a priority of political elites.

This leads us to a second type of factors explaining the non-use of the study to support the development of low-carbon policy – i.e.: the **governance problems**. A number of actors consider that by having the foresight studies analysed at their disposal, the political authorities have all the information needed for developing climate mitigation policies and that the reason why such policies are not implemented yet concern problems in climate mitigation governance.

«Après, il n'y a rien qui se passe. Il n'y a pas de passage à l'acte. Et ça, de nouveau, c'est un problème de gouvernance.»
(WU-RW)

It appears that a number of governance problems lead to inertia in climate mitigation policy. Those governance problems are the low priority given by political authorities to climate-energy issues, the lack of political willingness to implement ambitious climate mitigation policies, the absence of political momentum favourable to the implementation of such policies, the short time horizon of policy-making, the interests at stake, the division of competences to steer the low-carbon transition, and more fundamentally, the capacity of public authorities to steer the low-carbon transition. The governance challenges that lead to political inertia will be discussed in more detail in the section devoted to the discussion of the study findings (see section “5.2. Governing the low-carbon transition: A predictable failure?” of the same chapter).

Another explanatory factor concerns the **low-level of institutionalization of foresight**. As explained in the chapter devoted to the contextual background, foresight is a scarcely institutionalized practice in Wallonia, and more generally in Belgium (see section “4.1. Foresight: A scarcely institutionalized practice” of chapter II). This little culture of foresight was reflected during the interviews, particularly through three elements. A first one is the semantic confusion. Many actors confuse foresight with forecast. A second illustrative element of the weak institutionalization of foresight is the low perceived credibility of this approach. A number of actors view foresight as lacking credibility because nobody knows what tomorrow will be made of and that most of the futures described in the scenario exercises did not come true. This reveals a poor understanding of what foresight actually is. As previously explained, the purpose of foresight is not to predict the future and the scenarios analysed in foresight exercises are not intended to come true. Instead, this type of exercise aims at better understanding either the opportunities and threats of possible future developments, or the conditions to make a desirable future come true (see section “3.1.2. Scenarios for envisioning and exploring alternative images of the future” of Chapter I).

«Crédibles, elles le sont moins. Il y a une partie inhérente à la prospective, de toute façon, puisqu'on ne connaît pas de quoi demain sera fait. Ça, c'est pour ceux qui ont une boule de cristal!» (ENG-BE)

«C'est amusant, parce que je me rappelle à l'époque avoir dû faire des dissertations sur la fusion nucléaire, qui était le graal qui allait arriver. On devait aussi parler de la fin du pétrole en 2000 (...) et finalement, toutes ces études prospectives se sont plantées. A si grand horizon, le monde change trop rapidement, les hypothèses changent trop rapidement. Il n'y a jamais eu autant de pétrole et de gaz que maintenant» (ENG-RW)

Finally, some actors simply admit that they are not familiar with foresight and that they do not have the habit of using such tool.

«Mais c'est vrai que c'est peut-être simplement aussi un outil que nous ne connaissons pas. Les outils de prospective, on n'a pas le réflexe d'y recourir. C'est peut-être simplement ça aussi. Je m'interroge, là maintenant, en vous attendant, je me dis ne devrait-on pas pouvoir justement utiliser des réflexions qui ont été faites pour se projeter? Là se pose probablement, comme toujours, la question pratique: En pratique, comment pourrais-je l'utiliser? En pratique, comment aurais-je le temps d'en prendre connaissance, de vraiment l'analyser pour pouvoir l'utiliser?» (ENG-RW)

Despite this little culture of foresight, I met a few persons that know pretty well foresight approaches. These include, among others, members of the Green Party. Compared to traditional parties, the Greens recognize more the value of foresight as a decision support tool for designing environmental policies. As a reminder, the ecologists are at the initiative of two of the studies analysed (i.e.: “Low-carbon Wallonia” and “100% renewable energy”) and are apparently the only political party who rely on this type of study as part of their function.

It is interesting to note that other tools such as statistics, forecasts, and more recently, evaluation, have experienced a similar situation before becoming mainstream decision support tools. That said, it appears that some characteristics of foresight could make its integration in political practices particularly difficult. Such difficulties will be discussed further in the section devoted to the discussion of the study findings (see section “5.1. Foresight: An oddity in the political landscape” of the same chapter).

Distortive Role

In addition to the instrumental role, the four case studies are also similar regarding the distortive role. I did not observe any distortive role for the studies analysed. As a reminder, a distortive role occurs when wrong, insufficient or biased information confuses or derails the policy process. An example of such role was mentioned earlier, when presenting the climate-energy foresight study ordered by the Federation of Belgian industrial energy consumers (Febeliec) (see section “4.2.2. Climate mitigation scenarios for Wallonia” of Chapter II). When presenting the study carried out by VITO/EnergyVille, Febeliec deliberately avoided to mention some elements and distorted the conclusions of the study so that it favoured a pro-nuclear vision. Similar cases have been reported during the interviews, but they apparently didn't concern the studies that I analysed. The reason why I haven't observed such phenomena might be related to the fact that most of the studies under consideration have been ordered by administrative authorities, that are supposed to act in favour of the general good and not to defend vested interests.

Note that there was a risk of generating distortive role with the study “100% renewable” that was ordered by the four ministers of energy at the initiative of Minister Nolle (Ecolo) who wanted to prove that the transition towards a nuclear and fossil-free Belgium is feasible by 2050. As a reminder, the Greens tried to influence the choice of model assumptions with a view to maximizing the chance of demonstrating that the transition to a 100% renewable energy-based system was feasible. They wanted, for instance, to adopt a hypothesis assuming a strong increase in oil price to favour renewable energy. However, the authors of the study haven't adopted such model assumptions in order to avoid the study to be discredited by incumbents.

4.1.2. Differences between Case Studies

If we look at the other types of roles, we can see that the four studies present different profiles. The “Energy transition” study distinguishes the most from the other ones. It is actually the study that had the fewest impact. It had only a little conceptual role which was related to the multidisciplinary approach that it involved. By exploring the interactions between the technical and social variables of the energy system, the analysis highlighted issues that could not have been identified with a purely technical approach. This made some actors realized that the energy transition was not only a technical

issue and that it could have an impact on social cohesion. Such conceptual role was however pretty low, because very few actors knew the study “Energy transition”. Apart from that conceptual role, the study had no real impact. Both external and internal factors helped to explain such failure. The little interest of members of traditional political parties for climate-energy issues appears to have been an important explanatory factor. The study was indeed presented to the Cabinet of the Walloon Minister in charge of energy and to the Energy Commission of the Walloon Parliament, but not much interest has been expressed and it hasn’t left a mark in political authorities’ memories – with the exception of the Greens who attended the presentation at the Parliament. The study was published in 2015, at a time when climate mitigation issues had been completely pushed aside: The Greens had been relegated to the opposition after the 2014 election and the Minister of energy, Paul Furlan (PS), hadn’t made climate mitigation a priority issue. The Minister of energy focused on his other competencies (i.e.: local government, city and housing), considering that energy policy was driven by the market and the European regulation. Internal characteristics of the study also contribute to explain its small impact on policy-making. These are the low level of participation in the scenario building process, the absence of quantitative data, and the lack of communication of the study’s findings. Finally, when looking at the other cases, we observe that the actors that use the more a study are usually its sponsors. The fact that IWEPS ordered the study might contribute to explain its non-use – IWEPS being a public research institute and not a political or administrative authority in charge of energy-climate related matters just like the sponsors of other studies.

Conceptual Role

Regarding the other three case studies, we observe similarities with respect to their conceptual and political roles. They all have a rather important conceptual role. All three studies increase knowledge and understanding of the low-carbon transition, and/or introduce new ideas or concept in policy-making. To me, this conceptual role is the most valuable contribution of the studies in policy-making. Specific characteristics of each study explain their conceptual role. The “low-carbon Wallonia” study brought new knowledge among the actors of the climate-energy policy because it was the first low-carbon scenario analysis in Belgium, but also one of the first at the European level. In that context, the Walloon actors drew a number of lessons regarding the feasibility of the low-carbon transition as well as the conditions required to make such transition possible. Some of the federal actors had heard about this study when the “Low-carbon Belgium” study was published. Thanks to the many activities of communication carried out by the Federal Climate Service to promote it, the analysis at the national scale have contributed to create a common language and frame of reference regarding the low-carbon transition among the Belgian stakeholders. The study “100% renewable” is apparently the one that had the more important conceptual role. This is the study that penetrates the more the political sphere. The important conceptual role of the study may be explained by the facts that it was ordered by four ministers, that it was communicated a lot by the authors, that it has been very much in the media and that the scenarios include disruptive elements – i.e.: having a shift towards seasonal production in some industries to cope with intermittent energy production. It appears that uch disruptive elements made an impression, triggered reactions, fostered reflection and helped to prepare mentalities.

Political Role

The studies “Low-carbon Wallonia”, “Low-carbon Belgium” and “100% renewable” also have a quite important political role. They are all feasibility studies that demonstrate that the transition towards a low-carbon society or a 100% renewable energy-based system is possible by 2050 if ambitious policies are implemented as of now. This is why a number of actors endorsing those visions refer to the studies when supporting political actions to develop renewable energy or to mitigate climate changes. Such actors are primarily members of environmental and development NGOs, renewable energy lobbies, workers unions and Green party.

«L'élément principal que nous en avons ressorti, c'est l'élément de faisabilité. Dans le sens où il y a quelques années, quand nous disions qu'il faut aller vers du 100% renouvelable, il faut aller vers une Belgique 0% où 5% d'émission de gaz à effet de serre, on nous répondait "vous êtes des doux rêveur les ONG". Donc, arriver avec des études techniques solide menées par des bureaux d'études indépendants, ça a renforcé notre argumentation pour pouvoir démontrer qu'on était pas en train de prôner n'importe quoi. (...) Sans être un grand expert de ces éléments, je peux me baser sur une série d'études pour dire que "à certaines conditions, il est faisable de prendre la direction qui est par ailleurs absolument nécessaire, parce que sinon c'est les pays en développement qui vont assumer des conséquences dramatiques"» (NGO-BE)

«Ces études, pour nous, ça sert surtout à dire: "voilà il y a des études sérieuses qui ont été faites qui montrent que c'est possible d'arriver à une Belgique basée par exemple sur 100% d'énergies renouvelables". Ça appuie disons les choses que nous on veut faire, qu'on veut appuyer sur le plan politique.» (WU-BE)

«Elles sont souvent brandies par les ONG environnementales etc. C'est utile. Ça permet de garder à l'agenda politique cette urgence climatique. En tout cas, cette transition climatique. C'est utile. Mais politiquement, au-delà de maintenir cette thématique sur la scène médiatique, sur la scène politique, politiquement, la traduction en décision, franchement...» (PA-RW)

Besides the actors that support the 100% renewable energy and/or 80-95% GHG reduction targets, various actors extract from the studies very specific elements such as figures or numbers to give credibility to their discourse.

«Nous, on les utilise, mais si vous voulez, pour nous c'est un input dans le sens où "le Bureau du Plan a dit...", Climact a dit..." On y croit on y croit pas. (...) On prend ce qui nous arrange. (...) C'est un peu dommage d'ailleurs parce que souvent en prenant des extraits, on prend de manière politique les extraits, on reprends des phrases hors contexte et des choses comme ça.» (ENG-BE)

That said, because of the counter-expertise developed by the Belgian incumbents for the studies “Low-carbon Belgium” and “100% renewable”, some actors sometimes prefer not referring to those two studies.

More specifically, the “Low-carbon Wallonia” was used by Minister Henry (Ecolo) to support the adoption in the Climate Decree of the objective of 80-95% reduction in GHG by 2050. Including this objective in one of the pillars of the Walloon climate mitigation policy was actually one of the reasons why the minister initiated the study. On his side, Minister Nollet (Ecolo) initiated the study “100% renewable” to crystalize the position of the Walloon and Flemish socialists in favour of the transition towards 100% renewable energy in 2050 and to promote the renewable energy development policy he wanted to implement by demonstrating that such transition is feasible. He referred to the study to remind the socialists the stance they took when participating to the elaboration of the study but hasn't really used it to support a pro-renewable energy policy, because of the economic and social conditions to be met to develop a 100% renewable energy-based system highlighted in the study.

Process Role

Finally, the only studies presenting a process role are the “Low-carbon Wallonia” and “Low-carbon Belgium”. While the other two studies involved one or two consultations, those analyses carried out by CLIMACT were based on several workshops with a large panel of stakeholders. Their process role takes different forms. Because “low-carbon Wallonia” was the first participatory process that gathered so many different stakeholders to discuss the regional long-term mitigation policy, it showed that there was a potential to mobilize the civil society in favour of the low-carbon transition and incited emerging actors (i.e.: renewable energy actors) to structure themselves and to define their position. By involving a large number of stakeholders in the development of the study “Low-carbon Belgium” and more generally in the “Project 2050” that includes the “Low-carbon Belgium” study, the macroeconomic analysis of the scenarios and the national debate on carbon pricing, the Federal Climate Service aimed at creating a continuous process of learning and dialogue with the Belgian stakeholders. The consultations held as part of the “Project 2050” elicited a thinking process on the low-carbon transition and contributed to develop the common language and frame of reference among the stakeholders.

The consultations organized for this study but also for the “Low-carbon Wallonia” study fostered, to a certain extent, the dialogue between different stakeholders. The participative approach developed by Climact actually faced a number of limits in facilitating the dialogue. The most important limitation is related to the fact that it is always the same actors with the same well-honed speech who are participating. Even if the participants are invited to speak as experts and not as representatives of their organizations, they present their institutional discourse, leaving little room for the emergence of a real discussion.

«On est dans des workshops où vous voyez tout le microcosme belge. Vous aviez Elia, Fluxis, les distributeurs, les renouvelables, BBL, Greenpeace, WWF, tout ceux qui représentent les renouvelables étaient autour de la table. C'est un peu les débats belges. Vous retrouvez un peu toujours les même qui disent un peu toujours les mêmes choses. Quand vous avez des workshops, c'est un peu un scoop quand vous entendez quelque chose d'autre. (...) C'est souvent un peu difficile d'aller au-delà des slogans. Les gens qui engagent des vrais discussions sont assez rares. Il faut dire que souvent, on engage des gens qui ont l'étiquette public affairs et dont le message est justement de donner une position et puis après, surtout pas bouger. Quand on monte le niveau des intervenants, vous pouvez avoir des débats qui sont meilleurs. Ca c'est clair. Si vous avez un débat entre le CEO de Fluxys, le CEO d'Elia, le directeur du Bureau du plan, le débat sera nettement meilleur, mais on n'en a pas beaucoup.» (ENG-BE)

This difficulty in developing a real dialogue is not specific to those two studies. It is indeed a limit encountered in many participative approaches. Inviting the participants to speak as experts and not as representatives of their organizations doesn't necessarily allow to overcome this problem. A solution would be to invite to the scenario workshops not spokespersons who have for mission to present the position of their organization, but rather the directors of these organizations. These people who are in charge of taking decisions within their organization would probably be more inclined to discuss, which could contribute to develop a real dialogue.

4.2. Appropriation and Use of the Studies per Actor

The second section devoted to the cross-case analysis focused on the appropriation and use of the studies by the different actors. Just like the role in policy-making, the level of appropriation of the different studies per actor has also been represented in a radar chart [Figure 81]. Each axis corresponds to a type of actor. The center of the chart equates to a low level of appropriation and the extremity to a high level of appropriation. A colour is assigned to each case study: “low-carbon Wallonia” in blue, “Low-carbon Belgium” in green, “100% renewable” in red and “Energy transition” in yellow.

Figure 81. Level of appropriation of the different studies per actor. Each axis corresponds to a type of actor. The centre of the chart equates to a low level of appropriation and the extremity to a high level of appropriation. A colour is assigned to each study, as indicated in the caption of the graph.

We can see that globally, the actors that the most appropriate themselves the foresight studies are the members of public administrations. This is not surprising inasmuch as those actors have either ordered the studies analysed or followed closely the realization of the study by taking part to the steering comity. AWAC is the only actor who have used one of the studies analysed as a decision support tool when developing the Climate-Air-Energy Plan. The Climate Federal Service uses the study more as an instrument to generate a process of learning and dialogue with the Belgian stakeholders.

Conversely, what might seem surprising is that for the studies “low-carbon Belgium” and “100% renewable”, the employers federations and energy market operators more appropriate themselves the studies than environmental and NGOs and workers’ unions, while the later use the studies to support their discourse in favour of an ambitious climate mitigation policy. As said before, environmental and NGOs and Workers’ unions often refer to the studies “Low-carbon Belgium”, “100% renewable”, but also “Low-carbon Wallonia”, to give credibility to their discourses, but it appears that their knowledge of the studies is often limited to the main conclusions. On the contrary, the employers’ federations and the dominant energy market operators know usually very well the studies “low-carbon Belgium” and “100% renewable”, even if they don’t use them. Many incumbents know the main conclusions of the study, but also more specific elements mentioned in the report (e.g.: model's parameters, scenarios’ assumptions, conclusions per sector) because they have analysed the studies to develop counter-expertise. This applies more to Belgian than Walloon actors. It might be explained by the fact that Belgian employers’ federations also includes Flemish industrial lobbies who are generally much more reactive and vocal than Walloon organizations since they represent the interests of refineries and most of the Belgian chemical industries. The majority of such big companies that emit a lot of GHG emissions are indeed located in Flanders.

Finally, we observe a very low level of appropriation and use of the studies by political authorities and to a lesser extent by political advisors. It should be noted that this concerns more the members of traditional parties than Greens. This is not a surprise inasmuch as two of the studies have been initiated by Green ministers and as climate mitigation and nuclear phase out are two of the main Ecolo’s hobbyhorses. Back in the opposition, they don’t use the study to device policy, but rather to support their discourses in favour of an ambitious climate-energy policy. On the contrary, climate-energy issues are far from a priority for traditional parties. This materializes with a low level of appropriation and use of the studies by members of those parties. They often have little or no knowledge of the studies. The “100% renewable energy” study is the one that have penetrated the most the political sphere. Almost all the political authorities or political advisers I met, if they did not read the study, had at least heard of it. As said before, this may be explained by the facts that the study was ordered by four ministers, that it had been very much in the media and that some of the conclusions of the study were very controversial and trigger reactions. Nevertheless, the penetration of the study in the political sphere is limited to specialists of climate-energy issues. In each party, there are very few such specialists. It appears that climate-energy issues are of little interest to members of political parties because it is not a political priority, but also because those issues are of high complexity and technicity.

Unlike other actors, political authorities and political advisors haven’t been involved in the consultation process that took place in the study analysed. This could also have contributed to explain the low level of appropriation of the studies by those actors. A way to foster the appropriation of the studies by political authorities and political advisors might thus be to involve them in the scenario building process. However, as said before, a process of co-construction of low-carbon scenarios with political authorities requires to create a demand from these actors to develop such a process, which is challenging.

«Pour que ces études aient plus d’impact, il faut une certaine appropriation du politique. (...) [Or, dans ces études], on n’introduit pas le politique» (ADM-RW)

«[ndlr.: La participation des décideurs politiques] ça reste une condition importante. Parce que faire comprendre à un décideur tout le processus qui a eu lieu, de réflexion, d’identification de thématiques et ensuite, croire qu’on va facilement

lui reporter et qu'il va comprendre et qu'ils vont prendre des décisions, je pense que c'est compliqué. Donc j'ai l'impression qu'il faut les embarquer avec soi. Et si on les embarque avec soi, il y a une chance qu'à un moment donné, ça ait un impact. (...) Le problème d'embarquer les décideurs avec soi, c'est qu'il faut qu'ils soient demandeurs.» (PRI-RW)

5. Discussion

When crossing the four case studies, we have observed that the role in policy-making varies strongly from one foresight study to another. However, few examples of purely instrumental use of studies as orientation and decision support tools to devise mitigation policies have been noted. Studies are rather used to justify decisions already taken or to improve someone's relative position in the policy systems compared to opponents (i.e.: political role). Studies also contribute to expand the knowledge base and introduce new ideas or concepts in policy (i.e.: conceptual role). Moreover, even if none of the analysed studies rests on real exercise of scenarios co-construction, some studies have a process role. This is in line with the conclusions drawn from other empirical studies exploring the role of scenario analyses in policy-making. Fobé & Brans (2013) and Rijkens-Klomp (2012) who explored the political use and influence of foresight studies in other political domains (i.e.: technology and innovation policy, environment policy and territorial planning) and contexts (i.e.: the Netherlands and the Flemish region (Belgium)), reach the same general conclusions. A difference lays in the observed process role, which is relatively more important in those two analyses. Rijkens-Klomp even concludes that *"The case studies illustrate that the added value that policy-makers experience is especially related to the process-oriented impacts of the methods"* (Rijkens-Klomp 2012, p. 438).

As mentioned earlier, in light of the relationship between knowledge and governance, the implementation gap between low-carbon scenarios and policy is not surprising (see section "5.2.1. Knowledge and governance: Beyond the rational knowledge-based policy-making model" of Chapter I). The relationship between sciences and policy is neither linear, nor mechanic; and the vision of a rational knowledge-based policy-making model is rather naive: *"The political sociology of the environment (Lascoumes, 1994) has indeed shown that the role of knowledge was much more to insert a question into the state apparatus, to make it readable and treatable institutionally, than to effectively govern it"* (Foyer 2016, p. 6). The purely instrumental use of scientific knowledge in policy-making is generally quite limited, especially in highly politicized context like Belgium (see section "4.1.1. Similarities between case studies" of the same chapter). Instead, knowledge usually have a more diffuse and indirect influence on policy-making – i.e.: conceptual and process roles. That said, in the present research, such conceptual and process roles were observed among nearly all the actors, excepted for political authorities. Political authorities mark little interest in low-carbon scenario analyses. This aspect deserves further discussion. In the present section, I discuss a number of factors that are conducive to the very low level of appropriation of low-carbon scenarios by political authorities. Those are related to the very nature of both foresight and climate mitigation governance. While foresight appears as "UFO" among the decision support tools at the disposal of political authorities, climate mitigation governance is characterized by a number of challenges that lead to political inertia.

5.1. Foresight: An Oddity in the Political Landscape

As mentioned in the previous section, a reason explaining the little impact of the studies analysed is the low level of institutionalization of foresight (see section "4.1.1. Similarities between case studies" of the same chapter). In Wallonia, foresight emerged in the 70's, mostly with the activities of the Destrée Institute, and started to become an effective public practice less than 10 years ago. Despite recent advances, foresight keeps a relatively marginal place in the Walloon (and Belgian) political and administrative system. This approach is still little known by the political-administrative authorities and the term "foresight" is often confused with the notion of "forecast". A number of actors also question the credibility, the legitimacy and the relevance of scenario approach as a tool for decision support (see section "4.1. Foresight: A scarcely institutionalized practice" of chapter II) (Petit Jean, 2016). Other tools such as statistics, forecasts, and more recently, evaluation, have passed through there before becoming mainstream decision support tools. Intuitively, we might therefore think that, over time, foresight will also become an institutionalized practice in the Walloon political system. However, I

believe that some characteristics of foresight make its integration in political practices particularly challenging. Scenario approach is scarcely compatible with the current governance system. This view is supported by Van der Steen & van Twist who explain that “*policy-makers do not ‘choose’ to neglect or decline future oriented notions, but find it problematic/impossible to apply them to their reality (...) in day-to-day practice of making public policy*” (Van der Steen & van Twist 2012 p. 477). Many other scholars point out this **mismatch between foresight and policy-making** (Van der Steen, 2017; Kunseler & al., 2015; Van der Steen & van Twist, 2013; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; Riedy, 2009; Hayward, 2003; Glenn & al., 2001).

One of the more obvious barriers in the integration of foresight in political practices lies in the **discrepancy between the temporal scope of foresight studies and the time horizon of policy-making** (Brunet, 2014; Van der Steen & van Twist). While foresight involves a long-term perspective, the time horizon of most of the political authorities doesn’t go beyond the forthcoming elections, which corresponds to less than five years. The current system encourages political authorities to implement policies that will have positive effects in the short term – within the next elections to be re-elected, or even within the end of the year to achieve a balance budget. As a result, long-term issues are far from policy-makers’ reality. As stated by Van der Steen & van Twist, “*policy-makers are troubled by present-day crises, while foresight downplays those in the light of future developments*” (Van der Steen & van Twist 2012, p. 482). Some political matters such as climate-energy have however a longer time horizon. That said, it doesn’t exceed the medium term. For instance, the climate mitigation political agenda imposed by the European Union doesn’t go beyond 2025 and 2030, which correspond respectively to the deadline for the nuclear phase-out and to the time horizon of the National Energy Climate plan that should be submitted to the European commission (see section “3.5.1. Emergence of climate mitigation governance and first commitment period of the Kyoto Protocol (2008-2012)” of Chapter II). In that context, foresight analyses with a 2050-time horizon appear less policy-relevant.

Furthermore, foresight rests on other **ontological and epistemological foundations** than traditional policy tools like statistics, forecasts or evaluation. While the later are mostly based on a positivist philosophy of science assuming that the reality is objective and measurable, foresight often rests upon a constructivist philosophy of sciences assuming that the reality is socially constructed through intersubjective meanings and that science is discursively laden (i.e.: double hermeneutic) (Geels & al, 2016). It appears that political authorities often expect sciences to establish and quantify direct causal-effect relationships – just like positivist approaches do. Conversely, foresight doesn’t provide this type of knowledge. Foreknowledge is most of the time complex, multidimensional and not necessarily quantified. Van der Steen & van Twist depict extremely well this mismatch between foreknowledge and policy-making: “*Futures studies tend to complicate things, instead of resolving them. (...) Futures thinking gets lost in the process of creating clear policy texts (...) Policy-makers need clarity, while foresight provides them with new complexity. They seek solutions, while foresight reframes or even adds problems.*” (Van der Steen & van Twist 2012, p. 482). More fundamentally, the main purpose of foresight – i.e.: coping with uncertainties – is incompatible with policy-making, since policy-makers are intolerant toward uncertainties, even if their environment is uncertain, fuzzy and ambiguous (Van der Steen & van Twist 2012).

As previously explained, climate change is a super-wicked problem and its high complexity cannot be ignored (see section “2.2.1. From normal science to post-normal science and foresight” of Chapter I). On the contrary, I think that it must be acknowledged and managed. For several authors, (Super-)wicked problems need to be addressed with multidisciplinary approaches embracing their inherent multidimensionality, non-linearity, unpredictability, uncertainty, and conflicting values (Head, 2014; Batie 2008). Foresight, but also post-normal sciences (Funtowicz & Ravetz 1993), are often perceived as suitable approaches for tackling such problems – conversely to traditional modes of knowledge production which political authorities are accustomed to. In that context, I believe that it is of **primary importance to “reconcile” foresight and policy-making**. The link between foresight and policy-making “*needs to be forged – and sometimes perhaps forced*” (Van der Steen 2017, p. 194). Several works have

been done to understand how to further connect foresight and policy-making. Those works provide various suggestions either for improving foresight practice in order to increase its use for policy-making (i.e.: “policy-oriented foresight”), or for reconfiguring policy-making in order to create a governance system more permeable to foresight (i.e.: “future-oriented policy” or “anticipatory governance”) (Kunseler & *al.*, 2015; Brunet, 2014; Hughes, 2013; Van der Steen & van Twist, 2013 and 2012; Rijkens-Klomp, 2012; Habegger, 2010; van Asselt & *al.*, 2010; Fuerth, 2009; Da Costa & *al.*, 2008; Riedy, 2009; Chermack, 2004; Hayward, 2003; Glenn & *al.*, 2001).

To me, a promising way to connect foresight and policy-making lies in the **development of process-oriented foresight and associated culture of participation in knowledge production processes**. Even if none of the analysed studies includes a real exercise of co-construction of scenarios, the two studies based on stakeholders’ consultations have a process role. At a more individual level, I have generally observed that the persons who participate to the consultations understand and appropriate more the study than those who did not took part to the consultations. In addition to increasing understanding and appropriation, scenarios coproduction process can have various effects like facilitating collective learning, constructing a common cognitive frame of reference, promoting empowerment, developing a network of actors, fostering dialogue and exchange of opinion among different actors, enabling engagement and participation of stakeholders in the policy-process, creating negotiating space helping to the construction of consensus among stakeholders, or building a common future vision and a shared sense of commitment (Miller & *al.*, 2015; Gunnarsson-Östling & *al.*, 2012; Rijkens-Klomp, 2012; Quist & *al.*, 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Svenfelt, 2010; Habegger, 2010; Da Costal & *al.*, 2008; Garb & *al.*, 2008; de Smedt, 2006; Georghiou & Keenan, 2006; Paillard, 2006; Lévêque & Urien, 2005). Because of the potential influence of participatory process, an increasing number of process-oriented foresight attaching more importance to the process than to the products of scenario analyses are observed (e.g.: Miller & *al.*, 2015; Hisschemöller & Bode, 2011). There is indeed a shifting emphasis from informing policy with foresight products to facilitating policy implementation and enabling changes through foresight processes (Da Costa & *al.*, 2008). However, such shift from product-oriented to process-oriented foresight doesn’t occur everywhere. The scenario analyses carried out in Wallonia are often desk researches or researches based on stakeholders’ consultations. Those consultations are rarely real exercise of co-construction of scenarios and are often limited to members of administrations and representatives of civil society organizations. The omnipresence of civil society organizations is not specific to scenario analyses. Owing to the corporatist characters of the Belgian political system, *“knowledge production processes are negotiated and involve representatives of different societal visions”* (Petit Jean 2016, p. 260). Yet, I think that scenario analyses with higher level of participation involving other types of actors like political authorities, but also citizens could contribute to forge the link between foresight and policy-making. Such process-oriented foresights could facilitate the policy implementation and enable changes (i.e. process role), but also lead to the definition of better solutions to (super-)wicked problems. Participatory approaches benefit from the so-called “wisdom of crowds” (see Surowiecki, 2008), that is the ability of heterogeneous groups – that are often profane in one area – to offer visions of the future better informed than those of individual experts. In the longer term, process-oriented scenario analyses might also be more effective than product-oriented analyses to create a culture of foresight in the Walloon political system. Developing projects of co-production of scenarios with political authorities or citizens is nevertheless quite challenging. Involving Walloon political authorities in scenario building process appear particularly complex since they are not in the habit of participating in knowledge production. Regarding citizens, every participatory process involves a risk on not including certain parts of the population that do not have the resources (e.g.: information, time) to take part to such project. The intuition concerning **the role of process-oriented foresight in policy-making needs to be empirically verified**. To my knowledge no in-depth analysis of the process role of highly participatory scenario analyses does exist. This is a fruitful **avenue for future research**.

5.2. Governing the Low-Carbon Transition: A Predictable Failure?

As a reminder, to explain the implementation gap between low-carbon scenarios and policy, many actors claim that the studies don't meet the policy-makers' information needs inasmuch as they don't effectively inform on *how* to make the low-carbon transition happen. On the contrary, other actors consider that by having such studies at their disposal, the political authorities have at their disposal all the information needed for developing climate mitigation policies and that the reason why such policies are not implemented yet concern governance problems (see section "4.1.1. Similarities between case studies" of the same chapter). I think that there is some truth in both points of view. To me, the four foresight studies analyse doesn't inform effectively policy-makers on *how* to make the low-carbon transition happen. By not providing information neither on how to govern the low-carbon transition nor on how to finance such transition, those studies are difficult to translate into political action. However, I believe that even if political authorities had all the information they need, they would not implement ambitious climate mitigation policy. There is actually a number of challenges inherent to climate mitigation governance that lead to inertia in climate-energy policy.

A first problem often mentioned by the actors for explaining the implementation gap between low-carbon scenarios and policy concerns the **very complex multi-level architecture of climate mitigation governance in Belgium**. As explained in the section devoted to the contextual background, the competences to mitigate climate changes are fragmented between the federal state and the regions, and also between different political and administrative authorities within each entity. In total, ten ministers and eleven administrations have levers for action to ensure the low-carbon transition (see section "3.2. Climate mitigation: A shared competence between the federal state and the regions" of Chapter II). One reason often cited by political-administrative authorities to justify their low level of appropriation or use for the studies is their lack of competence in the areas of climate mitigation policy. This is the case for the actors at the federal level who state that they don't implement climate mitigation policy because they have very few political levers since most of the levers have been regionalized, but also for the Walloon and federal actors in charge of transports or energy policy who explain that they don't know those studies because they don't work specifically on climate mitigation. While the latter case is particularly revealing the low level of integration of climate mitigation objectives in other policy domains, the former is, in my opinion, more an excuse for inaction. The federal authorities actually control a number of levers for taking action to reduce GHG emissions, including offshore energy production, major infrastructures of production and storage of energy, transport of energy, products' standards and taxation. In that context, I think that if they had a real ambition to reduce GHG emission, federal authorities would implement policy. To me, the complex multi-level architecture of climate mitigation governance is, above all, an argument for justifying their lack of political will. This has also been highlighted empirically by Sander Happaerts, who after analysing the climate policies of the national and subnational governments concludes that "*Belgian federalism allows – or sometimes even encourages – governments to shift their responsibilities upon each other*" (Happaerts 2013, p. 18).

In addition to the fragmentation of competences, several actors claim that the very complex multi-level architecture of climate mitigation governance in Belgium hinders the emergence of a shared vision of the low-carbon transition. They state that such a common vision is a prerequisite for the development of a low-carbon strategy and that the **absence of a long-term vision of the low-carbon transition shared by national and subnational governments** hampers the implementation of climate mitigation policies. I partly agree with this statement. Developing visions of the future expected by us is essential to give orientation (i.e.: where to go) and guidance (i.e.: what to do) to the actors involved in the energy transition process (Quist & al., 2011). A vision shared by national and subnational entities would provide a framework for the development of a coherent climate mitigation policy. However, in light of the divergent views between the North and the South of the country, the construction of a consensual vision of the low-carbon transition in Belgium is a real challenge. As explained in the introduction, there is no one right solution to wicked problems such as mitigating climate change (see

section “2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition” of Chapter I). Instead, there are several solutions that are better or worse for this or that actor. The choice of one vision of the low-carbon transition over another is therefore based on values, which leads to ideological confrontations. As a reminder, in Belgian partitocracy, those ideological confrontations are structured around the political parties, and more generally, around the pillars (see section “3.1. Overview of the Belgian political system” of chapter II). With asymmetric coalitions between the federal and regional governments, it is unlikely that those government with different ideologies would agree on a common vision of the low-carbon transition. From the 2004 elections until the formation of a MR-cdH majority in summer 2017 after the eviction from the Walloon government of the socialists, the federal and regional governments were controlled by different coalitions. In his analysis of the Belgian multilevel climate governance, Happaerts (2013) observes that ideological confrontations between coalitions composed of different political parties have led to blockages in intergovernmental negotiations. Since summer 2017, there is to some extent a symmetry between federal and subnational governments, and, as mentioned before, the Interfederal Energy Pact which aims at developing a long-term vision of Belgian energy policy was approved by the regional and federal government in spring 2018 (see section “3.5.2. Post-2012 Climate mitigation Policy” of Chapter II). It remains to be seen whether this vision will be clear, precise and ambitious enough to provide orientation and guidance to the development of a coherent low-carbon policy. I acknowledge the advantage of having a common vision to ensure consistency between the policies implemented by the different entities, but in light of the climate emergency, I think that the lack of such a vision should not hinder the implementation of ambitious climate mitigation policies. To me, not implementing climate mitigation policy due to the absence of common vision is the result of a lack of awareness of climate emergency or simply another excuse for inaction.

A supplementary aspect that leads to political inertia in climate-energy policy, and by no means an insignificant one, is the **low ambition of political elites in mitigating climate change**. This has been highlighted several times during the interviews by various actors ranging from environmental and development NGOs, workers unions, administrations, political authorities to incumbents. The low ambition of political authorities has also been demonstrated by Sander Happaerts (2013) in his analysis of national and subnational climate mitigation policies. It is materialized either by inaction or by the implementation of mini-measures that are insufficient to enable the major behavioural and technical changes required to reach a low-carbon society. The political authorities often adopt a “wait and see” attitude and essentially settle for transposing European regulation. Wallonia was more dynamic between 2010 and 2014, when the Greens were in power. At the initiative of Minister Henry (Ecolo), the Region developed its low-carbon scenarios and includes the target for reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% in the Climate Decree. At that time, the Walloon region positioned itself as precursor in long-term climate mitigation policy compared to other European regions. However, after the 2014 elections, the Greens relegated to the opposition were not able to pursue their policy, and their successors have shown no proactive, considering that energy policy was driven by the market and the European regulation. Two important factors can contribute to explain the low ambition of political elites in mitigating climate change.

First, **the low-carbon transition is far to be a political priority for traditional parties**. Economic or social issues appear to be much more important to them. This strong dissociation of economic, social and environmental objectives might be related to the Belgian pillarization. As a reminder, a pillar is “*a set of organizations that share a common ideology and that ensure its influence in the organization of society*” (CRISP, 2018) (see section “3.1. Overview of the Belgian political system” of Chapter II). Such system assumes the existence of cleavages that significantly structure the society. The three main pillars correspond to the three traditional parties. Those are the socialist, the Christian and the liberal pillars. Even if the Greens reject the system of pillarization, it seems that this political party forms with various environmental organizations gravitating around it a fourth pillar. The existence of a “green” pillar erects the environmentalism as an ideology that opposes to other pillars’ ideologies, which might hinder its integration in other pillars and, by extension, in traditional parties’ programmes.

A second factor that helps to explain the low ambition of political elites in mitigating climate change is related to the **difficult social acceptance of climate-energy policies**. The low-carbon transition requires the implementation of ambitious policies to promote major behavioural and technical changes. Such fundamental changes, but also the policy instruments to be implemented to encourage them, can be perceived negatively by citizens, companies and various political actors. This is linked on the one hand to the impacts they can generate on economic growth, competitiveness, employment, energy bill, comfort level or even landscape, and on the other hand to reluctance to change. Climate mitigation policies are likely to cause negative impacts in the short term, but their positive impacts on climate change will be visible only in the long-term. As a result, there is a tension between the potential negative impacts and the absence of noticeable results in the short term. In a context where the actions of political authorities are evaluated by citizens right before the elections, at the end of their five-years term, implementing such policies requires a lot of political courage. A greater acknowledgement of short-term co-benefits of climate mitigation measures on health for instance might help to increase social acceptance of these measures.

Finally, in light of the major behavioural and technical changes required to make the low-carbon transition happen and the growing backlog in implementing ambitious mitigation policy, **one might wonder more fundamentally whether public authorities (still) have the capacity to steer such transition**. Excepted for “command and control” instruments that, by limiting or excluding some behaviours, directly influence the range of options available to target groups, the other types of policy instruments have unpredictable effects. While the legitimacy and desirability of restricting individual freedoms with “command and control” instruments to limit climate change is, in my opinion, highly questionable, other means of intervention such as subsidies, taxes or information campaigns for instance, don’t necessarily induce individuals to make decisions and take actions compatible with objectives pursued by public authorities. It is particularly challenging to anticipate the efficacy of policy instruments in climate mitigation matters. As previously explained, climate mitigation is a very recent political matter that is constantly evolving (see section “3.5. Main climate mitigation policies” of Chapter II). Unlike other policy domains that are based on well-established modes of governance, everything has yet to be invented. In addition to the difficulty in devising policy instruments that can effectively foster the major behavioural and technical changes required to make the low-carbon transition happen, the time lost in doing nothing – or very little – to mitigate climate change makes the governance of such fundamental transition process increasingly challenging. As time passes, the political authorities’ room for maneuver to govern the low-carbon transition decreases. In that context, questioning the capacity of public authorities to steer the low-carbon transition makes even more sense.

This question does not apply only at the Belgian scale. The widening gap between climate mitigation policy target and ambitious political actions to reduce GHG emission is also observed at the global level. Aykut & Dahan (2016), who have extensively analysed the international governance of climate mitigation, describe this discrepancy between on the one hand what we know and what should be done, and on the other hand what is actually done as a “schism of reality”. Between the institutionalization of climate governance at the international level which corresponds to the establishment of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in 1992, and 2012, CO₂ emissions rose by 38% – and not only just because emerging countries raised their standard of living (Oreskes & Conway, 2014). Against this background, several experts consider that no transition policy could help to *completely* prevent the global collapse that is well underway (Semal, 2017; Servigne & Stevens, 2015). Semal further explains that we have to “*mourn the overly ideal conception of transition – one that promises a knowledgeably steered, controlled, deliberate transition towards green growth for all*” and consider the global collapse as the context in which the transition takes place (Semal 2017, p. 7). This approach to transition that involves combining mitigation and adaptation policies is referred to as “**transition in catastrophe**” by Semal (2017). Without going into a catastrophist discourse, Andy Stirling (2014) also highlights and discusses the limits associated with the idea of controlling the sustainability transition. He states that the most profound radical social

changes that occurred in the past have not been achieved by top-down controlled 'transitions', but predominantly by unruly bottom-up **"transformations"**. This leads him to define two ideal-typical forms of fundamental social change, i.e.: *"transitions" that are "often driven by technological innovation, managed under orderly control, by incumbent structures according to tightly-disciplined frameworks for knowledge, towards a specific known (presumptively shared) end"* and *"transformations" that "entail more plural, emergent and unruly political re-alignments, involving social and technological innovations driven by diversely incommensurable knowledges, challenging incumbent structures and pursuing contending (even unknown) ends"* (Stirling 2014, p.1). In view of all the elements set out above, it appears to me wiser and more realistic to move away from the widespread idea that the transition towards a low-carbon society can be perfectly mastered by public authorities.

6. Limits of the Study

The present research has a number of limitations. A first one is related to the very nature of the exercise – i.e.: analysing the use and influence of foresight studies in policy-making. Such exercise is particularly challenging inasmuch as the impacts of a study in policy-making are most of the time not visible. The relationship between sciences and policy is indeed neither linear, nor mechanical. Direct translation on studies in policy are hardly ever observed. Instead, the impacts of studies are often diffuse and hardly observable since they are of a more conceptual nature. New knowledge can alter the attitudes of the individuals that compose the network of actors, which can potentially induce attitudes changes at the collective level. Such cognitive changes are impalpable and therefore difficult to identify. It is also particularly challenging to isolate the impacts of a particular study since it is part of a larger information flow. This is especially the case of issues such as climate mitigation. Studies on that issues are regularly produced by public or private actors from local to international scale. In addition to the interactions with other sources of information, the time dimension also has an influence. It may actually take time before the knowledge is integrated and induce noticeable attitude changes.

I analysed the use and influence of foresight studies in policy-making mainly on the basis of in-depth interviews. This approach has a number of limitations. The first one is that the data are obviously limited to what the respondent says. This is influenced by the questions posed by the interviewer, the way the respondent understands the question and what he wants to reveal. When developing the interview guide, I paid attention to make sure the various questions covered the different types of role of knowledge in policy-making considered as part of this research. In light of the answers provided by the respondents, it seems that they generally understood the questions correctly. The problem lies in their willingness to provide honest responses. I observed a social desirability bias in that some respondents felt uncomfortable telling me that they don't know or don't use the studies. Several respondents told me that they knew the studies, but as the questions went along, I realized that it was not the case. Some participants admitted that they felt ashamed of not knowing the studies and of not being able to discuss them with me.

Another limit of the research lies in the analysis of the data collected through in-depth interviews. The 74 interviews I carried out allowed me to meet virtually all the major actors of long-term climate mitigation policy in Wallonia and in Belgium. However, it has generated a significant amount of material to be transcribed and analysed. Apart from being tedious, this task was particularly complex. The approach used to analyse such vast amount of unstructured raw qualitative data involves a certain amount of subjectivity. The data reduction that consists in "*selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstracting and transforming*" the empirical material, and the conclusion drawing which implies to "*decide what things means (...) noting regularities, patterns, explanations, possible configurations, causal flows, and propositions*" (Miles & Huberman 1994, p. 10-11) are quite subjective. Two inherent risks of those components of qualitative data analysis are to leave out important elements and to misinterpret the content of the interview.

Finally, a number of limits are connected to the case studies. First, such studies are quite recent. They were indeed published between 2012 and 2015. They might therefore have more influence over the next few years – all the more so as they are future-oriented and as we can assume that climate mitigation will become a more important issue. An additional limit lies in the fact that none of the studies involve a real exercise of co-construction of scenario with stakeholders. Moreover, the consultations carried out as part studies did not involve political authorities. As a result, those case studies were probably not the more suitable for analysing the process role. Exploring the influence of more participatory foresight offers one fruitful avenue for future research. Such research would be even more relevant if the case studies selected would involve political authorities.

Conclusion to the Chapter

The review of the literature highlighted the lack of empirical research on the role of scenario analyses in policy-making. The lack of such investigation is particularly marked in social sciences literature – the debate on the interactions between scenarios and governance being, with few exceptions, limited to scenario literature. The present empirical study aimed at exploring the role of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making on the basis of conceptual frameworks and methodological tools developed in the knowledge utilization literature. It consisted in a multiple case study analysing the role in policy-making of four energy foresight studies carried out for the Walloon Region (Belgium). The studies analysed are the following: “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050” (CLIMACT, 2012), “Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050” (CLIMACT & VITO, 2013), “Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050” (VITO & *al.*, 2012) and “Prospective study: Energy transition” (CLIMACT & *al.*, 2015). The analysis has been carried out on the basis of an analytical framework developed in the knowledge utilization literature (see Gudmunson & *al.*, 2009). This framework considers five types of knowledge role in policy-making, namely instrumental, conceptual, political, process and distortive roles. The exploration of the use and influence of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making is based on documentary analysis and 74 semi-structured interviews with the actors involved in the long-term climate mitigation policy in Wallonia. Those actors are political authorities, political advisors, administrative authorities, employers’ federations, workers’ unions, environmental and development NGOs, advisory councils, energy market operators, public transport operators, public research institutes, consultancy agencies and universities. The important empirical material collected was analysed with the method of thematic coding. After exploring the role in policy-making and the level of appropriation per actor for each of the four foresight studies, I have conducted a cross-case analysis in order to highlight the similarities and differences between the four studies.

The cross-case analysis revealed that the role in policy-making varies strongly from one foresight study to another. However, few examples of purely instrumental use of studies as orientation and decision support tools to devise mitigation policies have been noted. Studies are rather used to justify decisions already taken or to improve someone’s relative position in the policy systems compared to opponents (i.e.: political role). Studies also contribute to expand the knowledge base and introduce new ideas or concept in policy (i.e.: conceptual role). Moreover, even if none of the analysed studies rest on real exercise of scenarios co-construction, some studies still have a process role. The implementation gap between low-carbon scenarios and policy is not surprising since the relationship between sciences and policy is neither linear, nor mechanic – the vision of a rational knowledge-based policy-making model being rather naïve. The purely instrumental use of scientific knowledge in policy-making is generally quite limited, especially in highly politicized context like Belgium. Instead, knowledge usually has a more diffuse and indirect influence on policy-making – i.e.: conceptual and process roles. That said, in the present research, such conceptual and process roles were observed among nearly all the actors, political authorities excepted. The cross-case analysis actually showed that the level of appropriation of foresight studies varies greatly from one actor to another, and that the public actors within administrations seem to be more permeable to the investigated foreknowledge, whereas, on the contrary, political authorities mark little interest in the scenario exercises. Finally, the cross-case analysis suggested that a specific constellation of factors contributes in explaining the (non-)use and influence of each study. That being said, it seems that the particular characteristics of each study affect less the role of the studies in policy-making than external factors such as the governance setting.

The last section of this chapter focused more specifically on the factors that can contribute to explain the very low level of appropriation of low-carbon scenarios by political authorities. In this discussion, I demonstrated that the low levels of interest of political authorities in low-carbon scenarios can be related to the very nature of both foresight and climate mitigation governance. On the one hand, I highlighted a mismatch between foresight and policy-making that makes the integration of foresight in political practices difficult – if not impossible. However, in light of the need for modes of knowledge production like foresight to address super-wicked problems such as climate change, I think that it is

necessary to forge the link between scenario approach and policy. I presented the development of process-oriented foresight as a potential way to forge that link, emphasizing the need for further empirical research to better understanding the process role of scenario analyses. On the other hand, I pointed out a number of challenges inherent to climate mitigation governance that lead to political inertia. This political inertia, together with the decreasing political authorities' room for maneuver as times passes, led me to question the capacity of public authorities to steer the low-carbon transition. In that context, I introduced the concepts of "transition in catastrophe" (Semal, 2017) and "transformations" (Stirling, 2014) as wiser and more realistic approaches compared to the widespread notion of transition, which implicitly assumes that the shift towards a low-carbon society can be perfectly controlled.

CHAPTER IV.

Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios: A Needs Assessment

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Introduction

As shown in the previous chapter, many actors explain the implementation gap between low-carbon scenarios and policy by mentioning the argument that the studies don't meet the policy-makers' information needs. They state that those foresight studies don't effectively inform on *how* to make the low-carbon transition happens. This is in line with the observation made by Schubert & al. (2015) who maintain that we are currently witnessing a shift of attention from *if* to *how* could we manage the low-carbon transition (Schubert & al., 2015). The question of *how* encompasses, among others, the governance issues – i.e.: *How to steer the low-carbon transition? What public policies to implement? At what levels of power? By who? What are the institutional changes required to ensure such transition?* Etc. As illustrated in the section devoted to climate mitigation governance, there is much that we still don't know about how to govern the low-carbon transition (See section “4.3. How to govern the low-carbon transition: A knowledge gap” of Chapter I). Against that background, Schubert & al. (2015), but also many authors, claim that low-carbon scenarios including governance issues as variables might be perceived by policy-makers as being more relevant than the purer technical-economic studies (Schubert & al., 2015; Hughes, 2013; Nilsson & al., 2011; Söderholm & al., 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Such socio-technical scenarios might simply contribute to bridge the above mentioned implementation gap between scenario analyses and policy-making, bearing in mind that, besides their perceived relevance, many other factors influence the use of scientific objects in policy formulation and that the role of science in the policy process is not limited to instrumental use (Olsson & al., 2015; Schubert & al., 2015) (see section “5.2.2. Role of scenario analyses in policy-making” of the same chapter).

Through a review of low-carbon scenarios including governance, I noticed that very few low-carbon scenarios provide comprehensive representation of governance (See section “5.3.2. On the need for further investigation on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios” of Chapter I). Considering the three dimensions of governance (See section “4.1.2. policy, politics and polity dimensions of governance” of Chapter I), it has been observed that the *policy* dimension is addressed in most of the scenario analyses, while the *polity* and *politics* dimensions are missing in many analyses. In light of the challenges posed by the vertical and horizontal interactions in the multi-level governance framework of climate change, the under-representation of *polity* and *politics* dimensions in low-carbon scenarios is questioning. We can actually wonder why the constellation of actors and their role in the policy process (i.e. *politics*) as well as the mode of political steering and the institutional arrangements (i.e. *polity*) are less represented than the policy process and its outputs (i.e. *policy*). Are those issues less relevant for policy-makers? If this is not so, why are they less addressed in scenario analyses? Is it too difficult from a methodological point of view to include those dimensions in low-carbon scenarios? Or do the scenarios producers do simply not perceive the policy-relevance of the *polity* and *politics* issues? As explained by Cash & al. (2002) “*what the scientist considers relevant information may not be the same as what the decision maker considers relevant, and vice versa*”. They add that “*there must be some way that the expert can know what kinds of questions to ask in order to produce knowledge that is salient to the decision maker*” (Cash & al. 2002, p. 2). In that context, the following question emerges:

“What do political actors need to know to steer the low-carbon transition?”

This question is divided into two sub-questions:

- I. What knowledge about governance do political actors need to devise long-term mitigation policies?
- II. Is foresight a suitable approach to provide this knowledge?⁴³

The chapter develops on an empirical study aiming to apprehend and compare the perceptions of different actors of the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition. Just like in Chapter III, the actors are those involved in the long-term policy process of GHG-emissions' mitigation in the Walloon Region (Belgium). The needs assessment is carried out with a Q methodology, a qualitative but statistically supported method that allow understanding the variety of discourses around a given topic (see Barry & Proops, 1990). As part of the Q-survey, 54 participants sorted a set of potential research questions covering the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance according to their relevance to devise mitigation policies. A principal component analysis of the data was carried out in order to indentify factors, that are ideal-typical versions of the way to perceive the subject of study shared by a number of participants. I undertaken an analysis of the similarities and differences between the factors with a view to highlighting the areas of consensus and the terms of the debate regarding the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition.

The first section is dedicated to the Q methodology. After presenting the general characteristics and the different steps of the Q methodology, I discuss the advantages of this method regarding other survey approaches, but also its limits. I then present the respective characteristics of forced and free distributions, and the reason why I have decided to combine those two approaches. I then provide information on how I conduct the study. Afterwards, the results of the survey are presented and discussed. The chapter closes with a discussion of the method, and more specifically the lessons learned from the combination of forced and free distributions in Q survey.

⁴³ Note that this second question was finally left out. The objective was to understand whether scenario analysis is a suitable approach to address the governance issues identified as policy-relevant. With that aim in mind, I asked the participant during the post-sorting interview if they had any idea of the type of approach that would be suitable to address the governance issues they considered as the most policy-relevant. However, I haven't obtained any exploitable results for this concluding question, for several reasons. The first one is a practical reason. This question was the final point of the interview guide, and, pretty often, we didn't have much time left at the end of the interview for discussing the methods to be used to analyse the governance of the low-carbon transition, or if we had time, I sometimes felt that the respondent was tired and was not very motivated to intensively discuss this last question. Secondly, several persons told me that they didn't have enough knowledge of the approach that could be used to carry out an analysis of the governance of the low-carbon transition. The last reason is related to the influence of the first part of the interview and to the social desirability bias. The fact that the first part of the interview was about foresight and low-carbon scenarios (see Chapter IV) has influenced the way the participants respond to the last questions. When I asked "*What approach would you encourage to analyse the issues that you considered as very relevant?*", many participants suggested a foresight approach. Since it was the theme of the first part of the interview, some participants thought it was the "correct" answer.

1. Q Methodology

1.1. Q Methodology: An Outline

With a view to analysing the perception of the different actors concerning the knowledge on the governance of the low-carbon transition that are needed, I used the Q methodology (see Watts & Stenner, 2005; Barry & Proops, 1990). It is a qualitative, but statistically supported survey method that allows understanding the variety of discourses around a given topic. A discourse corresponds to the way a person “sees” and speaks about this topic. As there are as many points of view as they are participants, the Q methodology aims at highlighting, in a structured and interpretable manner, similarities and differences in the perceptions of participants in relation to the subject of the study (Barry & Proops, 1999). It thus allows classifying the participants on the basis of their perception (Cools & *al.*, 2012).

The Q methodology was developed by the psychologist William Stephenson in the 1930s (Barry & Proops, 1999). By the 1990s, this investigative method has grown in popularity among different fields of social scientists and has started to be used by a larger audience (Brown & *al.*, 2015). It is now used in other fields of study, including the environment (see Zabala & *al.* 2018). Q methodology is actually particularly suited to the analysis of social phenomena that give rise to a certain amount of debate and even conflict (Barry & Proops, 1999).

1.2. Conduct of a Q Methodology

A Q methodology is conducted in several steps. Carrying out a Q survey requires a lot of preparation upstream from the survey. As for any other survey, a preliminary step is the identification of the population to be interviewed and the construction of the sample – which is called “**Q sample**”. The Q methodology does not require a lot of participants (Cools & *al.*, 2012; ten Klooster & *al.*, 2008; Barry & Proops, 1999). According to Barry & Proops (1999), from twelve participants statistical analysis can yield significant results.

Another preparatory step – and probably the more time consuming – consists in identifying the field of discourse to study and to formulate a range of statements covering this field of discourse. The set of statements is supposed to cover all the possible points of view in relation to the object of study. Usually, a first list of items comes from exploratory interviews with participants (Davies & Hodge, 2007). That said, statements can also be defined only on the basis of desk research. Once the list of items is completed, the researcher has to carry out a selection among that list to obtain a manageable number of items for the survey. They form what Q methodology practitioners call the “**Q set**”. Watts & Stenner define the Q set as “*the collection of ‘heterogeneous items’ which the participants will sort*” (Watts & Stenner, 2005, p. 74). It is recommended to use between 40 to 80 statements (Zabala & *al.*, 2018; Watts & Stenner, 2005; Cools & *al.*, 2012). While a number of statements below 40 leads to the risk of not adequately covering the discourse, more than 80 items become difficult to classify (Watts & Stenner, 2005).

The grid in which the statements will be ranked is then developed. The grid is a quasi-normal distribution. In the such a grid, the statements are ranked according to one dimension. Typically, they are classified according to the degree of agreement, starting from most disagree to most agree. That said, it is possible to classify according to other dimensions. Most of the time, the scale comprises 11 or 13 points, which mean that the possible ranking values range from -6 or -5 for the statements that are considered as the most disagree to +6 or +5 for the statements that are considered as the most agree. The distribution can be either “forced” or “free”. In a forced distribution, a defined number of statements must be placed under each ranking position (Watts & Stenner, 2005). Such ranking grid usually has an inverted pyramid shape inasmuch as they are fewer items under both extremities and more items as one moves toward the middle position (Giannoulis & *al.*, 2010). The figure below

represents an example of grid involving a forced distribution used to rank statements according to the degree of agreement in a Q survey [Figure 82].

Figure 82. Example of how the items are sorted in a Q survey involving a forced distribution

In the case of a free distribution, the number of piles for the sorting as well as the number of items to allocate in each of those piles are defined by the participant during the Q survey (Du Plessis, 2005). The following figure illustrates how the items can be sorted in a Q survey involving a free distribution [Figure 83].

Figure 83. Example of how the items can be sorted in a Q survey involving a free distribution

The forced distribution is used more often than the free distribution by Q methodology practitioners (Watts & Stenner, 2005). The question of the choice between forced and free distribution is discussed in more detail later in this chapter (see section “1.4. Forced and free distributions” of the same chapter).

The “**Q survey**” can finally start. The Q methodology provides two modes of data collection. The traditional approach involves conducting interviews in which participants are asked to position the items printed on individual cards on a paper template representing the ranking grid. The other way of collecting data is to use software to perform an online questionnaire. Several Q sorting software tools have been developed (see International Society for the Scientific Study of Subjectivity, 2018). At the end of the sorting process, one gets a “**Q sort**” for each participant, namely, all the items ranked against each other’s (Lefin & Boulanger 2010, p. 15). Once the participant is satisfied with his sorting, a post-sorting interview or questionnaire is administered. This aims at understanding the rationale behind the ranking and more especially the reasons why the respondents put certain items in the extreme positive or negative position in the ranking grid. The post-sorting interview is also intended to identify

additional items that might have been included in the Q set and to allow the participant to express himself about the exercise in general (Watts & Stenner, 2005)

Figure 84. Illustration of a Q sorting (Ellingsen & al. 2014, p. 4)

Following the survey, on the basis of all the obtained Q sorts, a principal component analysis leads to the identification of factors. Each factor corresponds to a “**typical Q sort**” inasmuch as it allows grasping “*the common essence of several similar individual Q sorts*” (Lefin & Boulanger 2010, p. 15). In other words, they constitute ideal-typical versions of the way to perceive the subject of study, which are shared by a number of participants. Theoretically, they are not formulated as such by any participant.

The last step aims at describing and interpreting the factors (Cools & al., 2012; Lefin & Boulanger, 2010; Davies & Hodge, 2007; Barry & Proops, 1999). This interpretative step “*involves the production of a series of summarizing accounts, each of which explicates the viewpoint being expressed by a particular factor*” (Watts & Stenner 2005, p. 82). It is based on both the typical Q sorts (i.e.: the factor arrays) and the post sorting interviews.

1.3. Advantages and Limitations of the Q Methodology

The following section describes the advantages and limitations of the Q methodology in comparison to competing methods. The main competing method of the Q methodology is the Likert survey. Both approaches aim at understanding attitude by using a predetermined set of items that must be assessed by the respondent on an x-point scale (ten Klooster & al., 2008).

A first advantage of the Q methodology over the Likert survey is that it combines the respective strengths of qualitative and quantitative analyses. A profound analysis of the data depicting the respondents’ subjective representations of views combined with a statistical analysis of such data provides “*an in-depth analysis of the structure in the opinions and attitudes of respondents*” (ten Klooster & al. 2008, p. 516). This is even more true for a Q survey involving post-sorting in-depth interviews. Such interviews provide additional qualitative data that can greatly contribute to grasp the perception of the participants about the topic under study and to understand the rationale behind the ranking of the items (ten Klooster & al., 2008).

When comparing Likert survey and Q methodology, it appears that a Q survey requires more time for the respondent to rate the items. In a purely practical point of view, it is a disadvantage. However, some Q methodology practitioners explain that since the participant takes more time thinking about how to sort the items, the Q survey increases the validity of the score assigned to the item (Serfass & Scherman, 2013; Block, 1961). Note that, as we will see in the following section (see section “1.4.1. Respective characteristics of forced and free distributions” of the same chapter), this advantage applies more to a Q survey involving a forced distribution than a free distribution.

Still compared to a Likert scale survey, a Q survey involves less response bias like nay saying, acquiescence, extreme responding and midpoint responding. During a Q survey, the participant is indeed not allowed neither to disagree or agree with everything, nor to attribute extreme or moderate scores for every item – as does occur frequently when conducting Likert scale survey (Serfass & Scherman, 2013; Block, 1961). Again, this strength of the Q methodology assumes that the Q survey involves a forced distribution.

However, the Q methodology is subject to another type of bias: the item order effects. It appears that the participants have a tendency to sort the items presented near the end of the Q survey in the middle of the distribution. Inasmuch as those items get fewer extreme scores, their variance is lower (Serfass & Scherman, 2013). Serfass & Scherman (2013) suggest randomizing the order in which the items are proposed to the participants to reduce such bias. The randomization seems to reduce the bias at the level of the dataset, but not at the level of the Q sort. Each individual Q sort is still potentially subject to the item order effects. Therefore, Serfass & Scherman state that randomization is a “*viable adjustment for some researchers (e.g.: those interested in the effect of personality on behaviour across a sample of participants, who do not care as much about the validity of each individual’s rating) but not for others (e.g.: clinicians concerned about the description of a single patient’s personality)*” (Serfass & Scherman 2013, p. 857). In the latter case, the authors suggest using composites of multiple ratings. The use of composites of Q sorts with randomized items can actually increase the validity of each individual composite (Serfass & Scherman, 2013).

Still regarding the data analysis, a disadvantage of the Q methodology is the lack of tool to assess the validity of the results. On the contrary, the data collected with Likert scale questionnaire can be analysed with various statistical techniques to evaluate the reliability and the validity of the results (e.g.: sensitivity analysis) (ten Klooster & *al.*, 2008).

From a practical perspective, a disadvantage of the Q methodology is that it is relatively tedious. As explained in the presentation of the steps to carry out a Q methodology, the researcher is led to identify beforehand all the possible discourses related to the subject studied (See section “1.2. Conduct of a Q methodology” of the same chapter). He has to carry out in-depth review of the literature and/or exploratory interviews to formulate the items that compose the Q set. As a result, it takes lots of time and energy to develop the questionnaire (Barry & Proops, 1999).

A Q methodology also requires extra efforts from the part of the researcher to guide the respondent during the survey. Compared to Likert survey, the Q methodology is not a very popular method. The respondents are usually unfamiliar with such a method and, as a result, they need more supervision during the sorting session (ten Klooster & *al.*, 2008).

That said, time and energy can be saved inasmuch as the number of participants can be quite limited. As mentioned before, the Q methodology has the advantage of not requiring a large sample for ensuring data validity (Cools & *al.*, 2012; ten Klooster & *al.*, 2008; Barry & Proops, 1999). Statistical analysis can yield significant results from twelve participants (Barry & Proops, 1999). The Q score obtained for each participant actually offers a significant amount of information.

Even if they are most of the time unfamiliar with Q methodology, the respondents often perceive this method as an attractive way to collect data. ten Klooster & *al.* consider this feature of the Q methodology as an advantage over Likert scale survey “*in a time when people’s willingness to participate in questionnaire-based research is definitely decreasing*” (ten Klooster & *al.* 2008, p. 516).

Finally, ten Klooster & *al.* compared Likert questionnaire and Q survey by using those two methods to conduct a survey on the same topic. They submitted to similar respondent groups the exact same items and they observe a high degree of similarity between both methods regarding the rating assigned to each item, which strengthen the validity of the results obtained with both methods: “*the tasks of ordering statements in a normal distribution and judging statements on a 5-point scale do not lead to substantially different rankings of the statements*” (ten Klooster & *al.* 2008, p. 516). The difference between Likert questionnaire and Q survey lies in the analytical tools that can be employed to process

the data and the conclusions that can be drawn from such analysis. The choice between the two methods will therefore mainly depends on the objectives of the research. A Likert scale survey provides specific rating of individual items as well as an overall picture of the attitude towards the object under study expressed in one composite average score. This enables to analyse the relations between the attitude and different characteristics of the sample. Conversely, the Q methodology doesn't provide an overall picture of the perception regarding the object under study. Instead, it yields a higher level of detail by identifying groups of respondents who share the same attitude (i.e.: factors). To summarize, *"instead of segmentation on the basis of the target audience's background characteristics, the Q sort method results in segmentation on the basis of functional, content-specific criteria"* (ten Klooster & al. 2008, p. 516).

1.4. Forced and Free Distributions

I have mentioned in the section devoted to the presentation of the main steps involved in a Q methodology that the distribution can be either forced or free (see section "1.2. Conduct of a Q methodology" of the same chapter). Even if the forced distribution is often preferred by Q methodology practitioners, *"this apparent forcing (or restriction) of participants may alarm some qualitative researchers"* (Watts & Stenner 2005, p. 77). Besides showing that such fears – which usually result from a misunderstanding of the method – are misplaced, the following section aims at presenting the respective characteristics of the forced and free distributions, but also why I decided to combine them.

1.4.1. Respective Characteristics of Forced and Free Distributions

As described earlier, in a forced distribution, the participant is forced to rank the items in a Q sort diagram. Such diagram has a defined number of empty boxes under each ranking position. The Q sort diagram is usually designed as an inverted pyramid (Watts & Stenner, 2005). In such diagram, the participants can only put a limited number of items at each extreme of the grid and have to rank most of the items in the centre of the grid which corresponds to the "neutral" score. Conversely, in a free distribution, neither the number of piles for the sorting nor the number of items to allocate in each of those pile is predefined. The participant is thus free to place as many items as he wants in as many piles he desires (Du Plessis, 2005; Watts & Stenner, 2005). Examples of how the items are sorted in a Q survey involving a forced and a free distribution have been showed previously (see figures 82 and 83).

When originally introduced by William Stephenson in the 1930s, the Q methodology involved forced distribution (Brown, 1971). During the years that followed the introduction of the Q methodology, this particular feature of the approach developed by Stephenson generated some questions and criticisms (Brown & al, 2015; Block, 1961). The debate between forced *versus* free distribution was vivid until the end of the 1980s (see Bolland, 1985; Cottle & McKeown, 1980; Brown, 1980 and 1971; Gaito, 1962; Hess & Hink, 1959; Block, 1956; Jones, 1956; Cronbach & Gleser, 1953 and 1954). Today, apart from a few exceptions, like the Kampen & Tamás (2013) paper, this debate is behind us – the validity as well as the respective advantages and disadvantages of both approaches being widely acknowledged among the Q methodology practitioners' community (Giannoulis & al., 2010; Brown & al., 2015; Watts & Stenner 2005). However, inasmuch as a Q survey based on a forced distribution – just like the one I have carried out in this research – can appear disconcerting for readers unfamiliar with Q methodology, I will present throughout the rest of the section a number of criticisms levelled against the forced distribution as well as the responses to such criticisms. By discussing the main features of the two types of distribution, I also intend to provide guidance to choose between free and forced distributions.

The main reason why the forced distribution is often promoted in the Q methodology literature is that, as stated previously (see section “1.3. Advantages and limitations of the Q methodology” of the same chapter), the pyramid-shaped ranking grid encourages the participant to think more carefully when sorting the items (Serfass & Scherman, 2013; Brown & *al.*, 2015; Giannoulis & *al.*, 2010; Block, 1961). Forcing the sorting make the participant pays more attention when reading the items to understand and compare the nuance in different items (Ellingsen & *al.*, 2010). It forces participants to really prioritize and to think very clearly about what they really, truly value. This is claimed to increase the validity of the score assigned to the item (Serfass & Scherman, 2013; Block, 1961).

For their part, Kampen & Tamás (2013) don't share the view that the results obtained with a forced distribution are more valid than the ones obtained with a free distribution, rather the opposite. According to these authors, a major criterion to assess the validity of a method aiming at studying the subjective representations of views is the extent to which it respects respondents' expressions of views. To do so, the participants should be able to express the content and the strength of their view. Yet, Kampen and Tamás (2013) consider that ranking the items into a pyramid-shaped grid distorts the participants' views, questioning the validity of the results obtained with a forced distribution. This is more or less in line with the Jones' view who considers that sorting the items in a pyramid-shaped grid is not natural regarding the way individual subjective representations of views are shaped: “*The characteristic practice of forcing a quasi-normal distribution would seem to imply further that the characteristic shape of distribution of traits within individuals is also a quasi-normal distribution (...) [while] there is no evidence for a single characteristic distribution of any kind*” (Jones 1956, p. 90). In reply to the criticism that forcing the sorting doesn't enable participants to fully express their view, the proponents of such an approach defend themselves by explaining that forced distribution is far from being restrictive (Watts & Stenner, 2005). To illustrate this point, “*Brown (1980) presents a series of analyses which demonstrate that a study which employed a Q set of only 33 statements and a quite limited (+4 to -4) ranking distribution would make available to its participants 'roughly 11 000 times as many [sorting] options as there are people in the world' (...) [- Concluding that] Q methodology leaves more than 'sufficient room for individuality [to be expressed]'*” (Brown 1980 in Watts & Stenner 2005, p. 78).

Furthermore, from a psychological perspective, some argue that a Q survey based on a forced distribution destroys spontaneity and affects respondents' motivation (Gaito, 1962). A forced distribution can also generate frustration from respondents who can't fully express their views when sorting the items in the ranking grid (Du Plessis, 2005). I observed this kind of frustration when I carried out a Q survey as part of my master thesis. Several participants expressed their frustration when they were forced to assign to items a rating that did not correspond to their view (Fransolet, 2013). That said, despite such frustrations, the respondents usually adapt the rules of the game. Q methodology practitioners observe that the respondents do not usually have much difficulty to use the forced distribution and that some respondents even claim that the exercise helps them to clarify their thinking. Note that in case a participant doesn't succeed in sorting the items in the ranking grid, the Q methodology allows deviations from the forced distribution (Brown & *al.*, 2015). That said, the software that can be used to develop online Q survey does not necessarily offer such flexibility mechanisms.

A number of questions and criticisms regarding the statistical analysis of the Q sorts obtain with forced distribution were also formulated (see Gaito, 1962; Jones, 1956; Cronbach & Gleser, 1953 and 1954). Among others, Cronbach & Gleser (1953) considered forced distribution dubious because it throws out potentially important information about differences in scatter and provides data that cannot be properly proceeded with variance analysis. Block (1961), who supports forced distribution, states that this criticism should be replaced into the empirical realm. To him, it is necessary to understand the importance of the lost information in the overall scheme. He explains that some lost information is not worthy of consideration, and that other is relevant, but can be obtained more completely or more directly in other ways - through the post sorting interviews for instance. This is why Block considers

the Cronbach & Gleser 's statements *"not so much as a criticism but rather as a call for investigation of the weight and uniqueness of the eliminated information"* (Block 1961, p. 59).

More recently, Kampen & Tamás (2013) also formulate criticism regarding the analysis of Q sorts obtained under forced distribution. They explain that the variance of the rankings under forced distribution is lower compared with a free distribution. This leads to higher correlation of rankings across respondents, which increase the probability of respondents to be grouped in a factor. For Kampen & Tamás, the method doesn't enable the researcher to understand if respondents associated with a same factor following a forced distribution Q survey would have been clustered with a free distribution Q survey. For these authors, it implies that *"the method is unable to separate clustering by the design of the research instrument from clustering by truly shared views"* (Kampen & Tamás 2013, p. 7). In response to Kampen & Tamás' criticism, Brown & al. argue that *"It is only by distinguishing those statements that are preferred over others that those associated with the greater strength of feeling can be revealed"* (Brown & al. 2015, p. 531). They explain that in some cases, when the topic discussed is highly polarized for instance, the participants can potentially dichotomize the items if using a free distribution. This sorting of the items at the extreme poles of the distribution can make it difficult to distinguish points of view among the participants – while various viewpoints might exist. Forcing the distribution can contribute to reveal distinct points of view that could have been remained undetected with a free distribution (Brown & al., 2015).

Still regarding the analytical aspects, one of the reasons why Block (1961 and 1956) considers the forced distribution as a more effective approach than free distribution is that it produces comparable data-systems. He explains that when using a universal distribution, the respondents make the same number of discriminations between the items and this *"enables comparison between judges to be made straightforwardly without distortions due to "response sets" "* (Block 1956, p. 481). On the contrary, he thinks that the comparison of the Q sorts obtained under variable distributions can be *"muddled and just plain awkward to make"* (Block 1961, p. 58).

Finally, as mentioned in the previous section, inasmuch as the participant is not allowed neither to disagree or agree with everything, nor to attribute extreme or moderate scores for every item, the forced distribution involves less response bias such as nay saying, acquiescence, extreme responding and midpoint responding (Serfass & Scherman, 2013; Block, 1961).

With a view to clarifying the debate that used to oppose forced and free distributions, several empirical studies have analysed comparatively those two Q sorting procedures. All these studies lead to the conclusion that the type of distribution makes little difference regarding the statistical results (Cottle & McKeown, 1980; Brown, 1980 and 1971; Hess & Hink, 1959; Block, 1956). When comparing the results obtained with forced and free distribution, Brown observes that *"Q sorts with identical item orderings but with varied distributions are shown to provide essentially the same correlations and factors structures (...) leading to the conclusion that the same results are obtained, despite distribution and whether interval or ordinal statistics are used"* (Brown 1971, p. 283). The factors development in Q methodology is thus almost entirely affected by the patterns of item placement – the distribution effects being virtually nil (Brown, 1980). In this context, Block (1956) states that the choice between forced and free distribution should be based on the objectives of the research. He suggests opting for forced distribution in case the item order is considered paramount importance, and conversely opting for free distribution when this is the scale separation that matters and when the ordering of items is not that important.

1.4.2. Combining Forced and Free Distributions

In this research, I have decided to combine forced and free distributions. As further explained below (see section “2.3.2. Q survey” of the same chapter), the Q survey conducted in the present research included two steps. The first step was a pre-sorting of the items under a free distribution⁴⁴. In the second step, the participant had to sort the items in a pyramid-shaped grid that corresponds to a forced distribution. The Q methodology usually involves a pre-sorting of the items, but, most of the time, this first step consists in dividing the items into three piles (e.g.: “disagree”, “neutral” and “agree”). This pre-sorting step aims at making the ranking in the pyramid-shaped grid easier for the participant. The results of the pre-sorting step are habitually not taken into consideration in the data analysis. Several reasons led me to deviate from the “traditional” procedure.

I chose to carry out a Q survey involving a forced distribution because the ordering of the items was important in this research. I indeed intended to compare the policy-relevance of different governance issues. Under a free distribution, the respondent wouldn’t have been incited to assess the relevance of the governance issues in a comparative way. For instance, they could have sorted all the proposed issues as policy-relevant. Besides the fact that the forced distribution is more suitable to meet the objectives of the research, I also had a personal preference for this approach given its advantages previously mentioned. As explained earlier, the use of a pyramid-shaped grid seems to encourage the participant to think more carefully when sorting the items (Ellingsen & *al.*, 2010).

As said before, the forced distribution also has some shortcomings. This is to address the problems that I have encountered when doing a forced Q survey as part of my master thesis that I have decided to undertake a pre-sorting of the items under a free distribution. One of the main problems encountered during this first Q survey was the frustrations that some participants may experience when they were forced to assign to items ratings that didn’t correspond to their view. By letting the participant freely express their view regarding the items during the pre-sorting step, I meant to reduce such frustrations. The participants were indeed free to assign the score they wanted to the items in the pre-sorting step and, as we shifted into the forced distribution, I explained them that the score assigned to the items was no longer important – the objective being to compare the items with each other.

The other limit of the forced distribution that I tried to reduce by combining it with a free distribution was the distortion of the participants’ views potentially generated by the sorting of the items in the pyramid-shaped grid. I wanted to know whether the scores assigned under forced distribution didn’t substantially differ from the ones assigned under free distribution. A comparison of the results obtained with forced and free distributions as well as a discussion on the value of combining the two types of distribution are made at the end of the present chapter (see section “5.1. Forced and free distributions” of the same chapter)

⁴⁴ Note that this pre-sorting was not completely free inasmuch as the number of piles for the sorting was predetermined and not left to the participant. The participant was thus free to place as many items as he wants under the ranking position that I had defined beforehand.

2. Conduct of the Study

2.1. Construction of the Sample (Q Sample)

Just like in the study on the role of low-carbon scenario in policy-making (see Chapter III), the sample includes the actors involved in the long-term policy process of GHG-emissions' mitigation in the Walloon Region (i.e.: producers and intended users of scenarios). The contacted persons are therefore the same of those of the study presented in the previous chapter (see section "2.2.2. Semi-structured interviews" of Chapter III). The interviews were actually made up of two parts, the first one consisting of a discussion on the role of energy foresight studies in policy-making (i.e.: Chapter III), and the second one being the Q survey.

Among the 74 persons I interviewed, 54 persons participated in the Q survey. Some persons preferred not participating because they didn't work anymore on climate-energy issues or because they had not enough time after the first part of the interview. Five people began to sort the items but were unable to complete the ranking due to lack of time. Two people did not want to participate in the Q survey stating that one had all the knowledge needed to develop GHG emission reduction policies and that one therefore did not need additional studies.

The Q sample is composed of three political authorities, eleven political advisors, six administrative authorities, seven employers' federations, three workers' unions, five environmental and development NGOs, seven energy market operators, one public transport operator, four public research institutes, five consultancy agencies and two universities. The following table summarizes the distribution of respondents according to the categories of actors considered [Table 19]. It also reminds code I used to anonymize the collected data.

CATEGORY OF ACTORS		LEVEL		TOTAL
		WALLONIA (RW)	BELGIUM (BE)	
Intended users of scenarios	Political authorities (POL)	2	1	3
	Political advisors (PA)	4	7	11
	Administrative authorities (ADM)	4	2	6
	Employers' federations (BUS)	2	5	7
	Workers' unions (WU)	1	2	3
	Environmental and development NGOs (NGO)	1	4	5
	Advisory councils (AC)	0	0	0
	Energy market operators (ENG)	1	6	7
	Public transport operators (TRA)	0	1	1
Producers of scenarios	Public research institutes (PRI)	2	2	4
	Consultancy agencies (CA)	0	5	5
	Universities (UNI)	2	0	2
TOTAL		19	35	54

Table 19. Number of respondents for each category of actors

2.2. Formulation of the Items (Q Set)

The Q methodology involves the construction of a Q set. As a reminder, it corresponds to a set of items that is supposed to cover all the possible discourses in relation to the object of study. In the present research, the discourse deals with the knowledge concerning the governance of the low-carbon transition that political actors need to devise long-term mitigation policies. I therefore have tried to identify the knowledge gaps regarding the governance of the low-carbon transition.

With a view to identifying such knowledge gaps, I have used a matrix that crossed the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance above-mentioned (see section "4.1.2. Policy, politics and polity dimensions of governance" of Chapter I). The matrix is presented in the following figure [Figure 85]. This tool helped me to identify in a systematic way the governance issues that could be addressed in low-carbon scenarios. As a first step, I checked all the boxes of the matrix and tried to determine the

issues that emerge from the crossing of the governance dimensions considered. For instance, when crossing the dimensions “Locus of authority” (i.e.: level of action and division of competences) and “Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals”, we obtain two issues: “Vertical integration of the policy instruments” (i.e.: articulation of the policy instruments implemented at different levels of power) and “horizontal integration of the policy instruments” (i.e.: articulation of the policy instruments implemented at different sectors at the same level of power). This tool helped me to identify 22 governance issues.

Inasmuch as the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance are part of a “generic” analytical framework of governance, the issues identified by this way are not specific to the governance of the low-carbon transition. They could indeed apply to any public problem. This is why, this list of governance issues has been completed with issues that are more specific to the climate-energy governance. To do so, I carried out a literature review and exploratory talks with actors involved in the long-term decision-making process for climate mitigation in Wallonia. The six governance issues identified through the literature review are coloured in red in the matrix. They concern the incumbent sensitive climate-mitigation policy (Hansen, 2015; Geels, 2014), the representation of non-human beings (i.e.: animals, plants) and future generations in climate negotiations (Latour, 2015; Sébastien, 2006) and the foresight institutionalization (Petit Jean, 2016). The exploratory interviews contributed to the identification of two additional issues. Those issues – that are in bold in the matrix – concern the vision for 2050 and the long-term integration in the policy proces

		POLICY			POLITICS		POLITY		
		Way the problem is defined as a public issue	Goals set to deal with the problem	Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process	Role of the different stakeholders in the policy process	Locus of authority	Steering mode	Degree of formal institutionalization of the policy process
POLICY	Way the problem is defined as a public issue	• Way the problem is defined as a public issue							
	Policy goals set to deal with the problem	• Vision for 2050 (1)	• Policy goals set to deal with the problem (2)						
	Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy mix (3) • Regulatory framework (4) • Eco-fiscality (5) • Services and infrastructures (6) • Land use planning (7) • Information and awareness (8) • Education and vocational training (9) 					
POLITICS	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process				• Role of the political-administrative authorities (10)				
	Role of the different stakeholders in the policy process			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consideration of the incumbents' needs (13) • Resistances of the incumbents (14) • Mobilization of the incumbents (15) 	• Role of the different public and private actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the different stakeholders (11) • Role of the incumbents (12) 			
POLITY	Locus of authority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue (19) • Horizontal integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue (20) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical integration of the policy goals (21) • Horizontal integration of the policy goals (22) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical integration of the policy instruments (23) • Horizontal integration of the policy instruments (24) 			• Level of action and division of competences (16)		
	Steering mode					• Degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders (25)		• Steering mode (17)	
	Institutionalization of the policy process		• Long-term integration in the policy process (26)			• Representation of 'non-living' and future generations in the policy process (27)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutionalization of the policy process • Foresight institutionalization (18)

Figure 85. Matrix crossing the policy, politics and polity dimensions governance used to identify knowledge gaps regarding the governance of the low-carbon transition. The number in parenthesis is the reference number of the item to which the issue relates

The matrix completed with the literature review and the exploratory interviews enabled me to identify 30 governance issues that could be addressed in low-carbon scenarios. Among those 30 issues, three haven't been selected to compose the Q set. They are the way the problem is defined as a public issue, the institutionalization of the policy process, and the role of the different public and private actors. The first two issues were excluded because they don't appear to constitute a knowledge gap. The issue of the role of the different public and private actors was not included in the Q set to avoid having an item covering several issues. I preferred using two distinct issues: "Role of the political-administrative authorities" and "Role of the different stakeholders".

On the basis of the 27 remaining governance issues I formulated the items that compose the Q set. The table below lists the items as well as the governance dimensions they cover [Table 20]. As showed in the table, each item includes a reference number as well as the name of the governance issue considered followed by a research question. For instance, the first item is formulated as follows: "(1) Vision for 2050 - What kind of low-carbon society do we want to build?". This way of formulating the items is quite unusual in Q methodology. Most of the time, the items are presented in the form of a statement. According to the regular procedure, the first item would have been formulated as follows: "I believe that a study aiming at defining a low-carbon vision for 2050 should be conducted" or "I think that the issue of the low-carbon vision for 2050 is policy-relevant". I have hesitated quite a long time before deciding how to formulate the items. It is after discussing with Q methodology practitioners and testing different options that I choose to present the items with the name of the governance issue considered followed by a research question. This formulation appears more structured and easier to understand. The question format also aims at inciting the responded to consider whether he can answer the question or not, and on the basis of that, assess the policy-relevance of the issue.

ITEMS	DIMENSIONS OF GOVERNANCE
(1) Vision for 2050 - What kind of low-carbon society do we want to build?	Policy
(2) Policy goals - What policy objectives should be set for the different sectors / level of power with a view to building a low-carbon society?	Policy
(3) Policy mix - What mix of policy instruments should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? (i.e.: standards, taxes, awareness campaigns)	Policy
(4) Regulatory framework - What standards should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? (i.e.: norms, branch agreements) In what ways?	Policy
(5) Eco-fiscality - What economic instruments (i.e.: taxes, subsidies, carbon market) should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? In what ways?	Policy
(6) Services and infrastructures - What services (i.e.: TEC, SNCB) & infrastructures (i.e.: energy network) development policy should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? In what ways?	Policy
(7) Land use planning - What spatial planning policy should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society?	Policy
(8) Information and awareness - How to inform and raise awareness among citizens with a view to inspire the behavioural changes required for building a low-carbon society?	Policy
(9) Education and vocational training - How to rethink the education and training system to meet the new knowledge and skills needs engendered by the low-carbon transition? (i.e.: new building insulation techniques)	Policy
(10) Role of the political-administrative authorities - What role (i.e.: regulator, coordinator) should political-administrative authorities play with a view to building a low-carbon society?	Politics
(11) Role of the different stakeholders - What role should different stakeholders (i.e.: civil society organizations, citizens, scientists) play with a view to building a low-carbon society?	Politics
(12) Role of the incumbents - What role should incumbents (i.e.: oil companies, large retailers) play with a view to building a low-carbon society?	Politics
(13) Consideration of the incumbents' needs - What policy to implement to ensure the low-carbon transition while taking into account the needs of the incumbents?	Policy X Politics
(14) Resistances of the incumbents - How to address the incumbents' resistances to low-carbon transition?	Policy X Politics
(15) Mobilization of the incumbents - How to ensure that the incumbents (i.e.: oil companies, large retailers) take part in the low-carbon transition and mobilize their financial resources, their skills, and their contact networks with a view to accelerating the transition?	Policy X Politics
(16) Level of action and division of competences - At what level(s) should the low-carbon policies be devised? (i.e.: local, region, federal, supranational) How to organize the division of competences? (i.e.: de/re-centralization?)	Polity
(17) Steering mode - What steering mode would facilitate the low-carbon transition? (i.e.: top-down, bottom-up, market, network, community)	Polity
(18) Foresight's institutionalization - What structures should be set up with a view to institutionalizing foresight in the field of climate and energy policy? (i.e.: transition arena)	Polity
(19) Vertical integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue - How to articulate the way different levels of power define the issue of the low-carbon transition with a view to devising a coherent policy? (i.e.: energy supply Vs energy demand? Technological levers Vs behavioural levers?)	Policy X Polity
(20) Horizontal integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue - How to articulate the way different sectors at the same level of power define the issue of the low-carbon transition with a view to devising a coherent policy? (i.e.: energy supply Vs energy demand? Technological levers Vs behavioural levers?)	Policy X Polity
(21) Vertical integration of the policy goals - How to articulate the objectives adopted at different levels of power with a view to devising a coherent policy?	Policy X Polity
(22) Horizontal integration of the policy goals - How to articulate the objectives adopted by different sectors at the same level of power with a view to devising a coherent policy?	Policy X Polity
(23) Vertical integration of the policy instruments - How to articulate the policy instruments implemented at different levels of power with a view to devising a coherent policy?	Policy X Polity
(24) Horizontal integration of the policy instruments - How to articulate the policy instruments implemented in different sectors at the same level of power with a view to devising a coherent policy?	Policy X Polity
(25) Degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders - To what extent and in what way the different stakeholders should participate in the policy process with a view to building a low-carbon society?	Politics X Polity
(26) Long-term integration in the policy process - How to integrate the long-term in the policy process with a view to building a low-carbon society? (i.e.: Long-term Chamber (Jacques Attali))	Policy X Polity
(27) Representation of non-human beings in the policy process - How to represent the non-human beings (i.e.: animals, plants) and the future generations in the policy process?	Politics X Polity

Table 20. Q set

2.3. Data Collection

As mentioned in the section devoted to the Q methodology (see section “1.2. Conduct of a Q methodology” of the same chapter) two modes of data collection exist: the face to face interview and the online questionnaire. For this study, I chose the first approach. Several reasons led me to select the interview method instead of the questionnaire. A first reason is of a practical nature. I was going to meet the actors of the transition to a low-carbon society to discuss the use of the scenarios anyway (see Chapter III). I thus took advantage of this meeting to carry out the Q survey. The second reason that led me to conduct the survey via interviews rather than via an online questionnaire was to facilitate the interpretation of the results. By conducting an online Q survey as part of my master thesis, I found that the questionnaire did not encourage participants to justify their choice, which made the interpretation of the results difficult (Fransolet, 2013). Conversely, during a face to face interview, the participants naturally tend to explain their ranking and even if they do not, one can ask them afterwards. Finally, since the exercise, which took the form of a role play (see below), was not easy, I preferred to be present on the one hand to make sure the respondent understands what I expected of him, and on the other hand to answer any questions he may have.

The Q survey consisted of two parts: the introductory questions and the Q survey. A full version of the interview guide for the Q survey is available in appendix [Appendix 3].

2.3.1. Introductory Questions

Before starting the ranking, I tried to understand the policy relevance of governance issues compared to other questions. With this in mind, I presented to the participant a series of potential research themes connected with the low-carbon transition and they were asked to rate their policy relevance on a five-point scale ranging from irrelevant to highly relevant. These potential research themes correspond to the behavioural and technical levers, the social innovation, the financing, the governance and public policy, the social acceptability, and the employment. To make it more concrete and more comprehensible, the issues were followed by examples of questions they can cover. The proposed issues and the examples of questions are listed in the following table [Table 21]. These proposals were defined on the basis of exploratory interviews, literature, and, more globally, of my personal knowledge on the low-carbon transition challenges that I have developed over the past few years.

ISSUES	EXAMPLES OF QUESTIONS
Behavioural and technical levers	What are the technical innovations and behavioural changes that should be promoted in order to ensure the low-carbon transition?
Social innovation	What are the innovative approaches or pioneering projects developed by citizens? To what extent can these citizen initiatives help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions? How to support them?
Financing	How to mobilize public and private investment to finance the low-carbon transition? What are the innovative options for financing? How to ensure the profitability of investments in low-carbon technologies and limit risks? How to limit the socio-economic impacts for the "losers" of the low-carbon transition?
Governance and public policy	How to steer the low-carbon transition? What public policies to implement? At what levels of power? With what participation of the stakeholders / citizens? How to ensure coherence with other sectoral policies?
Social acceptability	Which low-carbon transition path is the most socially acceptable? How to promote social acceptability in relation to different low-carbon measures and policies?
Employment	What are the impacts of the low-carbon transition on employment? How to limit the negative impacts on employment in order to ensure a fair transition? How to modulate the training offer to meet the need for new skills generated by the low-carbon transition?

Table 21. Potential research topics whose policy-relevance had to be assessed by the respondent

Note that in order not to introduce any bias, I did not mention that I was interested in governance issues in the contact e-mail or when I introduced myself and my research in the beginning of the interview (see section “2.2.2. Semi-structured interviews” of Chapter III).

2.3.2. Q Survey

After this introduction, we began the Q survey. The survey was presented as a roleplay. The participant had to imagine that he was the sponsor of the forthcoming study on the low-carbon transition in Wallonia / Belgium and that this study would focus on governance and public policy issues. As sponsor, he had to prepare the terms of reference for this study and decide which issues should be addressed in the analysis.

During the first step of the survey, I distributed the items printed on cards one by one to the participant. From one participant to another, the items were distributed in the same order which is the one indicated in the table presenting the Q set (see table 20). As explained in the section devoted to the limits of the Q methodology (see section “1.3. Advantages and limitations of the Q methodology” of the same chapter), this method is subject to item order effects and randomizing the order in which the items are presented to the participants can reduce such bias at the dataset level, but not at the individual Q sort level (Serfass & Sherman, 2013). Inasmuch as the validity of each individual’s rating is quite important in light of my research interests (i.e.: mapping the knowledge need of each type of actors), I decided not to randomize order in which the items are presented, keeping in mind that the item order effects’ bias exist. Moreover, the order I defined follows a logical sequence which is intended to help the participant to understand the items.

The participant had to sort the items in the upper part of the grid according to the degree of policy relevance of the proposed issue. The ranking grid is shown in the figure hereunder [Figure 86]. The upper part of the grid is composed of an unlimited number of squares for each column. It corresponds to the free distribution. The ranking grid includes five columns, each corresponding to a specific degree of policy-relevance: Irrelevant (-2), of little relevance (-1), no opinion (0), relevant (+1) and very relevant (+2). The scale is smaller than average. I indeed mentioned in the section devoted to the presentation of the Q methodology (see section “1.2. Conduct of a Q methodology” of the same chapter) that a typical scale goes from -6 or -5 to +5 or +6. I decided to use such a small grid for three reasons. The first reason is that the Q set is quite small. With 27 items, the Q set is smaller than average (i.e.: 40-80 items, as previously explained). The second reason is that the policy-relevance of low-carbon transition governance issues is not really a polarized question (e.g.: while a carbon tax can be considered as extremely unacceptable (i.e.: high polarized debate), a study on the implementation of a carbon tax cannot be considered as extremely irrelevant). Finally, after testing the Q survey with a grid with a scale from -3 to +3 and another one with a scale from -2 to +2, I have realized that the second option was much more suitable. It was indeed quite difficult to distinguish the points on the -3 to +3 scale.

During the second step, after having distributed all the items in the five columns, the participant had to transfer them from the upper to the lower part of the grid. The lower part of the grid comprises 27 boxes, which corresponds to the number of items. This is the forced distribution. In this second stage of the ranking, the rating was no longer important, the objective being to classify the statements against each other.

2.4. Data Analysis

I used the Ken-Q Analysis⁴⁵ software to analyse the Q sorts obtained during the survey. Ken-Q Analysis is a free web application developed by Shawn Banasick (2016). Other Q sorts analysis software are available (see International Society for the Scientific Study of Subjectivity, 2018). In comparison with the software I used to carry out the Q sorts analysis in the context of my master thesis, PQMethod (see Fransolet, 2013), Ken-Q Analysis is much more user friendly.

The analysis aims to identify factors based on a principal component analysis followed by a factor rotation.

2.4.1. Principal Component Analysis

After encoding the data, a principal component analysis (PCA) was conducted to study the inter-correlations between the Q-sorts. The first step of the PCA provides the matrix of correlations between the Q-sorts. This matrix is shown below [Table 22]. A perfect positive correlation between two Q-sorts equals 100 and a perfect negative correlation equals -100. A correlation between two Q-sorts is considered significant when it is superior to 38 or 48⁴⁶.

⁴⁵ <https://shawnbanasick.github.io/ken-q-analysis/>

⁴⁶ With a standard error of 19 ($100/\sqrt{N}$ where N is the number of propositions), a correlation is considered significant if it is greater than 38 or 48 ($19*2$ or $19*2,5$).

	POL-BE-1	POL-RW-1	POL-RW-2	PA-BE-1	PA-BE-2	PA-BE-3	PA-BE-4	PA-BE-5	PA-BE-6	PA-BE-7	PA-RW-1	PA-RW-2	PA-RW-3	PA-RW-4	ADM-BE-1	ADM-RW-1	ADM-RW-2	ADM-RW-3	ADM-RW-4	BUS-BE-1	BUS-BE-2	BUS-BE-3	BUS-BE-4	BUS-BE-5	BUS-RW-1	BUS-RW-2	BUS-RW-3	BUS-RW-4	WU-BE-1	WU-BE-2	WU-RW-1	WU-RW-2	WU-RW-3	WU-RW-4	NGO-BE-1	NGO-BE-2	NGO-BE-3	NGO-BE-4	NGO-BE-5	NGO-BE-6	ENG-BE-1	ENG-BE-2	ENG-BE-3	ENG-BE-4	ENG-BE-5	ENG-BE-6	TRA-RW-1	PRI-BE-1	PRI-BE-2	PRI-RW-1	PRI-RW-2	CA-BE-1	CA-BE-2	CA-BE-3	CA-BE-4	CA-BE-5	UNI-RW-1	UNI-RW-2	ADM-BE-2
POL-BE-1	100	7	39	-30	50	23	-23	39	-20	7	30	-7	16	30	34	43	43	-7	9	-20	45	0	-5	0	-11	-20	9	18	9	48	-7	36	55	41	23	11	-11	14	18	50	23	20	-73	2	7	20	30	52	27	-14	48	7	-11	39					
POL-RW-1	7	100	23	16	32	0	9	-5	-34	-16	16	39	20	61	23	-2	-23	-9	43	-7	16	23	39	0	11	2	-36	-25	39	18	34	18	7	18	36	0	9	27	14	34	14	23	-7	20	11	-20	41	-2	32	39	18	27	16	-23					
POL-RW-2	39	23	100	-7	18	18	-2	18	-36	27	-23	5	20	14	23	18	-2	23	5	7	20	16	25	0	16	-16	-2	18	20	2	34	16	16	-2	9	-16	18	25	33	36	36	-20	0	14	20	32	20	32	14	39	0	-16	-14						
PA-BE-1	-30	16	-7	100	0	9	-7	-34	39	14	-20	-5	-11	23	5	-2	-14	9	25	39	-16	23	32	34	48	2	-32	-18	55	-45	16	-16	14	-5	-7	-16	59	-5	9	-5	-16	-11	2	-7	14	0	7	43	-34	-9	9	-23							
PA-BE-2	50	32	18	0	100	-14	-14	23	-2	-11	23	27	20	59	45	27	-7	-2	9	55	-2	45	-7	-18	-18	-18	0	45	18	9	23	48	34	-5	23	27	14	32	66	48	7	-55	48	23	2	27	18	-5	48	41	34	52	23						
PA-BE-3	23	0	18	9	-14	100	-5	16	-2	14	-14	-25	-32	-20	9	64	41	7	27	18	16	39	5	-14	-5	20	36	25	14	18	27	25	14	30	9	5	11	30	25	-7	16	20	-18	-16	5	11	43	43	27	-16	30	2	-16	11					
PA-BE-4	-23	9	-2	-7	-14	-5	100	2	-18	18	2	18	41	5	2	-11	-23	2	-32	-25	7	7	5	9	39	27	16	-23	-32	5	7	16	-55	11	-5	25	-7	48	30	-41	30	0	14	20	39	7	-20	11	9	-7	30	-14	-16	-5					
PA-BE-5	39	-5	18	-34	23	16	2	100	-18	-18	18	11	41	-11	30	32	30	18	2	25	43	5	-9	-41	-50	34	32	-2	2	43	-36	0	20	-7	23	20	-23	34	39	25	50	36	-39	11	27	25	-9	32	18	-36	30	-2	25	20	-2				
PA-BE-6	-20	-34	-36	39	-2	-2	-18	-18	100	0	-7	2	-30	-9	-2	2	9	-11	9	18	-34	11	-9	30	-5	14	2	-41	-5	-11	18	-11	-43	-2	36	-2	-11	5	-16	-20	32	-2	-14	2	-39	16	-30	9	-41	-20	0	-2							
PA-BE-7	7	-16	27	14	-11	14	18	-18	0	100	25	-27	9	16	16	9	-5	27	-23	2	9	2	-23	14	50	-11	2	-2	-7	-14	20	41	2	30	-7	-5	-7	25	-5	-20	-9	20	-2	-18	-14	14	7	43	-5	-5	32	11	-9	27					
PA-RW-1	30	16	-23	-20	23	-14	2	18	-7	25	100	2	41	50	50	-2	5	2	-7	-23	27	-20	-48	0	9	-11	0	-20	-2	59	-23	27	23	36	7	36	-20	30	-9	11	2	23	-20	-16	18	9	7	32	18	5	34	23	18	52					
PA-RW-2	-7	39	5	-5	27	-25	18	11	2	-27	2	100	9	36	11	-5	-16	-20	11	20	16	34	30	5	-18	23	-16	2	5	18	23	16	-23	7	2	25	5	5	25	16	30	14	27	5	16	-30	-2	-11	20	34	18	-5	36	-20					
PA-RW-3	16	20	-11	20	-32	41	41	-30	9	41	9	100	32	20	-25	0	14	-25	-2	41	-39	0	-14	18	-11	-9	-41	5	43	-23	9	2	16	30	16	-14	43	23	7	30	43	-20	18	36	41	-11	9	25	-2	30	5	5	0						
PA-RW-4	30	61	14	23	59	-20	5	-11	-9	16	50	36	32	100	50	5	-11	14	5	-7	41	5	18	9	34	-18	-14	-2	36	27	34	20	25	52	2	43	23	14	27	34	2	25	-20	16	14	20	20	25	57	39	16	36	27						
ADM-BE-1	34	23	23	5	45	9	2	30	-2	16	50	11	20	50	100	39	9	7	16	11	39	32	-18	11	9	-11	0	2	11	34	-18	7	41	27	-23	39	36	25	39	23	41	20	-34	-5	45	7	18	55	25	11	43	-9	20	61					
ADM-RW-1	43	-2	18	-2	27	64	-11	32	2	9	-2	-5	-25	5	39	100	43	18	27	30	45	57	9	16	-11	25	36	23	0	25	11	5	20	45	-9	25	30	20	43	9	20	7	-50	-2	25	-2	27	57	20	-11	27	-16	9	36					
ADM-RW-2	43	-23	-2	-14	27	41	-23	30	9	-5	-16	0	-11	9	43	100	0	5	25	34	-2	-2	-23	-45	11	27	23	7	27	7	23	25	34	20	20	0	2	18	30	5	-20	-48	-11	-7	0	23	27	-18	-16	20	27	14	30						
ADM-RW-3	-7	-9	23	9	-7	7	2	18	-11	27	2	-20	14	14	7	18	0	100	-2	5	30	7	11	-20	23	-9	34	11	-2	14	16	-16	-14	11	20	32	11	0	45	-2	-11	11	-18	-9	-2	32	-11	20	20	-7	16	-11	11	16					
ADM-RW-4	9	43	5	25	-2	27	-32	2	9	-23	-7	11	-25	5	16	27	5	-2	100	20	7	48	14	30	-16	-14	-20	-5	7	2	-7	5	25	16	30	14	27	5	20	9	18	39	-7	0	-9	0	-2	-23	18	34	30	-9	-14	-20	-9				
BUS-BE-1	-20	-7	7	39	9	18	-25	25	18	2	-23	20	-2	-7	11	30	25	5	20	100	27	27	11	-7	-23	43	5	20	-14	7	-23	16	0	-20	9	27	-5	18	16	14	5	7	7	2	7	5	0	-14	23	-18	0	52	5						
BUS-BE-2	45	16	20	-16	55	16	7	43	-34	9	27	16	41	41	39	45	34	30	7	27	100	14	23	-18	-11	14	16	-5	11	55	5	34	23	61	20	50	7	41	57	39	34	34	-52	30	18	32	34	48	23	7	66	14	43	39					
BUS-BE-3	0	23	16	23	-2	39	7	5	11	2	-20	34	-39	5	32	57	-2	7	48	27	14	100	18	39	2	23	2	11	-5	-25	5	-11	7	2	14	45	14	39	-2	9	0	-5	-14	-14	-18	32	43	20	9	11	-25	-5	7						
BUS-BE-4	-5	39	25	32	45	5	5	-9	-9	-23	-48	30	0	18	-18	9	-2	11	14	11	23	18	100	5	2	-9	-30	-5	50	-16	34	11	-14	7	27	-11	34	7	49	30	34	9	-18	41	20	-9	18	20	39	16	18	20	-48						
BUS-BE-5	0	0	0	34	-7	-14	9	-41	30	14	0	5	-14	9	11	16	-23	-20	30	-7	-18	39	-5	100	43	7	-20	-25	-11	-27	2	-9	0	7	-30	-14	52	7	-5	-16	-14	-27	2	-5	27	-11	-7	27	2	16	-30	-30	-39	-14					
BUS-RW-1	-11	11	16	48	-18	-5	39	-50	-5	50	9	-18	18	34	9	-11	-45	23	-16	-23	-11	2	2	43	100	-32	-23	-16	5	-7	16	-9	-11	11	-5	-9	25	7	0	-36	-11	0	5	-11	20	23	0	9	36	20	-2	-25	-39	-5					
BUS-RW-2	-20	2	-16	2	-18	20	27	34	14	-11	-11	23	11	-18	-11	25	11	-9	14	43	14	23	-9	7	-32	100	43	-30	-20	-5	9	7	-11	14	-16	23	2	34	25	5	14	18	5	9	-20	11	-23	-11	-11	-5	27	-14							
WU-BE-1	9	-36	-2	-32	-18	36	16	32	5	2	0	-16	-9	-14	0	36	27	34	-20	5	16	2	-30	-20	-23	43	100	45	-34	14	23	-9	-18	20	-34	64	-14	11	39	-23	-2	7	7	11	2	25	-34	27	-11	-23	20	-11	14	39					
WU-BE-2	18	-25	18	-18	0	25	-23	-2	14	-2	-20	2	-41	-2	2	23	23	11	-5	5	-5	11	-5	-25	-16	-30	45	100	-7	-2	27	-14	-11	2	-25	36	-16	-27	14	7	-9	-2	11	-7	-7	-18	-9	7	7	0	20	-27	5	34					
WU-RW-1	9	39	20	55	45	14	-32	2	-7	-2	5	5	36	11	0	7	-2	7	20	11	-5	50	-11	5	-20	-34	-7	100	-16	27	9	32	-9	20	-25	36	18	2	32	18	18	-20	5	18	-9	43	-11	11	52	9	41	32	-32						
NGO-BE-1	48	18	2	-45	18	18	5	43	-41	-14	59	18	43	27	34	25	27	14	2	-14	55	-5	-16	-27	-7	-5	14	-2	-16	100	-18	18	11	41	41	41	-30	18	27	14	27	32	-36	-14	23	27	20	55	-20	48	2	5	36						
NGO-BE-2	-7	34	34	16	9	27	7	-36	-5	20	-23	23	-34	-18	11	7	16	-7	7	5	25	34	2	16	9	23	27	-18	100	23	-18	20	-11	50	30	5	-20	48	11	16	16	34	-18	-2	-14	-5	41	41	2	-2	68	39	7	5					
NGO-BE-3	36																																																										

Based on the matrix of correlations between Q sorts, the PCA extracted eight factors. As a reminder, a factor corresponds to a typical Q sorts which is a particular point of view shared by several participants. The following matrix crosses those factors with the Q sorts [Table 23]. The values in the matrix represent the correlation between the factors and the Q sorts. A perfect positive correlation between a factor and a Q sort equals 1, while a perfect negative correlation equals -1. The eigenvalues of the factors and the (cumulative) percentage explanation of the variance are shown at the bottom of the matrix. The eigenvalue represents “the relative contribution of a factor to the explanation of the total variance in the correlation matrix” (Cools & al. 2012, p. 84).

Q SORTS	FACTOR 1	FACTOR 2	FACTOR 3	FACTOR 4	FACTOR 5	FACTOR 6	FACTOR 7	FACTOR 8
POL-BE-1	[0,6618]	-0,139	-0,1825	-0,2793	-0,3807	0,0377	-0,1091	-0,0179
POL-RW-1	0,3415	[0,5795]	-0,2371	0,2627	0,0131	-0,101	0,0581	-0,2905
POL-RW-2	0,3686	0,2007	-0,0307	0,171	-0,213	-0,2473	0,1151	0,2085
PA-BE-1	-0,1395	0,602	0,4077	0,1627	-0,1629	0,1269	-0,1319	0,1785
PA-BE-2	0,6415	0,4485	-0,1189	-0,3	0,2256	0,2276	-0,1787	-0,0103
PA-BE-3	0,3386	-0,1153	0,3681	-0,1212	-0,3809	-0,4311	0,3192	0,1756
PA-BE-4	0,0817	-0,2056	0,0448	[0,7157]	0,3176	-0,0097	0,1345	0,1404
PA-BE-5	[0,5156]	-0,369	-0,1046	-0,1709	0,2613	-0,3984	-0,3721	0,124
PA-BE-6	-0,294	0,0877	0,4996	-0,2233	0,0232	0,2352	-0,1967	0,1704
PA-BE-7	0,1477	-0,1365	0,082	0,2539	-0,3328	0,3815	0,3943	0,4194
PA-RW-1	0,4328	-0,2392	-0,2994	0,0821	-0,0578	0,5828	-0,1112	-0,1483
PA-RW-2	0,1833	0,3168	0,0311	0,1869	0,457	-0,1424	0,0159	-0,4852
PA-RW-3	0,3984	-0,1226	-0,4391	0,4312	0,2699	0,113	-0,2865	0,2446
PA-RW-4	0,548	0,4144	-0,0595	0,191	0,0799	0,545	0,0859	-0,2627
ADM-BE-1	[0,6359]	0,0103	0,2374	0,0528	-0,094	0,3436	-0,3342	-0,1387
ADM-BE-2	0,4569	-0,479	0,213	-0,2768	-0,0523	0,524	-0,0031	-0,1792
ADM-RW-1	0,5452	-0,1025	0,5636	-0,2158	-0,2378	-0,2297	0,0153	-0,0341
ADM-RW-2	0,3693	-0,1787	0,0708	-0,6025	-0,1007	-0,1495	0,1228	0,0936
ADM-RW-3	0,2231	-0,1697	0,1812	0,1511	0,0039	0,0047	0,1645	0,0767
ADM-RW-4	0,1577	0,2532	0,2785	-0,0994	-0,3394	-0,3277	-0,2426	-0,2971
BUS-BE-1	0,103	0,2249	0,4257	-0,3059	0,2786	-0,1815	-0,1191	0,1627
BUS-BE-2	[0,8398]	-0,0312	-0,0133	-0,0604	0,1609	-0,0137	0,0377	0,0625
BUS-BE-3	0,2226	0,2024	[0,64]	0,1222	-0,2098	-0,307	0,0649	-0,2468
BUS-BE-4	0,201	0,6646	-0,0039	0,1164	0,1876	-0,4083	0,081	0,0083
BUS-BE-5	-0,1538	0,2329	0,4571	0,3253	-0,3342	0,2323	-0,2589	0,0009
BUS-RW-1	-0,07	0,1573	0,1184	0,7001	-0,3501	0,4022	0,0487	0,1276
BUS-RW-2	0,0498	-0,1584	0,3551	0,0291	0,4346	-0,3153	0,0221	0,2536
WU-BE-1	0,1734	-0,6002	0,427	-0,1331	0,323	-0,0432	0,3147	0,0967
WU-BE-2	0,0404	-0,2128	0,3177	-0,3065	0,0125	-0,0212	0,3345	-0,3647
WU-RW-1	0,2221	[0,7225]	-0,1416	-0,1122	-0,0571	-0,0642	-0,0252	0,1622
NGO-BE-1	[0,6209]	-0,3722	-0,3134	0,0775	-0,0414	-0,0362	-0,0923	-0,3287
NGO-BE-2	0,0915	0,4313	0,2092	0,0453	0,0881	-0,0141	0,7684	0,0473
NGO-BE-3	0,4581	0,033	-0,2661	0,0461	-0,1729	-0,0142	0,4583	0,1708
NGO-BE-4	0,3538	0,1784	-0,0557	-0,4936	-0,3082	0,2472	-0,3808	0,2858
NGO-RW-1	[0,6325]	-0,0856	0,1434	0,0225	-0,1062	0,2645	0,3098	-0,1051
ENG-BE-1	0,2115	0,0447	-0,5632	0,1071	-0,3129	-0,4575	0,0733	-0,1376
ENG-BE-2	0,4991	-0,3188	0,3469	0,0147	0,4628	0,299	0,185	-0,3183
ENG-BE-3	0,1008	0,5635	0,5848	0,0652	-0,1114	0,1214	-0,2134	0,1642
ENG-BE-4	0,5001	-0,022	-0,0128	0,387	0,0604	-0,1555	0,0268	0,4084
ENG-BE-5	0,6372	-0,0441	0,4097	0,228	0,2811	-0,2409	-0,0305	-0,0396
ENG-BE-6	0,4463	0,3748	-0,2079	-0,5018	-0,0002	0,0161	-0,215	-0,0446
ENG-RW-1	[0,5054]	0,0995	-0,0579	0,1445	0,3003	-0,2822	-0,3138	0,2173
TRA-BE-1	0,4654	-0,0845	-0,1702	0,2987	0,0278	-0,145	0,0637	0,1245
PRI-BE-1	-0,6154	0,0059	0,1354	0,2449	0,339	0,0228	0,2332	-0,0454
PRI-BE-2	0,2109	0,1937	0,0028	-0,0364	[0,5418]	0,0057	-0,1276	0,2947
PRI-RW-1	0,3508	0,0316	0,1881	0,4707	0,1472	-0,0897	-0,43	-0,1218
PRI-RW-2	0,2549	-0,2148	-0,0136	0,0818	0,0462	0,124	-0,16	[0,5863]
CA-BE-1	0,3857	0,4324	-0,1805	-0,1488	-0,4399	-0,1363	0,3217	-0,0164
CA-BE-2	[0,6481]	-0,2626	0,3852	0,0688	-0,3489	0,0701	-0,0597	0,2053
CA-BE-3	0,404	-0,0481	-0,0522	0,5127	-0,2988	-0,2692	-0,1956	-0,3724
CA-BE-4	0,09	[0,7628]	0,0979	-0,0053	0,2546	0,3714	0,1897	-0,0354
CA-BE-5	[0,7954]	-0,1405	-0,1514	0,1755	0,0269	0,0008	0,3762	-0,0218
UNI-RW-1	0,1593	0,342	-0,4675	-0,3216	0,1351	0,0806	0,3577	0,2932
UNI-RW-2	0,313	0,2501	0,0332	-0,3608	[0,6608]	0,1607	0,0948	-0,0733
Eigenvalues	9,2036	5,522	4,49	4,2734	3,893	3,4664	3,1796	2,6474
% explained variance	17	10	8	8	7	6	6	5
Cumulative % explained variance	17	27	35	43	50	56	62	67

Table 23. Matrix of factors obtained with PCA. Significant correlations between the factors and the Q sorts are placed between square brackets.

I selected among those factors the significant ones. According to Cools & *al.* (2012), to be considered as significant, a factor must meet two conditions. First, its eigenvalue must be greater than one. Second, a significant factor must have at least two Q sorts that are correlated with it in a significant way. A Q sort and a factor are correlated in a significant way if the correlation between them is superior to 0,50 and if the correlations between the Q sort in question and the other factors are inferior to 0,40. On the basis of these criteria, I selected three significant factors.

2.4.2. Factor Rotation

After the PCA, the selected factors are rotated to obtain the final set of factors. There are two options to carry out the rotation, namely the objective or the judgmental / theoretical rotation (van Exel & de Graaf, 2005; Schmolck, 2013). With the objective rotation, the software “automatically” rotates the factors with a view to maximizing the contribution of those factors to the explanations of the variance. In the case of a judgmental / theoretical rotation, this is the user who rotates “manually” the factors on the basis of his theoretical concerns, his knowledge of the topic or some ideas that emerge during the survey. When manually rotating the factor, the user searches for confirmation of an idea or a theory (i.e.: judgmental rotation) or for an acceptable vantage point by statistical criteria (i.e.: theoretical rotation) (van Exel & de Graaf, 2005). According to van Exel & de Graaf *“the rotation does not affect the consistency in sentiment throughout individual Q-sorts or the relationships between Q-sorts, it only shifts the perspective from which they are observed”* (van Exel & de Graaf 2005, p. 9).

Inasmuch as I had neither preconception regarding the outcome of the study nor theory to confirm, I chose the objective rotation. The objective rotation tool integrated in the Ken-Q Analysis software is the varimax rotation. The varimax rotation of the three factors previously selected has led to the following matrix [Table 24]. The first factor is the most important because it explains 14% of the variance. The second and third factors account respectively for 13% and 9% of the variance. This implies that the combination of the three factors explains 36% of the variance. According to Q literature, it is a perfectly acceptable percentage (Zabala & *al.*, 2018).

Q SORTS	FG	FACTOR 1	FACTOR 2	FACTOR 3
POL-BE-1	F1-13	0,4647	0,3246	-0,4114
POL-RW-1	F2-3	-0,1218	[0,7014]	-0,0427
POL-RW-2	F2-11	0,1698	[0,3824]	-0,0452
PA-BE-1	F3-2	-0,1706	0,3018	[0,6542]
PA-BE-2	F2-1	0,2188	[0,7556]	-0,0897
PA-BE-3	F1-12	[0,4862]	0,0392	0,1598
PA-BE-4	F1-24	0,1748	-0,1196	-0,078
PA-BE-5	F1-11	[0,497]	0,0432	-0,405
PA-BE-6	F3-5	-0,0106	-0,208	[0,548]
PA-BE-7	F1-23	0,2116	-0,034	-0,0352
PA-RW-1	F3-9	0,2808	0,1334	[-0,4873]
PA-RW-2	F2-15	0,0106	0,3492	0,1135
PA-RW-3	F3-6	0,134	0,2312	[-0,5432]
PA-RW-4	F2-4	0,1938	[0,6613]	-0,0271
ADM-BE-1	F1-8	[0,5868]	0,3407	0,0176
ADM-BE-2	F1-5	[0,6598]	-0,141	-0,1684
ADM-RW-1	F1-2	[0,7313]	0,1336	0,2697
ADM-RW-2	F1-15	[0,39]	0,0681	-0,1288
ADM-RW-3	F1-18	0,3318	-0,0345	0,0116
ADM-RW-4	F3-12	0,1425	0,2349	0,3018
BUS-BE-1	F3-10	0,1874	0,1507	[0,4296]
BUS-BE-2	F1-6	[0,633]	0,4809	-0,2729
BUS-BE-3	F3-4	0,3927	0,1618	[0,5655]
BUS-BE-4	F2-5	-0,1489	[0,6366]	0,2338
BUS-BE-5	F3-7	0,008	-0,003	[0,5355]
BUS-RW-1	F3-13	-0,0637	0,0564	0,1909
BUS-RW-2	F1-20	0,2838	-0,1643	0,2148
WU-BE-1	F1-7	[0,6087]	-0,4476	0,042
WU-BE-2	F1-21	0,2825	-0,2047	0,1616
WU-RW-1	F2-2	-0,2272	[0,7218]	0,137
NGO-BE-1	F3-3	0,4734	0,1455	[-0,614]
NGO-BE-2	F2-16	-0,0207	0,3473	0,3421
NGO-BE-3	F2-14	0,1947	0,353	-0,3453
NGO-BE-4	F2-13	0,1564	0,3612	-0,0719
NGO-RW-1	F1-9	[0,5806]	0,2832	-0,1036
ENG-BE-1	F3-8	-0,1415	0,2741	[-0,5184]
ENG-BE-2	F1-4	[0,6861]	-0,0184	0,0038
ENG-BE-3	F3-1	0,1134	0,3802	[0,7158]
ENG-BE-4	F1-16	0,3761	0,2847	-0,1681
ENG-BE-5	F1-3	[0,6975]	0,2648	0,1386
ENG-BE-6	F2-8	0,0622	[0,5994]	-0,1402
ENG-RW-1	F2-10	0,3034	[0,3912]	-0,1536
TRA-BE-1	F3-11	0,3001	0,247	-0,3188
PRI-BE-1	F1-14	-0,394	-0,3907	0,2986
PRI-BE-2	F2-17	0,0721	0,2759	0,0265
PRI-RW-1	F1-17	0,3405	0,1966	0,0696
PRI-RW-2	F1-22	0,2791	-0,0114	-0,1824
CA-BE-1	F2-7	0,0048	[0,6024]	-0,0735
CA-BE-2	F1-1	[0,7911]	0,1067	0,0172
CA-BE-3	F1-19	0,2966	0,2148	-0,1848
CA-BE-4	F2-6	-0,2249	[0,626]	0,3963
CA-BE-5	F1-10	0,5803	0,3973	-0,4253
UNI-RW-1	F2-9	-0,2657	[0,4544]	-0,2895
UNI-RW-2	F2-12	0,138	0,3747	0,0473
% explained variance		14	13	9
Cumulative % explained variance		14	27	36

Table 24. Matrix of factors obtained after Varimax rotation. Significant correlations are placed between square brackets.

For each factor obtained, the software identified the Q sorts correlated in a significant way. Those are indicated between square brackets in the matrix.

Before beginning the presentation of the results, it seems interesting to specify the correlations between the three factors. The correlations between factors are shown in the following table [Table 25].

FACTORS	1	2	3
1	1	0,1372	-0,0492
2	0,1372	1	0,0718
3	-0,0492	0,0718	1

Table 25. Matrix of the correlations between factors

We observe that Factor 1 is closer to Factor 2 than Factor 3. The latter is more correlated to Factor 2 than Factor 1.

3. Results

3.1. Policy-Relevance of Governance Issues in Comparison with Other Questions

As explained in the section devoted to the data collection process, before starting the Q survey, the participants were invited to assess the policy-relevance of governance issues compared with other questions (see section “2.3.1. Introductory questions” of the same chapter). The following table summarizes the result of this assessment [Table 26].

ISSUES	IRRELEVANT	OF LITTLE RELEVANCE	NO OPINION	RELEVANT	VERY RELEVANT
Behavioural and technical levers	0%	4%	0%	26%	70%
Social innovation	0%	0%	11%	30%	59%
Financing	0%	8%	0%	22%	70%
Governance and public policy	0%	4%	4%	37%	55%
Social acceptability	4%	4%	4%	29%	59%
Employment	7,5%	7,5%	4%	33%	48%

Table 26. Relevance of governance issues in comparison with other questions

In light of the results, it appears that the most policy relevant issues are the financing and the behavioural and technical levers.

Governance and public policy issues are also considered as relevant by many actors. They are indeed perceived as very relevant by 55% of the actors interviewed and relevant 37% of the respondents. This echoes the discussions on the (non)-use of low-carbon scenarios conducted during the first phase of the interview (see section “4.1.1. Similarities between case studies” of Chapter III). When discussing the reason why the low-carbon scenarios were not used by policy-makers in devising mitigation policies, many actors argued that such scenarios didn’t provide knowledge about *how* to make the energy transition. According to those actors, energy foresight studies should inform policy-makers of what they needed to do *concretely* in order to make the low-carbon transition would happen. This involved, among others, the question of *How to steer the low-carbon transition?* i.e.: *What public policies to implement? At what levels of power? With what participation of the stakeholders / citizens? How to ensure coherence with other sectoral policies?*

Now that we have grasped the policy-relevance of governance issues in comparison with other questions and that we have confirmed the hypothesis that those governance issues should be addressed to provide decision support tools that would be perceived as policy-relevant by political actors, let’s try to understand more specifically what knowledge about the governance of the low-carbon transition is needed to devise long-term mitigation policies. In other words, which dimensions of the governance of the low-carbon transition should be analysed?

3.2. Governance Issues Perceived as the Most or Least Policy Relevant

Before presenting the three factors, I propose to identify the governance issues that are globally perceived as the most or least policy-relevant. The following table shows, for each item, all the scores attributed by the participants [Table 27]. The scores are ordered decreasingly. One colour is assigned to each score to ensure better readability of the results. Positive scores are coloured in green, while negative scores are in red. The higher the score, the darker the tint assigned to it.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	
2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	
2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	
2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	0
2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	0
2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	0
2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	2	0
2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	-1	-1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	0	
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	-1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	-1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	-1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	-1	-1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-1	
0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-1		
0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-1		
0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	1	-1		
0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	1	-1		
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	-1	0	0	-1		
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-2	-2	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-1	0	-2		
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-1	0	-2		
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-2		
-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-2		
-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-2		
-1	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2		
-2	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2		
-2	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	-1	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2		
-2	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2		
-2	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2		
-2	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2		
-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2		
-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2		
-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2		
-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2		
-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2		
15	28	46	25	27	22	17	8	15	-24	-2	-48	-40	-29	-16	1	2	-21	-12	-17	-2	-3	7	-5	10	32	-36	

Table 27. Scores obtained by each item ordered decreasingly. The last row corresponds to the sum of the scores obtained by each item. The three higher global scores are highlighted in light grey and the three lower global scores are highlighted in dark grey

3.2.1. Governance Issues Perceived as the Most Policy-Relevant

The governance issues that are perceived as the most policy-relevant are 3, 26 and 2. The issue that obtains the higher score is the one related to the policy mix.

(3) Policy mix - What mix of policy instruments should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? (i.e.: standards, taxes, awareness campaigns)

With a global score corresponding to 46, this item stands out clearly from the others. It is interesting to note that besides its very high global score, it has never been classified as irrelevant.

The issue that gets the second highest global score is about how to integrate the long-term into the policy process.

(26) Long-term integration in the policy process - How to integrate the long-term in the policy process with a view to building a low-carbon society? (ex.: Long-term Chamber (Jacques Attali))

For many actors, the lack of acknowledgement of long-term stakes by political authorities is a significant barrier to the development of an effective climate mitigation policy.

«Ca c'est une excellente question! Comment voulez qu'un politicien décideur dans le parlement voie autre chose que sa réélection ou les idées de son parti? C'était la belle idée du Sénat il y a 100 ans - le comité des sages. Ca a été galvaudé. C'est un gros problème ça, surtout pour un système dont le cycle de vie, c'est 10-20 ans. Les élections, c'est tous les 4 ans. On n'a plus de personnes qui sont redevables de la politique à long terme.» (ENG-BE-5)

In view of the matrix of the scores obtained by each item, we note that this is the question that has been ranked the most as very relevant. However, unlike the question of the policy mix, the policy-relevance of this problem is not unanimous. A number of actors have indeed considered it irrelevant. They recognize the problems related to the lack of acknowledgement of long-term stake by political authorities, but they state that integrating the long-term in the policy process requires too important changes or is incompatible with a democratic regime. Those actors believe that a study could not help in that regard.

The third question that is perceived as the most policy-relevant is the one concerning the policy objectives.

(2) Policy goals - What policy objectives should be set for the different sectors / level of power with a view to building a low-carbon society?

Just as the issue of the long-term integration into the policy process, some actors have however considered this issue irrelevant.

3.2.2. Governance Issues Perceived as the Least Policy Relevant

The governance issues that are perceived as the least policy-relevant are 11, 13 and 27. It should be noted that although they obtain an overall score that is well below zero, these three issues are not unanimously recognized as policy-irrelevant. All three are perceived as relevant, if not very relevant, by some actors.

It is interesting to observe that two of the three least policy-relevant relate to incumbents. They concern the role of incumbents as well as the question of the policy to implement to ensure the low-carbon transition while taking into account the needs of the incumbents.

(12) Role of the incumbents - What role should incumbents (i.e.: oil companies, large retailers) play with a view to building a low-carbon society?

(13) Consideration of the incumbents' needs - What policy to implement to ensure the low-carbon transition while taking into account the needs of the incumbents?

A number of respondents explain that we should not focus specifically on the dominant actors of the "high-carbon" regime when developing long-term climate mitigation policies. They consider that leaving too much room to those actors could hinder the low-carbon transition. Many actors think that, whatever the decisions taken by public authorities, the incumbents will adapt to future policies.

«Je mets ça en non pertinent. C'est un peu choquant, je sais. (...) Les acteurs dominants, avec tout le respect, si tu les fais trop intervenir, la transition va pas se passer. C'est ça mon raisonnement. Je pense que, autant sans me nier, c'est très important de consulter les parties prenantes, en ce compris les acteurs dominants du système énergétique actuel – donc il faut consulter les raffineries, les électriciens – autant c'est important de prendre de la distance en disant "on a bien compris que vous allez avoir des soucis avec vos raffineries, mais désolé, on arrête les combustibles fossiles"» (CA-BE-3)

«Les acteurs dominants, ils s'adapteront à la législation. C'est pas à eux à définir (...) Ils ne sont pas là pour imposer leur vision.» (ENG-BE-5)

The item that gets the third lowest global score concern the representation of non-human beings in the policy process.

(27) Representation of non-human beings in the policy process - How to represent the non-human beings (i.e.: animals, plants) and the future generations in the policy process?

Many actors consider that this question is interesting from a philosophical or theoretical point of view, but very far from their current concerns.

3.3. Similarities and Differences between the Factors

As mentioned in previously, the statistical analysis led to the identification of three factors (see section “2.4.2. Factor rotation” of the same chapter). The purpose of the following section is to present those factors. The presentation includes a discussion of the similarities and differences between the factors. The similarities between the factors corresponds to the areas of consensus. The area of consensus includes the items that have a similar score for all three factors. Conversely, differences between the factors corresponds to the terms of the debate. The debate lies around the items that obtain different scores from one factor to another. The following table summarizes the factor Q sort values for each item sorted on a “consensus versus disagreement” scale [Table 28]. The most consensual items are at the top of the table, while the least consensual items are at the bottom of the table.

ITEMS		FACTORS			Z-SCORE VARIANCE	
		1	2	3		
5	Eco-fiscality	1	1	1	0,024	↑
7	Land use planning	1	1	1	0,033	
9	Education and vocational training	0	1	0	0,035	
8	Information and awareness	1	0	2	0,075	
10	Role of the political-administrative authorities	0	-1	-1	0,113	
3	Policy mix	2	1	1	0,137	
4	Regulatory framework	1	0	0	0,145	
6	Services and infrastructures	1	2	0	0,204	
25	Degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders	1	-1	-1	0,316	
19	Vertical integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue	-2	0	0	0,32	
11	Role of the different stakeholders	0	-1	-1	0,33	
22	Horizontal integration of the policy goals	0	0	1	0,334	
27	Representation of non-human beings in the policy process	-1	-1	-2	0,391	
18	Foresight’s institutionalization	0	-1	-2	0,408	
23	Vertical integration of the policy instruments	-1	2	1	0,455	
21	Vertical integration of the policy goals	-1	1	2	0,532	
16	Level of action and division of competences	-1	1	-1	0,666	
2	Policy goals	2	0	-1	0,685	
20	Horizontal integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue	-2	0	0	0,719	
17	Steering mode	-1	2	-1	0,75	
24	Horizontal integration of the policy instruments	-2	2	0	0,868	
12	Role of the incumbents	-1	-2	1	1,03	
14	Resistances of the incumbents	0	-2	0	1,117	
15	Mobilization of the incumbents	0	-1	2	1,281	
26	Long-term integration in the policy process	2	0	-2	1,612	↓
1	Vision for 2050	2	-2	-2	1,708	
13	Consideration of the incumbents’ needs	-2	-2	2	2,121	

Table 28. factor Q sort values for each item sorted on a consensus versus disagreement scale

3.3.1. Similarities between the Factors: Area of Consensus

Regarding the similarities that link the factors, they are three items that have a similar score for all three factors. The following table sets out these items and the corresponding score for each factor [Table 29].

ITEMS	FACTORS		
	1	2	3
(5) Eco-fiscality - What economic instruments (i.e.: taxes, subsidies, carbon market) should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? In what ways?	1	1	1
(7) Land use planning - What spatial planning policy should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society?	1	1	1
(9) Education and vocational training - How to rethink the education and training system to meet the new knowledge and skills needs engendered by the low-carbon transition? (i.e.: new building insulation techniques)	0	1	0

Table 29. Consensual items and factor Q sort values for each of them

It is interesting to note that all these issues concern policy instruments: Eco-fiscality, land use planning, and education and vocational training. The first two are perceived as policy-relevant. The question of how to rethink the education and training system to meet the new knowledge and skills needs engendered by the low-carbon transition obtains a score of +1 (i.e.: relevant) for Factor 2 and a score of 0 (i.e.: neutral) for Factors 1 and 3.

3.3.2. Specificities of Each Factor: Terms of the Debate

In order to highlight the specificities of each factors, their typical Q sorts are represented as ranking grids [Figures 87, 88 and 89]. In those grids, the distinguishing items of each factor are highlighted with a dot. Contrary to the consensus items that were presented in the previous section, these items enable to distinguish one factor from all the others by the score it attributes to them. A list of the distinguishing items of the three factors is set out in appendix [Appendices 4, 5 and 6].

For easily identifying the main features of each factor in the representations of their typical Q-sort, I have also assigned colours and symbols to the items that cover connected or similar issues. I have defined eleven clusters of questions: “Role of the public and private actors”, “Policy instruments”, “Policy goals”, “Vision for 2050”, “Level of action, division of competences and steering mode”, “Incumbent sensitive policy”, “Horizontal and vertical integrations”, “Participation of the stakeholders in the policy process”, “Long-term oriented issues”, “Foresight’s institutionalization”, and “Representation of non-human beings in the policy process”. The following table draws up a list of the colours and symbols used in the typical Q sorts’ representations as well as the cluster of issues to which they relate [Table 30]. As we will see in the presentation of the specificities of each factor, the items that compose a cluster often obtain similar scores for the same factor.

CLUSTERS OF ISSUES	DIMENSIONS OF GOVERNANCE	ITEMS	SYMBOLS
Role of the public and private actors	Politics	10 and 11	
Policy instruments	Policy	3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9	
Policy goals	Policy	2	
Vision for 2050	Policy	1	
Level of action, division of competences and steering mode	Polity	16 and 17	
Incumbent sensitive policy	Politics X Policy	12, 13, 14 and 15	
Horizontal and vertical integrations	Policy X Polity	19, 20, 21, 22, 23 and 24	
Participation of the stakeholders in the policy process	Polity X Politics	25	
Long-term oriented issues		1, 2, 18 and 26	
Foresight's institutionalization		18	
Representation of non-human beings in the policy process		27	

Table 30. Colours and symbols used in the typical Q sorts' representations and the cluster of issues to which they relate

The presentation of the main features of each factor focuses more specifically on the distinguishing items and on the items that were assigned an extreme score (i.e.: -2 or +2).

After identifying the main features of each factor, I have assigned them a name. This process, which is extremely simplifying, aims to highlight the emblematic characteristic of each factor. The names attributed are the following: the *reformists* for Factor 1, the *revolutionists* for Factor 2 and the *incumbents* for Factor 3.

Factor 1: The Reformists

Twelve Q sorts are significantly correlated with Factor 1. The table below lists those Q sorts [Table 31].

Q SORT	TYPE OF ACTOR	WEIGHT
CA-BE-2	Consultancy agency	2,11387
ADM-RW-1	Administrative authority	1,57187
ENG-BE-5	Energy market operator	1,35851
ENG-BE-2	Energy market operator	1,29637
ADM-BE-2	Administrative authority	1,1683
BUS-BE-2	Employers' federation	1,05617
WU-BE-1	Workers' union	0,96712
ADM-BE-1	Administrative authority	0,89512
NGO-RW-1	Environmental and development NGO	0,87572
PA-BE-5	Political advisor	0,66008
PA-BE-3	Political advisor	0,63661
ADM-RW-2	Administrative authority	0,45999

Table 31. Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 1

Among the actors whose discourse is associated with this factor, one observes a predominance of administrative authorities. Four of the six members of administration who participated in the Q survey are actually associated to this factor. The other two members of the administration are not significantly associated with any of the three selected factors. That said, one of them (i.e.: ADM-RW-3) is close to Factor 1, but its correlation with this factor – which equal to 0,3318 – is not considered as significant (see table 24: Matrix of factors obtained after Varimax rotation). The administrative authorities are highlighted in grey in the table listing the Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 1.

The other eight Q-sorts significantly correlated with Factor 1 are those from different types of actors, namely one consultancy agency, two energy market operators, one employers' federation, one workers' union, one environmental and development NGO and two political advisors.

Figure 87. Representation of the typical Q sort for factor 1. The distinguishing items of each factor are marked with a dot

When looking at the idealized Q sort for Factor 1, we can observe that the most policy-relevant issues for this factor related to the *policy* dimension of governance. Those are **coloured in blue** in the ranking grid [Figure 87]. The issues of the low-carbon vision for 2050 (1; +2)⁴⁷, the policy goals to realize this vision (2; +2) and the policy mix to be implemented with a view to reach those objectives (3; +2) are distinguishing items for Factor 1. These three issues are perceived as very relevant. The question “*What standards should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? (i.e.: norms, branch agreements) In what ways?*” (4; +1) which is seen as relevant is also a distinguishing item. The item concerning the five other types of instruments that are the services and infrastructures (6; +1), information and awareness (8; +1), land use planning (7; +1), eco-fiscality (5; +1) and educational and vocational training (9; 0) are globally considered policy-relevant too.

The questions of the visions, of the policy goals and of the policy instruments follow a logical progression: define a desirable vision for 2050, set the political objectives for the different sectors / levels of power, and finally define the policy instruments to be implemented to reach the objectives. They are very operational questions and it is not surprising that actors from public administrations in quest of solutions in their daily work – for the elaboration of climate-energy plans for instance – consider them as very relevant.

«*[Ce qui est important], c’est de rentrer dans l’opérationnalisation*» (ADM-RW-2)

«*Dans les trucs très pertinents, c’est surtout des problématiques qu’on retrouve actuellement. Fiscalité verte et information/sensibilisation, c’est des choses qui sont importantes et qui pour l’instant n’ont pas vraiment de solution qui satisfont, par exemple.*» (ADM-RW-1)

The fourth proposal, which has been given an extremely positive score, is the question of the long-term integration in the political process (26; +2). With three long-term oriented questions among the four issues considered to be the most relevant, Factor 1 seems to be pretty concerned with the future.

Another distinguishing item for Factor 1 is the question “*To what extend and in what way the different stakeholders should participate in the policy process with a view to building a low-carbon society?*” (25; +1). This issue of participation is perceived as being policy-relevant. Compared to the other two factors, the score attributed is higher.

As we can see in the typical Q sort representation, Factor 1 can be distinguished from the other factors by the negative scores attributed to the items that concern the vertical and horizontal integration that are **coloured in cyan** in the ranking grid. Those are indeed distinguished items for Factor 1. An extreme negative note is attributed to the issues related to the horizontal and vertical integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue (19 and 20; -2) and to the horizontal integration of the policy instruments (24; -2). The other questions related to the integration are perceived as of little relevance (21 and 23; 0) or neutral (22; 0). Some actors justify their choice by explaining that the coordination of the actions undertaken by different entities comes up naturally within institutional structures like the National Climate Commission (see section “3.2.1. Vertical integration” of Chapter III) or simply through discussions between different administrations or political cabinets. For those actors, the political integration cannot be seen as a problem.

«*Pour la Commission nationale climat, vous avez plein de monde qui vont se cacher derrière "ça ne fonctionne pas, ça ne va pas" alors qu’il suffit de faire fonctionner la structure*» (ADM-RW-2)

«*Il faut qu’on parle, et c’est pas une étude qui va aider. (...) On le fait naturellement et comme il n’y a pas de problème grave, on n’a pas besoin de se faire aider par quelqu’un de l’extérieur*» (ADM-RW-1)

⁴⁷ The first digit corresponds to the reference number of the item and the second one is the score associated with it for the Factor took into consideration.

Still regarding the left side of the ranking grid, we note that Factor 1 doesn't consider the questions related to the *polity* dimension of governance as policy-relevant. Those are coloured in green in the representation of the idealized Q sort for factor 1. The questions "At what level(s) should the low-carbon policies be devised? How to organize the division of competences?" (16; -1) and "What steering mode would facilitate the low-carbon transition?" (17; -1) are sorted in the -1 column. The question of the level of action and division of competences is connected to the issues concerning the vertical integration mentioned previously and that were also assigned a negative score. Similar argument is advanced to justify the perceived irrelevance of this issues:

«Chaque entité a son mot à dire, parce que chacune a des compétence différentes. Elles sont réparties de façon plus ou moins claire. Parfois il faut les éclaircir un petit peu et ça, on le fait entre nous: il y a des accords de coopération que nous établissons entre les régions et le fédéral pour que chacun ait ses tâches à faire. C'est quelque chose que nous faisons. Donc pour moi, dans l'état actuel des choses, ce n'est pas pertinent de faire une étude là-dessus, parce que c'est quelque chose qu'on fait au quotidien.» (ADM-RW-1)

This view is not shared by all the actors associated to Factor 1. Indeed, some of them acknowledge that the current institutional framework characterized by divided competences between the federated entities can be a source of blockage to develop efficient climate mitigation policy. However, they think that we will not rethink the institutional framework "just" to allow the low-carbon transition and that a study centered around climate mitigation issues could not bring about such institutional reform. They thus consider this issue definitively relevant, but too conceptual and not concrete enough.

«C'est une question qui est vraiment très pertinente, mais si on veut faire bouger les choses à un horizon de quelques années, on va pas rechanger les institutions pour ça. Donc, moi, je trouve que c'est une question complètement pertinente et on voit que c'est source de blocage, maintenant... Est-ce qu'on va faire bouger les choses avec une étude autour des questions de transition? Je ne crois pas.» (ADM-BE-1)

Inasmuch as the actors associated to Factor 1 consider developing low-carbon policies (i.e.: issues related to the *policy* dimensions perceived as policy-relevant), while remaining within the existing institutional framework (i.e.: issues related to the *polity* dimensions perceived as of little policy-relevance), I have decided to call them the **reformists**.

Finally, factor 1 shows little interest for incumbent-related questions. Those are coloured in pink in the ranking grid. While the question "What incumbent-sensitive policy should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society?" (13; -2) is seen as irrelevant, the issue of the role of incumbents in building a low-carbon society is considered of little relevance (12; -1). The other two items that concern the mobilization of the incumbents (15; 0) and the way to address their resistances (14; 0) were assigned a neutral score.

Factor 2: The revolutionists

Eleven Q sorts are significantly correlated to Factor 2. As shown in the table below, those Q sorts are from many different types of actors, namely two political advisors, one workers' union, two political authorities, one employers' federation, two consultancy agency, two energy market operators and one university [Table 32].

Q SORT	TYPE OF ACTOR	WEIGHT
PA-BE-2	Political advisor	1,76085
WU-RW-1	Workers' union	1,50654
POL-RW-1	Political authority	1,38078
PA-RW-4	Political advisor	1,17508
BUS-BE-4	Employers' federation	1,07054
CA-BE-4	Consultancy agency	1,02955
CA-BE-1	Consultancy agency	0,94558
ENG-BE-6	Energy market operator	0,93568
UNI-RW-1	University	0,5726
ENG-RW-1	Energy market operator	0,46182
POL-RW-2	Political authority	0,44785

Table 32. Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 2

Figure 88. Representation of the typical Q sort for Factor 2

When analysing the idealized Q sort for Factor 2, we observe that this factor attaches importance to the issues related to the *polity* dimension of governance (in green). The proposals concerning the steering mode (17; +2) and the level of action / division of competences (16; +1) are indeed distinguishing items for this factor. The first one is considered very relevant and the second one relevant. The actors stating that such issues should be studied often explain their choice by emphasizing the great potential of local and community-based actions to contribute to the low-carbon transition. They explain that reflections on how to transfer competences at the local level and how to develop such a community-based governance of energy are needed.

«C'est pertinent, car on a un marché européen de l'électricité et il y aurait une possibilité de le réorganiser beaucoup plus localement. Et ça, je pense que ce serait super profitable pour faciliter l'intégration du photovoltaïque, des véhicules électriques, parce que quand tu l'organises localement tu sais gérer aussi localement l'équilibre entre production et consommation... l'aspect local, oui. Et ça c'est cet aspect où il y a de vrais blocages faits par les GRD qui ne veulent pas cet aspect local, car ils ont peur de perdre leur monopole sur la distribution. Ça va avec le mode de coordination aussi. C'est assez lié.» (UNI-RW-1)

«Je dirais très pertinent. Je pense à un élément très particulier pour ce qui concerne le développement de l'énergie renouvelable. Il est apparu qu'il y avait des oppositions locales très fortes et en même temps, il y a une demande citoyenne d'implication et de réappropriation de l'énergie. Et donc, je pense qu'on doit réfléchir à des formules plus locales de type régions autonomes, coopératives etc. Et aujourd'hui c'est un peu en friches ce sujet-là, donc, ça, ça me paraît pertinent.» (POL-RW-2)

Another argument to promote studies addressing the question of the level of action / division of competences is based on the limitations of current institutional architecture.

«Le problème, c'est que les compétences sont partagées et chacun veut exercer ses compétence. Donc à un moment donnée, la région flamande ne va pas demander à la région wallonne si elle peut mener telle ou telle politique. Voilà, il ne fallait pas régionaliser. il y a une limite à ce raisonnement-là.» (POL-RW-2)

All in all, Factor 2 highlights the limitations of current institutional structures as well as the need to develop local and community-based governance to foster the low-carbon transition. Conversely to the *reformists*, they consider as relevant a study aiming at rethinking the institutional framework. This is why I decided to name the actors correlated to this factor the **revolutionists**.

Again in contrast with the *reformists*, the *revolutionists* globally attribute positive scores to the items that concern the vertical and horizontal integration (in cyan). The ones that concern vertical and horizontal integrations of policy instruments (23 and 24; +2) obtain a positive extreme score. The four other potential research questions about the integrations are ranked as relevant (21; +1) or neutral (19, 20 and 22; 0). In addition to the problems related to the divisions of competences between the federal level and the regions, they highlight the lack of coherence between the different policy domains at the same level of power.

«Prenons l'exemple de la mobilité électrique. Pour moi, c'est quelque chose qui est extrêmement lié à la compétence énergie. Les dossiers sont liés. (...) C'est une compétence transversale, mais le cabinet de l'énergie n'a pas la mobilité. Ça n'a plus de sens. Il devrait avoir énergie, mobilité et aménagement du territoire. (...) Il faut de la cohérence» (UNI-RW-1)

The fourth and last extreme positive score is assigned to the question “*What services (i.e.: TEC, SNCB) and infrastructures (i.e.: energy network) development policy should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? In what ways?*” (6; +2). The other issues covering the *policy* dimension of governance are considered as relevant (9, 3, 5 and 7; +1) or neutral (8, 2 and 4; 0) (in blue). The only exception is the question of the vision for 2050 (1; -2) which is seen as an irrelevant issue. Several actors explain that we already have a 2050 low-carbon vision, or at least studies that propose such a vision – e.g.: Sustainable development vision elaborated by the Federal Planning Bureau previously mentioned (see Task force développement durable, 2007).

«On a déjà beaucoup travaillé sur la vision. C'est vrai qu'il faut avoir une vision, mais c'est pas ça qui pose le plus de problèmes à mon avis. Tout le monde est plus ou moins d'accord sur la vision. Il n'y a pas de gros clivages.» (WU-RW-1)

Other don't perceive the usefulness of developing a low-carbon vision for 2050.

«Pour moi, c'est rêver sans agir» (UNI-RW-1)

Another specific feature of Factor 2 lies in the extremely negative scores attributed to the items linked to the incumbents (in pink). Those four items are distinguishing. The question of what role the incumbents should play in the low-carbon transition (12; -2), how to address their resistances (14; -2), and what policy to implement to ensure the low-carbon transition while taking into account the needs of these actors (13; -2) are perceived as irrelevant. The last incumbents-related questions, "How to ensure that they take part in the low-carbon transition and mobilize their resources?" (15; -1), is seen as of very little relevance. Beside the arguments that dominant actors of the "high-carbon" regime will adapt to mitigation policies, some respondents believe that we will not be able to involve them in the low-carbon transition. Another argument is that such actors are beyond the direct control of domestic government inasmuch as they operate at European or global level.

«Je ne crois pas à la mobilisation des acteurs dominants. Je ne crois pas qu'on pourra y arriver... Sauf à leur donner le pouvoir. Mais les associer... D'ailleurs au niveau wallon, les acteurs dominants travaillent à une échelle tellement plus vaste que la Wallonie, les multinationales etc..» (CA-BE-4)

The role that the different private (11; -1) and public (10; -1) actors should play with a view to building a low-carbon society are also considered not really relevant research questions (in red). For many respondents, the role of the different actors is already defined and should not be studied.

The same applies to the question of the degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders (25; -1) that is ranked in the "of little relevance" column (in yellow).

Factor 3: The Incumbents

The last factor has ten significantly correlated Q-sorts. However, of the ten Q sorts, four are correlated negatively. In other words, these four Q-sorts significantly oppose the typical Q sort of factor 3 in the discourses they contain. These negatively correlated Q-sorts are indicated in red in the table below [Table 33].

Q SORT	TYPE OF ACTOR	WEIGHT
ENG-BE-3	Energy market operator	1,4676
PA-BE-1	Political advisor	1,14353
NGO-BE-1	Environmental and development NGO	-0,98551
BUS-BE-3	Employers' federation	0,83125
PA-BE-6	Political advisor	0,78314
PA-RW-3	Political advisor	-0,77065
BUS-BE-5	Employers' federation	0,75075
ENG-BE-1	Energy market operator	-0,70884
PA-RW-1	Political advisor	-0,63911
BUS-BE-1	Employers' federation	0,52685

Table 33. Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 3. The negatively correlated Q sorts are indicated in red.

Interestingly, among the six positively correlated Q sorts, there are four people who defend the interests either of large energy-intensive industries that emit a lot of GHG, or of companies that produce energy from fossil sources. These actors are highlighted in light grey in the table listing the Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 3. The two remaining Q sorts are those of members of a traditional conservative political party. These actors are highlighted in dark grey in the table listing the Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 3. All in all, they all represent dominant actors of the current regime. This is why I have decided to call them the *incumbents*.

On the other hand, by focusing on the four negatively correlated Q sorts, we note that one of them belongs to a person working for an environmental or development NGO and two others belong to political advisers who, if not ecologist, have at least a clear environmental awareness. The fourth negatively correlated Q sort is that of an energy market operator.

Figure 89. Representation of the typical Q sort for Factor 3

Factor 3 differs from other factors in its particular interest in incumbent issues (in pink). The four issues related to the incumbents are distinguishing statements for factor 3. The questions “What policy to implement to ensure the low-carbon transition while taking into account the needs of the incumbents?” (13, +2) and “how to mobilize the incumbents to accelerate such a transition?” (15, +2) are perceived as very relevant. The role of the incumbents in building a low-carbon society (12, +1) is also seen as a relevant issue. The item related to the resistances of the incumbents (14; 0) is ranked in the “neutral” column. Inasmuch as all the participants associated to Factor 3 represent dominant actors of the current regime, this is not surprising that they are interested in questions that directly affect them, and more specifically on the questions that aim to define “how to go to win-win between low-carbon and economic objectives” (BUS-BE-1).

«Je pense que c'est important de tenir compte des besoins réels des industriels ou des acteurs quand on élabore une législation, un règlement, qu'on fixe des objectifs. C'est assez primordial. On nous fixe des objectifs au niveau européen et mondial, mais il faut aussi pouvoir tenir compte de ce qui est concrètement faisable sur le terrain.» (BUS-BE-5)

«C'est un peu compliqué quand on ne joue pas avec les grands groupes, ceux qui ont les capitaux.» (PA-BE-1)

The question of the vertical integration of the policy goals (21; +2) also gets an extreme positive score and is a distinguishing item for Factor 3. The other items related to the vertical and horizontal integrations are considered either relevant (22 and 23; +1) or neutral (19, 20 and 24; 0) (in cyan). In that context, the *incumbents* raise similar arguments as the *revolutionists* (Factor 2) – i.e.: the problems of coordination between the many entities competent in climate-energy issues.

«Pour moi, le plus grand enjeu en Belgique, c'est l'absence de politique cohérente, et donc des investissements publics qui sont non rentables, parce que non coordonnés. Et donc, on perd tout ce qui est effet de levier des investissements publics, économies d'échelles, et donc la rentabilité n'est pas du tout garantie.» (PA-BE-1)

«Aujourd'hui, les gens sont confrontés à des actions communales, régionales, fédérales, européennes, mondiales qui ne vont pas toujours dans le même sens et qui n'incitent pas toujours au même type d'action. Pour moi, cette cohérence des différentes politiques, c'est très important» (BUS-BE-3)

«La cohérence de l'intégration est importante, parce que c'est quelque chose qui manque actuellement. Chacun fait un peu des trucs de son côté, même s'il y a des grosses tendances. Il y a des grosses lignes qui sont tracées, mais on constate souvent qu'il y a peu ou pas de dialogue entre les acteurs à différents niveaux de pouvoir et c'est vrai que c'est un problème. (...) Entre un responsable de climat et un responsable énergie, ils ne vont pas spécialement parler entre eux, alors qu'il y a des ponts évidents entre les deux matières. C'est sans doute ça qu'il faut améliorer.» (BUS-BE-5)

The last item that was assigned an extreme positive score is the question “How to inform and raise awareness among citizens with a view to inspire the behavioural changes required for building a low-carbon society?” (8; +2). It appears that the aspect of the question interesting the *incumbents* is the target of such instrument, namely, the citizen. Some *incumbents* explained that most of the climate mitigation policies that had been implemented so far have mainly targeted the industries and not the citizens. They estimate that those economic actors have already made great efforts to reduce their GHG and that we should think on how to encourage the citizen to contribute in the effort to reduce GHG.

«On a besoin de tout le monde. C'est souvent un peu le reproche qu'on fait dans les débats sur les politiques climatiques. C'est qu'on a l'industrie sur laquelle on a pas mal tapé. Il y a encore beaucoup de choses à faire, mais l'industrie est quelque part l'acteur le plus évident à qui on pouvait demander des réductions. Ensuite, il y a le tertiaire ou le transport (...) on nous dit à chaque fois que le transport est en train d'exploser, mais on n'a pas l'impression qu'il y a beaucoup de choses qui sont mises en œuvre pour réduire l'impact croissant du transport sur les émissions. Au niveau du citoyen, le politique est toujours partagé dans ses approches sur je vais mettre un objectif sur les entreprises. Par contre, sur les citoyens, c'est toujours très difficile, parce que le citoyen, c'est son vivier politique, c'est son vivier électoral. Il y a toujours un peu cette dualité dans les efforts et les engagements qu'on demande aux différents acteurs de la société. Maintenant qu'on demande plus à une entreprise qui émet plus de CO₂, c'est logique. Quand on parle d'un ménage ou d'un citoyen, les quantités restent marginales. Ce qu'il y a, c'est la multiplication qui fait la quantité importante. C'est vrai qu'à un moment donné il faudra

voir si le politique ne doit pas trouver des politiques qui puissent concrètement concerner le citoyen pour qu'il puisse contribuer aux efforts de réduction du CO₂». (BUS-BE-3)

Regarding the other types of policy instruments (in blue), we observe that the policy mix (3; +1), the eco-fiscality (5; +1) and the land use planning (7; +1) are sorted in the “relevant” columns, while the regulatory framework (4; 0), the services and infrastructures (6; 0) and the educational and vocational training (9; 0) are in the “neutral” one.

Conversely, Factor 3 consider long-term oriented issues as of little relevance or irrelevant. It distinguishes from other factors by assigning an extreme negative score to the issues of the long-term integration in the policy process (26, -2) and also to the institutionalization of foresight (18, -2). An argument that was mentioned several times regarding the later issue is that we already have enough institutions on Belgium. Whith regard to the question of the long-term integration in the policy process, some incumbents recognize the lack of consideration of future stakes by policy-maker, but they believe that it is not possible to change the system.

The questions “*What kind of low-carbon society do we want in 2050?*” (1, -2) and “*which objectives should be set to build such a low-carbon society?*” (2, -1) are respectively seen as irrelevant and of little relevance. Concerning the vision, the incumbents say that we already have a vision, namely the one developed by the Federal Planning Bureau (see Task force développement durable, 2007). When it comes to the objective, some actors explain that the definition of the objectives for the different regions and sectors is too political to be the object of a study.

Another distinguishing item for Factor 3 is the one related to the representation of non-human beings in the policy process (27, -2) which was given an extreme negative score. This question is often considered as too philosophic.

«Intellectuellement, c'est intéressant. Mais d'un point de vue politique, c'est peu pertinent (...) ça ne tient pas compte de la réalité actuelle.» (PA-BE-1)

The question “*To what extent and in what way the different stakeholders should participate in the policy process with a view to building a low-carbon society?*” is also a distinguishing item for factor 3 (in yellow). This potential research question is seen as of little relevance.

This is also holding true for the items related to the role of the political authorities (10; -1) and of the different stakeholders (11; -1) in the policy process (in red). Those are ranked in the “of little relevance” column. Just like the *revolutionists*, they explain that the role of the different actors is already defined and should not be studied.

4. Key Lessons Arising from the Q Survey

While the introductory questions have clearly highlighted the policy-relevance of governance issues in comparison with other questions such as the behavioural and technical levers, the social innovation, the financing, the social acceptability and the employment (see section “3.1. Policy-relevance of governance issues in comparison with other questions” of the same chapter), the Q survey has provided a massive amount of information, which can be somewhat overwhelming for the reader. The information contained in the typical Q sorts of the three factors is indeed dense and multidimensional. In the following discussion, I suggest focussing on the main lessons arising from the Q survey regarding the research question – i.e.: *What knowledge about the governance of the low-carbon transition do political actors need to devise long-term mitigation policies?*

With this in mind, I summarized the results of the data analysis in a radar chart [Figure 90]. This chart made with Excel contains eleven axes. Each axis corresponds to a previously defined cluster of questions: “Role of the public and private actors”, “Policy instruments”, “Policy goals”, “Vision for 2050”, “Level of action”, “Division of competences and steering mode”, “Incumbent sensitive policy”, “Horizontal and vertical integrations”, “Participation of the stakeholders in the policy process”, “Long-term oriented issues”, “Foresight’s institutionalization”, and “Representation of non-human beings in the policy process”. The points on the axes correspond to the average scores attributed by the three factors for each category of questions. One colour is assigned to each factor. The colour of the factor is the same as the one assigned to the cluster of questions that the factor in question perceives as the most policy-relevant: Factor 1 is in blue just like the cluster of issues “Vision for 2050, policy goals and policy instruments” (i.e.: *policy*), Factor 2 is in green just like the cluster of issues “Level of action, division of competences and steering mode” (i.e.: *polity*), and Factor 3 is in pink just like the cluster “Incumbent sensitive-policy”.

Figure 90. Position of the three factors in relation to the different categories of issues

A first lesson to be learnt from the analysis is that the different actors have globally similar perceptions regarding the policy-relevance of certain cluster of issues. Indeed, with a few exceptions, most of the actors consider that the questions of the **policy instruments** should be the subject of a study. They indeed state that knowledge regarding the policy instruments to implement with a view to building a low-carbon society are needed. A policy-relevant study could either analyse the entire policy mix or focus on a specific type of instruments – i.e.: Regulatory framework, eco-fiscality, services and infrastructures, land use planning, information and awareness, or educational and vocational training.

That said, it seems that the actors would prefer a study that analyses the policy mix as a whole. As mentioned earlier, the item related to the mix of policy instruments is the proposal that got the higher score and the only one that has never been classified as irrelevant (see section “3.2.1. Governance issues perceived as the most policy-relevant” of the same chapter). A study addressing the mix of policy instruments to be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society should therefore be perceived as policy-relevant by most of the actors. As explained in the introductory section, I haven’t been able to identify the approach that the respondents would encourage to study the governance issues that are considered the most policy-relevant (see section “Introduction” of the same chapter). That said, a scenario analysis approach could contribute to identify the mix of instruments to be implemented to foster the transition towards a low-carbon society in 2050. As previously explained, *policy* is the dimension of governance that is the most often analysed in the low-carbon scenario addressing governance (see “Section 5.3.2. On the need for further investigation on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios” of Chapter I). I showed that a variety of qualitative, but also quantitative approaches are available to make knowledge about policy instruments in low-carbon scenarios. The articulation between qualitative and quantitative approaches to explore the policy in low-carbon scenarios will be further discussed in the next chapter (see Chapter V).

On the contrary, some issues are globally perceived as of little relevance. This is the case for the question of the **representation of the non-human beings in the policy process**. This question, which was one of the three governance issues perceived as the least policy-relevant (see “section 3.2.2. Governance issues perceived as the least policy relevant” of the same chapter), gets with each factor a negative score. Note that the fact that this question is sorted as of little relevance or irrelevant in the typical Q sorts of the three factors doesn’t mean that nobody considers it policy-relevant. A factor has indeed a tendency to hide the variations between the individual perspectives that compose it. When looking at the table containing the scores assigned to each item by all the participants (see table 27), we observe that ten of the 53 respondents perceive the question of the representation of the non-human beings either as very relevant or relevant (see section “3.2. Governance issues perceived as the most or least policy-relevant” of the same chapter). Moreover, the fact that this question is globally perceived as not policy-relevant doesn’t mean that it should not be studied, rather the opposite. Such a study would probably not be used in an instrumental way by the policy-makers to devise low-carbon transition policies, but it could have a conceptual role in policy-making. By providing innovative ideas that challenge current mindset, a study addressing the representation of the animals, the plants and the future generations in the policy process could contribute to prepare mentalities regarding those new modes of governance. As explained in the previous chapter, thinking out of the box is one of the characteristics for foresight studies that can contribute to their conceptual role since the disruptive elements in scenarios can make an impression, inspire, but also foster the reflection and the debate among stakeholders (See section “4.1. Role of the studies in policy-making” of Chapter III).

It is also observed that the issues related to the **role of the public and private actors in the low-carbon transition** (i.e.: *politics*) is globally perceived as of little relevance. This result is quite surprising. It is indeed not in line with the opinion of several authors who claim that low-carbon scenarios should explore the roles of different actors in influencing the transition pathway. Many authors – whose views I share – consider that, in light of the crucial role of the actors in making low-carbon transition happen, policy-relevant scenarios should address the question of the actors of change (Li & *al.*, 2015; Hughes, 2013; Kiraly & *al.*, 2013; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Wangel, 2011b; Foxon & *al.* 2010; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). This is formulated as follows by Foxon & *al.* (2010): “*Current energy scenario work largely focuses on technically plausible futures and their likely costs and benefits, often using modelling approaches that assume a high level of economic rationality of actors. Despite its useful insights, such work does not illuminate how technological changes arise through the dynamic interactions between a range of actors with different perspectives and goals. Their decisions and behaviour are likely to be key influences on how to get from ‘here’ to a radically different low-carbon ‘there’— and need to be understood if effective policy strategies and instruments are to be developed.*” (Foxon & *al.* 2010, p.

1203). In many scientific papers calling for bringing governance back into low-carbon scenarios, the authors place greater emphasis on the *politics* dimensions compared with the *policy* and *polity* dimensions. Equally, the question of “*change by whom?*” is one of the issues that I perceive as the most policy-relevant. This is an illustration of a mismatch between what scientists and political actors might consider relevant knowledge (see Cash & al., 2003; Cash & al., 2002).

Most of the other issues fall somewhere in between those two extreme poles. They are perceived as policy-relevant by some actors, but irrelevant by others. The perception of the policy-relevance of an issue can indeed vary greatly from one actor to another. When looking at the radar chart, we can see that the most policy-relevant cluster of issues is different for each factor [Figure 90]. **The reformists (Factor 1)** – that comprise a major segment of members from public administrations – consider the questions related to the *policy* dimension of governance as the most policy-relevant. It includes the questions of the policy instruments to implement with a view to building a low-carbon society, but also the issues of the vision of the low-carbon society in 2050 and the policy goals to be set for the different sectors / levels of power to reach this vision.

The distinct interest of the *reformists* for such operational questions contrasts with the cluster of issues considered as the most policy-relevant by **the revolutionists (Factor 2)**. While the *reformists* request knowledge on the objectives and policies to implement with a view to reaching a desirable low-carbon vision whilst remaining within the existing institutional framework, the *revolutionists* are interested in understanding how to rethink this framework. They highlight the limitations of current governance structures (e.g.: fragmentation of the political competences between the federal and the regions, but also between the different policy domains at the same level of power; problems to articulate the policies developed by those different entities, inefficacy of top-down and market-based approaches) as well as the need to develop local and community-based governance to foster the low-carbon transition. For them, the most relevant issues concern the *polity* dimension of governance, namely the level of action and the division of competences as well as the steering mode.

In fine, **the incumbents (Factor 3)** are interested in questions that directly affect them. For those persons that represent the interest of dominant actors of the current regime, the most policy-relevant issues concern the way to develop an incumbent-sensitive policy: “*What policy to implement to ensure the low-carbon transition while taking into account the needs of the incumbents?*”, “*What role should incumbents play with a view to building a low-carbon society?*”, “*How to ensure that the incumbents take part in the low-carbon transition and mobilize their financial resources*”, and to a lesser extent “*How to address the incumbents’ resistances to low-carbon transition?*”.

The considerable variations regarding the perception of the policy-relevance of potential research questions combined with the potential mismatch between what scientists and political actors might consider relevant knowledge lead me to emphasize the **need to co-construct the research problem with the intended users** of a study. A producer of scenarios can’t guess what issues are perceived as policy-relevant by a specific actor. What is considered policy-relevant by a scenario producer can indeed be perceived differently by the intended users. Once the research problem is defined, a suitable approach to address it has to be designed. There is not a one size fits all approach. The most suitable approach to be used will depend on the one hand on the research problem (i.e.: governance issues to be addressed), and on the other hand on the intended role of the study in policy-making (i.e.: instrumental, conceptual or process role). The question of the approach for making knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios will be further discussed in the next chapter (see Chapter V).

5. Discussion of the Method

5.1. Forced and Free Distributions

5.1.1. Comparison of the Results Obtained with Free and Forced Distributions

If we compare the results obtained under forced and free distributions, we observe that the main difference between the two types of distribution is the predominance of positive scores in the free distribution. The following table shows all the scores attributed by the participants for each item under the free distribution [Table 34]. We can see that there are much more positive scores (in green), than negative scores (in red). It is also interesting to note that there are very few neutral scores. The predominance of positive scores is also visible in the representation of the typical Q sorts of the three factors that emerged from the analysis of the data collected under free Q survey [Figures 91, 92 and 93]. In such ranking grids, the items are distributed as follow: “-2”: 4 items; “-1”: 4 items; “0”: 2 items; “+1”: 9 items; “+2”: 8 items. The comparison with the scores assigned under free distribution allows to qualify the results obtained with the forced distribution. The later distribution forced the participants to assign negative scores to issues that they considered policy-relevant. Yet, globally, there is more issues perceived as relevant than issues perceived as irrelevant. For many actors, it was indeed quite difficult to sort the items because they considered most of them as policy-relevant.

«Il n’y a rien de pas pertinent, il faut faire tout ça!» (ENG-BE-5)

When looking at the global picture, the free distribution confirms that most of the actors consider that the questions of the policy instruments (3-9) should be the subject of a study. The issue of the integration of the long-term into the policy process (26) is also considered policy-relevant by a majority of actors. This is in line with the data collected under forced distribution (See section “3.2.1. Governance issues perceived as the most policy-relevant” of the same chapter).

relevant for both Factors 2. The Factors 2 obtained with forced and free distributions also coincide by attributing extreme negative scores to the cluster of issues “incumbent sensitive-policy”. Finally, the Factors 3 obtained with forced and free distributions distinguish by assigning higher scores than other factors to the clusters of issues “incumbent sensitive-policy” and, conversely, lower scores to the cluster “long-term oriented issues”.

Figure 91. Idealized Q sort for Factor 1: Forced versus free distribution

Figure 92. Idealized Q sort for Factor 2: Forced versus free distribution

-2	-1	0	1	2
27. Representation of non-human beings in the policy process 	10. Role of the political-administrative authorities 	20. Horizontal integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue 	7. Land use planning 	8. Information and awareness
18. Foresight's institutionalization 	25. Degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders 	19. Vertical integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue 	12. Role of the incumbents 	21. Vertical integration of the policy goals
26. Long term integration in the policy process 	16. Level of action and division of competences 	9. Education and vocational training 	23. Vertical integration of the policy instruments 	13. Consideration of the incumbents' needs
1. Vision for 2050 	2. Policy goals 	14. Resistances of the incumbents 	5. Eco-fiscality 	15. Mobilization of the incumbents
	11. Role of the different stakeholders 	24. Horizontal integration of the policy instruments 	22. Horizontal integration of the policy goals 	
	17. Steering mode 	4. Regulatory framework 	3. Policy mix 	
		6. Services and infrastructures 		

-2	-1	0	1	2
**◀ Degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders 	Role of the incumbents 	◀ Vision for 2050 	▶▶ Mobilization of the incumbents 	Vertical integration of the policy goals
Steering mode 	◀ Role of the different stakeholders 	▶▶ Vertical integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue 	▶▶ Resistances of the incumbents 	Regulatory framework
◀ Foresight's institutionalization 	◀ Role of the administrative authorities 		Horizontal integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue 	Horizontal integration of the policy goals
◀ Representation of non-human beings in the policy process 	◀ Long term integration in the policy process 		Information and awareness 	* Eco-fiscality
			Policy goals 	Policy mix
			Education and vocational training 	Horizontal integration of the policy instruments
			▶▶ Consideration of the incumbents' needs 	Vertical integration of the policy instruments
			Level of action and division of competences 	Land use planning
			◀ Services and infrastructures 	

Figure 93. Idealized Q sort for Factor 3: Forced versus free distribution

Figure 94: Position of the three factors in relation to the different categories of issues: forced versus free distribution

Concerning Q sorts significantly correlated, we note that seven of the twelve Q-sorts correlated to Factor 1 obtained with forced distribution are also correlated to Factor 1 obtained with free distribution; seven of the eleven Q-sorts correlated to Factor 2 obtained with forced distribution are also correlated to Factor 2 obtained with free distribution; and four of the six Q-sorts correlated to Factor 3 obtained with forced distribution are also correlated to Factor 3 obtained with free distribution. The following tables contains the correlation between the Q-sorts and the factors obtained with forced and free distributions [Tables 35, 36 and 37]. The Q sorts that are significantly correlated to the same factor under forced and free distributions are highlighted in grey.

Q SORT	WEIGHT	Q SORT	WEIGHT
CA-BE-2	2,11387	ADM-BE-2	8,94329
ADM-RW-1	1,57187	POL-BE-1	8,78732
ENG-BE-5	1,35851	ENG-BE-2	5,60707
ENG-BE-2	1,29637	ADM-RW-1	4,14782
ADM-BE-2	1,1683	PA-BE-2	3,94805
BUS-BE-2	1,05617	ENG-BE-5	3,48507
WU-BE-1	0,96712	PA-RW-1	2,93144
ADM-BE-1	0,89512	WU-BE-2	1,48759
NGO-RW-1	0,87572	<i>PRI-BE-1</i>	<i>-3,34678</i>
PA-BE-5	0,66008	<i>UNI-RW-2</i>	<i>-10</i>
PA-BE-3	0,63661	CA-BE-2	2,39251
ADM-RW-2	0,45999	PA-BE-5	2,25285
		NGO-RW-1	2,23711
		ADM-RW-2	2,22595
		PA-RW-4	2,05836
		ADM-RW-3	1,89858

Table 35. Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 1: Forced versus free distribution

Q SORT	WEIGHT	Q SORT	WEIGHT
PA-BE-2	1,76085	WU-RW-1	4,02249
WU-RW-1	1,50654	BUS-BE-2	3,69586
POL-RW-1	1,38078	CA-BE-1	3,28577
PA-RW-4	1,17508	POL-RW-1	3,20327
BUS-BE-4	1,07054	POL-RW-2	3,1726
CA-BE-4	1,02955	UNI-RW-1	2,9871
CA-BE-1	0,94558	PA-RW-3	2,84346
ENG-BE-6	0,93568	NGO-BE-1	2,82492
UNI-RW-1	0,5726	NGO-BE-3	2,21706
ENG-RW-1	0,46182	BUS-BE-4	2,07005
POL-RW-2	0,44785	ENG-BE-1	2,05288
		ENG-RW-1	1,69978
		PA-RW-2	1,67907
		ENG-BE-4	1,65799
		CA-BE-3	4,22447
		<i>PA-BE-6</i>	<i>-3,18617</i>
		<i>WU-BE-1</i>	<i>-3,90412</i>

Table 36. Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 2: Forced versus free distribution

Q SORT	WEIGHT	Q SORT	WEIGHT
ENG-BE-3	1,4676	BUS-RW-1	2,55726
PA-BE-1	1,14353	BUS-BE-3	2,43785
<i>NGO-BE-1</i>	<i>-0,98551</i>	ENG-BE-3	8,58148
BUS-BE-3	0,83125	PA-BE-1	3,51985
PA-BE-6	0,78314	ADM-BE-1	3,11353
<i>PA-RW-3</i>	<i>-0,77065</i>	PRI-RW-1	3,02499
BUS-BE-5	0,75075	BUS-BE-5	2,83758
<i>ENG-BE-1</i>	<i>-0,70884</i>	CA-BE-4	2,8327
<i>PA-RW-1</i>	<i>-0,63911</i>	NGO-BE-2	2,75873
BUS-BE-1	0,52685	PA-BE-3	1,52985

Table 37. Q sorts significantly correlated to Factor 3: Forced versus free distribution

5.1.2. Value of Combining Forced and Free Distributions

As explained previously, the reason why I have decided to combine forced and free distribution was to address the limits of forced distribution that I have experienced when I carried out a first Q survey as part of my master thesis (see section “1.4.2. Combining forced and free distributions” of the same chapter). The first limit was the frustrations that participants may feel when they are forced to assign ratings that don’t correspond to their view. Giving the participant the freedom to assign the score they want to the items in the pre-sorting step and taking note of what they wanted to say about the items appears to reduce the frustrations that the forced distribution can generate. The participants understood that I heard their thoughts about the items during the pre-sorting step and that the score assigned to the items was no longer important in the forced sorting step – the objective being to compare the items with each other. As a result, they did not complain about being forced to assign scores that did not correspond to their view.

By combining free and forced distributions, I also intended to grasp the distortion of the participants’ views potentially generated by the sorting of the items in the pyramid-shaped grid. By comparing the results obtained with free and forced distribution, I observed that there are more positive scores in the free distribution. This implies that the participants had to assign negative scores to issues that they considered policy-relevant in the forced distribution. Yet, globally, there are more issues perceived as relevant than issues perceived as irrelevant. The free distribution has thus allowed to shade the results obtained with forced distribution.

The comparison of the results obtained with forced and free distribution also reveal similarities regarding the sorting of the items, but also regarding the factors that emerged. The conclusions we could draw after analysing the data obtained with the two types of distribution are actually pretty similar⁴⁸. It enhances the robustness of the factor analysis, but it also leads to a question: What is the added value of adding a forced distribution-based sorting after the free distribution if we obtain almost the same results? Why not concluding the Q survey after the sorting based on a free distribution? In fact, we could end there. But forcing the sorting of the items leads to emphasizing the features of the factors which, in my opinion, make the interpretation of the results easier. When comparing the position of the factors obtained with forced *versus* free distribution in relation to the different categories of issues (see figure 94), we can distinguish more clearly the specificities of the factors that emerged after analysing the data collected under forced distribution. Of course, that doesn’t mean that forced distribution should necessarily be applied. As said before, the choice between forced and free distributions depends primarily on the objectives of the research and on what is considered as important: item order in case of forced distribution or scale separation in case of free distribution (see section “1.4.1. Respective characteristics of forced and free distributions” of the same chapter).

⁴⁸ This is in line with the empirical studies comparing the two Q sorting procedures. As a reminder, all these studies lead to the conclusion that the type of distribution makes little difference regarding the statistical results (Cottle & McKeown, 1980; Brown, 1980 and 1971; Hess & Hink, 1959; Block, 1956).

5.2. Limits of the Method

The following section concludes the chapter with a discussion on the limits of the method. A first risk to which the researcher exposes himself when conducting a Q survey is to forget important items when building the Q set. As explained earlier, the Q set is supposed to cover all the possible discourses in relation to the subject of study (see section “1.2. Conduct of a Q methodology” of the same chapter). It appears that the Q set I used in this study covers exhaustively the discourse regarding the knowledge on the governance of the low-carbon transition that political actors need to devise long-term mitigation policies. Indeed, at the end of the survey, when I asked the respondents if I forgot important governance issues, most of the time, the response was that everything was there. Some respondents have suggested a few extra items, but such items either don't corresponded to what I considered to be governance issues (e.g.: issues of the financing of the low-carbon transition) or were out of scope (e.g.: issues related to international climate mitigation policy, climate adaptation policy or North-South relations). In that context, I believe that the matrix I used to identify systematically the governance issues that could be addressed in low-carbon scenarios completed with literature review and exploratory interview was a suitable approach to draw up a comprehensive inventory of the knowledge gaps regarding the governance of the low-carbon transition.

The format of the items used in this research was quite unusual. As mentioned earlier, presenting the items with the name of the governance issue considered being followed by a research question is not common (see section “2.2. Formulation of the items (Q set)” of the same chapter). I choose this formulation because it appeared to be more structured and easier to understand. I observed during the Q survey that, apart from a few exceptions, most of the participants had no real difficulty understanding the content of the items. However, some respondents encountered difficulties in sorting such items, and this for two reasons. The first one is that several respondents considered that most of the governance issues presented were policy-relevant. It was thus not easy for them to rank them in the pyramid-shaped grid. The second reason is related to the unusual nature of the exercise. I indeed asked political actors to classify potential research questions according to their policy-relevance. I presented the exercise as a role-play where the participant had to imagine that he was the sponsor of the forthcoming study and that he was preparing the terms of reference for this study (see section “2.3.2. Q-survey” of the same chapter). Several respondents had difficulty to put themselves in the shoes of the sponsor of the study. Some of them lost sight of the objective of the exercise – i.e.: sorting governance issues regarding their policy-relevance. During the Q survey, some participants deviated from the initial objective and started to sort the issues regarding other criteria than policy relevance, such as the importance or the desirability. For instance, I saw several participants assigning positive scores to the item “(5) Eco-fiscality - What economic instruments (i.e.: taxes, subsidies, carbon market) should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? In what ways?” because they perceive this policy instrument as efficient and consider it should be implemented. Conversely, some respondents could attribute a negative score to the item “(4) Regulatory framework - What standards should be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society? (i.e.: norms, branch agreements) In what ways?” because they oppose command and control policy instruments. In such cases, I had to remind the respondent of the objectives of the exercise. It was possible to do that during the sorting process if the respondent provided “real time” comments on his/her choices. But when the respondent said nothing during the sorting process, I realized the mistake at the end of the survey when I asked him to explain the extreme scores. After having experienced such problems during the first interviews that I carried out, I tried in the following interviews to encourage the participant to communicate during the sorting to make sure that he understood the objective of the exercise.

Another limit of the Q methodology that I mentioned in the section devoted to the advantages and limitations of the method is the order effect. It is the result of a tendency of the participants to sort the items presented near the end of the Q-survey in the middle of the distribution (see section “1.3. Advantages and limitations of the Q methodology” of the same chapter). I didn't observe that the items presented near the end of the Q survey got more middle scores. That said, it is quite difficult to

identify such feature and, even if able to identify it, we would not be able to determine whether it is the result of the order effect or the score that the respondent would assign without such bias.

Finally, as mentioned before, the Q methodology has the advantage of not requiring too many participants, because each Q sort offers a large amount of information (see section “1.3. Advantages and limitations of the Q methodology” of the same chapter). This advantage can nevertheless turn against the researcher. It is indeed difficult to understand all the informations provided by each Q sort. Even if the factor analysis gives rise to the identification of typical Q sorts that allow to grasp the discourses shared by several similar individual Q sorts, the factors constitute ideal-types that are not formulated as such by any respondents. Therefore, in order not to draw erroneous conclusions, it is necessary to analyse the individual Q-sorts. Such analysis is not only tedious, but it also carries a risk of omitting important elements. This is why I consider that Q methodology allows to collect a lot of information but does not necessary offer the tools to exploit such information optimally.

Conclusion to the Chapter

The objective of this second empirical study was to provide an assessment of the need for knowledge about the governance of the low-carbon transition. More specifically, such assessment aimed at identifying and comparing the perceptions among different actors of the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition. Just like in Chapter III, the actors are those involved in the long-term policy process of GHG-emissions' mitigation in the Walloon Region (Belgium). The needs assessment has been carried out with a Q methodology, that is a qualitative but statistically supported method which allows understanding the variety of discourses around a given topic (see Barry & Proops, 1990). As part of the Q-survey, 54 participants sorted a set of potential research questions covering the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance according to their relevance to devise mitigation policies. A principal component analysis of the data led to the identification of three factors that are ideal-typical versions of the way to perceive the subject of study shared by a number of participants. Those are the *reformists*, the *revolutionists* and the *incumbents*.

The analysis of the similarities and differences between the factors allowed to highlight the areas of consensus and the terms of the debate concerning the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition. Regarding the areas of consensus, it has been observed that with a few exceptions, most of the actors consider that the questions of the policy instruments should be the subject of a study. They indeed state that knowledge regarding the policy instruments to be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society is needed. On the contrary, some issues are globally perceived as of little relevance. This is the case for the question of the representation of the non-human beings in the policy process, and, to a lesser extent, the question of the role of the different actors in the low-carbon transition (i.e.: *politics*). The latter finding contrasts with the opinion of several authors who claim that low-carbon scenarios should explore the roles of different actors in influencing the transition pathway. This points out a mismatch between what scientists and political actors might consider relevant knowledge. The other issues correspond to the terms of the debate: they are perceived as policy-relevant by some actors, but irrelevant by others. Each factor embodies a specific discourse. The *reformists* – that comprise a major segment of members from public administrations – consider the questions related to the *policy* dimension of governance as the most policy-relevant. It includes the questions of the policy instruments to be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society, but also the issues of the vision of the low-carbon society in 2050 and the policy goals to be set for the different sectors / levels of power in order to reach this vision. The distinct interest of the *reformists* for such operational questions contrasts with the cluster of issues considered as the most policy-relevant by the *revolutionists*. While the *reformists* request knowledge on the objectives and policies to be adopted with a view to reaching a desirable low-carbon vision whilst remaining within the existing institutional framework, the *revolutionists* are interested in understanding how to rethink this framework. They highlight the limitations of current governance structures as well as the need to develop local and community-based governance to foster the low-carbon transition. For them, the most relevant issues concern the *polity* dimension of governance. *In fine*, the *incumbents* are interested in questions that directly affect them. For those persons that represent the interest of dominant actors of the current high carbon regime, the most policy-relevant issues concern the way to develop an incumbent-sensitive climate mitigation policy. The considerable variations regarding the perception of the policy-relevance of possible research questions combined with the potential mismatch between what scientists and political actors might consider relevant knowledge led me to emphasize the need to co-construct the research problem with the intended users of a study.

The study was also quite original from a methodological point of view. I indeed carried out a Q survey combining forced and free distributions. The underlying idea was to address the limits of forced distribution that I have experienced when I carried out a first Q survey as part of my master thesis – i.e.: the frustrations that participants may feel when they are forced to assign ratings that don't correspond to their view, and the distortion of the participants' views potentially generated by the sorting of the items in the pyramid-shaped grid. It has been observed that the free distribution has

successfully offset the limits of the forced distribution. I therefore recommend this approach for the researchers who have to carry out a Q survey based on forced distribution (because the item order is more important than scale separation), but who consider the above-mentioned limits of the pyramid-shaped ranking grid as a problem. Finally, the comparison of the results obtained with forced and free distribution are similar. The conclusions we could draw after analysing the data obtained with the two types of distribution are indeed almost the same. This “double check” thus enhanced the robustness of the results of the statistical analysis of the Q set.

CHAPTER V.

Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios: A Critical Review of Socio-Technical Energy Transition Models

CHAPTER V. Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios: A Critical Review of Socio-Technical Energy Transition Models

Introduction

The previous chapters confirmed on an empirical basis the need for making knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (see Chapters III and IV). This raises methodological questions on how to develop low-carbon scenarios including governance dimensions as variables. Including governance variables into low-carbon scenarios is a significant methodological challenge (Li & *al.*, 2016; Prehofer & *al.*, 2014; Kiraly & *al.*, 2013). The development of scenarios capturing the socio-technical essence of the energy transition is indeed extremely complex, since it requires taking into consideration the co-evolution of many interrelated social and technological variables (Hughes, 2013).

The empirical investigation also corroborates the idea that quantitative analyses are needed when it comes to energy-related issues (see Chapter III). Low-carbon scenario analyses based on quantitative approaches are not only perceived as more policy-relevant, but also more consistent than purely qualitative scenario analyses. An exclusively qualitative analysis does indeed not allow to know if the scenarios developed reach the quantitative GHG reduction targets, are cost-effective or even technically feasible (Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Fortes & *al.*, 2015, Söderholm & *al.*, 2011). Low-carbon scenarios including governance should therefore be developed on the basis of quantitative approaches. That brings us to the question of the level of integration of governance variables in energy models.

This question is part of a broader discussion of the relations between quantitative models and social sciences (see Geels & *al.*, 2016). This debate opposes three conceptions of the relations between quantitative modelling and social sciences. A first perspective consists in advocating a full integration of social dimensions in models. The proponents of such an integrated approach consider that modelling tools should be based on social sciences theories and concepts, and fully integrate social dimensions as variables. Such integrated models are part of the larger area of integrated assessment which aims at combining knowledge, analyses and insights from the natural sciences and social sciences in a sort of meta-discipline in order to address wicked problems (Hamilton & *al.*, 2015; Weyant, 2009). An opposing point of view is that quantitative simulation and social analyses are incommensurable and should be applied separately (Geels & *al.*, 2016). Those in favour of pluralism consider that integrated assessment model-based analyses fail to capture the complexity of social dynamics. For Castree & *al.* (2014) integrated approaches “*reveal a limited conception of social science and virtually ignore the humanities. They thereby endorse a stunted conception of ‘human dimensions’ at a time when the challenges posed by global environmental change are increasing in magnitude, scale and scope*” (Castree & *al.*, 2014). Finally, an intermediate view is that quantitative models and social science concepts and theories should not be completely integrated, but rather combined. The defenders of this perspective argue that these different approaches are complementary, but hardly integrable. Instead, they suggest making alignment, bridges and iterations between quantitative simulations and social analyses with a view to combining their respective strengths (Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Geels & *al.*, 2016; Turnheim & *al.*, 2015).

This last study intends to contribute to the debate on the relations between quantitative modelling and social sciences. Positioning myself in favour of the complementarity-based approach, I aim at consolidating the foundations of this approach. My hypothesis is that the approaches that attempt to fully integrate social science concepts and theories into quantitative models-based analyses are not suitable to capture the complexity of the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition, and that, in that respect, complementarity-based approaches are more effective. To confirm this

hypothesis, I attempted to highlight the inability of integrated modelling to effectively address governance issues.

The research question is thus formulated as follows:

“What are the limits of scenario analyses based on integrated modelling in addressing the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition?”

This question involves three sub-questions:

- I. Which dimensions of governance are included in integrated energy models?
- II. Which approaches are used to integrate these social dimensions?
- III. What are the limits of integrated energy models in addressing governance issues?

With a view to grasping these questions, I carried out a critical review of fifteen socio-technical energy transition (STET) models. They correspond to “*formal quantitative energy models (...) [that capture] the elements of socio-technical transitions, including societal actors and the co-evolutionary nature of policy, technology and behaviour*” (Li & al., 2015, p. 291). I analysed if and how those integrated models make knowledge about governance through a framework allowing to assess the way they address the *policy, politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance.

In the first section of the chapter, after a presentation of the integrated modelling approach, I introduce the main characteristics of STET models. Afterwards, I move on to the methodological note. In the next section, I develop the framework I used for analysing how STET models make knowledge about governance. I then present the review of STET models emphasizing their limits in addressing the *policy, politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance. In the last section, I discuss the factors that might explain the limited integration of governance issues in STET models as well as the necessity of combining models with complementary approaches to provide policy relevant information concerning energy transition governance.

1. Integrating Governance in Energy Transition Models

1.1. Integrated Modelling

Integrated models are part of the larger area of integrated assessment. Applied in the field of climate change, integrated assessment can be generally defined as “*an attempt to combine information, analysis and insight from the physical sciences (physics, chemistry and biology, and all fields that build on them) and social sciences (economics, psychology, sociology, anthropology and all fields that build on them) to address the nature of climate change and to develop possible policy responses to it*” (Weyant 2009, p. 317). A more in-depth definition is suggested by Hamilton & al. (2015) who consider integrated assessment as “*the integration of components across and within ten interrelated dimensions [— i) issues of concern, ii) governance settings, iii) stakeholders, iv) natural and v) human systems, vi) spatial and vii) temporal scales, viii) disciplines, ix) methods, models, other tools and data, and x) sources and types of uncertainty]*” (Hamilton & al., 2015, p. 215). As stated in the first definition, integrated assessment is mostly designed as a decision support tool for policy-making. This process is indeed devised to assess the impact of a specific policy or to compare different policies regarding their propensity to reach a particular goal (Weyant, 2009). Integrated assessment aims at carrying out a comprehensive analysis of the issue and this is why it is often applied in the field of climate change — and more broadly in the field of environmental issues — which goes beyond the boundaries of sectors, system components and disciplines. The proponents of integrated assessment actually argue that a meta-discipline is required because the traditional disciplinary methodologies face a number of limits in addressing such (super-)wicked problems (Hamilton & al., 2015).

Due to its ability to provide a systemic and transparent integration approach, model is usually considered as a key tool in the meta-discipline of integrated assessment (Hamilton & al., 2015). A model is here understood as “*a simplified, stylized and formalized representation of (a part of) reality*” (Holtz & al. 2016, p. 43). Models can differ in term of temporal, spatial and material scope, but also regarding the approaches adopted (van Beek, 1999). Many different types of modelling approaches can be distinguished: top-down (i.e.: macro-economic detail) versus bottom-up (i.e.: technological detail), agent-based versus “one-actor”, simulation versus optimization and process-based versus cost-benefit (Turnheim & al., 2015). Some of these approaches can be applied to integrate dimensions of governance in energy models. Cost-benefit analysis can be used to explore the *policy* dimension of governance. Applied in the field of energy modelling, cost-benefit analysis is intended to balance the cost and benefits of mitigation policies (e.g.: Gomi & al., 2011). Besides, agent-based modelling allows studying the *politics* dimension. This approach aims at capturing the behaviour of different autonomous agents, their interactions as well as the results of such interactions (Chappin, 2011). While initially developed in the field of social sciences, agent-based modelling is frequently used to model the energy system (e.g.: Zheng, 2004). Dimensions of governance can also be integrated in models through dynamic simulation. This approach is based on the system theory and consists in representing stocks and flows within a system (Chappin, 2011). Dynamic simulation can cover a broad scope and include non-physical elements, such as policies and actors’ behaviours. Social elements can thus be included in energy models based on dynamic simulation (e.g.: Prehofer & al., 2014).

1.2. Socio-Technical Energy Transition (STET) Models

In the field of transition studies, one has witnessed for several years the emergence of a small sub-community of researchers attempting to modelling socio-technical transition dynamics (see Holtz & al., 2016; Halbe & al., 2015; Holtz, 2011; Haxeltine & al., 2008; Timmermans & al., 2008). Socio-technical energy transition (STET) models fall within this current. I first heard about socio-technical energy transition (STET) models during the PhD course “Innovation and sustainability transition” organized by the Norwegian Research School in Innovation (NORSI) at the University of Tromsø (Coenen, 2015). Such models directly arouse my curiosity. STET models correspond to “*formal*

quantitative energy models (...) [that capture] the elements of socio-technical transitions, including societal actors and the co-evolutionary nature of policy, technology and behaviour” (Li & al. 2015, p. 291). They are thus supposed to grasp the socio-technical character of energy transition. At first glance, STET models appeared to me as promising tools to make knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenario analyses. This is why I have decided to take a closer look at it and how they make knowledge about governance.

Li & al. (2015) who conducted an extended review of STET models both in the transition studies and energy modelling literature⁴⁹, set out the criteria that models must meet to be considered as STET models. As outlined in the following figure [Figure 95], there are three such families of criteria: (A) Techno-economic detail, (B) explicit actor heterogeneity and (C) transition pathway dynamics. (A) STET models must depict the shift from a high to a low-carbon system. With this in mind, they must include a range of technological levers, each associated with specific cost and performance. The models must also be delimited by operational or resource limits. (B) To be considered as STET model, a simulation tool must represent the various behaviours of (constellation of) actors who can take decisions likely to shape the energy transition. It is therefore necessary to take into consideration not only producers and consumers of energy, but also political-administrative authorities and civil society organizations. (C) STET models must represent the transition dynamics. They have hence to evaluate the feasibility of normative goals as well as exploring diverse pathways to reach these objectives. The time horizon of the scenarios must be long enough to analyse radical changes and path dependencies. Finally, the models must also take into account radical changes in technologies and behaviours that are likely to put an end to the high carbon regime (Li & al., 2015).

Figure 95. Methodological requirements for STET models (Li & al. 2015, p. 293)

⁴⁹ All the models reviewed by Li & al. (2015) don't refer explicitly to transitions theory.

2. Methodology

The STET models analysed in this study are those who have been reviewed by Li & *al.* (2015). Since the purpose of the review conducted by Li & *al.* (2015) was to identify from the literature models fulfilling the STET criteria (i.e.: techno-economic detail, explicit actor heterogeneity and transition pathway dynamics), it is limited to analysing the way STET models meet these methodological requirements. The analysis remains rather superficial and doesn't cover the way STET models address governance issues. By examining the same cases studies through a framework allowing to assess the way they address the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance (see section "3. Framework for analysing how STET models make knowledge about governance" of the same chapter), I have introduced an additional analytical dimension to the review conducted by Li & *al.* (2015).

I reviewed the fifteen STET models listed in the table below [Table 38]. Note that for practical reasons, just as Li & *al.* (2015), I did not analyse the simulation tools *per se*, but the papers presenting the models in question. A list including the complete references of the papers reviewed is set out in appendix [Appendix 7].

STET MODELS	DEMONSTRATED FIELDS OF APPLICATION	REFERENCES
BLUE-MLP	Power sector (UK)	Incorporating Behavioural Complexity in Energy-Economic Models (Strachan & Warren, 2011) Linking a storyline with multiple models: A cross-scale study of the UK power system transition (Trutnevyte & <i>al.</i> , 2014)
CASCADE Model Framework	Power sector (UK)	CASCADE: An Agent Based Framework for Modeling The Dynamics of Smart Electricity Systems (Rylatt & <i>al.</i> , 2013) Exploring Possible Energy Futures For The UK: Evolving Power Generation (Allen & <i>al.</i> , 2013) Modelling sustainable energy futures for the UK (Allen & Varga, 2014)
Chappin's Power Sector Agent-Based Model (ABM)	Power sector (Netherlands)	Agent-based modelling of energy infrastructure transitions (Chappin & Dijkema, 2008b) Modelling Strategic and Operational Decision-Making—An Agent-Based Model of Electricity Producers (Chappin & <i>al.</i> , 2007) On the impact of CO ₂ emission-trading on power generation emissions (Chappin & Dijkema, 2009) Simulating Energy Transitions (Chappin, 2011)
ElecTrans	Power sector (Netherlands)	An Exploratory Analysis of the Dutch Electricity System in Transition (Kwakkel & Yücel, 2012) A simulation-based analysis of transition pathways for the Dutch electricity system (Yücel & van Daalen, 2012)
ENGAGE DFR Module	National energy demand and supply	Agent-based modelling of climate policy: An introduction to the ENGAGE multi-level model framework (Gerst & <i>al.</i> , 2013b) Discovering plausible energy and economic futures under global change using multidimensional scenario discovery (Gerst & <i>al.</i> , 2013a)
RAND Computer Assisted Reasoning (CAR) Framework	Global energy demand and supply	Carrots and sticks for new technology: Abating greenhouse gas emissions in a heterogeneous and uncertain world (Robalino & Lempert, 2000) A new decision sciences for complex systems (Lempert, 2002)
Tran's Alternative Fuel Vehicle (AFV) Model	Passenger car market (UK)	Technology-behavioural modelling of energy innovation diffusion in the UK (Tran, 2012) Simulating early adoption of alternative fuel vehicles for sustainability (Tran & <i>al.</i> , 2013)
Struben's Alternative Fuel Vehicle (AFV) Model	Passenger car market (California)	Essays on transition challenges for alternative propulsion vehicles and transportation systems (Struben, 2006a) Identifying challenges for sustained adoption of alternative fuel vehicles and infrastructure (Struben, 2006b) Transition challenges for alternative fuel vehicle and transportation systems (Struben & Sterman, 2008)
Transition Lab Framework	Ground vehicle transport (UK, US)	Modelling Socio-technical Transition Patterns and Pathways (Bergman & <i>al.</i> , 2008a) A transitions model for sustainable mobility (Köhler & <i>al.</i> , 2009)
Transition Lab Framework	Residential buildings (UK)	Transition to sustainable development in the UK housing sector: from case study to model implementation (Bergman & <i>al.</i> , 2008b)
REMG and IMAGE/TIMER	Residential buildings (Multiple Countries)	Model projections for household energy use in India (van Ruijven & <i>al.</i> , 2011) Model projections for household energy use in developing countries (Daioglou & <i>al.</i> , 2012)
Charlier's Residential Sector Model	Residential buildings (France)	Evaluation of the impact of environmental public policy measures on energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions in the French residential sector (Charlier & Risch, 2012)
Res-IRF and IMACLIM-R	Residential buildings (France)	Comparing and Combining Energy Saving Policies: Will Proposed Residential Sector Policies Meet French Official Targets? (Giraudet & <i>al.</i> , 2011) Exploring the potential for energy conservation in French households through hybrid modelling (Giraudet & <i>al.</i> , 2012)
Yücel's Housing Stock Model	Residential buildings (Netherlands)	Extent of inertia caused by the existing building stock against an energy transition in the Netherlands (Yücel, 2013)
Chappin's Consumer Lighting Agent-Based Model (ABM)	Residential buildings (lighting) (Netherlands)	An agent-based model of transitions in consumer lighting: Policy impacts from the E.U. phase-out of incandescents (Chappin & Afman, 2013)

Table 38. STET models reviewed in the present research (Li & *al.*, 2015)

3. Framework for Analysing how STET Models Make Knowledge about Governance

When analysing the way STET models address the governance issues, I considered the three dimensions of governance defined in the first chapter — i.e.: *policy*, *politics* and *polity* (see section “4.1.2. Policy, politics and polity dimensions of governance” of Chapter I). For each dimension of governance, I defined a number of questions. The questions are listed in the table below [Table 39]. Through these questions, one has moved from a “generic” conceptual framework of governance to an analytical framework that allows grasping the way STET models address governance issues.

DIMENSIONS	ISSUES	QUESTIONS
POLICY	Representation of the societal problem	Are the rationales behind the steering of the energy transition defined in the study? If so, what are they?
	Goals set to deal with the problem	Are the goals of the energy transition defined in the study? If so, in which form? (targets or visions)
	Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals	Are the policy instruments to be implemented with a view to steering the energy transition analysed in the study? If so, which types of instruments are taken into consideration? (command and control, economic, service and infrastructure, collaborative agreements and communication and diffusion)
POLITICS	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process	Is the role of the political-administrative authorities in steering the energy transition analysed in the study? If so, how and which actors are taken into consideration?
	Role of the different stakeholders in the policy process	Is the role of the different stakeholders in steering the energy transition analysed in the study? If so, how and which actors are taken into consideration? (civil society, scientists and citizens)
POLITY	Locus of authority	Is the <i>locus</i> where the energy transition policies are devised defined in the study? If so, which <i>loci</i> are taken into consideration? (local, regional, national or international)
	Steering mode	Is the steering mode of the energy transition defined in the study? If so, which steering modes are taken into consideration? (hierarchy, market, network or communities)
	Institutionalization of the policy process	Are the institutional structures required for steering the energy transition defined in the study? If so, what are they?

Table 39. Framework for analysing how STET models make knowledge about governance

4. Review of STET Models

4.1. Making of Knowledge about Governance in STET Models

The literature review reveals that, while the *policy* dimension is explored in most of the STET models, the *politics* and *polity* dimensions are missing in almost all the simulation tools. Taking a closer look at how the different issues of governance are understood and analysed, I highlighted five significant limits of STET models in addressing social dynamics. Before presenting these limits, I want to make it clear that all of them don't apply to the same extent to the various models. More specifically, the STET models explicitly based on transition or political theories, such as the Transition Lab Framework and the ENGAGE DFR Module which are respectively built on the Multi-level perspective on transition (see Rip & Kemp, 1998) and on the two-level games framework (see Putnam, 1988), take a more detailed look at the governance issues. I also wish to state that some STET models, such as the BLUE-MLP, were difficult to analyse because their variables and assumptions are not clearly set out in the papers reviewed. To understand the specific features of each model, the reader is therefore invited to consult the following table that summarizes the results of the literature review [Table 40].

STET MODELS	DIMENSIONS AND ISSUES OF GOVERNANCE							
	POLICY			POLITICS		POLITY		
	Representation of the societal problem	Goals set to deal with the problem	Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process	Role of the stakeholders in the policy process	Locus of authority	Steering mode	Institutionalization of the policy process
BLUE-MLP	Reduction of GHG from the production and consumption of energy through technical and behavioural innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	?	The model integrates policy instruments, but the papers reviewed don't provide details about the type of instruments took into consideration.	-	-	?	?	?
CASCADE Model Framework	Reduction of GHG from the production of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Long-term quantitative reduction targets for GHG emissions adopted by the government of the studied area	Test various adjustments of a specific instrument (different rates of carbon tax) and assess its effect when combined with other instruments (subsidies and support to scientific research)	-	-	The model analyses the geographical distribution of electrical generation capacity by assessing the relative attractiveness of different locations under various scenarios.	-	-
Chappin's Power Sector Agent-Based Model (ABM)	Reduction of GHG from the production of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Long-term quantitative reduction targets for GHG emissions adopted by the government of the studied area	Evaluate the stand-alone impact of a single instrument (CO ₂ emissions trading schemes)	-	-	-	-	-

STET MODELS	DIMENSIONS AND ISSUES OF GOVERNANCE							
	POLICY			POLITICS		POLITY		
	Representation of the societal problem	Goals set to deal with the problem	Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process	Role of the stakeholders in the policy process	Locus of authority	Steering mode	Institutionalization of the policy process
ElecTrans	Reduction of GHG from the production of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	-	Assess the combined effect of several instruments (subsidies and CO ₂ emissions trading schemes)	-	-	-	-	-
ENGAGE DFR Module	Reduction of GHG from the production of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	?	Test various adjustments of a specific instrument and the combined effect of several instruments (three different types of carbon tax revenues recycling schemes combined with subsidies and support to scientific research)	This model is based on the Putnam two-level games framework, an approach aiming to simulate international negotiations (see Putnam, 1988). It thus explores the role of negotiators from different countries in international climate negotiations as well as the influence of policy preferences of firms and households on national policy-making. This exploration of <i>politics</i> dimension is however not very detailed.	-	By applying the Putnam two-level games framework, which is intended for grasping the entanglements of domestic and international politics, the model simulates the interactions between national and international policy formulation.	-	-
RAND Computer Assisted Reasoning (CAR) Framework	Reduction of GHG from the production of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Long-term quantitative reduction targets for GHG emissions adopted by the government of the studied area	Assess the combined effect of several instruments (carbon tax and subsidies)	-	-	-	-	-
Tran's Alternative Fuel Vehicle (AFV) Model	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Increase the use of less carbon intensive vehicles	-	-	-	-	-	-

STET MODELS	DIMENSIONS AND ISSUES OF GOVERNANCE							
	POLICY			POLITICS		POLITY		
	Representation of the societal problem	Goals set to deal with the problem	Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process	Role of the stakeholders in the policy process	Locus of authority	Steering mode	Institutionalization of the policy process
Struben's Alternative Fuel Vehicle (AFV) Model	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Increase the use of less carbon intensive vehicles	Assess the combined effect of several instrument (subsidies and development of service and infrastructure stimulating energy transition)	-	-	The model analyses the distribution of fuelling infrastructures in California taking into account national as well as local factors	-	-
Transition Lab Framework (applied to transports)	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical, social and behavioural innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	?	Assess the combined effect of several instruments (regulations, incentive taxes, subsidies and development of service and infrastructure stimulating energy transition)	-	?	-	?	-
Transition Lab Framework (applied to buildings)	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical, social and behavioural innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	?	Assess the combined effect of several instruments (regulations, incentive taxes, subsidies and development of service and infrastructure stimulating energy transition)	-	The model integrates citizens' participation in their local communities as a variable.	-	The model integrates power structure as a variable. The power can be wielded by local authorities (c.f.: top-down), shifted down to communities (c.f.: bottom-up) or shared between local authorities and communities.	-

STET MODELS	DIMENSIONS AND ISSUES OF GOVERNANCE							
	POLICY			POLITICS		POLITY		
	Representation of the societal problem	Goals set to deal with the problem	Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process	Role of the stakeholders in the policy process	Locus of authority	Steering mode	Institutionalization of the policy process
REMG and IMAGE/TIMER	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical innovations with a view to fostering sustainable development	Long-term quantitative reduction targets for GHG emissions and energy consumption adopted by the government of the studied area + Social goals (improving energy access and security)	Evaluate the stand-alone impact of a single instrument (carbon tax)	-	-	-	-	-
Charlier's Residential Sector Model	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Long-term quantitative reduction targets for GHG emissions and energy consumption adopted by the government of the studied area	Assess the combined effect of several instruments (regulations, incentive taxes and subsidies)	-	-	-	-	-
Res-IRF and IMACLIM-R	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Long-term quantitative reduction targets for GHG emissions and energy consumption adopted by the government of the studied area	Evaluate the stand-alone impact of a single instrument and the combined effect of several instruments (regulations, incentive taxes and subsidies)	-	-	-	-	-

STET MODELS	DIMENSIONS AND ISSUES OF GOVERNANCE							
	POLICY			POLITICS		POLITY		
	Representation of the societal problem	Goals set to deal with the problem	Policy instruments implemented to reach the goals	Role of the political-administrative authorities in the policy process	Role of the stakeholders in the policy process	Locus of authority	Steering mode	Institutionalization of the policy process
Yücel's Housing Stock Model	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Long-term quantitative reduction targets for energy consumption adopted by the government of the studied area	Assess the combined effect of several instruments (regulations and other instruments not explicitly defined in the paper reviewed)	-	-	-	-	-
Chappin's Consumer Lighting Agent-Based Model (ABM)	Reduction of GHG from the consumption of energy through technical innovations with a view to mitigating climate change.	Reduce the use of incandescent bulbs	Evaluate the stand-alone impact of a single instrument (regulations, incentive taxes and subsidies)	-	-	-	-	-

Table 40. Dimensions and issues of governance integrated in STET models

4.2. Limits of STET Models in Making Knowledge about Governance

This section aims at presenting five significant limits of STET models in addressing governance issues that I have highlighted:

4.2.1. Problem of Scope

The first limit of STET models is that they face a problem of scope. STET models tend to focus on a specific market or (a part of) the energy system — generally at the national level —, but hardly consider the policy process that steers this market or system, and even less the broader political context whose this system is part (e.g.: international level) and the sub-systems that compose it (e.g.: local level). They thus don't explore extensively neither the role of the different public and private actors in steering the energy transition, nor the interactions between different political-administrative levels. Yet, these issues are crucial, especially when steering the low-carbon transition as it involves complex entanglements between different levels of power and, within each level, many interplays between various actors whose values and interests differ (see section "2.1. Wicked nature of the low-carbon transition" of Chapter I).

The role of the political-administrative authorities in steering the energy transition is often described in a simplified way. Basically, a central authority, usually the government, devises and implements policies. By limiting the role of political-administrative authorities to regulating, STET models overlook other essential functions of the authorities, such as mediating conflicts or managing networks of stakeholders. Furthermore, as they consider that the energy transition is steered by a central authority, they don't acknowledge the various types of public actors. For instance, they don't consider the role of the diverse administrations or political parties, as well as the interactions between the different public actors. Yet, depending on the type of public actors involved, the output of the policy process may vary significantly, from success to policy failure (see Happaerts, 2013).

While the role of the different stakeholders in a specific market or (a part of) the energy system is quite well defined in STET models, their part in the policy process is most of the time completely omitted. Though, stakeholders influence to a greater or lesser extent the steering of the energy transition. Even in a hierarchical steering mode, the political-administrative authorities' room for manoeuvre is commonly limited by their reliance on stakeholders, whether they are their electorate to whom they must legitimize their actions or civil society organizations putting pressure on them.

Most of the STET models don't really address the issue of the locus of authority. By focusing on a specific level, generally the national one, these models don't pay attention to the division of competencies and the interactions between different political-administrative levels. Yet, since climate change is not limited to national borders and as the configuration of a low-carbon society often goes beyond the levers of public action available for national governments, mitigation policies will have to be implemented within several levels of power so that the coherence between the policies devised at different levels represents a real challenge (Geels & *al.*, 2016; Happaerts, 2013).

4.2.2. Absence of Vision

The review of STET models reveals that no long-term goal is expressed as a vision, here understood as "*desirable state in the future*" (Wiek & Iwaniec 2014, p. 497). Indeed, the goals correspond most of the time to long-term quantitative reduction targets for GHG emissions and/or energy consumption adopted by the government of the studied area. The STET models assess the feasibility of the quantitative target and sketch pathways towards it. Consequently, the futures described in the scenarios meet the reduction targets for GHG emissions and/or energy consumption (which is very important), but they are not necessarily desirable. There are indeed several possible futures low-carbon societies — more or less desirable for this or that actor — and it is important to define which society "we" want. Developing visions of the future we want is essential to give orientation (c.f.: where

to go) and guidance (c.f.: what to do) to the actors involved in the energy transition process (Quist & *al.*, 2011). In light of the crucial role of visioning to achieve the low-carbon transition, I believe that the absence of vision in STET models represents a major limit of the approach.

4.2.3. Technocentric Perspective on Energy Transition

I observe that the solutions envisaged for reducing GHG emissions are often restricted to technical innovations, leaving out behavioural and social changes. Only the BLUE-MLP and the Transition Lab Framework integrate social and behavioural changes as variables. The advent of a low-carbon society would be the result of a combination of different innovations ranging from purely technical innovations (e.g.: energy efficiency, electrification) to social (e.g.: car sharing, fab lab) and behavioural (e.g.: simple living, modal shift) ones. By not taking into consideration the latter, STET models ignore a whole range of options that could contribute to reducing GHG emission and implicitly suggest that technology provides all of the answers — which is, in my view, completely misleading.

4.2.4. Instrumental Understanding of the Policy Process

In STET models, the policy process is often understood in an instrumental / technocratic perspective where a central authority outside the system implement economic instruments, such as incentive taxes, subsidies or CO₂ emissions trading schemes, that will linearly entail behavioural changes among rational and fully informed agents. Most of the simulation tools are actually based on cost-benefit analysis assuming that prices are the main factors influencing agent's decisions and that, therefore, economic instruments aiming at altering the relative attractiveness of different technologies or behaviours should guide agents' choice towards more sustainability. Even if prices are of crucial importance in low-carbon transition, this kind of analysis is often based on too restrictive assumptions. Most of the time, cost-benefit analysis doesn't consider agent's irrationality, awareness of environmental issues, incomplete information, strategic behaviours, capabilities, rebound effects and uncertainties surrounding the evolution of energy prices (Geels & *al.*, 2016).

Some STET models are nevertheless based on more sophisticated approaches trying to display a more realistic representation of policy instruments and their impacts on agents' decisions. Through agent-based modelling techniques, several STET models, such as the ENGAGE DFR Module and the transition Lab Framework, intend to take into account the fact that agents are not fully rational, have imperfect information and act also in accordance with their own interests or ecological sensitivity. Other STET models using system dynamics techniques, the Struben's Alternative Fuel Vehicle (AFV) Model for instance, attempt to generate a more realistic representation of the diversity of agents' behaviour as well. Then, by distinguishing different groups of households according to their income, location (rural or urban) or tenure (tenants or homeowners), the REMG and IMAGE/TIMER, Charlier's Residential Sector Model, Res-IRF and IMACLIM-R and Yücel's Housing Stock Model try to grasp the various capabilities of agents to change their practices. Besides, the Res-IRF and IMACLIM-R assesses the direct rebound effect for space heating. Finally, a number of models integrate other types of policy instruments, such as regulations, support to scientific research, and development of service and infrastructure stimulating energy transition.

4.2.5. Non-Integration of Polity Dimensions as Variables

The last limit is related to some facets of governance, such as the institutionalization of the policy process and the steering mode (i.e.: *polity*), that are hardly ever included in STET models. While the first issue is not even mentioned, the second is implicit. Most of the models actually assume implicitly hierarchical steering modes, either top-down hierarchy where the government devises and implements policies that directly apply to private actors, or market-based mode of governance implying that government let the market solve a societal problem. Non-hierarchical steering modes such as networks and communities are, with one exception (i.e.: Transition Lab Framework), not

considered in STET models. Yet, it seems that grassroots innovations which consist in bottom-up solutions led by networks of activists and local communities (see Smith & *al.*, 2015), have a real potential to foster the low-carbon transition and should therefore be also included as an object of study.

5. Discussion

5.1. Factors that Might Explain the Failure of STET Models in Capturing the “Reality” of Governance

Overall, the literature review reveals a number of limits regarding the way STET models address governance. Some governance issues are hardly ever taken into consideration and those that are integrated in STET models are very often represented in an oversimplified way and/or not thoroughly explored. Several factors might help to explain the propensity of STET models not to capture the complexity of social dynamics. In this section, I discuss the two potential explanatory factors that appear to be the more important: the path dependence of scientific innovation and the substantial differences in epistemological and ontological foundations.

5.1.1. Path Dependence of Scientific Innovation

The path dependence of scientific innovation might contribute to explain the failure of STET models in capturing the “reality” of governance. This was also suggested as an explanatory factor by Wangel (2011a) who reached similar conclusions after analysing how backcasting studies for sustainable development explore governance issues. Scientific development is a path dependent process that is likely to generate lock-in in “non-optimal” research methods and practices (see Latour, 2003). This kind of mechanisms could contribute to explaining the lack of integration of governance issues in STET models. Apart from a few models explicitly based on transition or political theories, STET models stay deeply rooted in the modelling paradigm, which — so far — doesn’t usually integrate social issues as an object of study (Geels & *al.*, 2016; Schubert & *al.*, 2015; Turnheim & *al.*, 2015; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Despite a greater recognition of actor heterogeneity and a more sophisticated representation of agents’ behaviour, most STET models do indeed not differ significantly from “traditional” energy transition models in terms of approach or methodology (c.f.: cost-benefit analysis, agent-based models, dynamic modelling), but also regarding the way governance is comprehended. In both cases, the policy process is often understood in an instrumental / technocratic perspective where a central authority outside the system implement economic instruments that will linearly entail behavioural changes among rational and fully informed agents (Mercure & *al.*, 2016; Geels & *al.*, 2016; Turnheim & *al.*, 2015; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Such a linear understanding of governance is characteristic of the rational positivist philosophy of sciences within which modelling falls.

Furthermore, in the modelling paradigm, several practitioners continue to believe that scientists must be objective, free of value and external to the policy process. They acknowledge a continuum between scientists who are supposed to produce value neutral information and policy-makers who are the only ones allowed to take a stance on the societal problem (Voinov & *al.*, 2014). This could explain the fact that STET models don’t aim at developing visions of desirable futures or providing prescriptive analysis including recommendations on governance. The quest for objectivity might be one of the reasons why modelers generally resort to cost benefit analysis to analyse policy instruments and leave out the *politics* and *polity* dimensions that would require less “objective” analytical approaches.

The lack of attention to the entanglements between different levels of power could also be explained by path dependence of scientific innovation. It is actually a limit of both modelling and transition studies that is often mentioned in the literature: While modelling is acknowledged as focusing mainly on global or national level (Turnheim & *al.*, 2015), transition studies are criticized for insufficient attention to spatial perspective (Coenen & *al.*, 2012; Smith & *al.*, 2010). This also holds true for the over-representation of technical innovations compared to social and behavioural ones. There is indeed, in modelling and to a lesser extent in transition studies, a historical tendency to pay greater attention to technology-based solutions.

5.1.2. Substantial Differences in Ontological and Epistemological Foundations

All of that leads me to mention the second explanatory factor, namely, the substantial discrepancies in ontological and epistemological foundations between modelling and governance analyses. The failure of STET models in integrating governance could be explained by the fact that integrating social dimensions in models is merely impossible because of epistemological and ontological mismatch. As previously explained, different research paradigms co-exist (see section “2. Ontological and epistemological posture” of the Introduction). A research paradigm is here understood as *“the basic belief system or worldview that guides the investigator, not only in choices of method but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways”* (Guba & Lincoln 1994, p. 105). In other words, each research is guided by basic assumptions stemming from foundational philosophical presuppositions concerning aspects such as the nature of reality, what we can know about the reality and how this knowledge can be produced (Voros, 2007; Marsh & Furlong, 2002). Different foundational philosophical presuppositions lead to different views on governance (see Geels & al., 2016). While modelling falls within the positivist paradigm – which is dominant in natural sciences –, social sciences exploring governance are rarely based on the same ontological and epistemological foundations. This mismatch makes the development of models that would completely integrate governance issues as main variables and thus accurately represent socio-technical transition impossible. Several components of the energy transition, and more specifically social ones, could indeed never be modelled (Geels & al., 2016; Li & al., 2015; McDowall, 2014). This is summarized as follows by Geels & al.: *“An overarching super-integration of social sciences in integrated assessment models is unlikely. Some social science theories, which adhere to a positivist philosophy of science and work within a rational choice paradigm (for example, mainstream economics, operations research and some planning and management theories) may be integrated into integrated assessment models because of shared assumptions and methods. But other social science theories with different ontologies (for example, interpretivism, structuralism and conflict theories) and philosophies of science cannot feasibly be integrated into integrated assessment models. These other theories do, however, address important dimensions of low-carbon transitions, including power, conflict, discourse, learning and norms. We therefore argue that the analysis of low-carbon transitions should be based on a plurality of approaches, with bridges enabling dialogue and interaction, rather than seamless integration”* (Geels & al. 2016, p.4).

5.2. Combining Complementary Approaches to Explore the Governance of the Low-Carbon Transition

For the above-mentioned reasons, it is quite unlikely that integrated modelling approaches – however sophisticated – could enable to represent the social dynamics of low-carbon transition without omitting essential elements and risking missing crucial questions. Since a full integration of governance issues in models doesn’t seem possible, there remains to ask the question whether modelling and social sciences should be combined or employed separately. As mentioned in the introduction, I am in favour of the complementarity-based approach. I indeed believe that energy models when combined with complementary approaches, might improve their pertinence for informing decision makers or for enhancing the corpus of scientific knowledge in the field of transition studies. Such need for quantitative data regarding climate-energy matters has been highlighted through the interviews I carried out with actors involved in the long-term policy process of GHG-emissions’ mitigation in the Walloon Region (see Chapter III). In this last section, I discuss advantages of the complementarity-based approach compared to the pluralistic approach and present some methods that can be used to conduce iterations between modelling and complementary approaches to build low-carbon scenarios addressing governance issues.

5.2.1. Advantages of the Complementarity-Based Approach compared to the Pluralistic Approach

Modelling doesn't appear as an effective approach to capture the complexity of social dynamics, but in comparison with less formalized approaches, it presents a number of positive attributes (Holtz & al., 2015; McDowall, 2014; Söderholm & al., 2011; Alcamo, 2008). As mentioned in the introduction, quantitative analyses are needed when it comes to energy-related issues. I explained that low-carbon scenario analyses based on quantitative approaches are not only perceived as more policy-relevant, but also more consistent than purely qualitative scenario analyses. An exclusively qualitative analysis does indeed not allow to know if the scenarios developed reach the quantitative GHG reduction targets, are cost-effective, or even technically feasible (Robertson & al., 2017; Fortes & al., 2015, Söderholm & al., 2011). Modelling also has several extra advantages. It enables to grasp the dynamics of complex systems that human mind can hardly — or not — conceptualize, such as non-linear process, feedback loops and long-time horizon. Furthermore, when designing the model, the variables and the relations between them must be explicitly set out, which fosters dialogue between researchers and stakeholders participating in the foresight exercises. In turn, this clarification leaves little room for ambiguity. Another attribute of modelling is its ability to articulate in a structured way different pieces of knowledge. Finally, by playing with variables of the models, one can carry out experiments that would be impracticable in the field (Holtz & al., 2015). In light of the strengths and limits inherent in models, it sounds useful to combine them with complementary approaches to explore socio-technical transitions (Robertson & al., 2017; Geels & al., 2016; Turnheim & al., 2015; Fortes & al., 2015; McDowall, 2014; Trutnevyte & al., 2014; O' Mahony & al., 2013; Söderholm & al., 2011; Kowalski & al., 2009; Alcamo, 2008).

5.2.2. Complementarity-Based Approaches for Making Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios

The complementarity-based approach consists in conducting iterations between quantitative modelling and other approaches that allow to analyse social components of sustainable transition. The iterations are intended to offset the weakness specific to each approach and thus “*promise to enrich each of the approaches, while providing the basis for a more robust and complete analysis of sustainable transition pathways*” (Turnheim & al. 2015, p. 239). Several methods can be used to make such iterations between models and qualitative approaches.

Storyline and Simulation (SAS) Approach

The “storyline and simulation” (SAS) approach (see Alcamo, 2008) that consists in developing scenarios by conducting iterations between storytelling and modelling is an often-used complementarity-based approach. Basically, on the basis of a first draft of storylines outlined by the researchers and the stakeholders' panel, the model is adapted and then used to quantify the storylines. In turn, in light of the modelling outputs, inconsistent storylines are revised. Scenarios can also be enriched with new information generated by the model. Iterations between storytelling and modelling are carried out until the scenarios are perceived as complete and robust enough (Alcamo, 2008). The SAS approach thus mobilizes and combines the technical rigor of modelling as well as its capacity to assess the techno-economic feasibility with the ability of storytelling to account for social dynamics, to trigger creativity and to offer an accessible communication tool (McDowall, 2014; Trutnevyte & al., 2014; O' Mahony & al., 2013).

This kind of approach has already been used to build low-carbon scenarios by, *inter alia*, Fortes & al. (2014), McDowall (2014), Trutnevyte & al. (2014) and Robertson & al. (2017). The last two papers are

particularly interesting. As part of the “Realising Transition Pathways⁵⁰” project, the research consortium has developed and applied an innovative methodological framework which consists in linking energy transition storylines with multiple models. Yet, the most interesting thing is that the aforesaid storylines depict three modes of governance in the UK power system differing in respect of the actors leading the low-carbon transition: government, market or civil society. The three governance pathways, respectively named “Central coordination”, “Market rules” and “Thousand flowers”, were developed through stakeholder workshops and desk research on the basis of transition theories. Each storyline depicts in 5-7 pages the steering mode, the role of the different public and private actors in steering the low-carbon transition, the policy goals and instruments adopted, the interactions between political-administrative levels, the institutional changes, as well as the technical, social and behavioural solutions implemented to reduce GHG (Realising Transition Pathways, 2018; Foxon, 2013). They were “translated” into modelling assumptions. Eight pre-existing energy models covering different scopes ran with these assumptions with a view to verifying the consistency of the storylines. The storylines were then revised on the basis of the modelling output. This process was repeated iteratively (Trutnevyte & al., 2014; Robertson & al., 2017). The “Realising Transition Pathways” project thus contributes to developing innovative methodologies to combine storytelling and modelling, but also to integrate governance in low-carbon scenarios. More details about the project are provided in the general introduction of the thesis (see Section “1. Towards a Social Analysis of Low-Carbon Scenarios” of the Introduction).

Combining Modelling, Socio-Technical Transition Analysis and Initiative-Based Learning

Eventually, an alternative approach aiming at combining quantitative models with qualitative approaches to analyse social dimensions of sustainability transition and that is worth being mentioned is the one currently devised in the “PATHWAYS⁵¹” Project (PATHWAYS, 2018). The methodology proposed here consists in aligning (creation of a common problem formulation and concepts definition), bridging (exchange of information and data) and undertaking iterations between three different approaches: modelling, socio-technical transition analysis and initiative-based learning. The following approach is suggested. Firstly, the model produces a range of possible least-cost sustainability transition pathways. Afterwards, the socio-technical transition analysis and the initiative-based learning verify the social feasibility of the pathways. On the one hand, the socio-technical transition analysis could focus on the role of the different actors in fostering or hindering the sustainability transition. By studying concrete local projects, the initiative-based learning could, on the other hand, complete the analysis with insights on learning processes. On the basis of the results of these analyses, the model could be revised and used to develop more consistent pathways. Respective strengths and limits of the three approaches should thus complement each other to tackle the analytical challenges posed by the sustainability transition (Geels & al., 2016; Turnheim & al., 2015). The authors explain that “*each approach is a lens that generates only a partial understanding of sustainability transitions and their related challenges*” (Turnheim & al. 2015, p. 250). More specifically, this framework promises to provide policy relevant information concerning the governance issues (Geels & al., 2016).

We note, however, that the approaches developed in the “Realising Transition Pathways” and “PATHWAYS” projects, despite their ability to address different dimensions of governance, do not allow to develop visions, here understood as “*desirable state in the future*” (Wiek & Iwaniec 2014, p. 497). The aforesaid projects aim indeed at building exploratory scenarios, and not visionary (or normative) ones (see Dreborg, 2004). Yet, since visioning is essential to give orientation (c.f.: where to

⁵⁰ <http://www.bath.ac.uk/realisingtransitionpathways/>

⁵¹ <https://www.pathways-project.nl>

go) and guidance (c.f.: what to do) to the actors involved in the transition process (Quist & *al.*, 2011), I believe that designing and analysing visions of the future we want is a prerequisite for the sustainability transitions (Wiek & Iwaniec, 2014; Happaerts, 2013). In this context, I think that it would be relevant to elaborate a methodological framework combining backcasting — a largely employed visioning approach (see Quist, 2013) — with the previously mentioned approaches to develop low-carbon scenarios including dimensions of governance as variables. Besides the methodological challenges, one of the difficulties in devising such exercise would be to strike a balance between the complexity of the approach and the need to make it intelligible for policymakers. This sounds like a promising avenue for future research.

Conclusion to the Chapter

In light of the governance challenges posed by the low-carbon transition, it is more than ever necessary to design approaches to build low-carbon scenarios including governance issues as variables. This kind of approaches could indeed provide relevant information for policy-makers in quest of solutions to such a super-wicked problem as climate change. Through this last study, I intended to contribute to the discussion on the relations between quantitative models and social sciences which brings into opposition three approaches: the integrated, the complementarity-based and the pluralistic approaches. Positioning myself in favour of the complementarity-based approach, I aimed at consolidating the foundations of this approach. My hypothesis was that the approaches attempting to fully integrate social science concepts and theories into quantitative models-based analyses fail to capture the complexity of the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition and that, in that respect, complementarity-based approaches are more effective. With a view to confirming this hypothesis, I tried to highlight the inability of integrated modelling to effectively address governance issues. I carried out a critical review of fifteen socio-technical energy transition (STET) models. They correspond to “*formal quantitative energy models (...) [that capture] the elements of socio-technical transitions, including societal actors and the co-evolutionary nature of policy, technology and behaviour*” (Li & al. 2015, p. 291). I analysed if and how those integrated models make knowledge about governance through a framework allowing to assess the way they address the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance.

The analysis showed that while the *policy* dimension is explored in most of the STET models, the *politics* and *polity* dimensions are missing in almost all the simulation tools. Moreover, apart from a few models explicitly based on transition or political theories, I observed that most of STET models don't differ significantly from “traditional” energy transition models in terms of ontology (c.f.: rational choice), methodology (c.f.: cost-benefit analyses, agent-based models, dynamic modelling), and, by extension, regarding the way governance is understood and analysed. In that respect, I highlighted five limits of STET models in making knowledge about governance. Firstly, they face a problem of scope. The STET models tend to focus on a specific market or (a part of) the energy system — generally at the national level —, but hardly consider the policy process that steers this market or system, and even less the broader political context whose this system is part (e.g.: international level) and the sub-systems that compose it (e.g.: local level). They thus don't explore extensively neither the role of the different actors in steering the energy transition, nor the interactions between different political-administrative levels. Secondly, no long-term goal is expressed as a vision. Thirdly, the approaches envisaged for reducing GHG emissions are often restricted to technical innovations, leaving out social and behavioural changes. Fourthly, the policy process is often understood in an instrumental / technocratic perspective where a central authority outside the system implement economic instruments that will linearly entail behavioural changes among rational and fully informed agents. Fifthly, some facets of governance, such as the steering mode and the institutionalization of the policy process (i.e.: *polity*), are hardly ever included in STET models.

As have been illustrated through the review, some of these limits can be addressed with more sophisticated models. However, I believe that because of substantial discrepancies in ontological and epistemological foundations, several social dimensions of the low-carbon transition could never be accurately modelled. The point of this chapter was not to denigrate modelling. On the contrary, I consider that in comparison with less formalized approaches, energy models — and more specifically STET models that offer a greater recognition of actors' heterogeneity and a more sophisticated representation of agents' behaviour — present a number of positive attributes and provide a part of the answer to the question of the low-carbon transition. In this context, I argued in favour of the complementarity-based approach to offset the weakness specific to models and purely qualitative approaches. I indeed think that energy models when combined with complementary approaches, such as transition theories, initiative-based learning, storytelling or visioning, should better capture the socio-technical nature of the low-carbon transition. In turn, the low-carbon scenarios resulting from

this kind of foresight exercise might be more consistent and perceived as more relevant by policy-makers. Combining different approaches remaining a methodological challenge, a timely avenue for research would be to develop and test such complementarity-based approaches.

CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION

1. Key Contributions of the Research

With a view to achieving the 2°C objective anchored in the Paris Agreement, the global GHG emissions will have to be reduced by around 40-70% by 2050 compared to 2010 level. This drastic reduction in GHG emissions should lead to emissions levels near zero or below by the end of the century (IPCC, 2014a). The pathway towards a less carbon intensive society is generally referred to as **low-carbon transition**. Since GHG are emitted through everyday acts of production and consumption, the low-carbon transition requires societies to completely rethink their transportation, housing, industry, energy production, and food systems. Such transition should result in a society that is radically different from the present in numerous aspects, including technology, infrastructures, every day practices, societal organization and governance (Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Foxon & *al.* 2013). This is related to the **co-evolving relation between society and technology** (Foxon & *al.*, 2010; Geels, 2004; Weber, 2003). Technological systems are indeed *“both socially constructed and society shaping”* (Hughes 1987, p. 45).

To engage in the low-carbon transition, the European Union, many states and various subnational governments have started to set GHG reduction targets, to draw up roadmaps and to implement climate mitigation policies. However, despite the increasing number of climate mitigation policies since the institutionalization of climate change problem in the 90’s, the global GHG emissions have continued to increase (Aykut & Dahan, 2016). This is a symptom of the challenging nature of the low-carbon transition. Climate change can actually be seen as a **super-wicked problem** involving complex interconnections of multiple causes, effects and actors whose values and interests differ (Rittel & Webber, 1973). For several authors, such highly complex problems cannot be addressed with traditional forms of knowledge production and modes of governance (Wright & *al.*, 2018; Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Batie, 2008; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004; Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994). Both normal science and classic top down modes of governance are often perceived as obsolete when facing super-wicked problems. Against that background, many consider that **alternative approaches are required for knowing and governing super-wicked problems** (Head, 2014; Turnpenny & *al.*, 2009; Koppenjan & Klijn, 2004).

A number of scholars – whose view I share – consider that super-wicked problems need to be addressed with multidisciplinary mode of knowledge production embracing their inherent multidimensionality, non-linearity, unpredictability, uncertainty, and conflicting values (Head, 2014; Batie 2008). Foresight meet all these desirable attributes and is therefore often claimed as a suitable approach for tackling this type of problems (Pérez-Soba & Maas, 2015; Head, 2014; Ho, 2012; Kok & *al.*, 2011; Fobé & Brans, 2013; Sardar, 2010; Marien, 2010; Levin & *al.* 2009; Kosow & Gaßner 2008; Mulder, 2007). For this reason, scenario approach is frequently used for envisioning and exploring alternative images of low-carbon future as well as transition pathways to reach those futures. Over the last few years, **low-carbon scenario** analyses have flourished (Miller & *al.*, 2015; Robertson & *al.*, 2017; Torrie & *al.*, 2013; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Those analyses are intended to help policy-makers navigate the maelstrom of confusion and conflicts associated with the problem of climate change. Foresight is indeed by its very nature a decision support tool (Ramos, 2006; De Smedt, 2006; Aligica, 2005; Mermert, 2005; Lévêque & Urien 2005). This non-predictive future-oriented approach has the potential to help decision-makers to react to anticipated changes (i.e.: “preactivity”) and to act with a view to achieving desired changes (i.e.: “proactivity”) (Godet, 2004).

In order to be perceived as relevant by policy-makers, several authors consider that **low-carbon scenarios must include governance dimensions as variables** (Li & *al.*, 2016 ; Olsson & *al.*, 2015; Fortes & *al.*, 2015; Schubert & *al.*, 2015; Miller & *al.*, 2015; Kalnins & *al.*, 2014; Foxon, 2013; Hughes, 2013; O’

Mahony & *al.*, 2013; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Svenfelt & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Hughes & Strachan, 2010; Foxon & *al.*, 2010). They say that low-carbon scenarios should not only represent in a clear and structured manner the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance, but also embrace the co-evolving nature of technology and society (Li & *al.*, 2016; Hughes & Strachan, 2010). Such scenarios would enable to capture the socio-technical essence of the low-carbon transition (Li & *al.*, 2016; Wangel, 2011a). Moreover, in light of the limits of traditional modes of governance for addressing the low-carbon transition, many reckon that governance needs to be considered in scenario analyses as an object of (fundamental) change, in the same way as the modes of energy production and consumption (Kiraly & *al.*, 2013; Wangel, 2011a; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011). Low-carbon scenarios should indeed explore the functioning and the performance of alternative modes of governance, but also how those “new” steering modes emerge, diffuse and scale up (Wangel, 2012; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011).

By reviewing the scenario literature published over the past few years, we observe significant methodological developments, in particular at the level of the calculus or data-sets. Such contributions have generated an increasing technical sophistication of scenario building methods. All this contrasts with the relative **absence of social sciences research on scenarios** (Kaljonen & *al.*, 2012; Volkery & Ribeiro, 2009; Garb & *al.*, 2008; De Smedt, 2006). It appears that scenario analyses have received little academic attention from social sciences, whether they are political science, sociology, philosophy of science or science and technology studies (STS). Yet, scenario analysis being, in essence, a social activity, social sciences scholars should consider it as an object of study (Garb & *al.*, 2008). Various issues could be addressed under a social scientific perspective on scenarios: *“there is the disciplinary linking of those that study social, technological, and biophysical systems; there are the epistemic questions regarding the coupling of more subjectively and intuitively produced storylines with the apparently objective enterprise of quantitative modeling; there are questions related to how the scientific and policy communities respond differently to the indeterminacy of the future versus the determinism of the models used; and there are questions of the intended and actual users and uses of scenario products and their linkage to policy”* (Garb & *al.* 2008, p. 2).

The present thesis intends to bridge this research gap by providing an **empirical contribution to social sciences research on scenarios**. Scenarios are here understood as **“boundary objects”** (see Star and Griesemer, 1989) **linking different social worlds** (van der Steen & *al.*, 2013; Garb & *al.*, 2008; Hulme & Dessai, 2008). In this research, two linkages have been considered, starting with the link between **science and policy**. As previously explained, foresight is by definition an orientation and decision support tool. Both scenarios products and processes are designed to contribute – directly or indirectly – to policy-making in environment with high uncertainties and conflicting stakes (Ramos, 2006; De Smedt, 2006; Aligica, 2005; Mermet, 2005; Lévêque & Urien, 2005). The second linkage is the disciplinary linking. Since scenario analysis is an interdisciplinary approach addressing technical and social aspects of a problem in a systemic and holistic way, it aims at linking **natural and social sciences** (Petit Jean, 2016; Godet & Durance, 2011; Garb & *al.* 2008; de Jouvenel, 1999). This thesis aspires to create an enhanced understanding on **how scenario analyses perform such “boundary work”** (see Jasanoff, 1990).

More specifically, the following social analysis of low-carbon scenarios is based on a twofold perspective focusing: on the one hand, on the **interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance (i.e.: link between science and policy)**, and, on the other hand, on the **making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios (i.e.: link between natural and social sciences)**. In other words, this analysis explored “scenarios in governance” and “governance in scenarios”. This twofold perspective on scenarios for knowing and governing low-carbon transition is illustrated in the figure below [Figure 96].

Figure 96. Overview of the research

The social analysis of low-carbon scenarios has been carried out through **three research axes, each based on its particular empirics.**

Interactions between Low-Carbon Scenarios and Governance: A Multiple Case Study (Chapter III)

The first empirical study aimed at exploring the role of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making on the basis of conceptual frameworks and methodological tools developed in the knowledge utilization literature. It consisted in a multiple case study analysing the role in policy-making of four energy foresight studies carried out for the Walloon Region (Belgium). The studies analysed are the following: “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050” (CLIMACT, 2012), “Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050” (CLIMACT & VITO, 2013), “Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050” (VITO & *al.*, 2012) and “Prospective study: Energy transition” (CLIMACT & *al.*, 2015). The analysis has been carried out on the basis of an analytical framework developed in the knowledge utilization literature (see Gudmunson & *al.*, 2009). This framework considers five types of knowledge role in policy-making, namely instrumental, conceptual, political, process and distortive roles. The exploration of the use and influence of low-carbon scenarios in policy-making is based on documentary analysis and 74 semi-structured interviews with the actors involved in the long-term climate mitigation policy in Wallonia. Those actors are political authorities, political advisors, administrative authorities, employers’ federations, workers’ unions, environmental and development NGOs, advisory councils, energy market operators, public transport operators, public research institutes, consultancy agencies and universities. The important empirical material collected was analysed with the method of thematic coding. After exploring the role in policy-making and the level of appropriation per actor for each of the four foresight studies, I have conducted a cross-case analysis in order to highlight the similarities and differences between the four studies.

The cross-case analysis revealed that the role in policy-making varies strongly from one foresight study to another. However, few examples of purely instrumental use of studies as orientation and decision support tools to devise mitigation policies have been noted. Studies are rather used to justify decisions already taken or to improve someone’s relative position in the policy systems compared to opponents (i.e.: political role). Studies also contribute to expand the knowledge base and introduce new ideas or concepts in policy (i.e.: conceptual role). Moreover, even if none of the analysed studies rest on real exercise of scenarios co-construction, some studies still have a process role. The implementation gap

between low-carbon scenarios and policy is not surprising since the relationship between sciences and policy is neither linear, nor mechanical – the vision of a rational knowledge-based policy-making model being rather naïve. The purely instrumental use of scientific knowledge in policy-making is generally quite limited, especially in highly politicized context like Belgium. Instead, knowledge usually has a more diffuse and indirect influence on policy-making – i.e.: conceptual and process roles. That said, in the present research, such conceptual and process roles were observed among nearly all the actors, excepted for political authorities. The cross-case analysis actually showed that the level of appropriation of foresight studies varies greatly from one actor to another, and that the public actors within administrations seem to be more permeable to the investigated foreknowledge, whereas, on the contrary, political authorities mark little interest in the scenario exercises. Finally, the cross-case analysis suggested that a specific constellation of factors contributes in explaining the (non-)use and influence of each study. That being said, it seems that the particular characteristics of each study affect less the role of the studies in policy-making than external factors such as the governance setting.

The last section of this chapter focused more specifically on the factors that can contribute to explain the very low level of appropriation of low-carbon scenarios by political authorities. In this discussion, I demonstrated that the low levels of interest of political authorities in low-carbon scenarios might be related to the very nature of both foresight and climate mitigation governance. On the one hand, I highlighted a mismatch between foresight and policy-making that makes the integration of foresight in political practices difficult – if not impossible. However, in light of the need for modes of knowledge production like foresight to address super-wicked problems such as climate change, I think that it is necessary to forge the link between scenario approached and policy. I presented the development of process-oriented foresight as a potential way to forge that link, emphasizing the need for further empirical research to better understanding the process role of scenario analyses. On the other hand, I pointed out a number of challenges inherent to climate mitigation governance that lead to political inertia. This political inertia, together with the decreasing political authorities' room for maneuver as times passes, led me to question the capacity of public authorities to steer the low-carbon transition. In that context, I introduced the concepts of “transition in catastrophe” (Semal, 2017) and “transformations” (Stirling, 2014) as wiser and more realistic approaches compared to the widespread notion of transition, which implicitly assumes that the shift towards a low-carbon society can be perfectly controlled.

Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios: A Needs Assessment (Chapter IV)

The objective of this second empirical study was to provide an assessment of the need for knowledge about the governance of the low-carbon transition. More specifically, such assessment aimed at identifying and comparing the perceptions of different actors of the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition. Just like in Chapter III, the actors are those involved in the long-term policy process of GHG-emissions' mitigation in the Walloon Region (Belgium). The needs assessment is carried out with a Q methodology, that is a qualitative but statistically supported method which allows understanding the variety of discourses around a given topic (see Barry & Proops, 1990). As part of the Q-survey, 54 participants sorted a set of potential research questions covering the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance according to their relevance to devise mitigation policies. A principal component analysis of the data led to the identification of three factors that are ideal-typical versions of the way to perceive the subject of study shared by a number of participants. Those are the *reformists*, the *revolutionists* and the *incumbents*.

The analysis of the similarities and differences between the factors allowed to highlight the areas of consensus and the terms of the debate concerning the need for knowledge about governance to steer the low-carbon transition. Regarding the areas of consensus, it has been observed that with a few exceptions, most of the actors consider that the questions of the policy instruments should be the subject of a study. They indeed state that knowledge regarding the policy instruments to be

implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society are needed. On the contrary, some issues are globally perceived as of little relevance. This is the case for the question of the representation of the non-human beings in the policy process, and, to a lesser extent, the question of the role of the different actors in the low-carbon transition (i.e.: *politics*). The later finding contrasts with the opinion of several authors who claim that low-carbon scenarios should explore the roles of different actors in influencing the transition pathways. This points out a mismatch between what scientists and political actors might consider relevant knowledge. The other issues correspond to the terms of the debate. They are perceived as policy-relevant by some actors, but irrelevant by others. Each factor embodies a specific discourse. The *reformists* – that comprise a major segment of members from public administrations – consider the questions related to the *policy* dimension of governance as the most policy-relevant. It includes the questions of the policy instruments to be implemented with a view to building a low-carbon society, but also the issues of the vision of the low-carbon society in 2050 and the policy goals to be set for the different sectors / levels of power in order to reach this vision. The distinct interest of the *reformists* for such operational questions contrasts with the cluster of issues considered as the most policy-relevant by the *revolutionists*. While the *reformists* request knowledge on the objectives and policies to be adopted with a view to reaching a desirable low-carbon vision whilst remaining within the existing institutional framework, the *revolutionists* are interested in understanding how to rethink this framework. They highlight the limitations of current governance structures as well as the need to develop local and community-based governance to foster the low-carbon transition. For them, the most relevant issues concern the *polity* dimension of governance. *In fine*, the *incumbents* are interested in questions that directly affect them. For those persons that represent the interests of dominant actors of the current high carbon regime, the most policy-relevant issues concern the way to develop an incumbent-sensitive climate mitigation policy. The considerable variations regarding the perception of the policy-relevance of possible research questions combined with the potential mismatch between what scientists and political actors might consider relevant knowledge led me to emphasize the need to co-construct the research problem with the intended users of a study.

The study was also quite original from a methodological point of view. I indeed carried out a Q survey combining forced and free distributions. The underlying idea was to address the limits of forced distribution that I have experienced when I carried out a first Q survey as part of my master thesis – i.e.: the frustrations that participants may feel when they are forced to assign ratings that don't correspond to their view, and the distortion of the participants' views potentially generated by the sorting of the items in the pyramid-shaped grid. It has been observed that the free distribution has successfully offset the limits of the forced distribution. I therefore recommend this approach for the researchers who have to carry out a Q survey based on forced distribution (because the item order is more important than scale separation), but who consider the above-mentioned limits of the pyramid-shaped ranking grid as a problem. Finally, the comparison of the results obtained with forced and free distribution are similar. The conclusions we could draw after analysing the data obtained with the two types of distribution are indeed almost the same. This “double check” thus enhanced the robustness of the results of the statistical analysis of the Q set.

Making of Knowledge about Governance in Low-Carbon Scenarios: A Critical Review of Socio-Technical Energy Transition Models (Chapter V)

Through this last study, I intended to contribute to the discussion on the relations between quantitative models and social sciences which brings into opposition three approaches: the integrated, the complementarity-based and the pluralistic approaches. Positioning myself in favour of the complementarity-based approach, I aimed at consolidating the foundations of this approach. My hypothesis was that the approaches attempting to fully integrate social science concepts and theories into quantitative models-based analyses fail to capture the complexity of the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition and that, in that respect, complementarity-based approaches are more effective. With a view to confirming this hypothesis, I tried to highlight the inability of integrated

modelling to effectively address governance issues. I carried out a critical review of fifteen socio-technical energy transition (STET) models. They correspond to “*formal quantitative energy models (...) [that capture] the elements of socio-technical transitions, including societal actors and the co-evolutionary nature of policy, technology and behaviour*” (Li & al. 2015, p. 291). I analysed if and how those integrated models make knowledge about governance through a framework allowing to assess the way they address the *policy*, *politics* and *polity* dimensions of governance.

The analysis showed that while the *policy* dimension is explored in most of the STET models, the *politics* and *polity* dimensions are missing in almost all the simulation tools. Moreover, apart from a few models explicitly based on transition or political theories, I observed that most of STET models don't differ significantly from “traditional” energy transition models in terms of ontology (c.f.: rational choice), methodology (c.f.: cost-benefit analyses, agent-based models, dynamic modelling), and, by extension, regarding the way governance is understood and analysed. In that respect, I highlighted five limits of STET models in making knowledge about governance. Firstly, they face a problem of scope. The STET models tend to focus on a specific market or (a part of) the energy system — generally at the national level —, but hardly consider the policy process that steers this market or system, and even less the broader political context whose this system is part (e.g.: international level) and the sub-systems that compose it (e.g.: local level). They thus don't explore extensively neither the role of the different actors in steering the energy transition, nor the interactions between different political-administrative levels. Secondly, no long-term goal is expressed as a vision. Thirdly, the approaches envisaged for reducing GHG emissions are often restricted to technical innovations, leaving out social and behavioural changes. Fourthly, the policy process is often understood in an instrumental / technocratic perspective where a central authority outside the system implement economic instruments that will linearly entail behavioural changes among rational and fully informed agents. Fifthly, some facets of governance, such as the steering mode and the institutionalization of the policy process (i.e.: *polity*), are hardly ever included in STET models.

As have been illustrated through the review, some of these limits can be addressed with more sophisticated models. However, I believe that because of substantial discrepancies in ontological and epistemological foundations, several social dimensions of the low-carbon transition could never be accurately modelled. The point of this chapter was not to denigrate modelling. On the contrary, I consider that in comparison with less formalized approaches, energy models — and more specifically STET models that offer a greater recognition of actors' heterogeneity and a more sophisticated representation of agents' behaviour — present a number of positive attributes and provide a part of the answer to the question of the low-carbon transition. In this context, I argued in favour of the complementarity-based approach to offset the weakness specific to models and purely qualitative approaches. I indeed think that energy models when combined with complementary approaches, such as transition theories, initiative-based learning, storytelling or visioning, could better capture the socio-technical nature of the low-carbon transition. In turn, the low-carbon scenarios resulting from this kind of foresight exercise might be more consistent and perceived as more relevant by policy-makers. Combining different approaches remaining a methodological challenge, a timely avenue for research would be to develop and test such complementarity-based approaches.

Returning to the initial question of the thesis – i.e.: how do scenario analyses perform the linkage between different social worlds? – **what are the key finding and lessons emerging from those empirical studies? What are their implications for knowing and governing super-wicked problems like climate change?**

If one first looks at how **scenario analyses** link science and policy, one observes that the results of those analyses **are hardly ever used to support the formulation of policy**. This finding is not surprising. A persistent gap between science and policy – which is not specific to foresight – has been highlighted through a significant body of empirical research in the field of knowledge utilization. The model according to which policy-makers facing with uncertainty use scientific knowledge to identify and select appropriate solutions to solve a problem has indeed scarcely been empirically observed (Fobé

& Brans, 2013; Bauler, 2012; Gudmundsson & al., 2009; Hezri & Dovers, 2006; Weiss & al., 2005; Henry & Mark, 2003; Weiss, 1978). The little use of science-based artefacts for policy-making is related to the fact that the policy process is guided by many factors, including power relations, organizational procedures (Van der Steen & van Twist, 2012) as well as contrasted worldviews amongst actors. The linear rational knowledge-based policy-making model is all the more far from empirical reality when it comes to (super-)wicked problems like climate change. The idea that new knowledge leads to less uncertainty, which in turn leads to “appropriate” decisions does indeed not apply to (super-)wicked problems because of their inherent irreducible uncertainties and high stakes (Batie, 2008). New scientific findings often highlight new problems, new risks and new uncertainties (see Beck, 2008). **Despite the obvious limits of the linear rational knowledge-based policy-making model for knowing and governing (super-)wicked problems, this conception of the relation between science and policy still seems to be dominant, in both the political and the scientific world.** When they are facing uncertainties, the standard response of political actors consists in calling experts to bridge the knowledge gap. The need for “evidence-based” decision making appears as a virtually unchallenged mantra in climate – and more broadly environmental – governance. The call for evidence-based policy has led to the emergence of scientific institutions like the IPCC and the proliferation of studies in the field of climate change. Despite the accumulation of scientific knowledge about the problem of climate change and the solutions that could be applied to mitigate it, the measures that could enable to efficiently limit global warming have not been implemented and global GHG emissions continue to increase. In view of this, many political actors and scientists are surprised and upset that all this knowledge is not used to design ambitious mitigation policies. To me, the dominance of the linear rational knowledge-based policy-making model for addressing the problem of climate change is closely related to the **widespread idea that the transition towards a low-carbon society can be controlled**, which is, in my view, misleading. As previously mentioned, the limits associated with the idea of intended human control over the planet system are further discussed by Luc Semal (2017) and Andy Stirling (2014).

The little evidence of using the results of scenario analyses as the direct basis for decisions does not mean, however, that they do not contribute to policy-making. The empirical study highlighted that scenario products and processes can potentially contribute to expand the knowledge base and introduce new ideas or concepts in policy. In this way, scenarios can potentially contribute to the development of what Sheila Jasanoff (2015) refers to as “**sociotechnical imaginaries**” that are “*collectively held, institutionally stabilized, and publicly performed visions of desirable futures, animated by shared understandings of forms of social life and social order attainable through, and supportive of, advances in science and technology*” (Jasanoff 2015, p.4). By envisioning and exploring alternative desirable futures, foresight is, in my view, a potentially powerful approach for facilitating the emergence of sociotechnical imaginaries. According to Jasanoff (2015), imagination is “*a crucial reservoir of power and action*” (Jasanoff 2015, p.17). Collective visions of desirable futures can generate what François Jullien (2010) calls “**silent transformations**” that is a transition resulting from a long and slow accumulation of tiny gradual invisible changes. To me, **this is through various silent transformations that the transition towards a low-carbon society could happen** – and not through control. The mechanisms through which sociotechnical imaginaries emerge, gain stability and become transformative are complex and haven’t been analysed as part of this research. Some frameworks developed in STS literature like the coproduction idiom (see Jasanoff, 2004) or the actor network theory (see Latour, 1990) could help in understanding such mechanisms. Analysing how disruptive visions imagined as part of scenario analysis are translated into performative collective imaginaries of desirable futures constitutes a relevant avenue for research.

Considering the second focal point of the research, i.e.: how scenario analyses link natural science and social sciences, one observes that **low-carbon scenarios rarely achieve the disciplinary linking**. Despite the multitude of calls for interdisciplinarity in the field of climate science, social science approaches are rarely mobilized to envision and explore low-carbon futures. Low-carbon scenarios are most of the time the outputs of quantitative models which allow analysing the technical and

behavioural changes in producing and consuming energy required to reduce GHG as well as the costs associated with those transition pathways (Li & *al.*, 2016; Fortes & *al.*, 2015; Schubert & *al.*, 2015; Miller & *al.*, 2015; Király & *al.*, 2013; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Svenfelt & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Hughes & Strachan, 2010; Foxon & *al.*, 2010). These types of scenarios provide a high level of detail for the technical and economic dimensions, but do not or hardly address the social changes required to mitigate climate change. The society, the policy and the culture are indeed rarely considered as object of change in low-carbon scenarios. A number of integrated assessments attempted to provide more comprehensive analysis of the low-carbon transition. However, the analysis of STET models revealed the limits of the integrated approaches in addressing the social dynamics involved in the low-carbon transition. According to Mike Hulme (2011), the **asymmetrical incorporation of technological and social change into future-oriented analyses of climate change** results from the rise of a powerful epistemic community of earth system modellers in climate change studies combined with the lack of theory-making about the interactions between climate and society. The limited consideration of the social dimensions of climate-energy issues is not unique to scenario analyses. In climate change studies, social sciences (except for economy) are globally under-represented and analyses bridging natural and human sciences are rare (Holm & Winiwarter 2017; Miller & *al.*, 2015; Holm & *al.*, 2013). Yet, in light of the co-evolving relation between society and technology (Foxon & *al.*, 2010; Geels, 2004; Weber, 2003), **the society needs to be considered as an object of (fundamental) change – in the same way as technology – when addressing climate change.**

Against that background, the problem of climate change could be framed as a “**socio-technical controversy**” as defined by Michel Callon, Pierre Lascoumes et Yannick Barthe (2001). According to the authors – whose view echoes a number of the above-mentioned elements – those controversies involving social and technical uncertainties cannot be addressed with traditional top-down technocratic approaches, and call for alternative forms of knowledge productions and modes of governance. They argue for deepening democracy through what they call “**dialogic democracy**”. This alternative mode of democracy that is based on mutual learning processes aims at expanding the debate on technical issues beyond traditional actors (technical experts, politico-administrative authorities, organized civil society), by enrolling new kinds of expertise such as the expertise of ordinary users of techniques, and more broadly every actors concerned by the issue at stake. By promoting a re-appropriation of technical questions by the actors that are concerned by them, Callon et *al.* (2001) thus intend to deconstruct the established boundaries between experts and profanes, and policy and citizens. The authors’ proposal of “**democratizing democracy**”, i.e. widening the set of expertise involved in policy processes about technical issues, appears to me as a promising way for knowing and governing (super-)wicked problems like climate change. As previously explained, problems involving deep uncertainties and dissents could greatly benefit from including citizens in the reflexion on how to tackle them. Citizen participation could facilitate the policy implementation and enable changes, but also lead to the definition of “better” solutions to (super-)wicked problems. Participatory approaches benefit from the so-called “**wisdom of crowds**” (see Surowiecki, 2008), that is the ability of heterogeneous groups – that are often profane in one area – to offer “better” solutions to a given problem than individual experts. With a view to supporting the dialogic democracy, Callon et *al.* (2001), argue in favour of “**hybrid forums**” that are places for dialogue and debate for heterogenous actors concerned by the issue at stake. I will close this conclusion by positioning **process-oriented foresight as a tool that could be mobilized in hybrid forums**. Envisioning and exploring alternative visions of desirable low-carbon futures in forums gathering the various actors concerned by the question could indeed contribute to the development of rich “sociotechnical imaginaries” that could support the “silent transformations” required to reach a low-carbon society.

2. Avenues for Future Research

By exploring through these three studies the interactions between low-carbon scenarios and governance and the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios, this thesis has provided an empirical contribution to social sciences research on scenarios. It enabled to create an enhanced understanding on how scenario analyses perform (or not) their “boundary work” in linking science and policy as well as natural and social sciences. However, the present thesis is just one small piece in the puzzle. The social science research on scenarios is an extremely wide area of study that has yet to be developed. So many facets of scenarios as social objects need to be investigated, creating an exciting and promising research agenda. This last point of the thesis defines a number of avenues for future research.

As previously mentioned, process-oriented scenario analyses are claimed as having a great potential for facilitating policy implementation and enabling changes. Many authors highlight the benefits of participatory foresight processes, like contributing to collective learning, constructing a common cognitive frame of reference, promoting empowerment, developing a network of actors, fostering dialogue and opinion exchange among different actors, enabling engagement and participation of stakeholders in the policy-process, creating negotiation spaces helping to the construction of consensus among stakeholders, or building a common future vision and a shared sense of commitment (Miller & *al.*, 2015; Gunnarsson-Östling & *al.*, 2012; Rijkens-Klomp, 2012; Quist & *al.*, 2011; Wangel, 2011a; Svenfelt, 2010; Habegger, 2010; Da Costal & *al.*, 2008; Garb & *al.*, 2008; de Smedt, 2006; Georghiou & Keenan, 2006; Paillard, 2006; Lévêque & Urien, 2005). However, such process role hasn’t been thoroughly explored so far. **Empirical investigations on the influence of process-oriented scenario analyses** thus constitutes a first avenue for future research. More particularly, I think that it would be extremely interesting to consider process-oriented scenario analyses involving political authorities and/or citizens.

In the present thesis, I studied the policy use and influence of low-carbon scenario analyses in the Walloon Region. Additional **empirical studies on the role of scenario analyses in other contexts** are obviously needed, inasmuch as the role of science-based artefacts depends strongly on the social context within which they are embedded (i.e.: coproduction (Jasanoff, 2004)). As previously explained, Wallonia has a very limited culture of foresight. It would therefore be interesting to explore the role of scenario analyses in political system with higher level of institutionalization of foresight practice, like Sweden, Finland, The Netherlands or the United Kingdom. The role of scenarios products and processes can also vary depending on the level to which the foresight exercise applies. A foresight exercise will probably not have the same impact if it is carried out at the local or at the global level. In light of the strong development of subnational actions in climate governance, I think it would be worthwhile to examine the role of scenario analyses carried out at a more local level. Moreover, the study presented as part of this thesis focused on low-carbon scenarios commissioned by public authorities. Yet, I demonstrated that many NGOs, employers’ federations, or big companies develop their own low-carbon scenarios. The use and influence of such private initiatives deserve further attention. *In fine*, I showed that climate change policy is a domain marked by profound inertia, which reduces the likelihood of low-carbon scenarios to be used as a support to design policy – since it is politically difficult to implement the policy recommendations of scenario analyses. In that context, that would be relevant to explore the impacts of scenarios carried out for other policy domains.

The role of foresight can vary according to the social context within which it is embedded, but also depending on time. The impacts of a scenario analysis after five years might not be the same than the impacts after ten years or more. By envisioning and exploring alternative futures, scenarios can contribute to plant the seeds of change in the minds of the actors, but attitude and behaviour changes might become visible only in the longer run. The more disruptive the change is, the more it might take time to materialize. To me, a “good” scenario exercise has to consider disruptive changes. In the present research, I analysed in 2017 the role of foresight studies published between 2012 and 2015.

The research therefore considers the impacts of scenario analyses in a quite short term. **Empirical studies exploring the impact of scenario analyses in the longer term** could be extremely valuable.

The study on the role of scenarios in policy-making is based on concepts and methods developed in the knowledge utilization literatures. Many other research areas in the field of social sciences consider science-based artefacts as object of study. As previously explained, the discussion of scenarios as social objects has so to speak not entered the mainstream debates in social sciences. This opens the door to a host of new possibilities for exploring the social “role” of scenarios through other lens than the one adopted in this study. **The social “work” of scenarios could be investigated through many different perspectives, like the theories of “actor–network”** (see Akrich & *al.*, 2006), **“coproduction”** (see Jasanoff, 2004), **“epistemic communities”** (see Haas, 1990) or **“boundary objects”** (see Jasanoff, 1990; Star & Griesemer 1989) (see Garb & *al.*, 2008).

The discussions on the observed implementation gap between low-carbon scenarios and policy-making led to the conclusion that the link between scenario approach and policy need to be forged. Further works are therefore required to understand, on the one hand, **how to improve foresight practice in order to increase its impact on policy-making**, and, on the other hand, **how to reconfigure policy-making or resolve moral impediments to foresight use in order to create a governance system more permeable to foresight**. In this respect, theoretical investigations, but also applied research testing different potential solutions are needed.

For its part, the research on the making of knowledge about governance in low-carbon scenarios highlighted the advantages of the complementarity-based approach compared to the integrated and the pluralistic approaches. This approach based on iterations between quantitative modelling and qualitative analyses enables *“to enrich each of the approaches, while providing the basis for a more robust and complete analysis of sustainable transition pathways”* (Turnheim & *al.* 2015, p. 239). However, developing such approach for exploring low-carbon pathways presents significant methodological challenges – which explains the under-representation of complementarity-based compared to integrated and pluralistic ones. Against that background, a major avenue for future research is to **develop and test complementarity-based approaches for envisioning and exploring low-carbon futures**.

In fine, the present thesis pointed out a **knowledge gap regarding the governance of the low-carbon transition**. As previously explained, the low-carbon transition requires to deeply rethink, reshape and reform governance (Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Termeer & *al.*, 2016; Jordan & *al.*, 2015; Urpelainen, 2013; Kunchornrat’ & Phdungsilp 2012; Montini, 2011; Nilsson & *al.*, 2011; Söderholm & *al.*, 2011; Foxon & *al.*, 2009; Boulanger, 2008). This thesis has also demonstrated the presence of “new” modes of governance involving innovative policy instruments and various initiatives led by an increasing number of private actors, subnational governments and transnational networks. Even if the presence of such “new” forms of governance for addressing climate change has been empirically demonstrated by many authors, we don’t know much about the emergence, the functioning, the performance and the diffusion of these steering modes (Sovacool and Van de Graaf, 2018; Bernstein & Hoffman, 2018; Jordan & *al.*, 2015; Meckling & *al.*, 2015; Bulkeley & *al.*, 2014; Hoffmann, 2011). This raises a number of questions for potential futures research on climate governance: How and why do various private and subnational actors start to act in favour of the low-carbon transition? How and why do “new” policy instruments emerge? Through which mechanisms are such “new” modes of governance maintained, diffusing and scaling up? What is the role of public actors in maintaining, diffusing and scaling up them? How can these modes of governance generate and accelerate the low-carbon transition? Are they filling the gap left by the weakness of traditional modes of governance? How do various modes of governance interact with each other? What are the strengths, weakness, opportunities and threats inherent in these different modes of governance? Which alternative is the best regarding this or that criteria?

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APPENDIXES

APPENDIXES

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Appendix 2. Interview Guide

Clarification before Starting

- You are invited to speak personally.
- The interview is anonymous: your name and your organization name will not be mentioned.

Introduction

- What is your definition of foresight (“la prospective”)? [to avoid confusion with forecast (“prévisions / projections”)]
- Are you familiarized with foresight?
- Do you use foresight in your organization? Among all the decision support tools you use, what is the proportion of foresight studies?
- What do you think about foresight as a decision support tool? Do you think that foresight studies are useful for political actors⁵²? How?
- How would you describe the demand for foresight from political actors in Wallonia / Belgium? Do you need foresight?
- (+Why?)

[I present the four foresight studies I analyse to the respondent⁵³]

- Do you know these different studies?

[The respondent is invited to choose one or several energy foresight studies to discuss]

Brief presentation of the study (if the respondent is an author or a sponsor of the study that I haven't met during the exploratory interviews or if I need some more information regarding the study)

Reception of the Study by Political Actors

- How did you become aware of the study?
- Did you or your organisation react when the study was published (i.e.: press, advisory boards...)?
- Did you disseminate the study? To whom? How?
- (+Why?)

(Non)-Use of the Study by Political Actors

- **Internal application:** Did you use the study for your own work? For the communication within your organisation?
- **External application:** Did you use the study to communicate with other actors?
- **Decision support:** Did you use the study for the elaboration of reports, documents or plans? For decision making?
- (+Why?) (+ If not, what do you use instead?)

⁵² The political actors include political authorities, administrations and *stakeholders*.

⁵³ The foresight studies are «*Vers une Wallonie bas-carbone en 2050*», «*Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050*», «*Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050*» and «*Etude de prospective: Transition énergétique*». I bring a print version of each study and the respondent is allowed to take a look at it.

Beyond Use: Influence of the Study on Policy-Making

- **Individual level:** Did the study influence your opinion regarding the feasibility / acceptability of the low-carbon transition? Were you surprised by some aspects of the study? Did you learn something? What do you remember? (+Why?)
- **Interpersonal level:** Did the study lead to changes in the way some aspects of the low-carbon transition are perceived? At which level? Did the study lead to a discussion / debate among different actors? Was the study used by you / other political actors to justify a decision? Was the study used by you or other political actors to support some arguments? (+Why?)
- **Collective level:** Did the study contribute to put some issues at the political agenda? Did the study lead to changes in public policies (objectives, measures, instruments...)? Did the success of the study inspire other actors who then developed their own low-carbon scenarios? (+Why?)

Process Role: Influence of the Scenario Building Process on Policy-Making

- Did you participate in the scenario workshops?
- How was it? Do you feel that you have been listened to?
- Did you learn something during the scenario workshops?
- Do you think that the scenarios workshops fostered the dialogue among different actors? Stimulated the construction of a consensus among different actors? Facilitated linkages among different actors?
- (+Why?)

Evaluation of the Studies Regarding their Credibility, Legitimacy and Salience (see Cash & al., 2002 and 2003)

- Several researchers say that to be useful for political actors, scientific information must be credible, legitimate and salient. What do you think about these three criteria? How would you define them?
- Do you think that a foresight study must meet other criteria to be useful?
- Could you assess the study regarding these criteria?

Study	Credibility	Legitimacy	Salience
«Vers une Wallonie bas-carbone en 2050» (1)	/10	/10	/10	/10	/10	/10
«Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050» (2)	/10	/10	/10	/10	/10	/10
«Towards 100% renewable in Belgium by 2050» (3)	/10	/10	/10	/10	/10	/10
«Etude de prospective: Transition énergétique» (4)	/10	/10	/10	/10	/10	/10

- Do you have any other comments on the study? On foresight in general?

Appendix 3. Q Survey

Are you familiarized with the low-carbon transition issues? [if relevant]

Relevance of Governance Issues Compared to Other Issues

Several studies showed that the transition towards a low-carbon society is technically feasible. However, the low-carbon transition still raises a number of questions. Could you assess the policy relevance of the following issues? [+ justifications]

Issues	Examples of questions	Irrelevant	Of little relevance	No opinion	Relevant	Very relevant
Behavioural and technical levers	What are the technical innovations and behavioural changes that should be promoted in order to ensure the low-carbon transition?					
Social innovation	What are the innovative approaches or pioneering projects developed by citizens? To what extent can these citizen initiatives help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions? How to support them?					
Financing	How to mobilize public and private investment to finance the low-carbon transition? What are the innovative options for financing? How to ensure the profitability of investments in low-carbon technologies and limit risks? How to limit the socio-economic impacts for the "losers" of the low-carbon transition?					
Governance and public policy	How to steer the low-carbon transition? What public policies to implement? At what levels of power? With what participation of the stakeholders / citizens? How to ensure coherence with other sectoral policies?					
Social acceptability	Which low-carbon transition path is the most socially acceptable? How to promote social acceptability in relation to different low-carbon measures and policies?					
Employment	What are the impacts of the low-carbon transition on employment? How to limit the negative impacts on employment in order to ensure a fair transition? How to modulate the training offer to meet the need for new skills generated by the low-carbon transition?					

Q Methodology

The last part of the survey is a role play. You are the sponsor of the forthcoming study on the low-carbon transition in Wallonia / Belgium. This new study will focus on governance and public policy issues. Imagine that you are now preparing the terms of reference for this study. I'm going to suggest you a number of issues that could be addressed in the study (see Q set).

1. Could you sort these issues on the Likert scale regarding their policy relevance? The scale ranges from -2 to +2. +2 corresponds to the issues that you consider very relevant and that you would definitely like to investigate in the study. -2 corresponds to the issues that you consider irrelevant and that you would not address in the study. Between those two, you can put the issues that you consider relevant (+1), of little relevance (-1), and those for which you have no opinion (0).
2. In the second step, we have a limited number of squares for each column, but the rating is not important anymore. Could you choose the 4 more relevant issues and put them under the "+2"? Among the remaining issues, could you choose the 6 more relevant ones and put them under the "+1"? You can follow the same procedure to sort the remaining issues.
3. If you want, you can make modifications to the sorting.
4. Could you explain why you assigned a "+2" / "-2" to the following issues?
5. Do you think that I forget issues regarding the governance of the low-carbon transition that should be looked at in a study?
6. Do you have any comments or questions regarding this exercise?

Foresight and Governance

We are still assuming that you are preparing the terms of reference for this study. What approach would you encourage? Why (not) foresight?

Appendix 4. Distinguishing Items for Factor 1

ITEMS		FACTORS		
		1	2	3
3	Policy mix	2 *	1	1
1	Vision for 2050	2 *	-2	-2
2	Policy goals	2 *	0	-1
26	Long-term integration in the policy process	2 *	0	-2
4	Regulatory framework	1 *	0	0
25	Degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders	1 *	-1	-1
11	Role of the different stakeholders	0 *	-1	-1
14	Resistances of the incumbents	0	-2	0
15	Mobilization of the incumbents	0 *	-1	2
22	Horizontal integration of the policy goals	0 *	0	1
21	Vertical integration of the policy goals	-1 *	1	2
23	Vertical integration of the policy instruments	-1 *	2	1
12	Role of the incumbents	-1 *	-2	1
27	Representation of non-human beings in the policy process	-1	-1	-2
17	Steering mode	-1 *	2	-1
13	Consideration of the incumbents' needs	-2 *	-2	2
24	Horizontal integration of the policy instruments	-2 *	2	0
19	Vertical integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue	-2 *	0	0
20	Horizontal integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue	-2 *	0	0

Table 41. Distinguishing items for Factor 1. P <.05: Asterisk (*) Indicates Significance at P <.01

Appendix 5. Distinguishing Items for Factor 2

ITEMS		FACTORS		
		1	2	3
6	Services and infrastructures	1	2 *	0
24	Horizontal integration of the policy instruments	-2	2 *	0
17	Steering mode	-1	2 *	-1
16	Level of action and division of competences	-1	1 *	-1
21	Vertical integration of the policy goals	-1	1 *	2
20	Horizontal integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue	-2	0 *	0
22	Horizontal integration of the policy goals	0	0	1
2	Policy goals	2	0 *	-1
8	Information and awareness	1	0 *	2
26	Long-term integration in the policy process	2	0 *	-2
25	Degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders	1	-1 *	-1
27	Representation of non-human beings in the policy process	-1	-1	-2
11	Role of the different stakeholders	0	-1	-1
15	Mobilization of the incumbents	0	-1 *	2
12	Role of the incumbents	-1	-2 *	1
13	Consideration of the incumbents' needs	-2	-2 *	2
14	Resistances of the incumbents	0	-2 *	0

Table 42. Distinguishing items for Factor 2. P <.05: Asterisk (*) Indicates Significance at P <.01

Appendix 6. Distinguishing Items for Factor 3

ITEMS		FACTORS		
		1	2	3
15	Mobilization of the incumbents	0	-1	2 *
13	Consideration of the incumbents' needs	-2	-2	2 *
21	Vertical integration of the policy goals	-1	1	2 *
22	Horizontal integration of the policy goals	0	0	1
12	Role of the incumbents	-1	-2	1 *
24	Horizontal integration of the policy instruments	-2	2	0 *
14	Resistances of the incumbents	0	-2	0
20	Horizontal integration of the way the problem is defined as a public issue	-2	0	0 *
17	Steering mode	-1	2	-1 *
11	Role of the different stakeholders	0	-1	-1
2	Policy goals	2	0	-1 *
25	Degree and mode of participation of the different stakeholders	1	-1	-1 *
10	Role of the political-administrative authorities	0	-1	-1 *
26	Long-term integration in the policy process	2	0	-2 *
18	Foresight's institutionalization	0	-1	-2 *
27	Representation of non-human beings in the policy process	-1	-1	-2 *
15	Mobilization of the incumbents	0	-1	2 *

Table 43. Distinguishing items for Factor 3. P <.05: Asterisk (*) Indicates Significance at P <.01

Appendix 7. References of Papers Reviewed to Analyse STET Models

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